
Grant agreement no. 951754 — FCCIS — H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020 / H2020-INFRADEV-2019-3

Future Circular Collider

Futur collisionneur circulaire

DELIVERABLE REPORT

SUMMARY OF LAYOUT CONSTRAINTS AND OPPORTUNITIES

Document identifier:	FCC-2107150900-CER 10.5281/zenodo.7569138
Date of version:	30/01/2025
Working group:	FCCIS - WP3 Integrating Europe
Organisation:	Cerema - CERN - LD
Version:	V04.00
Status:	Released
Domain:	Implementation
Key words:	FCC, implementation, environmental impacts, territorial opportunities

This page is intentionally left blank.

SUMMARY

This report sets out the methodology used by the FCC feasibility study to develop a balanced site scenario based on the three pillars of the project:

- 1) scientific excellence;
- 2) territorial compatibility;
- 3) risks stemming from the implementation of the project.

It presents the requirements and constraints specific to the scenario development process, and illustrates with concrete examples how they are taken into account when determining the configuration and layout of the FCC.

This report also highlights the changes to the scenarios under study, with its various phases: start of the exploratory study in 2014, proposal of a baseline scenario for the site in 2021, review of a likely scenario with local stakeholders in 2023. The scenario serves as a reference to further explore the various elements of the feasibility study: for example, studies of underground stability, proposals for access to the site during the construction and operation phases, scenarios for the supply of electricity and water, approaches considered for the management of excavated materials, development of potential local synergy, questions concerning integration in the landscape, proposals for support and compensation measures.

In 2022, after eight years of studies, a circular collider with a circumference of approximately 91 km, including eight surface sites, appeared to be the most likely scenario. The iterative process to construct the scenario is described in this document.

The existence of a sufficiently large community of users committed to operating the infrastructure for several decades is a prerequisite for justifying the construction of a research infrastructure of this scale. Scenarios involving a much smaller collider, i.e. with a circumference of less than 90 km, do not meet the performance requirements of a large-scale research program that needs to attract a critical mass of scientists. Proposals for locations suitable for scenarios involving a collider with a circumference well in excess of 91 km and comprising more than eight surface sites would be impossible in terms of territorial compatibility and entail risks as to their realization. Finally, in terms of geological feasibility, only two types of configurations and layouts correspond to a very limited number of scenarios: a collider with a circumference of between 89 and 91 km and eight surface sites, and a collider with a circumference of between 97 and 98 km and twelve surface sites.

To date, only scenarios with a 91 km circumference and eight surface sites seem capable of satisfying the following three requirements: 1) acceptable scientific performance, 2) compatibility with territorial constraints and 3) compatibility with geological and technical constraints. It will become evident later that one of the scenarios (PA31) stands out from the rest, based on a multi-criteria analysis. It calls for in-depth studies and improvements, involving field work, and continuous discussions with the relevant departments in both involved countries and with stakeholders in the implementation area.

Territorial constraints and legal frameworks in host countries and within the European Union are constantly evolving. Between 2014 and 2023, several types of locations had to be ruled out due to these changes. The information contained in this document and the working hypothesis described here are therefore provisional. For the project to come to fruition, the validation of a scenario should be considered as soon as possible.

This page is intentionally left blank.

Document History

	Name	Organisation	Date
Writing	Pierre Boillon, Clotilde Malan, Stéphanie Favre, Gilles Chapelier, Federica Gorgerino, Cécile Tétrel, Julien Joos, Sandrine Tissandier	Cerema	Created on 15/07/2021
	Johannes Gutleber, Patrycja Laidouni, Volker Mertens	CERN	
	Maude Sauvain	Latitude Durable	
Editing	B. Arias	CERN	29/01/2025
	B. Arias, P. Laidouni	CERN	11/09/2024
	RapTrad (translators)	RapTrad	28/08/2024
	Clotilde Malan	Cerema	08/08/2023
	Patrycja Laidouni	CERN	13/07/2023
	J. Gutleber, P. Laidouni (V1.5)	CERN	31/05/2023
	P. Boillon, C. Malan (V1.4)	Cerema	16/05/2023
	Johannes Gutleber (V1.2)	CERN	15/05/2023
	Julie Hadre	CERN	07/02/2023
	David Goldsworthy	CERN	06/02/2023
	Suzanne Chibli	CERN	06/02/2023
	Johannes Gutleber	CERN	03/02/2023
CERN Translation Department	CERN	23/05/2022	
Approval	Johannes Gutleber (WP3 leader)	CERN	30/01/2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant agreement no. 951754).

The French Centre for Studies and Expertise on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning (Cerema), a public administrative body reporting to the French Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion (*Ministère de la Transition écologique et de la Cohésion des territoires*), the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), which is an international legal entity, and Latitude Durable, a private company based in Geneva, Switzerland, have been granted beneficiary status under the FCCIS (*Future Circular Collider Innovation Study*) project, co-funded by the European Commission.

This document is a deliverable produced by these three entities as part of this project. The studies and technical considerations presented here do not constitute an agreement or commitment by a CERN member state or the European Union to build and operate an extension to CERN's existing research infrastructure.

GLOSSARY:

All abbreviations used in this document are available and updated in the online glossary <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/FCC/GlossaryOfTerms>.

Modifications

Version	Date	Section	Description
1.1	07/02/2023	-	Numbers of illustrations and tables corrected
1.2	10/03/2023	15	Table added to section 15.1 showing the status of the technical feasibility assessment for surface sites.
		-	Image added: Montfleury water table updated
		-	Addition of a sub-section on environmental assessment in Switzerland
		16.4	
	16.5	Updated list of plots of land affected by scenario PA31	
	15/03/2023	4.1	New subsurface constraint in the Challex sector, taking into account the illustration to optimise the PL site
16/03/2023	16.2	Data list completed for 2023	
	16.6	Reference to the "Cellule interdépartementale cantonale" (cantonal interdepartmental unit)	
	2.3	Reference to the support provided by the Swiss Federal Council	
26/04/2023 08/05/2023	15	Chapter title updated to include description of PA31-4.0 reference scenario instead of generic conclusion	
11-15/05/2023	All chapters	Mention of reference scenario PA31-4.0 throughout the document wherever relevant (phases adapted to incorporate this scenario)	

1.5	16-17/05/2023	6	Integration of new versions of scenario presentation maps in territory: natural risks of land movement and flooding (Switzerland), technological risks (Canton of Geneva), demographic evolution maps (France and Switzerland)
		8	Integration of the proposed plots on several maps of the PB site: connecting routes, ecological infrastructure at 25 m, nocturnal continuum
		All	Reworking of location maps to ensure consistency, and addition of various details to map legends
		6.2.10 16.3	Blurring of catchment, drinking water supply and protective perimeter data: data is moved to a confidential document. "Confidential information" added
		5.1	Addition of legends to the water table and water protection map (Switzerland)
		16.5	Update of the list of plots in line with the plots provided for in scenario PA31-1.0
		6.5	Clarifications concerning the clearances for town or departmental roads
		9.3.1	Clarification of the PD site perimeter and Ur zoning in the PLU (Local Urban Plan)
		10.4.4	Addition of maps and details concerning the southern connection of the PF site
	12.1	Rework of foreseen plots of land for the PH site	
	31/05/2023	6.2.20	Addition of water evaporation in Lake Geneva Correction of Rhône and Arve flow rates
	14/06/2023	9.4.4	Addition of a map showing the RD903 development project at Nangy.
	30/06/2023	6.2.20.1	Update of water requirements and sampling reference scenario
1.6	28/07/2023	5.6	Maps of this section updated to take account of the PA31-3 and PA31-4 scenario footprints
		6.2.16	Updated map of urban planning documents
		8.2.3	Updated PB site map with ISOS zone and forest in red
		10	Updated plot of land location and constraint maps to include new footprints
		12	Update all PH site maps to include new footprints
		13	Update all PJ site maps to include new footprints
16.5	Table of concerned cadastral plots replaced by the one supplied by CERN		
1.7	11/08/2023	5.5, 5.6	Multi-criteria analyses updated for scenarios PA31-3.0 and PA31-4.0, updated description of PF site options at Eteaux and La Roche-sur-Foron

1.8	22/08/2023 01/09/2023 13/10/2023 01/11/2023	5.6.1 5.6.2 8 10 12 6.2.20 4.1.1 5.6.9 6.2.4 14 to 15	Modification of the map showing the 3 footprints Modification of the PA site map to correct the legend Modification of all maps, except access map Modification of maps of constraints, cadastre (land registry), operators, views Modification of the last non-compliant maps in scenario PA31-4.0, except for access map Water distribution updated Update of the PL (Challex) site with information provided by the municipality Adding of data source for electrical networks
1.9	15/11/2023	All 1.3 3.5 Chapters 5 to 14 and 16	Chapter introductions inserted Reading guide added Linear collider variant added Updated maps with the latest plots and the footprint for scenario PA31-4.0 Confidential appendix on drinking water catchments updated
2.0	December 2023	All	Maps updated Finalization of version to be published Reference to confidential document on water catchment areas in France Information added on the residual magnetic field for experiments in a new section 6.2.22 Integration of optimised transfer line illustrations (section 2.6) Addition of section 6.2.23 Compatibility with geothermal probes Data added on deep-seated and shallow landslides Illustrations added in chapter 15 and illustrations updated in the document

2.1	07/05/2024	<p>p. 9</p> <p>Section 2.8</p> <p>Section 2.9.3</p> <p>Chapters 3 and 5</p> <p>Section 6.2.17.2</p> <p>Section 6.2.18.2</p> <p>Section 6.2.19</p> <p>Section 6.2.20</p> <p>Section 6.3</p> <p>Chapters 7 to 14</p> <p>Section 8.3</p> <p>Section 8.4.3</p> <p>Section 10.4.4</p> <p>Sections 15.3 - 15.11</p>	<p>Correction of names and memberships</p> <p>Updated description of split surface sites</p> <p>Update on the potential benefits of residual heat recovery</p> <p>Modification of chapter titles to differentiate them clearly</p> <p>Add reference to noise sensitivity zone</p> <p>Updated summary of electricity needs during the construction phase</p> <p>Updated electricity consumption of TBMs</p> <p>Updated residual heat supply potential</p> <p>Updated water requirements (reduction)</p> <p>Section restructured and divided into two new sections (6.3 and 6.4)</p> <p>Update of main opportunities by site and associated maps</p> <p>Updated map of the Presinge sector concerning site PB</p> <p>Addition of analysis by RGR of road access to site PB</p> <p>Analysis of WSP/BG added for road access to PF site</p> <p>Update of surface site location descriptions and options added for the HGV site in Challex (France)</p>
2.2	May 2024	The entire document	Text corrected by CERN translation department and translation into English
2.3	September 2024	The entire document	<p>The term "altitude" has been replaced by "elevation".</p> <p>Updated WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical points in chapters 7 to 15.</p>
		Chapter 1	<p>1.2. "Avoid elevations above 750 m..." (700 m in the previous version).</p> <p>1.3. In chapter 16, « details on drinking water catchments" and "clarification of the environmental assessment" removed.</p>

2.3	September 2024	Chapter 2	<p>Modified illustrations: 1, 2, 7, 8, 12, 17, 28, 29, 30.</p> <p>Footnote 19. Updated text and added hyperlink.</p> <p>Table 2. Added protected natural area in France.</p> <p>2.5.3. "... elevations above 750 m are an obstacle due to ..." (700 m in the previous version).</p> <p>Table 5. Corrected total arc length current value.</p> <p>2.9.3. The production can reach up to 38,500 tCO₂.</p>
		Chapter 3	<p>Modified illustrations: 34, 40, 41, 42.</p> <p>Footnote 40. Updated hyperlink.</p> <p>Table 12 corrected.</p> <p>Table 13. Updated value of the carbon footprint for the construction of a circular collider.</p>
		Chapter 4	<p>Modified illustrations: 46, 47, 50, 51, 53, 54, 55.</p> <p>Table 14. Updated maximum elevation for the location of the shafts.</p>
		Chapter 5	<p>Modified illustrations: 59, 62, 66, 72, 76, 80, 85, 90, 92, 93.</p> <p>Footnote 49. Updated hyperlink.</p> <p>Table 16. Conditions after the 2024 developments taken into account. Updated total area of land used by the surface sites, total length of access roads to be constructed or improved, and total volume of excavated materials with "in situ" values.</p> <p>5.3. Total area, total length of access roads, and estimated total volume of excavated materials updated with 2024 data.</p> <p>Tables 17, 18 and 20 (5.5.). Corrected values for scenarios PA31-3.0 and PA31-4.0.</p> <p>Removed former footnote 53.</p> <p>5.6.8., illustration 100. The perimeter shown dates from January 2023.</p>
		Chapter 6	<p>Modified illustrations: 137, 138, 139, 142, 144.</p> <p>6.1. The analysis of each site is presented in Chapters 7 to 14.</p> <p>Footnote 69. Updated hyperlink.</p> <p>6.2.16.1. Removal of the mention of the absence of a PLU.</p> <p>6.2.16.2. Addition of information regarding the second update of the 2030 cantonal master plan.</p> <p>Footnote 41. Addition of hyperlink regarding the 2030 cantonal master plan.</p> <p>6.2.18.2. Addition of the hyperlink to the report provided by RTE concerning the preliminary technical feasibility study for connecting the FCC to the high-power electrical infrastructure.</p> <p>Addition of footnote 77 (6.2.18.2.).</p> <p>Footnote 82. Addition of hyperlink to the document in Zenodo.</p>

2.3	September 2024	Chapter 6	<p>6.2.20.1. New water intake in the Nangy area to be planned in cooperation with the Scientrier wastewater treatment plant (STEP). Added the quantity of m³/h of water that the STEP could supply.</p> <p>Table 27. The water source for the "Reduced PD" site could also be the Scientrier STEP. Updated values for PD and PJ.</p> <p>Table 28. Correction of the total minimum and maximum needs for initial estimates and addition of 2024 estimates.</p> <p>6.2.21.2. Updated percentage of electricity produced from wind turbines and photovoltaic installations. Added reference to the paragraph where the capacities are mentioned.</p> <p>Illustration 142. Updated.</p> <p>Illustration 144. Updated.</p> <p>Footnote 97. Addition of hyperlink to the document in Zenodo.</p> <p>Illustration 147. Addition of the hyperlink corresponding to the source.</p> <p>Footnote 107. Updated hyperlink.</p> <p>Footnote 108. Addition of hyperlink regarding the regional ecological coherence diagram.</p> <p>6.4.2. Updated information regarding the Plan de mesures OPair.</p> <p>6.4.6. Updated information regarding the directive on the treatment and disposal of construction site water and the VSA directive on urban stormwater management.</p> <p>6.4.7. Updated information based on three documents listed in the "Directives and recommendations".</p> <p>6.4.9. Updated information based on two documents listed in the "Directives and recommendations".</p> <p>6.4.10. Updated information concerning the OFEV document listed in the "Directives and recommendations".</p> <p>6.4.13. Updated information regarding the Federal law on the protection of animals.</p> <p>6.4.14. Updated information regarding the General regulations for application of the law on the protection...</p>
		Chapter 8	<p>Modified illustrations: 190.</p> <p>8.3. Updated the available area for a candidate surface site in the Presinge territory.</p> <p>Footnote 114. Addition of hyperlink to the document in Zenodo.</p>
		Chapter 9	<p>Modified illustrations: 209, 211, 212, 213, 218, 241.</p> <p>9.1. Updated the envisaged area for the main site.</p> <p>9.4.4. The consulting firm responsible for developing the various access scenarios for the PD site was WSP/BG. Removal of the sentence regarding the reduction of general road traffic in the area.</p>

2.3	September 2024	Chapter 10	<p>Modified illustrations: 243, 245, 246, 247, 252, 253.</p> <p>10.1. Updated the envisaged area for the south site as well as the length of the horizontal tunnel.</p> <p>Footnote 119. Updated hyperlink.</p> <p>Footnote 121. Updated hyperlink.</p> <p>Addition of footnote 122.</p> <p>10.4.1. Updated reference to the paragraph where solutions for connecting to the departmental network are presented.</p>
		Chapter 11	<p>Modified illustrations: 275, 277, 278, 280, 283.</p> <p>11.1. Updated the area of the proposed plots.</p> <p>11.3. Modification of the text regarding the zoning regulations to incorporate the Local Urban Plan (PLU) developed by Charvonnex.</p> <p>Removal of former footnote 121.</p> <p>Footnote 125. Updated hyperlink.</p>
		Chapter 12	<p>Modified illustrations: 317, 318, 319, 321.</p> <p>12.1. The 400 kV high-voltage line is displayed in Illustration 133.</p>
		Chapter 13	<p>Modified illustrations: 330, 332, 333, 334, 337.</p>
		Chapter 14	<p>Modified illustrations: 349, 351, 352, 353, 355, 357, 360.</p> <p>14.1. Presence of rented villa near the PL site. The two individual houses are located 300 meters from the nominal point. The presence of a forest and a village are taken into account as disadvantages. The Route de Dardagny is closed for cross-border crossing.</p> <p>Table 35:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updated maps of the various scenarios. - Scenario 4. Updated distance from the houses. - Scenario 6. Updated the available area and the distance to the nominal point. - Scenario 8. Updated available surface. In the disadvantages, the presence of a forest that includes wetlands is considered. <p>14.2.1. Correction of the road reference (D884 instead of D889).</p> <p>Former illustrations 356 and 359 (now 358 and 357) moved under the mention of the ecological corridor.</p> <p>Removal of former illustration 364.</p> <p>14.4.3. Updated the total distance to the shaft.</p> <p>14.5. The determination of possible locations was conducted in dialogue with the municipality (and not in consultation). The preferred location is the one located at the nominal point.</p>

2.3	September 2024	Chapter 15	<p>Modified illustrations: 378, 380, 381, 382, 385, 388, 389, 395.</p> <p>15.2.1. Updated the length of the tunnel between the shaft and the service cavern (PB). The preferred location for PH is mainly in Marlioz.</p> <p>15.3.1. Updated the area of the site extension at point 8 of the LHC.</p> <p>15.4.1. Updated the area of the site.</p> <p>15.5.1. Updated the area of the site.</p> <p>15.6.2. Updated the length of the horizontal tunnel between the access shaft and the collider tunnel.</p> <p>15.7.1. Updated the area of the main site.</p> <p>15.10.1. Updated text.</p> <p>15.10.2. Updated information on the different options.</p> <p>Addition of illustration 396.</p> <p>15.11. Updated text concerning PB and PL.</p>
		Chapter 16	16.3. Updated section.
3.0	17/10/2024	All	Document approved and published.
3.1	29/01/2025		New version created to implement the comments received from the Host States.
		Chapter 2	<p>2.2. Illustration 4. Updated legend.</p> <p>2.5.1. Addition of footnote 20. Corrections with respect to the SDA. Updated tables 2, 3 and 4.</p> <p>2.5.2. Corrected paragraph on strategic aquifers.</p> <p>2.5.3. Corrected text on the depth of the tunnel.</p> <p>2.7. Updated table 7.</p>
		Chapter 3	3.4. Corrected text in relation with PB.
		Chapter 4	4.2.2. Addition of SDA on Table 15.
		Chapter 5	<p>5.1. Corrected text on high-pressure water tables. Updated illustration 58.</p> <p>5.2. Addition of details about the weight of each criterium in the MCA.</p> <p>5.4.2. Illustration 64. Addition of the date when the data was made available.</p> <p>5.4 and 5.6.1. Addition in the title of the sections of the label "selected" / "not selected".</p>

3.1	29/01/2025	Chapter 6	<p>6.2.1. Updated from « town planning documents” to “town planning”. Corrected information about Swiss documents.</p> <p>6.2.11.1. Corrected the site impacted (PJ instead of PI). Updated the legend of illustration 114 (addition of footnote 64).</p> <p>6.2.15. Corrected the localisation of the reference to illustration 130 in the text.</p> <p>6.2.17.2. Addition of the consideration of new roads.</p> <p>6.2.20.1. Updated section (illustrations 137, 138 and 139, as well as table).</p> <p>6.4.2. Addition of footnote 114 (with hyperlink).</p> <p>6.4.3. Addition of reference OFEV 2006 (and related footnote 115). Updated “Consequences” as well.</p> <p>6.4.5. Addition of information to the “Consequences” about new power lines connecting to the existing grid and transformer stations</p> <p>6.4.6. Addition of the Subsurface resources act.</p> <p>6.4.7. Addition of the Spatial planning act. Deleted text about the construction of parkings.</p> <p>6.4.8. Addition of a directive and of explanatory text in the “Consequences”.</p> <p>6.4.13. Addition of OCAN references from 2018 and 2020 (and related footnotes 116 and 117).</p> <p>6.4.14. Addition of OCAN reference from 2008 (and related footnote 118).</p> <p>6.8.1. Addition of the need to plan a site for waste sorting and collection facilities.</p>
		Chapter 7	<p>7.3. Updated illustration 170 to show the presence of an ecological corridor. Updated text in relation to the “South polygon”.</p>
		Chapter 8	<p>8.3. “Management of hazards”. Addition of the Choulex plot number. Updated caption (illustration 192).</p> <p>“Possibilities for temporary storage and processing of excavated materials”. Updated text to make the contents clearer.</p> <p>“Ecological sensitivity”. Removed text about the house acquisition.</p> <p>8.4.2. Updated title.</p> <p>8.5. Corrected text to explicitly mention the nearby Abbaye de Presinge.</p>
		Chapter 14	<p>14.4.1. Addition of a note to consider the procedure to follow in the event a train station or a loading platform located in Switzerland is used for the removal of excavated materials to French territory.</p>
4.0	30/01/2025		Document approved and published.

Acknowledgements

This report was made possible by a large number of contributions. Our heartfelt thanks go to the more than 160 people listed below. We would like to express our sincere gratitude to any other contributors we may have omitted from this list.

Laurent Aleazzi, DT Geneva	Charles Cook, CERN
Leslie Alix, CNRS	Angel Navascues Cornago, CERN
Beatriz Arias Alonso, CERN	Laetitia Cottet, DT Geneva
Sophie Auchapt, McKinsey	Carine Cudre, Ecotec
Frédéric Bachmann, DT OCEau Genève	Roddy Cunningham, CERN
Austin Ball, CERN	Mehdi Daakir, CERN
Charles Barre, Egis	Werner Dallapiazza, ILF
Wolfgang Bartmann, CERN	Mogens Dam, University of Copenhagen
Fanny Battle, McKinsey	Heiko Damerau, CERN
Michael Benedikt, CERN	Gabriel De Los Cobos, GESDEC Geneva
Serena Bertoni, Setec als	Laurent Delprat, CERN
Sarah Beuvier, Ecotec	Adrian Dettling, Accenture
Amandine Bibet-Chevallier, Cerema	Yasmine Ducellier, DI Geneva
Alain Blondel, UNIGE	Maël Dugue, MD-Environment
Pierre Boillon, Cerema	Patrick Durand, Ecotec
Rémy Bonnet, Setec als	Friedemann Eder, CERN
Pierre Bouvatier, WSP BG	Stefan Eder, ILF
Benjamin Bradu, CERN	Julien Fattebert, Ecotec
Richard Brasier, WSP BG	Stéphanie Favre, Cerema
Johann Peter Brasser, Amberg	Emmanuelle Felix, Ecotec
Christine Brawand, OCLPF Geneva	Cindy Fressard, DI Geneva
Liam Bromiley, CERN	Frank Gerigk, CERN
Olivier Brunner, CERN	Chiara Gilbert, Accenture
Jean-Paul Burnet, CERN	Claire Gillette, Setec als
Heloise Candolfi, OCAN Geneva	Massimo Giovannozzi, CERN
Jérôme Chablais, Hydro-Géo Environnement	Thibault Girardet, Ecotec
Marie Champagne, Evinerude	Sylvain Girod, CERN
Didier Chanal, Cerema	Florent Godet, DDT 74
Gilles Chapelier, Cerema	David Goldsworthy, CERN
Suzanne Chibli, CERN	Federica Gorgerino, Cerema
Nicolas Clerc, GESDEC Geneva	Massimo Giovannozzi, CERN

Roberto Grecuccio, DT Genève	Volker Mertens, CERN
Christophe Grojean, CERN	Thierry Messenger, DI Genève
Monika Grothe, Accenture	Pascal Michel, DT Genève
Alain Guiavarch, Ginger Burgeap	Nicolas Montanaro, DDT 01
Nicolas Guilhaudin, CERN	Céline Montero, DREAL UD
Mathilde Giuliani, Setec als	Andrea Moscariello, University of Geneva
Kevin Gurcel	Tao Ni Song, McKinsey
Maximilian Haas, CERN	Katsunobu Oide, KEK and University of Geneva
Julie Hadre, CERN	John Osborne, CERN
Tristan Halle, Egis	Thomas Otto, CERN
Klaus Hanke, CERN	Amael Paillex, Ecotec
Philippe Herschke, Accenture	Yvan Papa, Ecotec
Michael Hofer, CERN	Francois Pasquini, DT OCEau Geneva
Jean-Francois Hotellier, GADZ	Franck Peauger, CERN
Audrey Houver, Ecotec	Marion Penelas, OCBA Geneva
Patrick Janot, CERN	Guillermo Peon, CERN
Erk Jensen, CERN	Luc Petitpain, Cerema
Julien Joos, Cerema	Pierre Philippe, SERMA Geneva
Anne-Laure Jorsin-Chazeau, DREAL UD	Michael Poehler, CERN
Ivan Karpov, CERN	Aude Poiron, Ecotec
Sonja Kleiner, CERN	Corentin Pueyo, CERN
Laurent Kompf, DDT 74	Tor Raubenheimer, SLAC
Elliot Lecointe, Ecotec	Cyrielle Regazzoni, Ecotec
Patrycja Laidouni, CERN	Emmanuel Renou, Ecotec
Pauline Le Guen, CERN	Fabrice Rolle
Yann Lechevin, CERN	Lucy Rew, Egis
Clarisse Lefort, Setec als	Werner Riegler, CERN
Yung Loo, ARUP	Thys Risselada, CERN
D. Magnard, DGITM	Youri Robert, CERN
P. Magnière, DGITM	Pierre Roche, Setec als
Clotilde Malan, Cerema	Nicolas Rongieras, Setec als
Laurène Mallet, Setec als	Ingo Rühl, CERN
Olivier Martin, MAE	Ali El Saied, Ginger Burgeap
Antoine Mayoux, CERN	Maude Sauvain, Latitude Durable
Sophie Meylan, Ecotec	Joscha Schabram, McKinsey
Thomas Muzi, RGR	Delphine Stagnara, Setec als

Joanna Louise Stanyard, CERN

Craig Sturzaker, ARUP

Matthew Sykes, ARUP

William Tachon, Mélica/Natura scop

Laurent Tavian, CERN

Cécile Tétrel, Cerema

Cyril Thomas, GADZ

Sandrine Tissandier, Cerema

Alexandra Tudora, CERN

Luisa Ulrici, CERN

Fani Valchkova-Georgieva, CERN

Jean-Marc Valet, Cerema

Thierry Valleix

Sophie Valette, CERN

Anne-Laure Verdier, CERN

Walter Vetterli, OCEV Geneva

Jean-François Vian

Jérémy Voiron, BG

Sébastien Voiriot, Ecotec

Anne Vuichard, DT Geneva

Timothy Watson, CERN

Gérard Widmer, DI Geneva

Markus Widorski, CERN

Matthieu Zahnd, Ecotec

Pauline Zaro, Setec als

Linhao Zhang, CERN

Erwan Zimmermann, Ecotec

Frank Zimmermann, CERN

Michael Zimmermann, RGR

Table of contents

SUMMARY	3
1. INTRODUCTION	26
1.1. STUDY OF THE FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER	26
1.2. SUMMARY OF THE GUIDELINES FOR SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT	28
1.3. READING GUIDE FOR THIS REPORT	30
2. SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT PROCESS	32
2.1. PURPOSE	33
2.2. OBJECTIVE	34
2.3. SUPPORT FROM FRANCE AND SWITZERLAND	38
2.4. SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT PROCESS	40
2.5. REQUIREMENTS AND CONSTRAINTS (STEP 1, PLAN)	42
2.5.1. <i>Territorial sensitivity grid</i>	42
2.5.2. <i>Underground constraints</i>	48
2.5.3. <i>Topography, bathymetry, and other surface features</i>	52
2.5.4. <i>Essential particle accelerator parameters</i>	54
2.6. DETERMINATION OF CONFIGURATION AND LAYOUT (STEP 2, DO)	61
2.7. MULTI-CRITERIA ANALYSIS (STEP 3, CHECK)	67
2.8. AVOID-REDUCE-COMPENSATE (STEP 4, ACT)	77
2.9. EXAMPLES OF THE APPLICATION OF ERC MEASURES IN SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT	82
2.9.1. <i>Avoid: moving a surface site</i>	82
2.9.2. <i>Reduce: adapt road access design</i>	83
2.9.3. <i>Compensate: example of residual heat use</i>	86
3. CONTEXT AND INITIAL LAYOUT SCENARIOS	89
3.1. HYPOTHESES AND INITIAL CONDITIONS	89
3.2. SCENARIOS WEST OF THE JURA	91
3.3. SCENARIOS EAST OF THE JURA	92
3.4. REFERENCE SCENARIO FOR INITIAL STUDIES	94
3.5. LINEAR COLLIDER VARIANT	97
3.5.1. <i>Introduction</i>	97
3.5.2. <i>Scientific research potential</i>	100
3.5.3. <i>Territorial compatibility</i>	101
3.5.4. <i>Implementation risks and costs</i>	102
3.5.5. <i>Summary</i>	103
4. DEVELOPING A BALANCED SCENARIO	107
4.1. ZONES TO AVOID AND PREFERRED ZONES	107

4.1.1.	<i>Layouts of interest in Switzerland near CERN</i>	107
4.1.2.	<i>Layouts of interest in France near CERN</i>	112
4.1.3.	<i>layouts of interest in Switzerland (left bank of the lake)</i>	113
4.1.4.	<i>Layouts of interest in France, in the Arve River Valley</i>	115
4.1.5.	<i>Layouts of interest in France, in the sector from Bornes plateau to Fillière</i>	116
4.1.6.	<i>Layouts of interest in France, between La Mandallaz and Les Ussets</i>	118
4.1.7.	<i>Layouts of interest in France, in the Vuache and Rhône zone</i>	119
4.1.8.	<i>Layouts of interest in the Jura zone of France</i>	121
4.2.	INVARIABLE CRITERIA AND VOLUNTARY OBJECTIVES	122
4.2.1.	<i>Invariable criteria for scenario</i>	122
4.2.2.	<i>Voluntary objectives for creating scenarios</i>	125
5.	DEVELOPMENT OF SCENARIOS	127
5.1.	TERRITORIAL CHANGES	128
5.2.	BASIC WORKING HYPOTHESIS PA31-1.0	131
5.3.	RESULTS OF THE SCENARIO OPTIMIZATION PROCESS	132
5.4.	SUMMARIES OF SELECTED SCENARIOS	134
5.4.1.	<i>PB17-0.8 (twelve sites; not selected)</i>	134
5.4.2.	<i>PB19-0.3 (twelve sites; not selected)</i>	138
5.4.3.	<i>PA21-0.3 (eight sites; not selected)</i>	145
5.4.4.	<i>PA38-0.1 (twelve sites; not selected)</i>	150
5.4.5.	<i>PA33-0.13 (eight sites; not selected)</i>	155
5.4.6.	<i>PA35-0.6 (eight sites; not selected)</i>	160
5.4.7.	<i>PA37-0.3 (eight sites; not selected)</i>	166
5.5.	COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SCENARIOS	172
5.6.	PREFERRED SCENARIO PA31 AND ITS ITERATIVE DEVELOPMENT	177
5.6.1.	<i>Description of scenario PA31 (selected)</i>	177
5.6.2.	<i>Changes made to the PA scientific site in Ferney-Voltaire, France</i>	181
5.6.3.	<i>Changes made to the PD scientific site in Nangy, France</i>	182
5.6.4.	<i>Changes made to the PG scientific site in Groisy and Charvonnex, France</i>	183
5.6.5.	<i>Changes made to the PJ scientific site in Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens, France</i>	184
5.6.6.	<i>Changes made to the PB technical site in Switzerland</i>	185
5.6.7.	<i>Changes made to the PF technical site in Eteaux or La-Roche-sur-Foron, France</i>	186
5.6.8.	<i>Changes made to the PH technical site in Cercier and Marlioz, France</i>	188
5.6.9.	<i>Changes made to the PL technical site in Challex, France</i>	189
6.	INTEGRATING THE PA31 SCENARIO IN THE TERRITORY	190
6.1.	FOOTPRINT OF PA31	190

6.2.	ANALYSIS OF THE OVERALL PA31 FOOTPRINT	192
6.2.1.	Introduction	192
6.2.2.	Topography.....	195
6.2.3.	Bodies of groundwater in France.....	196
6.2.4.	Bodies of water in Geneva.....	199
6.2.5.	Biodiversity and water.....	200
6.2.6.	Protection of Natura 2000 sites and biotope protection orders	201
6.2.7.	Ecological continuities of the SRADDET Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes.....	204
6.2.8.	Ecological continuities identified in Geneva's ecological infrastructure	205
6.2.9.	Surface water.....	206
6.2.10.	Drinking water supply (AEP) catchments and protection perimeters.....	207
6.2.11.	Natural and technological hazards.....	208
6.2.12.	Population density	218
6.2.13.	Demographics and employment.....	222
6.2.14.	Landscape units	225
6.2.15.	Landscape protection	226
6.2.16.	Urban planning documents	228
6.2.17.	Noise.....	231
6.2.18.	Networks and Systems.....	233
6.2.19.	Heat recovery and reuse.....	237
6.2.20.	Water resources: estimated needs and regulations	238
6.2.21.	Electricity needs and supply.....	249
6.2.22.	Residual magnetic field at the surface of scientific sites	260
6.2.23.	Compatibility with geothermal borehole probes.....	264
6.3.	SUMMARY OF TOOLS FOR IDENTIFYING ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN FRANCE.....	268
6.3.1.	Introduction.....	268
6.3.2.	Inventories of Natural Zone of Interest for Ecology, Flora and Fauna (ZNIEFF).....	268
6.3.3.	ZICO (priority zone for bird preservation) inventory	269
6.3.4.	Inventory of peatlands and wetlands	270
6.3.5.	Natura 2000 network	270
6.3.6.	Protected agricultural zones (ZAP)	272
6.3.7.	Protective perimeters for peri-urban natural and agricultural areas (PAEN).....	272
6.3.8.	Hazard prevention plans (PPRN, PPRI)	273
6.3.9.	Technological hazard prevention plans (PPRT).....	273
6.3.10.	SRCE and SRADDET	274
6.3.11.	Classified wooded area (EBC)	275

6.3.12.	<i>Protection of water catchments</i>	275
6.3.13.	<i>Environmental and river contracts to protect aquatic environments</i>	276
6.3.14.	<i>Listed historic monuments / buildings protected by local urban plan (PLU)</i>	276
6.3.15.	<i>Listed and classified sites</i>	277
6.3.16.	<i>Easement PT1 – Protection of radio reception centres against electromagnetic interference.</i>	277
6.4.	SUMMARY OF TOOLS FOR IDENTIFYING ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN SWITZERLAND	278
6.4.1.	<i>Introduction</i>	278
6.4.2.	<i>Protection of air quality</i>	278
6.4.3.	<i>Protection against noise</i>	280
6.4.4.	<i>Protection against vibrations and structure-borne sound propagation</i>	282
6.4.5.	<i>Protection against non-ionising radiation</i>	283
6.4.6.	<i>Protection of water</i>	284
6.4.7.	<i>Soil protection and territorial planning</i>	287
6.4.8.	<i>Polluted sites</i>	289
6.4.9.	<i>Waste and environmentally hazardous substances</i>	290
6.4.10.	<i>Environmentally hazardous organisms</i>	291
6.4.11.	<i>Major accident prevention and disaster protection</i>	292
6.4.12.	<i>Forest conservation</i>	292
6.4.13.	<i>Flora, fauna and biotopes</i>	293
6.4.14.	<i>Landscapes and sites</i>	296
6.4.15.	<i>Historical monuments and archaeological sites</i>	297
6.5.	PRIORITISATION OF EXAMINED CONSTRAINTS	298
6.6.	GENERAL INFORMATION ON ACCESS ANALYSIS	298
6.7.	CONNECTION TO MOTORWAY SERVICE AREAS	299
6.8.	GENERAL INFORMATION ON SURFACE SITES	301
6.8.1.	<i>Elements relating to surface sites</i>	301
6.8.2.	<i>Iterative integration process</i>	305
6.8.3.	<i>Amount of personnel at sites during operation</i>	306
7.	THE PA SITE - FERNEY-VOLTAIRE (AIN, FRANCE)	307
7.1.	DESCRIPTION	307
7.2.	URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	313
7.2.1.	<i>State of the premises</i>	313
7.2.2.	<i>Urban planning, architecture and landscape</i>	316
7.3.	ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS.....	317
7.4.	ACCESS ANALYSIS	319
7.4.1.	<i>Location in relation to the main road network and railways</i>	319

7.4.2.	<i>Departmental roads connecting to the main road network</i>	320
7.4.3.	<i>Connection to local road network</i>	324
7.5.	SUMMARY OF THE PA SITE	324
8.	THE PB SITE – PRESINGE/CHOULEX (CANTON OF GENEVA, SWITZERLAND)	325
8.1.	DESCRIPTION	325
8.2.	URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	329
8.2.1.	<i>State of the premises</i>	329
8.2.2.	<i>Urban planning, architecture and landscape</i>	331
8.3.	ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS	334
8.4.	ACCESS ANALYSIS	343
8.4.1.	<i>Location in relation to main road network and railways</i>	343
8.4.2.	<i>French departmental roads connecting to the Geneva main road network</i>	345
8.4.3.	<i>Connection to local road network</i>	350
8.5.	SUMMARY OF THE PB SITE	353
9.	THE PD SITE – NANGY (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE)	354
9.1.	DESCRIPTION	354
9.2.	URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	361
9.2.1.	<i>State of the premises</i>	361
9.2.2.	<i>Urban planning, architecture and landscape</i>	364
9.3.	ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS	365
9.4.	ACCESS ANALYSIS	367
9.4.1.	<i>Location in relation to main road network and railways</i>	367
9.4.2.	<i>Feasibility of connection to the Nangy motorway area</i>	370
9.4.3.	<i>Departmental roads connecting to the main road network</i>	373
9.4.4.	<i>Connection to local road network</i>	376
9.5.	SUMMARY OF THE PD SITE	386
10.	THE PF SITE - ETEAUX/LA ROCHE-SUR-FORON (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE)	387
10.1.	DESCRIPTION	387
10.2.	URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	394
10.2.1.	<i>State of the premises</i>	394
10.2.2.	<i>Urban planning, architecture and landscape</i>	395
10.2.3.	<i>The PF site (north)</i>	397
10.2.4.	<i>The PF site (south)</i>	399
10.3.	ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS	400
10.4.	ACCESS ANALYSIS	404
10.4.1.	<i>Location in relation to the main road network and railways</i>	404

10.4.2.	<i>Feasibility of connection to the Eteaux/Évires motorway area</i>	408
10.4.3.	<i>Departmental roads connecting to the main road network</i>	410
10.4.4.	<i>Connection to local road network.....</i>	411
10.5.	SUMMARY OF THE PF SITE	416
11.	THE PG SITE - CHARVONNEX/GROISY (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE).....	417
11.1.	DESCRIPTION	417
11.2.	URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	425
11.2.1.	<i>State of the premises</i>	425
11.2.2.	<i>Urban planning, architecture and landscape</i>	428
11.3.	ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS.....	429
11.4.	ACCESS ANALYSIS	438
11.4.1.	<i>Location in relation to the main road network and railways.....</i>	438
11.4.2.	<i>Feasibility of connection to the Crêts Blancs motorway area</i>	441
11.4.3.	<i>Departmental roads connecting to the main road network</i>	444
11.4.4.	<i>Connection to local road network.....</i>	447
11.5.	SUMMARY OF THE PG SITE	456
12.	THE PH SITE – CERCIER OR MARLIOZ (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE).....	457
12.1.	DESCRIPTION	457
12.2.	URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	465
12.2.1.	<i>State of the premises</i>	465
12.2.2.	<i>Urban planning, architecture and landscape</i>	468
12.3.	ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS.....	469
12.4.	ACCESS ANALYSIS	470
12.4.1.	<i>Location in relation to main road network and railways.....</i>	470
12.4.2.	<i>Departmental roads connecting to the main road network</i>	474
12.4.3.	<i>Connection to local road network.....</i>	476
12.5.	SUMMARY OF THE PH SITE	477
13.	THE PJ SITE - DINGY-EN-VUACHE/VULBENS (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE)	478
13.1.	DESCRIPTION	478
13.2.	URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	486
13.2.1.	<i>State of the premises</i>	486
13.2.2.	<i>Urban planning, architecture and landscape</i>	487
13.3.	ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS.....	490
13.4.	ACCESS ANALYSIS	491
13.4.1.	<i>Location in relation to main road network and railways.....</i>	491
13.4.2.	<i>Feasibility of connection to the Valleiry motorway area</i>	495

13.4.3.	<i>Departmental roads connecting to the main road network</i>	499
13.4.4.	<i>Connection to local road network</i>	500
13.5.	SUMMARY OF THE PJ SITE	502
14.	THE PL SITE - CHALLEX (AIN, FRANCE)	503
14.1.	DESCRIPTION	503
14.2.	URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS	514
14.2.1.	<i>State of the premises</i>	514
14.2.2.	<i>Urban planning, architecture and landscape</i>	516
14.3.	ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS	517
14.4.	ACCESS ANALYSIS	524
14.4.1.	<i>Location in relation to main road network and railways</i>	524
14.4.2.	<i>Departmental roads connecting to the main road network</i>	531
14.4.3.	<i>Connection to local road network</i>	532
14.5.	SUMMARY OF THE PL SITE	537
15.	REFERENCE SCENARIO PA31-4.0	538
15.1.	INTRODUCTION	538
15.2.	CHARACTERISTICS AND PARAMETERS OF THE PA31-4.0 SCENARIO	539
15.2.1.	<i>Characteristics</i>	539
15.2.2.	<i>Parameters</i>	541
15.2.3.	<i>Performance of scenario</i>	543
15.2.4.	<i>Establish of inventories of natural heritage</i>	544
15.3.	THE PA SITE IN FERNEY-VOLTAIRE (FRANCE)	545
15.3.1.	<i>Description of the surface site</i>	545
15.3.2.	<i>Constraints</i>	546
15.3.3.	<i>Synergies and potential</i>	546
15.4.	THE PB SITE IN PRESINGE (SWITZERLAND)	547
15.4.1.	<i>Description of the surface site</i>	547
15.4.2.	<i>Constraints</i>	548
15.4.3.	<i>Synergies and potential</i>	548
15.5.	THE PD SITE IN NANGY (FRANCE)	549
15.5.1.	<i>Description of the surface site</i>	549
15.5.2.	<i>Constraints</i>	549
15.5.3.	<i>Synergies and potential</i>	550
15.6.	THE PF SITE IN ETEAUX (FRANCE)	551
15.6.1.	<i>Description of the surface site</i>	551
15.6.2.	<i>Constraints</i>	552

15.6.3.	<i>Synergies and potential</i>	552
15.7.	THE PG SITE IN CHARVONNEX AND GROISY (FRANCE).....	553
15.7.1.	<i>Description of the surface site</i>	553
15.7.2.	<i>Constraints</i>	553
15.7.3.	<i>Synergies and potential</i>	554
15.8.	THE PH SITE IN CERCIER AND MARLIOZ (FRANCE)	555
15.8.1.	<i>Description of the surface site</i>	555
15.8.2.	<i>Constraints</i>	555
15.8.3.	<i>Synergies and potential</i>	556
15.9.	THE PJ SITE IN DINGY-EN-VUACHE AND VULBENS (FRANCE)	557
15.9.1.	<i>Description of the surface site</i>	557
15.9.2.	<i>Constraints</i>	557
15.9.3.	<i>Synergies and potential</i>	558
15.10.	THE PL SITE IN CHALLEX (FRANCE)	559
15.10.1.	<i>Description of the surface site</i>	559
15.10.2.	<i>Constraints</i>	560
15.10.3.	<i>Synergies and potential</i>	567
15.11.	FEASIBILITY OF SURFACE SITES	568
16.	ANNEXES	570
16.1.	SOURCE OF ILLUSTRATIONS	570
16.2.	DATA USED AND AREA OF RELEVANCE	570
16.3.	LIST OF CADASTRAL PLOTS FOR EACH SITE IN SCENARIO PA31-4.0	573
16.4.	INTERDEPARTMENTAL CANTONAL UNIT FOR CERN PROJECTS	577

1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides an introduction to the report, followed by guidelines summarizing the main constraints to be taken into account when determining a footprint. The chapter ends with an overview of the contents of this report.

1.1. STUDY OF THE FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER

The Future Circular Collider (FCC) feasibility study aims to develop a high-level concept and designs for a new research infrastructure to host the next generation of high-performance particle colliders, with the aim of broadening and deepening particle physics research once the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) research program comes to an end, around 2040.

The aim of this new research program is to push back the energy and intensity limits of particle colliders, with the ultimate goal of reaching collision energies on the order of 100 TeV, in the search for new physics. The program calls for two particle colliders to be installed and operated successively in a new underground facility with a circumference of between 90 and 100 km. This scientific research program, with these two machines, will continue until the end of the 21st century.

This study was requested by the world particle physics research community in the 2013¹ and 2020² updates of the European Strategy for Particle Physics. It is being conducted through an international collaboration of some 150 universities, research institutes and industrial partners from all over the world. They are developing concepts for two circular colliders, new detectors for experiments at the collision points and the technical infrastructure required to operate these facilities, as well as cost estimates, global implementation scenarios and appropriate governance structures.

The new particle colliders would be located in a quasi-circular underground facility consisting of a tunnel at a depth of between 150 and 500 m, depending on the topography, as well as caverns and shafts. Depending on the scenario being considered, eight to twelve access sites are planned at regular intervals for construction work, equipment installation and the provision of the necessary technical services (e.g. electricity, cooling water, cryogenic cooling systems, ventilation, telecommunications, offices and workshops, access roads to technical facilities, etc.). The area required for surface sites would average around 5 ha, only part of which would be used for technical buildings and facilities. The remaining surface area will be used to integrate the sites into their environment, landscape, and urban context.

The location of access sites to the tunnel and caverns depends on the geometrical configuration constraints imposed by the physical laws governing the operation of the particle accelerator. These shafts and sites can therefore only be relocated within certain limits, and subject to a case-by-case assessment of the impact on technical feasibility.

The particle beams, which travel in opposite directions in two independent vacuum tubes, intersect at several points (up to four) so that the particles can collide. It is at these intersections that particle interactions are studied, using detectors placed in large underground caverns. Access shafts must be positioned directly above these large caverns to allow for the installation and operation of particle detector equipment, and cannot be moved.

The infrastructure would be located in an area straddling Swiss and French territory. The tunnel would pass under Lake Geneva, as well as under the Arve and the Rhône rivers. The surface sites would be located in the Canton of Geneva, Switzerland, and in the French departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie.

The locations of the surface sites for the technical facilities are optimised according to the "Avoid - Reduce -

¹ https://cds.cern.ch/record/1551933/files/Strategy_Report_LR.pdf

² <https://home.cern/sites/default/files/2020-06/2020%20Update%20European%20Strategy.pdf>

Compensate" principles (ERC sequence of the French environmental code, article R122-5), by taking into account the constraints relating to the design of the particle collider and the territorial issues identified at the current stage, particularly in terms of urban planning, nature, agriculture, and many other aspects, with a view to limiting the impact while at the same time having a world-class scientific facility.

In order to reconcile the objectives for scientific excellence with objectives for territorial compatibility, the study group adopted the ERC approach, which also takes into account the risks associated with the project's implementation.

1.2. SUMMARY OF THE GUIDELINES FOR SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT

This section summarises the guidelines for developing a well-balanced project scenario. These guidelines were developed gradually, following eight years of studies on the configuration and location of the FCC.

- **Install** the underground structures, as much as possible, **in the molasse layer**, avoiding karstic limestone formations, risks of high-pressure water penetration, faults and areas of seismic instability, as well as significant overburden.
- Provide a technically feasible **connection to CERN's SPS** underground infrastructure **and**, if possible, to the **LHC** infrastructure.
- Dig the tunnel to a **sufficient depth below the lake bed** to ensure stability. The minimum depth will be defined by specific underground studies. The current assumption is 100 m below the lake bed.
- Dig the tunnel **deep enough under the Arve, Rhône and Usses rivers** to guarantee the micro-stability required for precise alignment of the accelerator.
- **Limit overburden** under the **Mandallaz, Fillière and Bornes** zones (minimum depth to be defined by specific underground studies).
- **Avoid elevations above 750 m** for surface sites, to limit the depth of shafts and ensure good site accessibility.
- Aim for **shaft depths of less than 250 m for scientific sites and 400 m for technical sites**.
- **Avoid** areas considered "**exclusion zones**" (in red) **in the territorial sensitivity grids** drawn up with partners in France (Cerema, grid reviewed by the *Direction Départementale du Territoire* and the *Direction Régionale de l'Environnement, de l'Aménagement et du Logement*) and Switzerland (Ecotec, reviewed by the DT services). These grids list environmental, urban planning and strategic constraints, as well as public health and safety constraints.
- **Give preference to close proximity for strategic project infrastructures** (e.g. pipelines, power lines, certain types of roads, railway lines) and stay clear of other infrastructures (e.g. geothermal probes, gas pipelines, oil pipelines).
- **Remain outside of town and village centres and hamlets**.
- As far as possible, avoid areas subject to particular territorial constraints (orange) or **reduce surface areas** in these zones.
- **Respect the fact that it is not possible to modify** the locations planned for **scientific sites** where particle beam lines cross.
- **Respect the limits for moving technical sites** along the ring, as these limits are determined by the ends of the straight sections, according to the possibilities offered by the various systems required on the technical sites for the operation of the accelerators.
- Consider the constraint for **positioning the shafts inside the ring** from the point of view of facilitating access to the transport zone in the tunnel.
- **Limit the length to around 400 m for the horizontal connection tunnels** from the technical sites to the shafts inside the ring. Building a longer tunnel is not out of the question but it would entail additional costs and difficulties.
- **If technically possible, limit the surface area of technical sites to 5 ha and the surface area of experiment sites to 8 ha**. These areas include buffer zones and take account of renaturation, reconstitution, replacement, or compensation measures. Wherever possible, seek synergies with existing infrastructures to reduce surface areas.
- **Avoid areas with difficult topography** (steep and potentially unstable slopes, unstable soils, areas at risk of flooding, discontinuous terrain).
- Ensure **adequate road connections** (7 m wide, 2 lanes, 20 m curvature radius, gradient well below 10%, minimum height of 4.4 m, compatibility with heavy goods vehicles of at least 44 t to the main road network in accordance with article R312 of the French highway code).

- Maintain a **minimum distance between residential areas and sites**. Depending on topographical conditions and the site's noise and visibility attenuation features, this minimum distance can be as much as 250 to 300 m, with a minimum distance of 100 m.
- **Avoid natural and historic heritage sites**, avoiding shared visibility between the sites.
- **Preserve as far as possible the views and landscape protection zones** as indicated.
- **Avoid rivers and streams** (to avoid having to modify or stabilise riverbanks).
- **Avoid wetlands** and protected areas.
- **Avoid protected forests** because of the need to clear them and **preserve existing biodiversity**; and because of their inaccessibility and topography, unless these areas are decisive choices to ensure feasibility.
- **Avoid protected agricultural areas/SDA surfaces (crop rotation areas)**, unless they are decisive choices to ensure feasibility.
- **Give preference to areas in close proximity to high-capacity power lines** (225 kV and 400 kV).
- **Look for opportunities with a connection or access to the motorway system.**
- **Look for opportunities with a connection or access to the railway system.**
- **Consider the use of known brownfield sites** for the installation of technical infrastructures that may be remote from the sites (e.g. electrical substations, pumping stations, cooling towers) and for the development of compensation areas.
- Look for scenarios that enable **all surface sites to be reached within a reasonable time** (30 minutes by car) **from strategic service and supply points** (e.g. CERN and LAPP).
- **Avoid creating new border crossings** and do not consider sites on both sides of the border.
- **Avoid vineyards and areas with fruit trees.**
- **Give preference to public land** over private land, undeveloped land over developed land, unused land over used land (special agricultural uses such as vineyards and protected fruit crops) and brownfields.

1.3. READING GUIDE FOR THIS REPORT

Chapter 1 provides an introduction to the report, followed by guidelines summarizing the main constraints to be taken into account when determining a footprint. The chapter ends with an overview of the contents of this report.

Chapter 2 describes the method for creating a site scenario. In particular, it details the stages of the iterative Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) approach:

- the initial data to be taken into account (e.g. characteristics of the FCC and territorial and underground constraints);
- the proposal of a scenario based on points of interest;
- the multi-criteria analysis to assess the relevance of the footprint and identify areas for improvement in subsequent iterations;
- the adjustment of the scenario from an ERC perspective, leading to the proposal of an improved scenario.

It also presents some concrete examples illustrating the ERC approach.

Chapter 3 sets out the background elements resulting in the need for a location scenario in the Franco-Swiss border region. It explains why alternative scenarios to the west of the Jura were examined, then discarded in favour of scenarios to the east of the Jura. It then reviews how the layout considered during the exploratory phase of the FCC study (2014-2018) demonstrated the feasibility of the FCC, and how the precise layout examined presented prohibitive obstacles in certain locations. Finally, it mentions the variant involving a linear collider, which was not selected.

Chapter 4 provides details, for each site, of the areas that are suitable for the layout and those that present constraints. Next, the conditions are listed that must be met by all acceptable scenarios (absolute necessities) and the conditions that the project owner has defined to make the scenario more acceptable at the territorial level (voluntary objectives).

Chapter 5 traces the changes made to the scenarios according to the iterative Avoid-Reduce-Compensate approach. First of all, it emphasises the constant evolution of the region, and the ever-increasing constraints, which limit the opportunities for new layouts. The main characteristics of the scenario now selected as the preferred scenario, PA31-1.0, are outlined, followed by a historical overview of how the main scenario types were developed. Three scenarios with twelve sites are presented first, followed by four scenarios with eight sites, which offer a more favourable layout. Section 5.5 compares all the scenario types detailed above, and shows that this iterative approach has resulted in the selection of a balanced scenario. Finally, the micro-improvements made to the preferred PA31-1.0 scenario are described, which, through an iterative process, led to the PA31-2.0, PA31-3.0 and finally PA31-4.0 scenarios, the most accomplished and well-balanced.

Chapter 6 describes the major constraints on the ring in France and Switzerland, and reviews the current regulations. The main issues relating to the layout are presented according to various subjects: topography, surface water and groundwater, biodiversity, risks, populations, landscapes, urban planning documents, noise, networks, potential waste heat networks, water requirements, electricity requirements and supply strategy, access, and the needs of required surface sites and the users of these sites. The chapter therefore takes a closer look at some of the resource requirements for the FCC. Finally, details of surface sites are provided.

Chapters 7 to 14 give a detailed presentation of each of the eight surface sites. The description of the site and its environment is followed by an urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (current constraints) and an analysis of access, particularly connections to the railway, highway and local road networks.

Chapter 15 provides an overview of the most successful and balanced scenario, PA31-4.0, its characteristics and overall performance, and then details the configuration of the various surface sites.

Chapter 16 contains appendices:

- source of illustrations;
- data used and area of relevance ;
- list of cadastral plots for each site;
- cantonal interdepartmental cell structure (Switzerland).

2. SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

Chapter 2 presents the method for developing a layout scenario. In particular, it provides details of the steps involved in an **iterative³ eco-design process based on the "Avoid-Reduce-Compensate" (ERC) approach**:

- the initial data to be taken into account, such as the characteristics of the FCC and the territorial and underground constraints;
- the proposal of a scenario based on points of interest;
- the multi-criteria analysis, in order to assess the relevance of the footprint and identify areas for improvement in subsequent iterations;
- the adjustments to the scenario through application of the ERC approach, which enables the scenario to be improved.

Lastly, a few concrete examples illustrating the ERC approach are proposed.

³ This approach complements the one adopted by the environmental management system (EMS), presented in ISO 14001. The implementation of an EMS helps to reduce the environmental impact of all the organization's activities, including all products and services. Reducing the impact of all products and services helps to achieve the EMS target objectives, which focus on eco-design projects according to the priorities set. These two approaches complement each other in the eco-design project. The concept of compromise is what makes the eco-design approach relevant. It plays a key role in this approach, as it impacts the organization's competitiveness and its ability to take account of environmental issues while sustaining its business. In fact, eco-design is part of a continuous improvement process: as the context evolves, the environmental impact of the product or service in question is regularly reassessed, with the aim of reducing it even further.

2.1. PURPOSE

To study the feasibility of a research infrastructure that will host the next generation of CERN accelerators, it is necessary to develop a specific scenario that fits into the local territorial context.

A scenario (Illustration 1) is characterised, on the one hand, by a layout (a footprint including surface sites that provide access to underground infrastructures), together with the allocation of technical systems to the access sites (the "configuration") and, on the other hand, by the location of the configuration within the territory. The location is identified by the coordinates of a fixed point on the layout (e.g. point A, named "PA"), the angle of rotation of the layout around this fixed point (named "azimuth"), the elevation of the tunnel floor (which lies on a single plane), the point on the footprint where the underground infrastructure plane is inclined, and an angle of inclination of less than 1%.

Illustration 1: Elements of a scenario.

The "layout" is determined solely by calculations and simulations of the physical validity of the particle beam lines. It therefore does not take into account the allocation of functions to the various sites or the choice of a specific location (see preliminary conceptual design report, CDR⁴, drawn up between 2014 and 2018, whose sole purpose is to determine technical feasibility). It is necessary to formulate a working hypothesis based on a specific configuration and location in order to determine the feasibility of the project in terms of territorial aspects and implementation issues.

⁴ <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1140/epjst/e2019-900045-4.pdf>

2.2. OBJECTIVE

From the outset, the objective of the study was **to draw up a scientific research program that reconciles, in an eco-design approach, 1) scientific excellence, 2) territorial compatibility and 3) consideration of acceptable risks associated with project implementation.** A systematic process therefore had to be set up to develop scenarios through an iterative approach, taking these three essential aspects into account at all times (Illustration 2).

Illustration 2: Three key performance indicators taken into account throughout the configuration and layout study. The aim is to achieve a balanced scenario that meets the following acceptance criteria: 1) territorial compatibility, 2) project implementation risks and 3) high scientific value likely to mobilise a worldwide research community for several decades.

The objective of the configuration and layout process is to develop scenarios that are compatible with existing requirements and constraints, so that they can be used as a reference for a more detailed study at a later date. The baseline scenario can then be presented to the three main stakeholders:

- 1) **the global scientific community**, which needs a sufficiently powerful infrastructure to achieve world-class excellence;
- 2) **the host countries** (France and Switzerland), who are the final judges of territorial compatibility;
- 3) **the funding bodies** for a project of this scale, who must be able to decide to invest in the project based on acceptable implementation risks.

The eco-design approach adopts the "**Avoid-Reduce-Compensate**" methodology, **which takes into account both constraints and opportunities** (Illustration 3).

This process, which was conducted in compliance with the French Environmental Code, the Environmental Protection Act and the Swiss Federal Ordinance relating to the Environmental Impact Assessment Regulation, is perfectly in line with the desire and **objective to arrive at a balanced scenario proposal.**

Illustration 3: The "Avoid-Reduce-Compensate" sequence.⁵

Ideally, all stakeholders are involved in the process from the outset. However, an iterative approach seems necessary given the limited knowledge of the technological choices to be made for periods longer than twenty years, the incomplete knowledge of changing territorial conditions, the limited possibilities of effectively involving stakeholders at all levels of society, and the limited availability of funds for conceptual studies and human resources. A process of this type uses the information available at the time of the studies. It gradually integrates other aspects and stakeholders as they are identified. This is the case, for example, for the participation of local representatives (municipalities, intercommunal structures, departments, regions, state government): depending on the configuration, the number of surface sites and their location, between twelve and twenty communes will be directly concerned and will need to be consulted (Illustration 4 below). A further 30 or so municipalities could be indirectly affected, in terms of access needs or infrastructure services (electricity, water, etc.), or simply because the tunnel passes under their territory. To this core group of people whose participation is necessary, other stakeholders will need to be added, such as local infrastructure operators (e.g. water, canals or road networks), representatives of local authorities responsible for certain subjects (e.g. traffic or nature) and associations (hunting, fishing, tourism, economic development, etc.). It seems prudent to approach these representatives as soon as the probability of their community being affected in some way is sufficiently high, in order to take into account their availability to be informed about the project vision, to designate the relevant contacts and to take into account the limited availability of the study group members (see Illustration 4 below for an example of municipalities directly or indirectly affected within the framework of a particular scenario).

⁵ French Ministry of Ecological Transition and Solidarity, "Les cahiers de BIODIV'2050 : Inventer, Guide d'aide au suivi des mesures d'évitement, de réduction et de compensation des impacts d'un projet sur les milieux naturels", no. 13 - April 2019.

Illustration 4: Overview of the layout scenario in the region, based on the current working hypothesis (reference scenario PA31-4.0), and specifying the municipalities and intercommunal structures potentially concerned, either directly or indirectly, in France (the Ain and Haute-Savoie departments) and Switzerland (Canton of Geneva).

An iterative approach, as presented in the international standards NF EN ISO 14001 (environmental management) and NF EN ISO 14006 (eco-design) has been adopted (Illustration 5).

Illustration 5: The *Plan-Do-Check-Act* model for environmental management, defined in standard NF EN ISO 14001, section 0.4, page vii, is the basis for "eco-design".

This approach is also set out in greater detail in the good practices guidelines for environmental impact assessments ⁶ established by the French Ministry of the Environment, and in standard NF EN ISO 31000 on risk management (page 8 of the ISO standard) (see also Illustration 6).

Illustration 6: Diagram from iterative impact study, French Ministry of Territorial Development and the Environment, 2001, p. 27, see footnote 6). It should be noted that, although this guide is old and regulations have changed considerably, the principles described in the diagram are still valid today. The words "Eliminate, reduce or compensate for harmful effects" could be replaced by "Avoid-Reduce-Compensate". For up-to-date regulatory information, please refer to the guide *L'évaluation environnementale des projets d'infrastructures linéaires de transport*, Cerema, 2022⁷.

⁶ Ministère de l'Aménagement du territoire et de l'Environnement (Ministry of Territorial Development and the Environment): *L'étude d'impact sur l'environnement*, 2001, p. 27 : <http://temis.documentation.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/document.html?id=Temis-0061372&requestId=0&number=1>

⁷ <https://www.cerema.fr/fr/centre-ressources/boutique/evaluation-environnementale-projets-infrastructures>

2.3. SUPPORT FROM FRANCE AND SWITZERLAND

As an international organization, CERN depends on the active support and guidance of its host countries, France and Switzerland, particularly in terms of involving the public and their representatives in current and future initiatives. This is why, as soon as exploratory studies began in February 2014, CERN informed the public authorities of the two host countries⁸ in writing of a study relating to a future research infrastructure for which CERN would provide the operating platform. This first phase of work brought together various departments in Switzerland⁹, while in France¹⁰, the Prefect of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region assigned informal working groups to analyse the administrative processes required to prepare and implement such a project in each host country, identifying the most critical points to be addressed at an early stage, and devising a process for drawing up a territorial scenario. The results of this cooperation, in particular the documents relating to the methodology, were sent to the President of the Council of State of the Republic and Canton of Geneva¹¹ and presented to the Prefect of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region, as well as to the Prefects of the Haute-Savoie and Ain departments¹². They were accompanied by a proposal to establish a dialogue aimed at best addressing the various processes in order to effectively pursue the study activities.

Immediately after the preliminary conceptual design report phase, CERN, as host of the international collaboration for the FCC, thanked the Prefect of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region and asked for support by cooperating on the next phase of this study¹³. At the start of 2020, CERN sent the Prefect of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region a proposal to set up a specific working structure, thereby reinforcing this continuing cooperation¹⁴.

In December 2021, the Canton of Geneva set up a cantonal interdepartmental unit to support CERN projects and coordinate exploratory studies (see also Appendix 16.4).

⁸ Personal letters from the Director-General of CERN to the President of the Geneva Council of State, the Prefect of Ain, the Prefect of Haute-Savoie, the President of the Ain General Council, the President of the Haute-Savoie General Council, the President of the Rhône-Alpes Regional Council, a number of deputies from Ain and Haute-Savoie, the Secretary of State for Education, Research and Innovation in Switzerland, 4 February 2014.

⁹ A working group on future projects was set up, bringing together the Permanent Mission of Switzerland to international organizations, the Swiss Federal Department of Foreign Affairs and the Département du Territoire of the Canton of Geneva.

¹⁰ Informal working sessions were held with the General Secretariat for Regional Affairs (SGAR) of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Prefecture, as well as regular working meetings convened by the Prefect of the region, with the participation of Cerema and CETU as technical bodies supporting both CERN and the SGAR.

¹¹ Letter from the Prefect of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region to the President of the Council of State of the Republic and Canton of Geneva, 5 June 2018.

¹² Meeting with the prefect of the region and the prefects of the Haute-Savoie and Ain departments on 10 October 2018 at the prefecture of the region in Lyon, 106 rue Corneille, salle Jean Moulin, from 2:30 to 4:30 pm. Objectives of the meeting: 1) provide first-hand information on the FCC study by CERN and CEREMA to key French government officials in the two departments potentially concerned by the FCC, 2) make these officials aware of the land management issues in advance, and 3) inform them of the need to organise information exchanges with elected representatives and the highest level of government.

¹³ Letter from FCC study manager to SGAR (France), 3 June 2020.

¹⁴ Letter from Director-General of CERN to the Prefect of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region, 6 February 2020.

On 10 March 2023¹⁵, the Federal Council decided to open the consultation on the draft amendment to the Law on the Promotion of Research and Innovation (LERI). This initiative follows on from the decision taken on 10 December 2021, to launch work on a federal sectoral plan focusing on the projects of the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN). This plan will provide the framework within which the various interests involved will be taken into account. The draft amendment calls for a division of powers between the Canton of Geneva and the Confederation with regard to the approval of plans for CERN buildings and facilities. In February 2024, the Federal Council approved this amendment to the LERI.

Starting in spring 2023, CERN, accompanied by the French government, met with representatives of the Ain and Haute-Savoie departments and departmental councils, as well as with the technical services of the Canton of Geneva and the municipalities potentially affected by the footprint of PA31 in both countries, to engage in discussions with stakeholders on the technical feasibility of this research infrastructure. The aim was also to identify the needs and constraints expressed by local players, and to plan discussions to identify potential synergies between the research infrastructure and the local regions. France sent comments on 30 November 2023¹⁶. This feedback was taken into account in the modifications to version 1.0 of scenario PA31 in order to develop the reference scenario, version 4.0, presented in chapter 15. This version has been used as the basis for considering plots of land in France, so that an in-depth study can be conducted starting in December 2023. In Switzerland, the identified plots were communicated to the Canton of Geneva in writing.

Optimization of surface site locations continues in collaboration with the concerned municipalities. From summer 2024 onwards, more detailed subsurface studies will be conducted in areas where geological knowledge is lacking, using geophysical measurements and geotechnical investigations.

¹⁵ <https://www.admin.ch/gov/fr/accueil/documentation/communiqués.msg-id-93632.html>

¹⁶ Letter from the Prefect of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region to CERN Management dated as of 30 November 2023.

2.4. SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The scenario development process is based on the iterative Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) approach, and incorporates the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) approach (Illustration 7).

Illustration 7: Illustration of the iterative process for developing the site location scenario during the initial phase of the feasibility study. The aim of this process is to develop scenarios that can be submitted for a subsequent, more detailed feasibility study. Given the regional changes and the improved knowledge of geological and hydrogeological conditions compared to the 2014-2018 period, only one type of scenario capable of meeting the requirements of the scientific research program could finally be retained for further study.

This process aims to determine a configuration and location for the research infrastructure that combines the pursuit of scientific excellence necessary to attract a large number of scientists from all over the world (over 15,000) through to the end of the 21st century, while considering territorial requirements and constraints, as well as various aspects of project implementation (planning, technical and financial risks).

It starts at a macroscopic level and progressively refines the choices made between the various configurations and locations under consideration, introducing additional information obtained from the study of promising variants and discarding variants as soon as obstacles are detected (Illustration 8). With regards to the territorial analyses, the process begins at a level that considers topography, bathymetry, geology, hydrography, protection of the environment and nature, and urban development. It then gradually expands to include additional aspects such as accessibility, transportation, disturbances, potentially conflicting planned developments, and the availability of technical and natural resources (e.g. electricity or water). It then incorporates additional elements, such as social factors, local preservation and development objectives, visibility, shared visibility, or disturbances for stakeholders affected directly (e.g. neighbours) and indirectly (e.g. communities affected by construction site traffic).

Lastly, the scenario-building process requires a more detailed analysis phase, aimed at obtaining the direct participation of stakeholders and local players in order to draw up a scenario adapted to the specific plot of land, always taking into account the three main issues (science, region, project) within the framework of an ERC approach.

As new information is integrated into this iterative process, automated and cartographic research must be progressively completed, followed by manual research, interviews with people with good knowledge of the region, field visits and consultation with stakeholders.

Illustration 8: As the configuration and location study progresses, additional information and stakeholders are included in the process to create a balanced scenario that meets the needs of all stakeholders.

2.5. REQUIREMENTS AND CONSTRAINTS (STEP 1, PLAN)

2.5.1. Territorial sensitivity grid

The first step is to identify local constraints using a sensitivity grid. The technical aspects of this grid were established during the preliminary conceptual design report phase with Cerema in France¹⁷ and with Ecotec in Switzerland¹⁸. It defines a list of elements to be taken into account at the surface level and underground, and groups them into four categories according to their constraint level, as shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Territorial sensitivity levels representing constraints for determining the configuration and location. Each colour-coded level represents several different data layers that can be shown on a map.

Level	Colour and designation	Description:
4	Unacceptable	The level of constraint is such that the zone cannot be considered for a surface site. These zones are considered to be exclusion zones and should be avoided .
3	High	The zone is not recommended for the location of a surface site, but may be considered if it is decisive for the feasibility of the project, with additional reduction, compensation, or mitigation measures.
2	Acceptable	The zone is acceptable for the location of a surface site with appropriate reduction, compensation or mitigation measures.
1	Low	The zone can be considered for a surface site without further significant measures . Compensation may still be necessary.

The different constraints¹⁹ considered for each of the four levels on French and Swiss territory are described in Table 2 (exclusion zones in red), Table 3 (undesirable zones, in orange) and Table 4 (acceptable zones, in yellow)²⁰. A geographic information system is used to create layers with different appearances and colour coding on the maps, making it easier to determine suitable and unsuitable sites for further studies.

¹⁷ A. Bibet-Chevalier, D. Chanal, J. Maître, F. Menez, N. Simand, C. Tetrel, J-M. Valet, *Étude de sensibilité du scénario d'implantation du projet FCC en France et de ses opportunités*, Cerema, FCC-INF-RPT-0040, 26 April 2018.

¹⁸ M. Zahnd, *FCC layout review in Switzerland*, Ecotec, FCC-INF-RPT-0007, 13 December 2017.

¹⁹ The grid of regional constraints was defined during the initial study phase conducted from 2014 to 2018 with public and private partners in France and Switzerland. Further information can be found in the FCC-2004171130, V2.0 project file. The grid was updated by the Setec/Ecotec/Marceleon consortium. The document is available through the following public link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13771877>

²⁰ The modifications implemented in Tables 2, 3 and 4 after V03.00 of the present document cannot be considered in the Environmental Initial State Analysis since they have been introduced once the EISA is very advanced.

*Table 2: **Exclusion zones (in red)**, to be avoided at all costs in France and Switzerland (FCC-2004171130 V2.0 of 8 December 2021). In France, the technical criteria have been established with Cerema and integrated into the 2018 report¹⁷ which has been submitted to the SGAR. In Switzerland, the criteria were drawn up on the basis of the ECOTEC report and reviewed by the Swiss Département du Territoire.*

France	Switzerland
<p>Drinking water catchment: immediate and close perimeter.</p> <p>Red zone for a natural hazard prevention plan (PPRN) for flooding or landslides, and/or technological risk prevention plan.</p> <p>Wetlands inventory.</p> <p>Regional peatland inventory.</p> <p>Natura 2000 zone: ZSC (Special Area of Conservation) and ZPS (Special Protection Area) - priority habitats or species.</p> <p>Downgrading to orange could be considered, if necessary, if it is established that the zone does not contain priority habitats or species.</p> <p>Biotope protection order (APB) and other regulatory zones: RNN (National Natural Reserve), RNR (Regional Natural Reserve), RBI (Integral Biological Reserve), RBD (Directed Biological Reserve), ENS (Environmentally Sensitive Area), centre of PN (National Park).</p> <p>Environmentally Sensitive Area or protected natural area (Np).</p> <p>Unbuildable area associated with a watercourse.</p> <p>Conflict with the main road and rail network.</p> <p>Conflict with existing underground structures: easement I1 relating to pipelines of general interest.</p> <p>Conflict with future projects identified and detailed in the PLU (urban development plan).</p> <p>Conflict with densely-populated residential areas.</p> <p>Registered site under the law of 1930.</p> <p>Listed site under the law of 1930.</p> <p>Known archaeological site.</p>	<p>Federal nature conservation inventory.</p> <p>Alluvial plain and marshland area of national importance.</p> <p>Prairie and dry grassland of national importance.</p> <p>Landscape of national importance.</p> <p>Ordinance on waterfowl and migratory bird reserves (OROEM).</p> <p>Ordinance on the protection of amphibian breeding sites of national importance (OBat).</p> <p>Emerald site.</p> <p>Cantonal nature reserve.</p> <p>Renatured area.</p> <p>Ramsar Convention site.</p> <p>Sector where geothermal boreholes are prohibited.</p> <p>Water protection zones (RDPPF).</p> <p>Sector Au - groundwater protection area.</p> <p>Sector B - groundwater protection area.</p> <p>Sector Ao - surface water protection area.</p> <p>Unbuildable area associated with a watercourse.</p> <p>Minimum space reserved for the watercourse.</p> <p>Protected vineyards.</p> <p>Federal inventory of construction sites of national importance to be protected in Switzerland (ISOS).</p> <p>Site plans.</p> <p>Conflict with the main road and rail network.</p> <p>Conflict with existing underground structures.</p> <p>Heating pipes.</p> <p>Diverse points.</p> <p>Telecom tubes.</p> <p>Diverse surfaces.</p> <p>Heating probes.</p> <p>Diverse pipes.</p> <p>Geotechnical surfaces.</p>

	<p>Geotechnical lines.</p> <p>Geotechnical points.</p> <p>Heating probe zones.</p> <p>Conflict with future projects.</p> <p>Conflict with waste disposal facilities.</p> <p>Conflict with gravel pits.</p> <p>Federal inventory of historic transport routes of Switzerland (IVS).</p> <p>Federal inventory of landscapes, sites and natural monuments (IFP).</p> <p>UNESCO sites (pile-dwelling sites in the lake).</p> <p>Other archaeological sites.</p> <p>Protected village areas (4B protected).</p> <p>Protected development areas (ZD 4A protected and ZD 4B protected).</p> <p>Hamlet zones (LaLAT).</p> <p>Protected natural perimeters (LPRArve, LPRLac, LPRRhône, LPRVers).</p> <p>Classified objects and objects listed in the inventory.</p>
--	--

Table 3: Undesirable zones (in orange) for which, if they cannot be avoided, the impact must be reduced on a case-by-case basis for a specific scenario (FCC-2004171130 V2.0 of December 8, 2021). In France, the criteria have been established on a technical level with Cerema and integrated into the 2018 report¹⁷ which has been submitted to the SGAR. In Switzerland, the criteria were drawn up on the basis of the ECOTEC report and reviewed by the Swiss Département du Territoire.

France	Switzerland
<p>Protective perimeter for historic monuments.</p> <p>Compensation site following on requests for exemption from the destruction of protected species and/or laws governing water and/or areas identified as to be avoided by development projects as part of avoidance measures.</p> <p>Site home to known protected species.</p> <p>Zoning linked to national plans of actions for threatened species (PNA).</p> <p>Habitat for known protected species.</p> <p>Natural Zone of Interest for Ecology, Flora, and Fauna (ZNIEFF) type 1.</p> <p>Priority zone for bird preservation (ZICO).</p> <p>Classified wooded area (EBC).</p> <p>Ecological corridor to be preserved in the PLU (local urban plan).</p> <p>Zoning AU (for urbanisation) of the PLU (local urban plan) when there are no OAPs (Planning and Development Guidelines) or regulations.</p> <p>Protected agricultural zoning (Ap) with landscape or ecological interest. Prefectoral decree.</p> <p>Drinking water catchment: remote perimeter.</p> <p>Biodiversity reservoir in the regional ecological coherence scheme (SRCE).</p> <p>Historic monument protected by the local urban plan (PLU).</p> <p>Polluted soil registered in the BASOL database (a national database that collects and keeps a record of several thousand "polluted or potentially polluted sites and soils").</p>	<p>Cantonal nature protection inventory.</p> <p>Natural environments worthy of protection, and protected flora and fauna according to the annexes of the Ordinance on Nature and Landscape Protection (OPN).</p> <p>Forest.</p> <p>Area listed in the land registry of polluted sites.</p> <p>SDA (crop rotation area) surface.</p> <p>Protection against noise - sensitivity level I.</p> <p>Sensitive surface waters.</p> <p>Flood hazard zone.</p> <p>Conflict with existing structures.</p>

*Table 4: **Acceptable zones (in yellow)** for which the impact must always be reduced through limited efforts, on a case-by-case basis, for a specific scenario (FCC-2004171130 V2.0 of December 8, 2021). In France, the technical criteria were established with Cerema and integrated into the 2018 report¹⁷ which was submitted to the SGAR. In Switzerland, the criteria were drawn up on the basis of the ECOTEC report and reviewed by the Swiss Département du Territoire.*

France	Switzerland
Unprotected agricultural zone (A) or natural environment (N).	All other sectors and objects to be protected of importance to communities.
Unprotected forest.	Wildlife corridor of regional and supra-regional importance.
Ecological corridor SRCE (regional ecological coherence scheme).	Flora priority site.
Natural Zone of Interest for Ecology, Flora, and Fauna (ZNIEFF) type 2.	Wildlife priority site.
Blue or white zone of a natural hazard prevention plan.	Inventory of historic communication routes in Switzerland (IVS).
National hunting and wildlife reserve (RNCFS).	Protection against noise - sensitivity level II.
Easement PT1: protection of radio reception centres against electromagnetic interference.	Unstable zones.
	OPAM through constructive measures.
	Agricultural areas in the canton of Geneva excluding crop rotation areas (SDA).

By applying the "Avoid" approach, the analysis eliminates all the exclusion zones shown in red, right from the early development stages of the initial scenario at the macroscopic level. It should be emphasised that, in all cases, the scenario development process also aims to avoid areas already developed if they are considered to be in active use (e.g. residences, farms, parking lots, industrial buildings and public infrastructure). Only brownfields or buildings that can be reliably described as unused (ruined houses, abandoned industrial warehouse, etc.) are examined on a case-by-case basis. In addition, for all the surface sites taken into consideration, choices have been made to avoid clearing protected forests, as well as destroying wetlands and hedgerows in agricultural areas.

Zones classified as "orange" are generally avoided, but a more detailed manual analysis of the underlying rationale for this classification is always conducted to understand whether and under what conditions such a zone might be considered for certain parts of the research infrastructure. This step requires a more detailed study of the different layers of constraint that make up the overall layers. It also requires additional information that the regional and local planning authorities of the two host countries are best placed to provide (for example, the various offices of the Département du Territoire and the Infrastructure Department of the canton of Geneva, the DREAL, the DDT 74 and the DDT 01 in France).

In France, the law of 22 August 2021, on combating climate change and strengthening resilience to its effects sets a target of zero net artificialisation of soils (ZAN). The ZAN initiative is a target set for 2050. It calls on local authorities, municipalities, departments, and regions to reduce the rate of artificialisation and consumption of natural, agricultural and forest areas by 50% by 2030, compared with the rate of consumption measured between 2011 and 2020. This constraint will have to be dealt with at the national level, as is the case for crop rotation areas (SDA) in Switzerland.

Right from the start of the studies, it became clear that there were no "green" areas in the two host countries with only negligible constraints. The minimum number of constraints in both countries corresponds to the "yellow" class, i.e. acceptable zones. In addition, Switzerland has special restrictions, imposed at the federal level, for a certain type of agricultural land known as crop rotation areas²¹ (SDA), the best arable land in Switzerland. A federal sectoral plan sets a minimum surface area to be maintained per canton (distributed among the cantons by quota). The Confederation monitors the maintaining of the minimum SDA area. Under certain conditions, SDAs can be allocated to specific projects, provided that all stakeholders at the federal and cantonal level agree and that the minimum is maintained. This constraint stemming from SDAs in the canton of Geneva is high, but the canton has been classified as an "orange" zone to leave open the possibility of downgrading and to provide an option for the FCC layout scenario. Specific coordination at the federal and cantonal levels is nevertheless required. Work has therefore been conducted with representatives of the canton, the Permanent Mission of Switzerland to International Organizations, and the Federal Department of Foreign Affairs to understand the legal constraints of a sectoral plan for CERN construction projects and facilities, and to allocate land for the development of such infrastructures²².

Agricultural areas in the canton of Geneva outside the SDAs are classified as acceptable "yellow" zones on the assumption that, if a scenario is validated at the administrative and political levels, a sectoral plan for CERN construction projects and installations could then be drawn up to enable a development project for this type of infrastructure to take root at the federal level. This sectoral plan will provide an instrument for land-use planning to solidly establish territorial decisions on the Swiss side, particularly with regard to the choice of surface land.

It is also important to point out that the initial classification of sensitivity layers is not fixed, but constantly changes as the territory evolves. Between 2014 and 2022, around 400 ha became "red" exclusion zones (unacceptable constraints) in the Haute-Savoie department. In the canton of Geneva, around 100 ha have been affected by new restrictions and are now part of the exclusion zones, mainly due to stricter surface and groundwater protection rules, resulting from improved knowledge of the subsurface. This led to the rejection of several candidate sites proposing a configuration and location initially considered as possible. These changes have made it even more difficult to continue developing scenarios, while at the same time highlighting the iterative aspect of the process.

²¹ <https://www.are.admin.ch/are/fr/home/developpement-et-amenagement-du-territoire/strategie-et-planification/conceptions-et-plans-sectoriels/plans-sectoriels-de-la-confederation/sda.html>

²² <https://www.admin.ch/gov/fr/accueil/documentation/communiqués/msg-id-86379.html>

Illustration 9: Examples of regional changes. Left: 17 ha of new exclusion zones in Ferney-Voltaire (France). Right: 790 ha of peatland inventory on the banks of the Rhone in France: in light red, previously orange zones that have become red zones.

Illustration 9 above shows two examples of these "lost spaces for layout scenarios". The first concerns sectors of Ferney-Voltaire that are now intended for a development project (6.3 ha for a hospital project north of the D35, "Route de Meyrin") and the classification of a sector as a compensation zone (2.8 ha south of the D35), which therefore cannot be compensated again. The second concerns a vast area north of the Rhone in France, which has been described as a "peatland inventory".

2.5.2. Underground constraints

Constraints include certain underground constraints, such as the presence of water protection zones (including the presence of strategic aquifers, buffer zones and no drilling zones among other), drinking water catchment areas, pipelines, power lines and gas mains, as well as reserved areas of public interest such as geothermal exploration zones.

An exclusion zone²³ has been defined by the geological consulting firms GADZ and ILF to take full account of geological conditions. These companies also examined the geological²⁴ and hydrological²⁵ situation documented by Cerema, based on the following elements:

- a) fault lines representing a sufficiently high risk of seismic activity and tunnelling problems;**
- b) interface between limestone and molasse;**
- c) potential high-pressure water penetrations or karstic formations that would expose the project to an unacceptable risk (Illustration 10).**

²³ ILF and GADZ *Geological high risk site investigation study*, ILF-SUI-OD-0004, report dated as of 9 October 2021.

²⁴ Cerema, *Pré faisabilité géologique et géotechnique*, report dated as of 8 September 2020.

²⁵ Cerema, *Synthèse des contraintes hydrogéologiques de pré faisabilité*, report dated as of 18 September 2020.

Given the experience gained from the construction of LEP underground structures and from the construction of underground transport structures in the region (e.g. the Vuache road tunnel), the risks of building a large tunnel and caverns, which could be unstable, move, collapse, or in which construction workers could be exposed to high-pressure water ingress that could lead to fatal accidents, are considered unacceptable and must be avoided. As far as possible, all underground structures should be located in the molasse layer, which forms a reliable barrier against aquifers.

Illustration 10 : Challenges posed by karstic limestone formations and high-pressure water tables.

Between 2014 and 2020, the project's initial study perimeter (shown in yellow in Illustration 11 below) had to be narrowed as additional knowledge was acquired and integrated into a 3D model of the subsurface (shown in red on Illustration 11).

Illustration 11: In yellow, the initial perimeter defined in 2014 for the development of the configuration and layout scenario. The red polygon represents the perimeter obtained on the basis of information and data collected between 2014 and 2021, and following the recommendations of Cerema, GESDEC, ILF and GADZ to avoid known karstic limestone formations and active faults, to respect the bathymetry of the lake and to remain as much as possible within the watertight, stable molasse layer. As the illustration shows, the LEP/LHC tunnel lies partly outside this defined perimeter. Firstly, the LEP/LHC tunnel is shallower and rises towards the Jura mountains. This tunnel only crosses the molasse/limestone interface outside this red boundary line. Major problems with limestone and unstable, water-bearing karstic volumes, encountered during construction of the LEP tunnel, led to this recommendation.

Although maps and modelling work have provided additional information, reliable data on the depth of interfaces between different geological layers in the Vuache and Jura zones is still lacking. The unavoidable limestone zones of Mandallaz and Bornes have yet to be studied. What's more, little is known about stability conditions under the lake, as well as the Arve and the Rhone rivers. Since these conditions have a major impact on the feasibility of the CFC, it is now necessary to obtain more information about the subsurface in the key areas identified, and to verify it by carrying out specific geophysical and geotechnical explorations (Illustration 12).

Illustration 12: The geological and topographical situation limits the circumference of a future circular collider to less than 100 km. The layout studies conducted between 2017 and 2021 concluded that, in order to obtain a circumference of over 90 km that would deliver good performance, and therefore a research infrastructure of excellence, and given the various constraints that the configuration must simultaneously meet in different locations, the available layout for the ring is limited to a strip with a width progressively reduced from 3,000 m to 300 m depending on the area concerned.

2.5.3. Topography, bathymetry, and other surface features

Information on topographical surface conditions is also taken into account from the outset of the study. Steep slopes in excess of 30% presenting risks of unstable terrain and landslides are to be excluded, as are cliffs, narrow valleys, and canyon-type formations. Since the tunnel must be placed at a sufficient depth below the lake bed, elevations above 750 m are an obstacle due to the depth of the shafts and unacceptable overloading (Illustration 13).

Illustration 13: In addition to the geological survey boundary line (red), other geological and topographical constraints must be taken into account from the outset. The fault lines shown on the lower left of the illustration (Vuache) are an example. The isolines at the top of the limestone are specific to different locations. They are shown by way of example in the left and top sections of the illustration. Examples of zones at higher elevations are shown in the lower and right-hand sections of the illustration (green and yellow zones are valleys that prove to be more favourable locations).

The bathymetry of the lake must be taken into account to ensure that the tunnel can be placed below the molassic substratum of the lake (located beneath the potentially poorly consolidated quaternary sediments), with as short a crossing as possible (Illustration 14). At the same time, other parts of the tunnel should not be located too deep under mountainous areas.

Illustration 14: Lake Geneva is more than 50 m deep beyond the Versoix-Corsier line. To avoid the tunnel becoming too deep over its entire footprint, it is necessary to stay below this line. Crossing the lake where it is narrow avoids areas of instability and minimises the risks associated with the presence of water.

These initial surface and subsurface constraints provide a starting point for a semi-automated search to determine approximate exclusion and candidate zones.

However, zones marked in orange (undesirable zones) and yellow (acceptable zones), which at first glance appear compatible with the location of a surface site, may prove to be unacceptable due to restrictions that are not "encoded" in available maps and publicly accessible documents. This additional information can be obtained in part by studying high-resolution maps, orthophotographs and data, by interviewing regional authorities and local stakeholders, and by means of walking tours (visual inspection of the surrounding area).

These restrictions include, but are not limited to, the following: unfavourably shaped areas (available surface too small, too narrow, non-monolithic or too irregularly shaped), presence of adjacent constraints (nature protection areas requiring buffer zones, natural hazard areas such as flood zones or unstable banks, residential areas, sensitive areas), limited access (no road or no possibility of creating one due to topographical conditions or other restrictions, rudimentary road unsuitable for regular traffic and unable to be upgraded to meet requirements), likely opposition or known conflicting development policies, known conflicting projects. These additional indirect constraints are taken into account in step 3 (Check) and have consequences for step 4 (Act).

2.5.4. Essential particle accelerator parameters

A set of parameters fundamental to particle accelerator design make up the starting conditions for scenario development. These parameters include the geometry of the configuration (for example, a symmetry or periodicity of sectors involving a specific number of surface sites), the length of the basic curved cells, called "arcs" (which repeat like the parts of a chain to build the curved sectors of the particle collider), the number of arc cells to be repeated and the lengths of the various types of straight sections between the arcs. Illustration 15 below shows two basic configuration geometries used in configuration and layout studies. The first geometry (image on the left) serves as a starting point: it groups together three experiment sites in the upper part of the geometry. It offers greater freedom in terms of moving the various surface sites but requires twelve surface sites. The second geometry (image on the right) represents the current development: the four experiment sites are evenly distributed (top, right, bottom, left) and only eight surface sites are required. However, the freedom to move sites is less than with the first geometry.

Illustration 15: Two different collider configuration geometries. The image on the left shows a configuration comprising twelve sites, based on a geometry with mirror symmetry. The image on the right shows an eight-site configuration, based on the repetition of a basic sector module. The arcs (blue) are separated by straight sections (green and red segments). Both configurations can accommodate up to four experiment sites (PL, PA, PB and PG for the twelve-site configuration, and PA, PD, PG and PJ for the eight-site configuration).

The design parameters determining the overall size of the configuration cannot be chosen arbitrarily. Table 5 presents and briefly describes all the initial parameters and their current state.

Table 5: Particle collider design parameters, their initial values for configuration and layout studies, and their current state after seven years of study.

Parameter	Initial value	Current value	Description
Geometry	Simple mirror symmetry	4 repetitions of a 90-degree sector, i.e. four-fold symmetry	<p>The initial configuration (12 sites) made it possible to group 3 experiment sites close to each other near the main CERN site, leading to shorter distances between surface sites and greater flexibility to lengthen and shorten the north and south sides.</p> <p>The current geometry (8 sites) enables a more regular design and thus facilitates performance optimization processes. The lepton collider can also have 4 interaction points.</p>
Number of surface sites	12	8	12 surface sites were required in the initial configuration, due to the need to insert 4 additional access points in the middle of the long arcs. In the end, it proved too difficult to find a suitable layout scenario, compatible with the territorial constraints and risks involved in implementing the project. A scenario with 8 sites offers less flexibility for the layout study, since the fixed interaction sites are geographically opposed, but the number of suitable locations to be found is lower.
Number of possible interaction points	2 for the lepton collider, 4 for the hadron collider	4 for the lepton collider, 4 for the hadron collider	The initial concept was to combine 3 experiment sites, but equipment integration proved difficult due to the need to combine experiments and injection at PL and PB points.
Arc cell length	213.03 m	275.79 m	The length of the cell must be compatible with the 2 particle colliders (lepton machine and hadron machine).
Radio frequency system harmonics (h)	<p>$h = 121440$ ($2^5 \times 3 \times 5 \times 11 \times 23$) provides good performance, with a circumference of 90.8369 km</p> <p>$h = 121380$ ($2^2 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 17^2$) provides acceptable performance, with a circumference of 90.792 km</p> <p>$h = 121200$ ($2^4 \times 3 \times 5^2 \times 101$) provides tolerable performance, with a circumference of 90.6574 km (circumference chosen for scenario PA31)</p>		<p>The stability and performance of the radio-frequency system (particle acceleration) depends on the circumference of the collider, which must be determined based on the circumference of the SPS and LHC accelerators and the frequencies used to control the particle bunches in the beam lines. For 91 km, 3 possibilities have been identified. A collider with a circumference of between 90.7 and 90.8 km is the best option. A length of 90.6 km is feasible but reduces the frequencies of the cavities in the radiofrequency system more than the others.</p>

Length of straight section at interaction points	1 400 m	1 400 m	700 m are needed on either side of the interaction point to focus the beam lines of the collider. The 2 colliders have different space requirements for crossing the two beam lines, so the tunnel needs to be widened by around 10 m to a distance of 1,400 m on either side of the interaction point.
Length of straight section at radiofrequency sites	2 800 m	2 032 m	A distance of 2 800 m between 2 straight sections was initially deemed adequate to accommodate the radiofrequency equipment that accelerates the beam lines. After various equipment integration studies, it was found that this value could be reduced. A distance of 2 x 2 030 m is now considered the lower limit.
Total number of arc cells	(4 sectors x 19 short cells) (4 sectors x 73 long cells) = 368	8 sectors x 26 cells = 208	The size of the particle collider curve can only be increased or decreased by inserting or removing an arc cell in each curve. The overall configuration must remain symmetrical.
Length of arcs	4.72 km for short arcs 16.22 km for long arcs, with an intermediate access point required every 8.11 km.	9.835 km	While the 12-site configuration features 4 short arcs, it also includes 4 long arcs, too long to remain without intermediate access points for technical and personnel safety reasons. An additional site must be placed at the midway point, at a distance of around 8 to 10 km from each end.
Total arc length	83.75 km	76.929 km (approximately 8% shorter than in the initial scenario)	The sum of all curved sections should be as long as possible to reduce curvature, and therefore energy loss, and achieve better performance. A circumference of 80 km is considered acceptable to provide the performance required for the scientific program. The current circumference is a compromise that remains acceptable, but it should not be reduced any further as this would limit the performance range too much.
Total circumference	97.75 km	90.65739 km	The initial objective was to design a particle collider infrastructure with a circumference of around 100 km. A reduction of 10%, to a circumference of 90 km, is considered to be the strictly acceptable limit, below which the performance obtained for scientific research would be too limited. The smaller the circumference, the smaller the radius of the curved sections and the more pronounced the curvature, resulting in greater energy losses and the need for more powerful magnets, which are technologically unattainable.

Cooling water requirements	4.9 million m ³ /y	Approximately 2 million m ³ /y but less than 3 million m ³ /y for the operating mode using maximum energy (ttbar)	With the aim of using resources responsibly, ongoing studies have already helped to reduce requirements. Further reductions can be expected due to the inclusion of the concept of heat reuse, taking into account technological developments and the development of water reuse synergies.
Electricity requirements	1.2 – 2.0 TWh/y, 1.5 TWh/y on average	1.0 – 1.77 TWh/y, 1.3 TWh/y on average, largely based on renewable energy sources	With the aim being to use resources responsibly, studies are underway to reduce requirements by 11 to 16%. Further reductions can be expected as a result of a more detailed operating plan and developments in magnet and radiofrequency technologies.

The development of a possible particle collider configuration requires an initial macroscopic study confirming that a closed orbit (Illustration 16) can be achieved, and that the scenario enables the collider to deliver the performance required to carry out the scientific research program.

A "closed orbit" means that the particles, which move through the circular accelerator in a wave-like oscillating trajectory, arrive after one revolution exactly at their point of departure, so that they can begin a new revolution. The movement is therefore continuous. In addition, the two particle beams travelling in opposite directions must intersect at all four interaction points. This is only possible with a limited number of frequencies in the radiofrequency system. In addition, the circumference must be compatible with the circumference of the infrastructure of existing injection accelerators (SPS, LHC), even if, in the future, the injectors will be new machines in these tunnels. Consequently, the circumference cannot be chosen freely. For each targeted circumference, a technical feasibility analysis is required. It gives the feasible length possibilities as close as possible to the desired circumference (for example, for a collider with a circumference of about 91 km, only three options exist: 90.8369 km, 90.792 km or 90.65739 km).

Illustration 16: The trajectory of the particle beam line, shown in red around the ring, is wave shaped. The trajectory must be perfectly closed for the accelerator to function. What's more, the particles travel in two beam lines in opposite directions. These beam lines must intersect at the points of interaction indicated by Xs in the illustration. A limited choice of circumferences is possible, based on the constraint of the achievable frequencies with the radio-frequency acceleration system. In addition, the circumference must be compatible, within the permitted harmonic values, with the circumference of the existing circular infrastructures of the SPS and LHC.

The performance range of the configuration has to be calculated for an electron-positron particle collider and for a hadron collider. In the case of the lepton (electron-positron) collider, a smaller circumference means more pronounced curves, resulting in greater energy losses. In the case of the hadron (proton) collider, more pronounced curves require more powerful magnets to maintain the particles on their trajectory (Illustration 17).

Illustration 17: The more the curvature of the ring is pronounced, the stronger the magnets need to be to keep the particles on their trajectory, and consequently the more energy the particles lose. In some facilities, this effect is taken advantage of by using the emitted radiation as a very powerful microscope for visualizing chemical interactions in real time. For a large collider designed for fundamental physics research, these energy losses must be limited. The target concept is therefore a very wide ring with low curvature.

For the lepton machine, the intensity that can be achieved, which corresponds to the number of particles interacting at each interaction point at a given moment, must be optimised for each of the four energy levels. Achieving this objective also requires a straight section long enough to focus the beam lines before interaction and defocus them after they cross (Illustration 18).

Illustration 18: It must be possible for the shape of the beam line envelope to vary along its trajectory. A minimum of 700 m is needed to focus the beam line on either side of the interaction point, in order to obtain the particle density required for the foreseen research program.

For the hadron machine, the particle collision energy must be optimised in the hypothetical configuration, taking into account the superconducting magnet technology potentially available and the limits on power consumption. For a total arc length of 77 km (as opposed to the 83.75 km for the basic configuration postulated in the technical design report), the required magnetic field strength would increase from 16 to 17.5 Tesla, requiring the development of a new type of superconducting material (Illustration 19). Given the low level of technological readiness, and the need for series production of thousands of elements, such developments can only be considered over a time frame of at least 25 years.

Illustration 19: Examples highlighting the impact of arc length, and therefore circumference, on the achieved collision energy (centre of mass) and on the magnetic field strength required by the hadron collider bending magnet.

For both machines, it is therefore necessary to estimate the energy losses and performance of critical particle accelerator components (e.g. bending magnets, focusing magnets and radiofrequency cavities) for the configuration under study, and their essential characteristics must be considered technologically feasible within the foreseen time frames (availability within 15 years for the lepton collider and 35 years for the hadron collider for series production and installation, including R&D, prototype production and pre-production).

To meet the scientific performance objectives, a particle collider circumference of over 90 km is required, resulting in the definition of acceptable lower curvature limits for both machines.

This preliminary conceptual design work requires a team of around 15 people over a continuous period of about three months. Once a particular scenario is considered, it needs to be analysed in greater depth, which requires around six months' additional work with the same number of people. This is why only two basic configuration scenarios (one comprising twelve sites, the other eight sites) could be initially considered, and why a limited number of scenarios can be retained for more detailed analysis prior to the launch of a technical feasibility study.

2.6. DETERMINATION OF CONFIGURATION AND LAYOUT (STEP 2, DO)

In order to determine the configuration and layout, it is first necessary to define a set of zones of interest based on the initial configuration of the particle collider and the approximate locations of the designated surface sites, using maps indicating territorial and geological constraints.

Illustration 20: Example of an automated search for an initial scenario comprising eight sites. The image shows two interesting regions, considered on the basis of cartographic studies, analysis of urban planning documents and interviews with people familiar with regional aspects, such as the DDT 74. The image shows that, in combination with the seven other target zones, the red dots, which represent the midpoints of the straight section extending 700 m on either side of the interaction point, are concentrated in a fairly small area. Many of the points are within the preferred zones, but some scenarios are also outside these zones. More detailed studies will examine the relevance of these scenarios, which do not fall within these preferred zones. These automated studies can also be used to identify recurring types of scenarios by grouping points together.

A semi-automatic search tool using random location generation highlights layout scenarios for analysis (see a close-up view of a semi-automatic search process for a particular surface site in Illustration 20). Polygons in various locations, considered potentially suitable, are drawn manually in this tool, according to the surface and subsurface constraints already defined. An algorithm then randomly generates location scenarios for a specific set of particle collider parameters (number of surface sites, number of arc cells, and therefore the total circumference). To do so, the algorithm moves an initially defined starting point into a starting polygon that has also been defined (by longitude and latitude) by rotating the particle collider within defined limits. The algorithm also automatically modifies the acceptable lengths of straight sections between portions of the arcs. The starting polygon and variable parameters are also chosen so as to achieve acceptable scientific performance, and to be able to eventually create transfer lines linking the new particle collider to CERN's existing particle accelerators (SPS and/or LHC).

An interactive version of the FCC Footprint Explorer tool can be viewed and used on the Web:

https://fcc-gis-data.web.cern.ch/fcc-gis-data/FFE/v02b/FFE3_8P.html

After this initial search, all randomly generated layouts with nominal points lying outside the defined polygons (the four interaction sites that require access shafts at a precise location and sufficient space on the surface) are rejected.

As the identified points are generally grouped together, the other scenarios are examined by "scenario type" and a model scenario is determined on the basis of these groupings of points, enabling a more detailed analysis.

In the next step (step 3, Check), carefully selected versions of these scenario types will be imported into three separate tools for in-depth analysis:

1. A tunnel optimisation tool (TOT²⁶);
2. A beam optics and transfer workflow based on the MAD-X accelerator design software²⁷;
3. A geographical information system (GIS²⁸).

The tunnel optimization tool cross-references the circular footprint at different depths with a 3D model of the subsurface. This step is used to create a scenario at a specific depth with a specific slope angle around two axes (Illustration 21).

Illustration 21: Selection of a depth and slope angle of the ring around two axes to analyse geological conditions and well depth.

The tunnel depth optimization tool indicates the geological layers encountered and provides information on shaft depths at theoretical midpoint locations. It is important to bear in mind that, at this stage of the study, this information is still imprecise for the two reasons explained below.

Firstly, the quality of the volumetric (3D) subsurface model requires extensive third-party data. At present, only scant information is available on several zones considered decisive for the feasibility of the project. By interpolating between locations where the information is known, information that is more or less precise can be obtained on the state of the subsurface, depending on the data available and how this data has been processed in the past. The positioning of depths can therefore only be considered as approximate, and insufficient to confirm the conditions of feasibility from a civil engineering point of view. Specific geophysical and geotechnical studies are essential in critical areas to obtain more information about soil stability and the interfaces between different geological layers.

²⁶ <https://accelconf.web.cern.ch/ipac2015/papers/tupty033.pdf>

²⁷ <https://mad.web.cern.ch/mad/>

²⁸ https://ge.ch/sitg/media/sitg/files/documents/cern_fcc_sitg_corrige.pdf

Secondly, the shaft depths are indicated at the theoretical midpoints of the straight sections, not where the surface sites would ultimately be located. Subsequent iterations make it possible to move, within certain limits, the surface shafts of technical sites where detectors are not foreseen for experiments (e.g. PB, PF, PH and PL in the eight-site configuration). As these displacements can be up to 900 m along the ring and up to 400 m inside the ring, an additional manual topographic search is conducted in this step and, if the scenario is considered for optimization, in the next step (Illustration 22).

Illustration 22: Example of a scenario layout analysis in the tunnel optimization tool, showing the geological layers crossed and the risks encountered due to geological interfaces and the presence of potentially deep shafts.

The process for calculating beam line optics and transfer is used to determine the scope of the scientific performance of the scenario, and to check that a connection to CERN's existing particle accelerators can be designed from a technical point of view. The link between the particle collider and CERN's existing accelerators has to be checked separately for each scenario. CERN's existing particle accelerators and the FCC are located at significantly different depths, and connections are only possible from certain points on the existing accelerators to specific points on the planned new machine (Illustration 23).

Illustration 23: Aspects to be taken into account when planning connections between the Future Circular Collider and CERN's existing particle accelerators, the SPS and the LHC.

Transfer lines must not exceed certain curvature limits, which extend in three spatial dimensions: the lateral curvature, the vertical curvature, and the transfer line slope angle. The slope is limited by the cooling of equipment, particularly superconducting magnets, which require the pumping of cryogenic fluids (e.g. liquid helium, or even superfluid helium). Once again, excessive curvature would lead to unacceptable energy losses, and would require magnets with field strengths that, from a technological point of view, are potentially unattainable. Illustration 24 below gives an idea of the type of work to be conducted at this stage for each scenario.

Illustration 24: Example of an analysis of the curves and distances of transfer lines from the LHC and SPS for the initial FCC scenario. The analysis also highlights the technical characteristics that the transfer line components must possess (mainly the required magnetic field strengths of the magnets, which indicate whether the use of normal conducting magnets is possible, which superconducting magnet technology is feasible, or whether the scenario is not feasible due to technical difficulties).

Transfer lines have been optimised for the current reference scenario, leading to a significant reduction in lengths between the FCC, SPS and LHC (see Table 6). In fact, the layout scenario makes it possible to use part of CERN's existing tunnels (Illustration 25), thereby lowering the cost of the project, speeding up the construction schedule, and reducing disturbances for local residents. The connection between the FCC and the LHC has also been optimised (Illustration 26).

Table 6: Length of transfer lines for reference scenario PA31.

Transfer line	Tunnel length
Prévessin - FCC	1.4 km (4.4 km in total, using 3 km of existing tunnel, 1.4 km to be built)
FCC - SPS	4.5 km
FCC - LHC	4.7 km

Illustration 25: Concept for transfer line (shown in magenta) between the CERN Prévessin site (indicated by an x in the illustration) and the FCC (green ring). The SPS is the small grey ring and the LHC is the large grey ring.

Illustration 26: Concept for transfer line between the FCC (shown in green) and the LHC (large grey ring) and the SPS (small grey ring).

The scenario is then imported into the geographical information system for the entire project, making it possible to analyse the various territorial constraints at a microscopic level, taking into account a large number of aspects that are summarised in a multi-criteria analysis approach. This stage also brings together urban and regional planning documents available at different levels (local urban plan, inter-commune local urban plan, sustainable planning and development project, territorial cohesion scheme, cantonal master plan, municipal master plan) and considers information enabling synergies to be developed. Potential benefits to society (e.g. supply of residual heat, sharing of technical infrastructures, reduced transport distances) are also indicated at this stage (Illustration 27 below).

Illustration 27: Example of use of information in the GIS for the overall project study in the Check and Act stages. Lines with black dots indicate high-capacity power lines (e.g. 400 kV). The red triangles and orange polygons represent quarries that can supply and accept materials. Multicoloured polygons indicate plots of land used for agricultural purposes, grouped together by known individuals or associations so that avoidance, reduction or compensation measures can be considered for these lands. This image gives only a rough idea of the information available and taken into account in the development of the scenario, which will subsequently be updated and used.

2.7. MULTI-CRITERIA ANALYSIS (STEP 3, CHECK)

A multi-criteria analysis scheme has been developed, based on an approach presented by Cerema in its guidelines for the environmental analysis of linear transport infrastructures²⁹. This approach was completed using the UNIDO *International Guidelines for Industrial Parks*, published in November 2019³⁰.

As required by the regulatory frameworks in France and Switzerland, the project is considered in broad terms, extending the analysis to various aspects such as indirectly affected stakeholders; legal, regulatory, social and economic factors; networks (roads, railroads, water, electricity, canals, public service and safety infrastructures); heritage sites; visual aspects; disturbances (noise, dust, light, smells, pollution) and potential benefits. As explained in the Cerema guide (page 103), this approach can then be used in subsequent phases of the project to assess the relative merits of each scenario, and contribute to the development of reduction, compensation and support measures in an open process. In Switzerland, and more specifically in the canton of Geneva, a parallel can be drawn with the strategic environmental assessment tool (EES). When plans, programs or projects (PPPs) are drawn up, the EES is sometimes designed to ensure that environmental and human health issues are taken into account systematically and at an early stage, as foreseen in the Environmental Protection Act. As such, it can be used as a decision-making tool, assessing the merits of different scenarios³¹.

The multi-criteria analysis results in a standardised qualitative analysis, to compare the suitability of different scenarios. Its use during the scenario-building process makes it possible to quickly identify the types of scenarios that present significant advantages or disadvantages, and to determine whether the differences between the scenarios are major or minor. This approach also offers the advantage of clarifying which elements have the greatest or least influence on the value of the scenario, and thus guides the development of new types of scenarios. This approach is then used in the subsequent optimization stages, for example with regard to moving shaft and surface sites to more suitable locations and taking into account the availability of existing infrastructures (e.g. roads, railroads, water supply and treatment, electricity), urban planning documents (PLU, PLUi, PADD, SCoT, PDcn, PDcom) and synergies and opportunities (e.g. supply of residual heat, sharing of technical infrastructures, reduced transport distances).

²⁹ Cerema, *L'évaluation environnementale des projets d'infrastructures linéaires de transport*, document updated in 2020, p. 69: <https://www.cerema.fr/fr/centre-ressources/boutique/evaluation-environnementale-projets-infrastructures>

³⁰ https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/files/2020-08/IP_FR_spreads.pdf

³¹ État de Genève, DT, OCEV, SERMA, *Évaluation environnementale stratégique - Guide d'aide à l'exécution*, December 2022: <https://www.ge.ch/document/guide-evaluation-environnementale-strategique>

The macroscopic list is made up of **nine criteria categories**, each comprising several detailed criteria. These criteria cover the various themes of the project, and enabled CERN to carry out multi-criteria analyses of the different scenarios in the early phases of the study. **32 criteria are taken into account:**

1. Land status

- 1.1. Availability of plots
- 1.2. Clearly defined ownership
- 1.3. Plot price
- 1.4. Acquisition time and expected difficulties in obtaining rights
- 1.5. Development cost

2. Road connections

- 2.1. Distance from transport, industrial and other infrastructures
- 2.2. Distance from populated areas

3. Raw materials and services

- 3.1. Availability of raw materials for construction and resources for operation
- 3.2. Proximity to service providers

4. Physical characteristics

- 4.1. Plot size and shape
- 4.2. Topography
- 4.3. Shaft depth
- 4.4. Drainage and sanitation requirements for construction
- 4.5. Surface soil condition
- 4.6. Water resources
- 4.7. Accessibility
- 4.8. Subsurface conditions (physical)
- 4.9. Subsurface conditions (regulatory)

5. Infrastructure

- 5.1. Accessibility of electrical power
- 5.2. Communication network
- 5.3. Water for industrial use
- 5.4. Drinking water
- 5.5. Waste water discharge, rainwater collection, disposal and treatment points
- 5.6. Temporary storage and processing areas during construction

6. Environmental and social factors

- 6.1. Existing environmental constraints
- 6.2. Fauna and flora
- 6.3. Existence of construction constraints
- 6.4. Adjacent constraints
- 6.5. Disturbances
- 6.6. Availability and accessibility of workforce
- 6.7. Involvement of local authorities
- 6.8. Support from civil society

7. Configuration

- 7.1. Geometry
- 7.2. Size
- 7.3. Transfer lines

8. Cost**9. Risks involved in implementation**

For each scenario, six macro-criteria are determined for each of the candidate locations for the surface sites in that scenario (land status, road connections, raw materials and services, physical characteristics, infrastructure, environmental and social factors) and three high-level criteria are determined for the overall scenario (configuration, cost, and risk).

Table 7: Criteria applied to evaluate each candidate location for surface sites in a scenario.

Criterion	Description	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
LAND STATUS						
Availability of plots	How difficult is it to obtain the available land for the site?	Existing construction and difficult to obtain	Existing construction	Reserved	Bare land with constraints	Bare land and available
Clearly defined ownership	How difficult is it to legally obtain rights or ownership of plots of land?	Very difficult	Difficult	Normal	Easy	Plots made available by an entity (state government or local authorities)
Plot price	What is the projected cost of the land?	Very expensive	Expensive	Normal	Inexpensive	Very low price or free
Acquisition time and expected difficulties during acquisition	What are the lead times and challenges involved in securing site use rights for construction and operation?	Very long or difficult	Long and difficult	Long	Normal and easy	Short and easy
Development cost	How much will it cost to develop the land to meet the project's needs?	Very expensive	Expensive	Normal	Inexpensive	Very low price or free
ROAD CONNECTIONS						
Distance from transport, industrial and other infrastructures	How far is the site from the required and relevant infrastructures?	Very far away	Far away	Normal	Close	Very close
Distance from populated areas	How far is the site from populated areas that will be disturbed by construction and operation?	Very close	Close	Normal	Far away	Very far away

Criterion	Description	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
RAW MATERIALS AND SERVICES						
Availability of raw materials	What is the situation regarding accessibility of materials (e.g. concrete, steel, cables)?	Very far away	Far away	Normal	Close	Very close
Proximity to service providers	How is accessibility foreseen for site operation services (including workforce when in operation)?	Very far away	Far away	Normal	Close	Very close
PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS						
Plot size and shape	How much space is available? Is the shape of the site favourable for the project?	Unfavourable or too small	Small	Normal	Satisfactory	More space than needed
Topography	To what extent are topographical conditions advantageous or unfavourable?	Unfavourable or sloped	Development work necessary	Acceptable	Suitable	Advantageous for the project
Shaft depth	What is the shaft depth?	Very deep (> 300 m)	Deep (250 to 300 m)	Acceptable (170 to 250 m)	Shallow (100 to 170 m)	Very shallow (< 100 m)
Drainage and sanitation conditions	How difficult or advantageous are drainage conditions during construction?	Difficult	Development work necessary	Acceptable	Suitable	Advantageous for project (e.g. gravity)
Soil (surface) condition	How difficult or advantageous are soil conditions for construction (e.g. muddy, swollen, unstable)?	Difficult	Development work necessary	Acceptable	Suitable	Advantageous for the project

Criterion	Description	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Water resources	How are the planned water resources for operation (cooling)?	Difficult	Development work necessary	Acceptable	Suitable	Advantageous for the project
Accessibility	How difficult is access to the site for construction purposes (existence of roads, height and width clearances, structure)?	Difficult	Development work necessary	Acceptable	Suitable	Advantageous for the project
Subsurface conditions (physical)	What is the level of technical risk for underground constructions?	High risk	Moderate risk	Normal	Low	Low with potential reuse
Subsurface conditions (regulatory)	What is the extent of underground construction constraints?	Major constraints	Minor constraints	Control procedures only	Normal procedures	No constraints
INFRASTRUCTURES						
Accessibility of electrical power	How far/difficult is it to bring electricity to the site?	Isolated and difficult	Isolated and feasible	Moderately difficult and feasible	Close and feasible	Very close
Communication networks	What is the expected availability of communication networks (data and voice)?	Isolated and difficult	Isolated and feasible	Average and feasible	Close and feasible	Very close
Water for industrial use	What is the expected availability of industrial water?	Isolated and difficult	Isolated and feasible	Average and feasible	Close and feasible	Very close
Drinking water	What is the expected availability of drinking water?	Isolated and difficult	Isolated and feasible	Average and feasible	Close and feasible	Very close

Criterion	Description	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Waste water discharge, rainwater collection, disposal and treatment points	What is the situation regarding drainage and disposal and treatment capacities for operational purposes?	Isolated and difficult	Isolated and feasible	Average and feasible	Close and feasible	Very close
Temporary storage and processing areas during construction	What is the status of temporary storage space during construction?	Isolated and difficult	Isolated and feasible	Average and feasible	Close and feasible	Very close
ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL FACTORS						
Existing environmental constraints	What is the status of the constraints identified for the plots belonging to the site?	Significant constraints	Moderate constraints	No constraints	Rather favourable environment	Favourable environment and potential synergies (benefits)
Fauna and flora	What is the likelihood of encountering protected species and interfering with ecological corridors?	Extremely high	High	Moderate	Low	Negligible
Existence of construction constraints	What is the extent of the constraints identified for plots belonging to the site (e.g.: building a bridge wide enough for the river)?	Potentially insurmountable difficulties	Significant constraints	Expected normal constraints	No particular constraints identified	Immediate construction possible
Adjacent constraints	What is the extent of the constraints around the site (e.g., visibility, shared visibility, visual impact on the landscape)?	Significant constraints	Moderate constraints	No constraints	Rather favourable environment	Favourable environment and potential synergies (benefits)

Criterion	Description	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Disturbances	What are the potential levels of disturbances generated by an installation on the site (noise, dust, traffic, pollution, etc.)?	Extremely high	High	Moderate	Low	Negligible
Availability and accessibility of workforce	How easy/difficult is it to transport workers and operators to and from the site (distance, various methods)?	Isolated and difficult	Isolated and feasible	Moderately difficult and feasible	Close and feasible	Very close
Involvement of local authorities	What support can be received from local authorities for building on the plots?	Not recommended	Not encouraged	Normal	Recommended	Encouraged
Support from civil society	What is the likelihood of opposition to construction on the plots?	Insurmountable difficulty	Opposition	Normal	Rather favourable	Favourable

Table 8: Criteria taken into account for the scenario as a whole.

Criterion	Description:	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
CONFIGURATION						
Geometry	How does the geometry differ from the ideal geometry?	Moving the layout significantly affects physical performance.	Moving the layout affects physical performance in an acceptable manner.	Access shafts are moved with no impact on physical performance, but functionality may be reduced.	Access shafts are moved in a minor way, with no impact on physical performance or functionality.	Complies with calculations
Size	What is the size of the ring?	<= 89 km	> 89 km <= 90 km	> 90 km <= 93 km	> 93 km <= 96 km	> 96 km
Transfer lines	How are connections to the SPS and LHC via transfer lines?	At the limit of technical feasibility or very long	Difficult to build or long	As in preliminary conceptual design report (feasible and acceptable)	Easy to build or short, but only for one of the machines (SPS or LHC)	Easy to build or short for both machines (SPS and LHC)
COST						
Cost of construction	What is the expected cost?	More than 10% more expensive than the preliminary Conceptual Design Report (CDR) scenario (> 20%)	5 to 10% more expensive than the CDR scenario	Comparable to what is indicated in CDR scenario (less than 5% cost difference)	5 to 10% less expensive than the CDR scenario	More than 10% less expensive than the CDR scenario
RISKS						
Risks stemming from implementation of project	What is the level of risk associated with implementation (e.g. taking geological faults into account)?	Very high	Higher than in the CDR scenario	Comparable to what is indicated in CDR scenario	Lower than in the CDR scenario	Much lower than in the CDR scenario

A spreadsheet is used to assign each criterion a qualitative score between -2 and +2, according to a defined evaluation grid (see list). A score of "0" represents a neutral assessment of the indicator. For each high-level criterion, the scores of its sub-criteria are added together to provide an indicator for that criterion. The spreadsheet also shows the macro-criteria scores, and presents a final score for all criteria in the form of a percentage between 0 and 100. Lastly, the values of the criteria are synthesised to provide indicators for 1) scientific excellence, 2) territorial concerns and 3) appropriateness of project implementation. This approach not only makes it possible to quickly estimate the value of a scenario and compare it with others, but also to highlight criteria that are insufficiently known and require in-depth study.

Values are assigned for the qualitative indicators through a collaborative process by the multidisciplinary team, based on cartographic studies and database analysis; interviews to discuss the most suitable footprint with staff from the administrative departments of the two host states (e.g. DT, GESDEC, OCEV, OCAN, OCT, DDT 01 and DDT 74); consultation with experts working in different technical fields (Cerema, Ecotec, HydroGéo, ILF, GADZ, particle accelerator designers working in many partner institutes, geologists employed in many partner universities); and feedback from local players during working meetings with municipalities, intercommunal entities and elected representatives. A disadvantage of this approach is that it simply adds up and averages the values: in some cases, there may be an obstacle related to territorial or scientific aspects, or to project implementation. However, averaging means that a single low value will lower the overall ranking, but will not necessarily show the blocking point in the summary. The multi-criteria analysis must therefore be complemented by an overall assessment of the scenario, which will highlight the potential benefits of one scenario that make it particularly preferable to others, or indicate whether the scenario is difficult or not feasible. Thus, scenarios presenting obstacles continue to be analysed and recorded, but they are rejected even if the value of a thematic indicator (scientific performance, territorial compatibility or project implementation) is higher than the acceptable threshold value for that element. Examples of such situations include the strong probability of encountering geological features that would expose the project to an unacceptably high risk (karst, crossing a fault, presence of high-pressure aquifers), almost certain and unacceptable opposition to a surface site due to its incompatibility with local or regional development policies, a collider circumference that would not allow the scientific research program to be conducted for technical reasons, or would not allow its operation to be viable (for example, a collider circumference significantly smaller than 91 km). The ranking is highlighted in summary diagrams such as those shown in section 3.4. See Illustration 28 for an example.

Territorial (T), implementation(I) and scientific (S) issues can be easily visualised and compared thanks to this standardised qualitative approach. Illustration 28 highlights the merits of the current working hypothesis PA31, which makes it a preferred scenario over the others for the detailed territorial and technical analysis. The overview also clearly shows that the scenarios involving twelve sites do not meet the required conditions to undergo an in-depth study. The illustration also shows the limitations of multi-criteria analysis: for example, two surface site locations in the PA0 scenario with twelve sites are located in areas considered to be blocking points, but this is only visible in the individual sheet for each site. The three-column summary alone, however, does not show these exclusion criteria, and must therefore be supplemented by a brief text description.

PA0-0.1	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP			RF			EXP			RF			97,75 km	
FCC-hh	EXP	EXP	Cryo		Cryo	Col		RF	Cryo	Col	Cryo	EXP		
Site														
Score	89	52	51	61	75	40	41	36	49	45	33	36	84	53

Illustration 28: Example of a summary view of the multi-criteria analysis of a scenario (PA0-0.1). The scenario seems feasible, even if the territorial feasibility would be low. In fact, a closer look at each site reveals many blocking points.

2.8. AVOID-REDUCE-COMPENSATE (STEP 4, ACT)

Once the more detailed version obtained at the end of step 3 (Check) has been deemed suitable for a scenario, the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) approach is again used to develop an updated version of this scenario, which in turn serves as a starting point for further iterations. It is then possible to modify the configuration and layout within certain limits to eventually find a better scenario, as shown in Table 9 below.

Table 9: Adjustable configuration and layout scenario.

Possible modifications to configuration and layout	Description and limitations
Moving the entire scenario	Move north, south, west, and east, within the established study perimeter, while ensuring that a connection to the CERN accelerators remains possible.
Rotation of the entire scenario	Select the mid-point of a straight section and rotate the entire scenario clockwise or counterclockwise, to ensure that a connection to the CERN accelerators remains possible. Surface sites close to the pivot point will move less than surface sites that are further away.
Moving technical sites	<p>Clockwise or counterclockwise movement of access shafts and surface sites to technical points no further than the ends of straight sections (generally less than 1,000 m on each side), limiting the movements as much as possible so as not to increase the performance and reliability requirements of technical systems.</p> <p>Possibility of moving an access shaft and a surface site further away from the collider tunnel. The new location is preferably inside the ring. A location outside the ring is not out of the question, but would entail significant additional costs. By consensus between all the technical engineering fields, the movement is limited to 400 m, which requires a horizontal access tunnel between the shaft and the collider at the collider tunnel.</p>
Splitting up surface sites	Possibility of splitting up the surface sites; the infrastructures that are essential for operations are located close to the shaft (e.g. ventilation and cooling facilities), while other infrastructures can be located up to 500 m away (e.g. electrical substation, cooling towers, water treatment plant).

<p>Reducing the size of surface sites</p>	<p>With regard to the initial requirements expressed in 2014 (12 x 9 ha = 108 ha), the surface site requirements³² set in 2014 served as the working basis for the layout study, requiring a total of 62 ha (9 ha for a primary experiment site, 6 ha for a secondary experiment site and 4 ha for a technical site, for the configuration comprising 12 sites).</p> <p>Adaptation of site perimeters to suit topographical and environmental conditions by accepting reduced capabilities for loading, unloading, installation and creation of buffer and renaturation zones.</p> <p>Elimination of access shafts for installation, maintenance and repair work by accepting an increase in cost and complexity for the installation and operation phases.</p>
<p>Modification of straight sections at interaction points</p>	<p>Enlarging or reducing straight sections at interaction points. The total length must not be less than 1 400 m.</p> <p>All straight sections must be modified according to the same parameter so that they are always the same length.</p>
<p>Modification of technical straight sections</p>	<p>Depending on the configuration (8 or 12 sites), different types of straight sections can be enlarged or reduced.</p> <p>In the initial 12-site scenario, the minimum acceptable length of the 4 short straight sections is 1 400 m, and the minimum length of the 2 long straight sections is 2 800 m. Excessive enlargement of the straight sections would waste materials and funds.</p> <p>In the 8-site scenario, the minimum acceptable length of the 4 technical straight sections is 2 032 m, to allow for equipment integration.</p> <p>All straight sections of the same type (short section or long section) must be modified using the same parameter to achieve the same length.</p>
<p>Changing the size of arcs</p>	<p>Depending on the configuration (8 sites or 12 sites), the arcs can be enlarged or reduced by adding or removing arc cells from the particle collider.</p> <p>In the 8-site configuration, all arcs must be modified according to the same parameter so that they always have the same length.</p> <p>The 12-site configuration has both short and long arcs. All arcs of the same type (short arc or long arc) have the same length.</p>
<p>Modification of total circumference</p>	<p>The total circumference can be slightly adjusted (about ten meters), by inserting or removing spaces a few centimetres long, evenly distributed throughout all the arcs of the collider. This adjustment is mainly to ensure that the total circumference is a specific multiple of the existing CERN accelerators, the SPS and the LHC, to guarantee that the injection of equidistant particle bunches will work. This minor circumference adjustment has no significant impact on the territorial layout.</p>

³² J. Gutleber, V. Mertens, *Preliminary layout review*, FCC-INF-SPC-0001, V2.0, EDMS 1816972, 23 October 2017.

The graphic in Illustration 29 below shows once again the possibilities for adjusting the configuration, using the current eight-site scenario as an example.

Illustration 29: The image shows possible ways for adjusting a specific configuration and layout scenario, using the eight-site configuration as an example. The position of the experiment sites is fixed: they cannot be moved. Their property requirements can be reduced, either by taking advantage of synergies with an existing CERN surface site nearby, or by removing one of the two access shafts foreseen for the experiments, accepting the drawbacks of these solutions. The entire ring can be moved north, south, east, and west. The ring can also be rotated around the location of one of the surface sites, chosen as a pivot point. Technical sites can be moved along the ring, inside the ring, or with a combination of both. The length of straight sections can be modified identically at points PA, PD, PG and PJ and at points PB, PF, PH and PL. Arc lengths can be modified evenly all around the ring.

If the check conducted in step 3 concludes that the feasibility of the scenario seems unlikely, or would become unlikely if other actions were taken in line with the ERC approach, the scenario is rejected and the reason for this is explained.

The multi-criteria analysis makes it possible to determine the project elements and locations for which the ERC steps would be most effective. The adopted approach consists primarily of avoiding unwanted inconveniences. If avoidance is not possible or does not lead to the desired result, a reduction measure is drawn up. Compensation measures are only drawn up once the scenario has been selected for more detailed analysis, as they generally depend on the location in question.

This process involves several iterative stages of the Plan-Do-Check-Act approach. In fact, for each avoidance, reduction or compensation measure that is proposed, checks must be conducted to determine the effects of each measure on territorial compatibility, and the associated risks for implementation and scientific performance.

The specific actions of the ERC approach are implemented in accordance with Cerema guidelines³³. Table 10 presents the main points concerning the implementation of these measures. Given the level of detail required for the application of ERC measures for the different project phases and sites, as well as the need to actively involve stakeholders in the process and the resources required to do so, a detailed ERC database is only created for the scenario that will be analysed in detail during the feasibility study phase.

³³ Cerema, *Évaluation environnementale - Guide d'aide à la définition des mesures ERC*, January 2018: <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/Théma%20-%20Guide%20d'aide%20à%20la%20définition%20des%20mesures%20ERC.pdf>

Table 10: Concept for the implementation of avoidance, reduction and compensation measures according to the different phases of the project, with provision for support to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed measures.

Phase	Avoid	Reduce	Compensate
Pre-construction	<p>Exclusion of zones hosting protected species and high-stakes zones.</p> <p>Avoidance of landscape and heritage sites.</p> <p>Distance of the project from sensitive sites and populations.</p> <p>Adaptation of layout options (underground, semi-underground).</p>	<p>Land-take limitation, choice of design and materials and proper integration in the environment to limit negative effects.</p> <p>Planning of transport means.</p>	<p>Upstream planning of compensation and support measures, and joint development of these measures with the relevant stakeholders for the construction and operation phases.</p>
Construction	<p>Use of alternative access points, distance from construction activities, avoiding discharges and waste, adaptation of work to the period and adaptation of working hours.</p>	<p>Adaptation of periods and schedules.</p> <p>Discharge and waste management planning, including recycling.</p> <p>Choice of technologies to reduce disturbances and pollution.</p> <p>Species and population protection.</p>	<p>Implementation and follow-up of compensation measures, with monitoring of their effectiveness.</p>
Operation	<p>Avoidance of discharges and waste, adaptation of periods and schedules for certain operations.</p>	<p>Support measures to monitor and limit negative effects.</p> <p>Choice of technologies with the least negative impact.</p>	<p>Implementation and follow-up of compensation measures, with monitoring of their effectiveness.</p>

2.9. EXAMPLES OF THE APPLICATION OF ERC MEASURES IN SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT

In this overview, we present three specific examples of the ERC (Avoid-Reduce-Compensate) approach, highlighting the different options available and how they depend on the scenario in question.

2.9.1. Avoid: moving a surface site.

The ERC approach was used to examine the various possible layout configurations and avoid impacts as far as possible.

The first example concerns the location of a specific surface site which, in step 3 (Check), was deemed suitable, but which still had two drawbacks: difficult access and the need to clear land. The constraint concerning the forest is acceptable (in the yellow constraint zone). On the other hand, the access route is a problem, as it would have to pass through a small village to the west, or through a hamlet to the east (possible disturbances for neighbouring homes). The creation of an access road to the nearest main road in the department could be a disturbance to neighbouring residences, due to vehicle traffic to the site. Lastly, at least two farmers would be affected by the creation of the site, one because of the use of land required for the site, the other because of the need to create an access road.

As part of the ERC approach, other possible locations were examined in order to overcome these two constraints.

The proposed site is a technical site used for radiofrequency systems. It can be moved within certain limits. An analysis using the geographical information system shows that the access shaft could be moved 800 m in a clockwise direction along the ring to another location with better access. In fact, it would be located directly at a main road in the department, thereby avoiding the hamlets. What's more, this new location is also close to a 400 kV high-voltage power line and a site for the possible creation of a water catchment station (Illustration 30). On the other hand, this new site will use agricultural land, which is a major constraint.

Finally, the choice of site location should be based on a comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of a move in terms of territorial layout, impacts in terms of civil engineering and technical equipment, and effects on scientific performance.

Illustration 30: An example of avoidance to improve a scenario at a very early stage. Moving the site 800 m would avoid the creation of an access road, the crossing of hamlets and clearing work. This solution solves the access issue, but uses agricultural land, which is a major constraint. The choice will have to be made after carefully weighing the advantages and disadvantages.

2.9.2. Reduce: adapt road access design

An example of a reduction measure considered at a very early stage concerns limiting the amount of land required for a surface site. The site in question could not be moved ("avoided"), since it is an experiment site located exactly opposite another experiment site, and requires a shaft leading to the experiment cavern. The creation of a sloped access road would require additional farmland. An attempt to relax road requirements by increasing the slope from 6% to 15% reduces land consumption by 5 ha (Illustration 31). This increased slope gradient reduces the land take, but requires the application of a "push/pull" method for transporting very large equipment.

A further reduction has been made; additional studies have confirmed the concept with a connection to the motorway via the service area to the north of the site for the construction phases. The possibility of a connection to the north (Illustration 32) via an existing forest road (to be widened) further reduces the land take. In addition, the view from the bottom of the slope would be largely preserved, resulting in better landscape integration.

Illustration 31: The example shows the reduction in required land and the improvement of landscape integration thanks to the use of an existing rural road that could be widened to provide access to the site. The road gradient rises from 6%, with a winding road, to 15%, requiring a special technique (e.g. push/pull) for transporting large, heavy equipment. In the end, this optimization was not retained, as new optimization made it possible to design an access route with even fewer constraints on the north side of the target perimeter (see following illustration).

Illustration 32: A further reduction has been made. Additional studies have confirmed the feasibility of connecting to the motorway via the service area located to the north of the site for the construction phases (yellow route), which further limits the land take and improves integration in the landscape.

2.9.3. Compensate: example of residual heat use

In some places, avoidance or reduction measures may not be possible for the surface site. However, other projects nearby may offer opportunities to compensate for much of the land use. For example, near one of the candidate sites in Ferney-Voltaire (Ain department, France), a residential³⁴ eco-district is currently under construction, and the construction of a hospital³⁵ is planned (Illustration 33). They could make use of the heat generated by the data centre and the cooling of technical equipment on site. The economic and ecological benefits are part of the existing range of compensation measures: for example, around 100 GWh are available at this surface site, which opens up the possibility of supplying **40 GWh of energy per year** for heating purposes and 12 GWh for cooling purposes per year³⁶. For the municipality, this represents **potential savings of 4 million euros a year** (around 100 euros/MWh). In terms of energy supplied by non-renewable sources, this represents **a potential reduction of around 5 000 tonnes of CO₂(eq) emissions per year**.

Illustration 33: Target area identified for the PA experiment site in the immediate vicinity of Point 8 of the CERN's LHC. The zones initially available to the north of the road became unavailable due to the construction of apartments and a hospital. These developments are now providing an opportunity to develop synergies, such as the supply of residual heat. A heat supply network has recently been set up by CERN in cooperation with local partners for the newly-built apartments.

³⁴ <https://52histoires2020.ademe.fr/histoire/recuperer-la-chaaleur-produite-par-le-cern-pour-alimenter-le-quartier-d-a-cote>

³⁵ <https://www.ferney-voltaire.fr/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/FM59-avril-mai-juin-2022-planche-ok.pdf>

³⁶ Data based on information concerning the residual heat recovery and reuse system currently being developed as part of a cooperative effort between CERN and the town of Ferney-Voltaire:

<https://www.terrinnov-spl.fr/le-reseau-danergie-de-la-zac-ferney-geneve-innovation-soutenu-par-france-re lance/>

This type of compensation measure is possible for several surface sites. For this reason, the territorial analysis of configuration and layout studies considers the proximity of potential customers (public institutions, schools and universities, residential areas, farms). This analysis is currently part of a study being conducted in Switzerland and France with the support of a company specializing in the technical-economic assessment of residual heat reuse and supply.

The supply of residual heat (or waste heat) from the FCC creates windfalls in three ways:

1) Compensation for carbon footprint of electricity supplies

Supplying the FCC with electricity (the working hypothesis is based on using electricity partly from renewable sources) would represent an average carbon footprint of around 40,000 tCO₂(eq)/y. This footprint can be fully compensated for by the yearly supply of around 320 GWh of energy from residual heat. Given that the total maximum residual heat capacity is around 1 600 GWh per year, compensating for the carbon footprint may be possible, provided that this heat supply can be implemented (Table 11). The technical-economic study showed that 220 GWh to 300 GWh of heat could be consumed within a radius of approximately 5 km around the surface sites.

Table 11: Residual heat supply potential by operating mode and infrastructure adaptation.

Description	Operating mode				
	Z	W	H	Maintenance	ttbar
Minimum	223 GWh	239 GWh	256 GWh	60 GWh	296 GWh
With adaptation of operating schedule	308 GWh	339 GWh	371 GWh	60 GWh	441 GWh
Maximum, with redistribution between sites	414 GWh	471 GWh	529 GWh	68 GWh	710 GWh

2) Reduction of carbon footprint of heating and cooling in the region

The supply of energy by a heating network using a high proportion of renewable energies (including residual heat) avoids the need for other sources of heat. Based on the minimum reuse hypothesis (220-300 GWh/year), the production of 27 500 to 38 500 tCO₂(eq) could be avoided each year. Adapting the operating schedule throughout the year would compensate for the carbon footprint of the consumed electricity.

3) Increasing purchasing power of local population

The organization operating the FCC is not in the business of making money. Energy can therefore be supplied by network operators at very competitive prices. According to the French multi-annual energy program (PPE³⁷), waste-to-energy plants (which recover waste heat) sell this heat at a very competitive price between 10 and €25/MWh. As a result, the heat supplied can then be the preferred choice for heating, hot water, and cooling. In the Anergie network (Ferney-Voltaire), the price of waste heat supplied by CERN equipment is even lower. According to a study by AMORCE and ADEME, the average selling price for networks supplied mainly by renewable and recovered energies (“EnR&R”) was €78.2 incl. tax/MWh in 2020³⁸ (these prices do not take into account the initial investment costs of the networks). According to the research firm Ginger BURGEAP, the average price was at the same level more recently. Based on this model, the potential savings are currently estimated at €50/MWh³⁹ compared with gas heating, and €140/MWh⁴⁰ compared with electricity, using energy prices on 1st November 2023, as a reference.

4) Limiting water consumption

Reusing residual heat would also reduce the need for cooling water. This potential can be explored at a later stage, when system concepts are better known.

³⁷<https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/20200422%20Programmation%20pluriannuelle%20de%20l'e%CC%81nergie.pdf>

³⁸ AMORCE and ADEME, *Enquête sur le prix de vente de la chaleur et du froid en 2020, 2022.*

³⁹ 50 €/MWh = 0.05 €/GWh

⁴⁰ 140 €/MWh = 0.14 €/GWh

3. CONTEXT AND INITIAL LAYOUT SCENARIOS

Chapter 3 provides the background which explains why a layout scenario in the Franco-Swiss border region is necessary. It explains why alternative scenarios to the west of the Jura were examined, then discarded in favour of scenarios to the east of the Jura. It then reviews how the layout considered during the exploratory phase of the FCC study (2014-2018) demonstrated the feasibility of the FCC, and how the precise layout examined presented prohibitive obstacles in certain locations. Finally, it mentions the variant involving a linear collider, which was not selected.

3.1. HYPOTHESES AND INITIAL CONDITIONS

The development of a scenario for the configuration and layout of the FCC in the region was based on the idea of taking advantage of existing CERN infrastructure for the project. The construction of a circular collider requires existing particle accelerators in operation with technical infrastructures that can serve as injectors; the availability of workspace, workshops, equipment and skilled workforce; as well as favourable legal, administrative and project management frameworks (Illustration 34). It is therefore essential that the chosen layout remain within reasonable proximity to an existing CERN site.

<p>Énergie stable et écologique accessible</p>			
<p>Relations de confiance avec les autorités</p>			

Illustration 34: Key factors in the decision to locate a future circular collider at CERN in the French-Swiss border region.

In addition, the particle collider must have a circumference greater than 90 km to accommodate two different particle colliders in the future (an electron-positron collider and a hadron collider), each of which must deliver the performance required to carry out the desired scientific research program.

The immediate research zone would be located to the south of CERN's Meyrin and Prévessin sites, away from the Jura mountains. Indeed, already during the LEP construction phase, major obstacles were encountered due to the presence of karstic formations and high-pressure water penetrations (Illustration 35), even though the LEP tunnel was located at a much shallower depth than the underground structures of the FCC.

Illustration 35: Due to geological uncertainties, the initial location of LEP had to be revised several times before construction began. However, major obstacles such as water penetrations of 100 l/s at a pressure of 8.5 bar were encountered during construction of the LEP tunnel.

Nevertheless, as the next section highlights, an unbiased examination of the situation was conducted so as not to overlook any other possible scenario.

3.2. SCENARIOS WEST OF THE JURA

One study looked at a layout in the Bresse plain (Dolois region), to the west of the Jura Massif (Illustration 36 below). The ring would have been located outside the Jurassic formations, at a depth of around 40 meters, but in any case the infrastructure would have encroached on existing national and regional parks and vast nature conservation areas. In addition, the required link to CERN's particle accelerator complex would have required a long tunnel of around 60 km for the transfer lines. This tunnel through the Jura mountain range would have passed through very unfavourable geological formations, with significant overburden. Given that the distance between the Jura mountains and the Petite Montagne du Jura is less than 20 km, it seems impossible to place a sufficiently large circular particle collider in this zone. These options had already been studied in 1997 and 2001 and were checked again between 2014 and 2019⁴¹.

Illustration 36: Comparison of land areas and protection zones to the west and east of the Jura chain.

⁴¹ A. Tudora, J. Osborne, V. Mertens, *Feasibility Study of a Trans-Jura FCC Scenario with one Transfer Line from the LHC*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4545604>.

In the end, this option was dropped from further studies for the following reasons:

- A long tunnel for the beam transfer line through the Jura mountain range would pose too many difficulties, both from a civil engineering and a technical point of view. Construction times and overall costs would increase considerably, by at least 30%.
- This scenario would require deep access shafts in difficult-to-access mountainous regions of the Jura massif, which are largely nature conservation areas. The rock is highly unstable, and the penetration of high-pressure water is certain.
- The loose soil in the Bresse region would require stabilization and protection measures. Hydrophilic gypsum swells considerably (ground movements of roughly one metre recorded in the Chienberg road tunnel), which is not compatible with large-scale cavern construction, nor with the requirement for a highly stable tunnel. Maintenance costs would be much higher than on stable ground.
- The installation would most likely interfere with nature protection constraints and cause significant disturbances to local residents during the construction phase.
- The space available between the Jura massif, its national park and the Petite Montagne du Jura area to the northwest is too small to accommodate a circular particle accelerator of sufficient size.
- There is no reasonable way of operating and maintaining the infrastructure from CERN or any other suitable partner organization nearby.

3.3. SCENARIOS EAST OF THE JURA

For the zone to the east of the Jura, an initial large search perimeter was defined in 2014 based on the following conditions:

- To ensure stability, the tunnel must cross Lake Geneva at a sufficient depth below the lake bed. Initial ideas of placing the tunnel in unstable ground (moraines, quaternary glacial deposits) or in a construction on the lake bed had to be rejected due to a) insufficient stability and b) the impossibility of creating suitable interfaces between the tunnel on either side of the lake and the construction in the lake.
- In order to be located at an acceptable depth below the lake bed and to remain as far as possible within the molasse layer, underground structures should be located at around 250 m above sea level, ideally avoiding crossing the limestone/molasse interfaces.
- A boundary line was drawn to the northwest (Jura zone) and to the west (Vuache zone) to ensure sufficient distance from high elevations leading to unacceptable overburdens, inaccessible and protected areas, unstable rocks, faults, seismically active zones, and unstable karstic formations where the penetration of high-pressure water is certain.
- To the southwest, the Mandallaz mountainous zone forms a natural border. Its crossing cannot be avoided. Consequently, the preferred scenarios are those for which the overburden and crossing length are low.
- To the south, a boundary line has been drawn northwest of the Montagne des Frêtes nature reserve to avoid elevations above 750 m (unacceptable, as they would lead to excessively deep wells), inaccessible and topographically unacceptable zones, and protection zones to the south. This line crosses the Fillière valley at Thorens-Glières and spans the acceptable elevations of the Bornes plateau as far as La Roche-sur-Foron.
- To the east, a boundary line has been drawn to avoid mountainous zones and thus remain in the Arve River valley.

The perimeter obtained in the study is compatible with a circular infrastructure with a circumference of 90 to 100 km, and can meet geological, topographical, environmental and urban planning constraints (Illustration 37). The maximum distance that can actually be used is 29 km from north to south and 30 km from west to east. The result is a zone capable of accommodating a circular collider with a circumference of up to 92 km for a configuration comprising eight sites, or up to 98 km for a configuration comprising twelve sites.

Illustration 37: Established study perimeter (red line). Exclusion zones and zones with too many difficulties for surface sites are indicated in red; favourable zones are indicated in blue.

3.4. REFERENCE SCENARIO FOR INITIAL STUDIES

The initial aim of the FCC study was to establish the technical feasibility of electron-positron and hadron particle colliders of such dimensions. The layout study was therefore limited to defining a location that could be used to verify the feasibility of civil engineering work, and to obtain an initial estimate of risks and costs. The work was based on a configuration, comprising twelve sites, which would enable the largest particle collider to be integrated into the defined zone. At this stage, only geological information served as a basis for the work (Illustration 38). The locations of the surface sites were chosen to meet the need to create a connection between the particle collider and existing CERN accelerators (SPS and LHC), and to avoid surface features clearly incompatible with the project, such as a) extremely high elevations, b) unsuitable topography, c) protection zones, taken from publicly available national maps, d) insufficient road connections and e) the absence of possible synergies with existing technical infrastructures such as the CERN Meyrin and Prévessin sites, national power grid infrastructures and existing water-cooling resources.

Illustration 38: Cross-section of base layout scenario showing expected geological features. 84% of the tunnel would be located in the molasse layer. Increasing this percentage and reducing the likelihood of encountering karstic and quaternary layers are measures that reduce risk for the project.

The scenario number PA0-0.1 (also known as the "Berlin 2017 scenario") was analysed by Ecotec and the French organization Cerema with regard to various territorial issues, in order to gain an initial understanding of its compatibility with local conditions. This work led to the creation of two reports (FCC-INF-RPT-007⁴² and FCC-INF-RPT-0040⁴³), which provided a better understanding of the relevant aspects to be taken into account in future studies. These reports have also been used to standardise the indicators to be used in future studies, and to develop a methodology following the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) approach, which can be used to develop a configuration and layout scenario that is balanced in terms of scientific performance, territorial compatibility and project implementation issues (Table 12).

Table 12: Multi-criteria analysis of each site location and of the 97.75 km footprint for scenario PA0-0.1 from the preliminary conceptual design report in 2018.

PA0-0.1	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP			RF			EXP			RF			97,75 km	
FCC-hh	EXP	EXP	Cryo		Cryo	Col		RF	Cryo	Col	Cryo	EXP		
Site														
Score	89	52	51	61	75	40	41	36	49	45	33	36	84	53

⁴² Ecotec, *Layout review in Switzerland*, V2.0, December 13, 2017, FCC-INF-RPT-0007, EDMS 1838912

⁴³ Cerema, *Étude de sensibilité du scénario d'implantation du projet FCC en France et de ses opportunités*, V2.0, FCC-INF-RPT-0040

In conclusion (Illustration 39), the feasibility of FCC on this particular site was unlikely for several reasons. Of the twelve surface sites, three present de facto obstacles from a territorial point of view (PH and PK in France, PL in Switzerland). One of the points is considered difficult because of its elevation, topography, and access (PF in France). The feasibility is considered to be low for a PG experiment site south of Thorens-Glières, in a zone with high ecological value that is currently inaccessible. The remaining eight sites are located in areas with moderate to severe constraints, requiring relocation or major adaptations. A site in the immediate vicinity of CERN, on unfenced CERN territory, also faces obstacles.

Illustration 39: Results of the multi-criteria analysis of the initial baseline scenario used during the exploratory study phase from 2014 to 2018.

Although efforts were made to seek as many synergies as possible with the CERN Meyrin site, the **PA** point would be located directly under the Swissgrid 400 kV power line, creating major compatibility issues. The new visitors centre project (“Portail de la science”) and the presence of several other underground tunnels make integration difficult. Although the site is located on the organization's unfenced land, the neighbourhood is already impacted by the immediate proximity of an experiment facility, and a further extension could meet with growing opposition that would, at the very least, have an impact on the timetable. Adaptations and agreements would then have to be reached by consensus with the neighbours of the CERN Meyrin site, which could lead to the relocation of all other sites and the need for a new scenario analysis.

The **PB** secondary experiment site would be located in Bellevue (Switzerland), in a no-drilling and water protection zone, characterised by the presence of two overlapping aquifers. Although the location is not considered impossible, technical difficulties should be expected, and the choice of shafts will require particular attention. The creation of at least two shafts, as required for an experiment site, must be considered a major challenge. The small size of the field means that the acquisition of a private residence on the neighbouring property must be considered, as necessary. In addition, this plot of land would be needed to create good road access. This private field belongs to a large number of private owners, which would lengthen the acquisition process. An amendment to the federal law on the promotion of research and innovation is under preparation and will provide the legal basis for acquiring the plots. This layout is considered difficult, but not impossible.

The **PC** technical site would be located within the immediate perimeter of a heritage site, and the construction of a surface site in this area is prohibited. A slight displacement would not lead to any significant improvement, given current landscape protection requirements. Moving the site further west would place it close to another heritage site. A move to the east could improve the situation. In this case, the site would be located in an agricultural area including crop rotation areas (SDA), requiring the establishment of a specific sectoral plan at the federal level, as well as direct acquisition negotiations between CERN and the private owner in order to obtain legal authorization to acquire the land for construction purposes. The location of this site is therefore considered to present implementation problems.

There are high territorial constraints on the **PD** technical site and its surroundings, making the location unsuitable, and its relocation within a distance of less than 1 000 m is difficult. The zones in question are subject to a ban on construction.

The **PE** technical site would be located in a zone with major constraints, but a short move of 100 m would provide a location that is potentially suitable.

The **PF** site would be located in a high-elevation mountainous area, with very steep slopes. The depth of the shaft would be over 475 m, at the limit of technical feasibility, with a potentially high impact on operability and maintenance capabilities. Local urban planning documents indicate the presence of numerous natural areas and protected zones, as well as a historical site, on this site and within its perimeter. In addition, the PF site is located in a natural hazard zone and a flood protection zone. Moving the access site and shaft 200 m could place them in a more suitable location, but the elevation of 920 m and the topographical conditions would still pose significant feasibility challenges.

The location of the second main **PG** experiment site south of Thorens-Glières would not be satisfactory. Although the site is located outside the municipality, it would be in a high-quality natural environment to the south of the Fillière, which would most likely arouse strong opposition. The zone is currently inaccessible and would require the creation of a special road access through the Thorens-Glières municipality along the D2 mountain road. Once again, this would lead to significant disturbance and, consequently, strong opposition would be likely. The depth of the three shafts would exceed 300 m, making installation, operation, and maintenance difficult. This analysis led to the conclusion that it would be preferable to select other scenarios to limit shaft depth to 300 m.

The **PH** technical site would be located in the centre of Charvonnex, with no possibility of moving the site to a reasonable location that would present suitable topographical and access conditions and no natural constraints. This layout is therefore considered to be very difficult.

The **PI** technical site would be located in a zone with high territorial constraints, and would have to be relocated to another zone at least 450 m away.

The **PJ** technical site would be located in an agricultural zone considered to be undesirable. Adaptations or relocations could be considered to find a workable solution.

The **PK** technical site near the Rhone would be located in an exclusion zone just north of the Rhone river bank. The whole area is characterised by major constraints, ranging from Natura 2000 zones to water protection zones and zones for the protection of flora and fauna. Originally, this site was already considered very difficult, and a potential move to a more remote location could have been considered. However, between the time of the analysis (2017) and the writing of this report, several hundred hectares of land have been reclassified in this zone, which now constitutes a vast exclusion zone. So even when the site was moved almost 2 000 m north, no suitable location could be found. The Vulbens forest area, south of the Rhône, is now also considered an area to be avoided. There are major nature conservation issues, and strong opposition is to be expected. The impossibility of finding a suitable location for this site therefore makes scenarios based on this scheme highly unlikely.

The secondary **PL** experiment site in Dardagny (Switzerland) would be located on agricultural land with crop rotation areas (SDA) requiring a zoning procedure under planning law (e.g. by drawing up a sectoral plan at federal level), as well as direct acquisition negotiations with private owners in order to obtain legal authorization to acquire the land for construction purposes. Although these conditions are difficult, they are not impossible. However, the site is now located in a water protection zone where drilling is prohibited. In addition, the agricultural area is only excluded from the strict protection zone for the surrounding flora and fauna at Allondon, as it has historically been used for this purpose. The feasibility of the original location would therefore now be considered unlikely, but not impossible.

3.5. LINEAR COLLIDER VARIANT

3.5.1. Introduction

The international particle physics research community, considering environmental assessment guidelines in the European Union, France, and Switzerland, has presented several variants of future colliders. This section therefore introduces the concept of the linear collider. The most advanced studies concern the CLIC⁴⁴ (*Compact Linear Collider*) and the ILC⁴⁵ (*International Linear Collider*). Two sites were considered for the CLIC layout: one in France and Switzerland, in connection with CERN, notably the Prévessin site; the other in Japan in the Kitakami mountains, in the Tohoku region, some 400 km north of Tokyo. The construction of this linear collider would enable an integrated research program based on two circular colliders forming part of a single infrastructure. However, the first CLIC phase (CLIC 380, Illustration 40) may raise certain research questions that can also be addressed during the first FCC phase, FCC-ee. It will be shown that a linear collider has less merit than the FCC in terms of scientific performance and impact on the region.

Illustration 40: Variant of a three-stage linear collider. The first stage (11.4 km long) can, under certain conditions, be compared to the electron-positron phase of the FCC (FCC-ee).

⁴⁴ Updated baseline for a staged Compact Linear Collider, 2016, arXiv:1608.07537v3: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2210892/files/arXiv:1608.07537.pdf>

⁴⁵ The International Linear Collider technical design report, arXiv:1306.6328, 2013: https://cds.cern.ch/record/1601969/files/ILCTDR-VOLUME_3-PART_II.pdf

The CLIC concept calls for several successive versions, differing in collider length, cost, and particle acceleration technology. The scenario chosen to summarise the potential contributions of this research infrastructure variant with a linear collider is based on the shortest length (around 11 km) for a collider used for the detailed study of the Higgs boson, called "CLIC 380 GeV". This version can be compared to the FCC-ee, as the collision energy achieved with the two 380 GeV beams is comparable to the highest collision energy of the FCC-ee, 365 GeV. However, FCC-ee also plans to operate at lower energies, including 91.2 GeV, 160 GeV and 240 GeV, to answer specific scientific questions.

CLIC 380 is based on particle acceleration by radiofrequency systems using "klystron" amplifiers. The klystron is a vacuum tube that amplifies radiofrequencies. It is often used in radar, in particle accelerators used in radiotherapy, in television stations and in satellite broadcasting stations. The FCC-ee circular accelerator uses the same technology. A linear accelerator deploys these elements along the entire length of the accelerator (Illustration 40). A circular accelerator, on the other hand, uses them only in a small part of the ring, accelerating particles in stages with each revolution. During each of these revolutions, the beams of "light" particles (electrons and positrons) lose some of their energy in the synchrotron radiation in the acceleration section. This loss must be compensated for after each revolution. The rate of loss is inversely proportional to the circumference of the accelerator. The smaller the ring, the higher the loss of energy with each revolution. In a linear accelerator, the beams do not lose energy during acceleration, but the particles must be accelerated to reach collision energy for each collision along the length of a collider section.

A circular accelerator with a sufficiently large circumference, optimised to achieve the highest desired collision energy, is more energy-efficient than a linear accelerator. If the circumference is too small, the energy lost through synchrotron radiation becomes too great, and no longer justifies the use of this type of accelerator. The energy loss per revolution in the FCC-ee is 0.06% for the lowest collision energy and 6% for the highest collision energy.

What's more, to accelerate "heavier" particles such as protons or atomic nuclei (ions), linear acceleration is inefficient, whereas energy loss through synchrotron radiation is low in a circular accelerator. This is why it is preferable to use a circular accelerator for proton and ion collisions at high energies, as planned in phase 2 of the FCC, the FCC-hh.

A linear collider has just one interaction point, where the two beam lines cross, whereas the FCC circular collider would have four. Beyond the intersection point, the accelerated particles disappear into elements designed to absorb the beam lines.

By performing acceleration in stages, together with the possibility of continuously injecting additional particles, and the multitude of possibilities for measuring and manipulating the beam line during each revolution in the circular accelerator, enable higher particle concentrations to be achieved than in linear accelerators. This density of particles per unit area and time is essential for scientific research, as it increases the number of interesting collisions to study and interpret.

Illustration 41: On the left, the linear accelerator concept; on the right, the circular accelerator concept.

The CLIC collider project is intended to evolve in several phases. In the second phase, the total length will be 29 km, and the collision energy will be increased to 1.5 TeV. In the third phase, the length would be 50.1 km, with a collision energy of 3 TeV. These two phases will require civil engineering work and the development of technical infrastructures, with the addition of surface sites. The first phase (Illustration 42) is less precise for the study of the Higgs boson, and offers much more limited prospects for physics than the first phase of the FCC (FCC-ee). The increase in energy proposed by the next two phases covers an area already explored by the LHC, and its scientific impact is clearly limited compared with that offered by the second phase of the FCC (FCC-hh), which will reuse the same infrastructure that was designed for FCC-ee.

Illustration 42: First phase of the linear collider (CLIC 380 GeV).

3.5.2. Scientific research potential

CLIC 380 (11 km long, with a fixed collision energy of 380 GeV) will enable detailed studies only of the Higgs boson and the top quark. The accelerator's design might enable operation at lower energies under certain conditions, but with a significant loss of luminosity⁴⁶. Luminosity is a key value that describes how many particles per cm² per second can interact at the point where the beam lines cross. The operations foreseen for the circular collider at collision energies of 91 GeV (Z boson), 160 GeV (W boson), 240 GeV (Higgs boson) and 350-365 GeV (Higgs boson and top quark) are essential to be able to carry out the physics program desired by theorists and experimental physicists. It should be pointed out that, depending on the collision energy required, the luminosity of the circular collider is 10 to 1 000 times higher than that of the linear collider, which has an impact on the required research time and accuracy of the results. The four points of interaction play a significant role here.

A linear collider comprises a single detector at the centre of the two beam lines. This limits the extent of scientists' involvement, and makes it impossible to design complementary experiments based on different particle detection methods, or to corroborate the results obtained through the work and observations of several research teams. Even more importantly, each additional experiment installed in the ring of a circular collider increases the number of collisions observed and reduces the research time, and therefore the energy consumption for this research.

The benefits this collider offers for research and the need for energy sobriety are already leading towards a preference for a circular collider with several interaction points, making it possible to almost quadruple the number of scientists who can carry out complementary research, without increasing the electrical energy consumption of the collider or the carbon footprint during operation.

Linear acceleration technology does not make optimum use of particle acceleration: beam line intensity is lower than that of a circular accelerator, and accelerated particles that do not participate in collisions at the interaction point are lost. These two factors, together with the fact that Higgs boson production at 380 GeV is almost half that at 240 GeV, have an important consequence: **only 150 000 Higgs bosons would be produced with a linear collider in eight years, whereas the FCC-ee, equipped with four detectors, takes just three years to produce ten times as many.** The degradation of measurement accuracy using a linear collider would directly affect the scientific impact. For the CLIC to obtain approximately the same level of accuracy as FCC-ee, it would have to operate for almost a century at 380 GeV, which is hardly realistic. Increased energy in the next two phases would partially bridge the gap with FCC-ee in roughly thirty years, but the CLIC would not be able to offer the accuracy offered by the FCC-hh after just a few years of operation.

⁴⁶ *The Compact Linear Collider (CLIC) 2018 Summary Report* : <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2652188/files/1812.06018.pdf>

3.5.3. Territorial compatibility

The completion of the CLIC implementation scenario (currently not optimised) would be a challenge. The location of the interaction point is to the northeast of the fenced-in CERN site in Prévessin (Illustration 43), on land made available to the organization that is currently used as farmland. However, only part of this land is currently allocated to CERN by the PLU local urban plan (UAcern zone, see Illustration 43). Most of the 40 to 50 hectares that have been allocated are designated as protected natural zones (Np) and protected agricultural zones (Ap).

Illustration 43: Approximate perimeter of the CLIC surface site, in purple, with the interaction point to the northeast of the CERN Prévessin site in light orange ("terrain du CERN") in France in zones Np and Ap.

For the shortest version of the collider, covering part of the FCC-ee research program, surface site 3, west of the interaction point, would be located in Saint-Genis-Pouilly in an area already planned for development (Zone for urban centrality, 1AUC, in an area covered by Planning and Development Guidelines: the Porte de France). Even if the environmental stakes are low, the compatibility of the FCC with this development project (which was in the public inquiry phase⁴⁷ in September 2023) still needs to be analysed and validated. There are no other locations that seem feasible at the required distance from the interaction point in this direction.

Site 2, to the east of the interaction point at Sauvigny, lies in a natural protection zone (Np) to be preserved for ecological reasons. The location is considered undesirable, but could still be feasible.

For the linear collider extension options, the shafts to the west of the interaction point are currently in zones not considered to be feasible. Shaft 5 is located in the Allondon zone in Switzerland reserved for absolute protection, and there is no location considered feasible within a radius of roughly 1 km. Shaft 7, to the west of Challex, lies in an area considered undesirable for natural protection reasons (Np), but could be feasible.

⁴⁷ Requalification du secteur de la Porte de France :

<https://www.ain.fr/app/uploads/2023/09/dossier-concertation-porte-france-web-2023.pdf>

Shaft 9, south of Collonges, lies within a zone reserved for absolute protection, the marshlands of Étournel, and on the Pougny water table. This location is not considered to be feasible. Shaft 11 is located in the Haute-Chaîne du Jura zone, the Fort l'Écluse pass, Étournel and Vuache. This zone reserved for absolute protection is not considered to be feasible, not only because of the presence of multiple protection zones, but also because of the difficult topography, the presence of a high-risk landslide zone and the lack of access. Shaft 4 (Divonne), which lies within a zone reserved for absolute protection, the Prodon marsh, is not considered to be feasible. Shafts 6, 8 and 10 are located in the Swiss canton of Vaud. At present, there is little data available to determine the feasibility of this approach. Based on available data, shaft 6 is located in an environmentally sensitive zone, on a crop rotation area (SDA). Shaft 8 is located on a protected crop rotation area. Lastly, shaft 10 does not appear to be feasible because it is located in the middle of a zone with protected vineyards, in the Domaine de Serreaux-Dessus⁴⁸.

3.5.4. Implementation risks and costs

The risks associated with implementing the CLIC project in the region are comparable to those of the FCC. If two additional phases are considered, an extension into the canton of Vaud will require the involvement of additional stakeholders in Switzerland. As mentioned in the previous section, the risks associated with environmental impacts in protected areas are not negligible. The absence of any investigation of the subsurface stability or of the hydrogeological conditions makes the CLIC project's completion within the same period as the FCC hardly seem possible. Subsurface investigations should be carried out, at least in areas presenting particular difficulties.

At this stage, no discussions about this variant have been initiated with stakeholders in the two host countries. If the project were to go ahead, these steps would have to be taken. A choice needs to be made as soon as possible between continuing the CLIC project or launching the FCC project, because CERN and the host countries have limited resources at their disposal.

From a technical point of view, the accelerator and the experiment are feasible, since prototypes have been built and tested in the laboratory. However, the extremely small cross-section of the beam lines (119 nm x 2.9 nm), with a diameter even smaller than that of DNA, will remain a difficulty to overcome for controlling particle collisions. By way of comparison, the FCC-ee beam line is 10 to 1,000 times larger than the CLIC beam line, ranging from 22 000 nm x 45 nm to 121 000 x 250 nm depending on beam line energy, which reduces the risk involved in mastering the technology.

In terms of costs, at first glance, the investments required for CLIC 380 appear to be significantly lower than those required for FCC-ee (around 8.4 billion Swiss francs, compared with 12.8 billion Swiss francs at 2023 value). However, subsequent phases of CLIC would require investment in civil engineering works. For the FCC, the FCC-hh infrastructure is the same as the FCC-ee, entailing no additional cost. In terms of operating costs, the majority will be personnel expenses, in particular the remuneration of researchers and engineers employed by the universities and research centres taking part in the project. These investments will be beneficial for scientific research and produce other direct advantages: scientific production and improvements in the quality of teaching and training, enabling the people involved to earn higher salaries throughout their careers, as has been the case with existing CERN projects. Since the CLIC project would involve far fewer scientists than the FCC, its benefits would also be less significant, which calls into question the value of the project.

⁴⁸ Domaine Serreaux Dessus, Begnins, Vaud, Switzerland: <https://www.serreaux-dessus.ch/>

3.5.5. Summary

Table 13, which compares different elements of the two variants (linear collider and circular collider), highlights their respective advantages and drawbacks. The values, presented in a summarised and simplified format, cannot be directly compared, and must be interpreted in their respective contexts.

The scenario for a short linear collider (total length of 11.4 km, energy of 380 GeV) has certain advantages, such as the cost, the carbon footprint of the construction and the number of surface sites required. However, these only seem valid for an initial research phase, comparable to the FCC-ee phase, and need to be estimated in greater detail, considering the construction material used. During phases 2 and 3 of the CLIC project, the work and associated costs are considerable, which calls into question the relevance of such a project.

On the other hand, the circular collider offers significant advantages in terms of the flexibility it offers, the number of scientists who can participate in the research, the total size of the surface sites, the electricity and water consumption required for the research program, the impact on natural areas and its scientific impact.

In conclusion, a research infrastructure based on two circular colliders in series is preferable to a variant based on a linear collider (see also Table 13). For this reason, this first variant was chosen for further examination, and feasibility studies for the FCC were launched in CERN's two host states.

Table 13: Linear collider/circular collider comparison: scientific aspects, territorial integration, and implementation. Values and comments are to be interpreted in their respective contexts. A direct comparison is not possible.

Aspect	Advantage with linear variant	Advantage with circular variant	Value of linear collider	Value for circular collider
Length in km	X		11.5 km-50 km	90.7 km
Number of surface sites	Only for 380 GeV version	For entire project	3 for the short version, 11 for the extensions	8
Amount of land used		X	40 ha for the extension of the CERN Prévessin site, around 50 ha in total for the 380 GeV version, around 80 ha for the extension up to 3 TeV	Approximately 40 ha in total for both phases FCC-ee and FCC-hh
Quantity of excavated material (in situ)	Only for 380 GeV version		~ 2 million m ³ for the short version at 380 GeV. The total volume of materials for the extension phases is currently unknown.	~ 6 million m ³
Impact on protected natural areas		X	High	Moderate
Duration of construction phase	Only for 380 GeV version		4.5 years for phase 1 (9 years total with the 50 km extension)	8 years, one civil engineering project
Operations possible at different energy levels with no new building projects		X	An increase in collision energy requires lengthening of the accelerator. Energy levels lower than the energy planned for the design (380 GeV) are possible but would lead to a significant drop in performance.	Possible. The currently foreseen operating modes are: 91.2 GeV, 160 GeV, 240 GeV and 365 GeV.
Particle beam line luminosity		X	Low to medium, depending on collision energy	High to very high, depending on collision energy
Number of experiments		X	1	4

Reusability		X	Possible increase in collision energy with the same particles at 1.4 TeV and 3 TeV with additional civil engineering projects and the installation of additional technical infrastructure	The same infrastructure can be used for a high-energy proton and ion collider (up to 100 TeV), depending on the magnet technology available around the year 2060. Other uses are also conceivable, for example for a high-energy muon collider.
Flexibility to adapt operations to intermediate research results		X	Low (fixed collision energy)	High (variable collision energy)
Ability to attract large numbers of scientists over an extended period of time		X	Low (about 3 times fewer scientists than for a circular collider with 4 experiments, and 10 times fewer than for the hadron phase of the circular collider)	High
Energy consumption for Higgs boson research		X	4.8 TWh (0.6 TWh per year x 8 years)	2.9 TWh (0.75 TWh per year x 1.3 TWh x 3 years)
Highest energy consumption		X	2.8 TWh/year for the operating phase at 3 TeV for 6 years; 16.8 TWh in total	1.8 TWh/year for the so-called "ttbar" operating phase for 5 years; 8.9 TWh in total
Cooling water requirements		X	1 170 m ³ /h for the 380 GeV version	< 900 m ³ /h (without injector, with 4 experiments, booster accelerator and transfer lines)
Machine efficiency		X	Low (particles are not reused)	High (particles are recirculated and accelerated once again)
Technical complexity		X	High	Moderate
Operational complexity		X	High (continuous beam line optimization is difficult)	Moderate (beam line optimization can be done continuously)
Reuse of CERN facilities		X	Extension of the Prévessin site from 40 ha to 50 ha in the required protected zone, connection to cooling water from lake, connection to the 400 kV Bois-Tollot power line (France)	Prévessin site, LHC point 8 site, connection to cooling water from lake, connection to 400 kV Bois-Tollot power line (France)

Construction necessary in Switzerland	380 GeV only	For total perimeter	None for the shorter 11 km version. 4 surface sites, connection to the Swiss high-voltage grid for subsequent phases.	A surface site
Construction necessary in France	380 GeV only	For total perimeter	3 surface sites in France for phase 1 (connection to the 400 kV power line in France for subsequent phases and 7 surface sites for phase 3)	7 surface sites, two connections to the 400 kV grid in France
Set-up costs	380 GeV only		7.3 billion Swiss Francs (2019 value) for the shortest 380 GeV version, amount updated to 8.4 billion Swiss Francs (2023 value)	Between 14 and 16 billion CHF depending on the number of experiments, including the radiofrequency system for the "ttbar" operation (2024 value)
Carbon footprint of construction	380 GeV only		~ 290 ktCO ₂ (eq) for phase 1 at 380 GeV	~ 527 ktCO ₂ (eq) ⁴⁹

⁴⁹ Mauree, D. (2024). FCC Construction Carbon Footprint Benchmark and Optimisation Strategies, V2.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13899160>

4. DEVELOPING A BALANCED SCENARIO

Chapter 4 provides details, for each site, of the areas that are suitable for the layout and those that present constraints. Next, the conditions are listed that must be met by all acceptable scenarios (absolute necessities) and the conditions that the project owner has defined to make the scenario more acceptable at the territorial level (voluntary objectives).

4.1. ZONES TO AVOID AND PREFERRED ZONES

The initial review of the configuration made it possible to define a systematic methodology for developing and assessing layout scenarios, identifying zones to be avoided and locations that may, on the contrary, be considered promising for the development of new, balanced scenarios.

In the end, roughly one hundred different scenarios (approximately seventy scenarios with eight sites and thirty scenarios with twelve sites) were developed using this approach. To ensure that no potentially feasible scenario was overlooked during the manual creation of scenarios, the automatic search algorithm of the interactive footprint tool was used with all the parameters to be prioritised to confirm that a scenario was the most suitable for the constraints encountered.

The scenarios were studied with various levels of detail, depending on whether they were to be dismissed quickly or subjected to an in-depth study of the various conditions. Some scenarios resulted in the geographical limit set for the study being exceeded. They were examined nonetheless to check whether the advantages arising from territorial compatibility outweighed the drawbacks due to geological and topographical conditions.

4.1.1. Layouts of interest in Switzerland near CERN

Illustration 44: Layouts of interest with underground and surface constraints between Challex (France) and Ferney-Voltaire (France) in Switzerland.

Illustration 44 above highlights the zones of Swiss territory to the west and east of CERN's Meyrin site that have proved to be suitable or unsuitable for a surface site. Lastly, only the sector west of the Allondon zone proved suitable for scenarios with surface sites within the geological boundary, and for which surface sites at all other points are potentially feasible. Only two plots on the “Route de Malval” road, between the French border and Dardagny, were found to be potentially suitable in this sector, as the whole zone is subject to high constraints in terms of protection zones (nature, wetlands, water protection, vineyards, and heritage buildings). The plots shown in blue are theoretically possible. Locations for a PL site, including potentially feasible surface sites for other points, are located in the triangle made of dotted black lines in the lower left-hand part of the image. Due to the limitations of graphic reproduction, hatched areas in orange appear in dark yellow in the illustration. Zones with drilling bans and water protection zones overlap and have not yet been encoded as red zones to be avoided. The dashed red line indicates the boundary line for geological feasibility. The scenarios must remain southeast of this geological feasibility limit. A PL technical site cannot be located further east of the triangle made of dotted black lines or south of the red geological boundary, as no PL technical site location in this area results in a layout scenario in which all other sites would be feasible. Illustration 45 shows that the location of a PL site east of Challex would result in a scenario that is not feasible due to the geological boundary being significantly exceeded (left) and the location of a PF site within the developed and urbanised perimeter of La Roche-sur-Foron. Several other layouts with zones to be avoided can be cited, but as thousands of different scenarios could be generated, such analyses are beyond the scope of this report.

Illustration 45: Examples of constraints leading to an infeasible scenario with the PL site located to the east of Challex. On the left, the scenario goes well beyond the geological limit. On the right, a close-up of the PF site shows that it would have to be located in the urbanised centre of the town of La Roche-sur-Foron.

The scenario for the current working hypothesis PA31-1.0 is shown in dark orange on the left-hand map of Illustration 45, including the PL surface site in Challex (France) and an experiment site (scientific site) in Ferney-Voltaire.

Based on a theoretical point located in the PL technical site in Challex, on the border between France and Switzerland, a move could be considered for the shaft of up to roughly 800 m on either side of this theoretical point.

Illustration 46: Location of proposed sites to the east of Challex, in Dardagny (Switzerland).

As shown on the Illustration 46, an entire zone is classified as to be avoided ("red" zone) for 900 m to the east on the Swiss side. A 4-hectare field straddling French and Swiss territory, cultivated by the same farmer, is on Swiss territory. This field lies 450 m outside the footprint (PA31-1.0, in brown). On the one hand, it is too far from the footprint, at the limit of acceptability with respect to geological conditions. Limestone is likely present at a depth of 250 m, but there is considerable uncertainty as to the location, the depth, and the presence of high-pressure groundwater. In early 2023, Switzerland's groundwater model and water management planning documents were updated to indicate the presence of a temporary water table in the zone following the GEothermie 2020 measurement campaign⁵⁰. This zone is now included in cross-border planning for drinking water resources. In line with the ERC approach, this new constraint meant moving the shaft even further west (Illustration 47). Before this new underground constraint was introduced, access to the field required either the creation of an access road on the French side, with cross-border access (customs station), or the creation of an access via winding roads in protected areas on the Swiss side. These two scenarios are not realistic and have therefore been abandoned.

The first theoretically possible locations at Dardagny are two cultivated fields at a distance of 1 300 m and 1 400 m. Moving the shaft to this distance is not technically feasible, as the shaft must remain in the straight section (1 050 m on either side of the theoretical point), with a sufficient margin up to the start of the curved section (around 150 to 200 m in this case).

⁵⁰ Schéma de protection, d'aménagement et de gestion des eaux (SPAGE) - Allondon - Mandement, updated 28 June 2022: <https://www.ge.ch/document/eau-spaga-allondon-mandement>.

Various layout scenarios were developed and analysed. If a technical site were to straddle the French (Challex) and Swiss (Dardagny) territories, around 450 m north of the footprint indicated in Illustration 48, the PA scientific site would be located in the town centre of Ferney-Voltaire (map on left). Assuming a location north of Dardagny, the PA site would be located in a zone that is no longer available due to development projects being examined or approved in Ferney-Voltaire (map on right).

Illustration 47: New underground constraints (2023) in the Dardagny (Switzerland)/Challex (France) sector.

Illustration 48: On the left, a map showing the location of the PA scientific site if the selected PL technical site straddles French and Swiss territory, between Challex and Dardagny. On the right, a map showing the location of the PA scientific site if the PL technical site is in Dardagny, Switzerland. It is located in an unoccupied area of the Prévessin-Moëns municipality, but its feasibility is unrealistic. Access to the zone would be through the urbanised area of Ferney-Voltaire, in a densely populated sector.

The choice of an even more distant location, north of Dardagny, would move a site to a zone recently developed by the town in the centre of Ferney-Voltaire (Illustration 49, map on left). There would also be major difficulties for the PG scientific site (Illustration 49, map on right), which would be located in topographically unsuitable zones (elevation between 800 and 900 m, steep slopes and valley) with difficult access to the south, in Fillière, as the only existing road is the D5, a mountain road with limited clearance. As a result, these scenarios have been abandoned.

Illustration 49: Left: location of a PB technical or scientific site in the centre of Ferney-Voltaire. Right: location of a PG scientific site south of La Motte and north of Nantizel, in Fillière, in a mountainous area, resulting from the location of a PL technical site in Dardagny (Switzerland). Scenarios with such features are considered unlikely to be feasible.

4.1.2. Layouts of interest in France near CERN

For the scenario to be suitable, the PL, PA and PB points must remain close to a CERN accelerator (SPS or LHC) that can be used as an injector. A summary of sites in Switzerland, to the west and east of CERN's Meyrin site, has already been provided. This section focuses mainly on the potential location of a PA experiment site in the zone east of Meyrin, France. Zones of interest lie to the south of the geological feasibility limit, marked by a red dashed line in Illustration 50.

Illustration 50: Locations in France, east of Meyrin (Switzerland) and Ferney-Voltaire (France), south of Prévessin (France) and west of Collex-Bossy (Switzerland).

There is little undeveloped land left in this highly urbanised zone, which covers the municipalities of Prévessin, Ferney-Voltaire and Ornex. The sector to the east of Ferney-Voltaire, in Switzerland, includes exclusion zones due to the presence of developed areas, heritage protection boundaries, ecological zones (the zone containing the Gobé stream in Switzerland and France), drilling bans or water protection restrictions (the Montfleury aquifer is fully protected due to its strategic importance as a drinking water reservoir for the canton of Geneva). Five potential locations were identified in the northern zone, just below the geological boundary line, but none of them leads to a theoretically feasible scenario because the geological boundary is exceeded in some zones for other surface sites. In the end, the study showed that only the zones south of the “Route de Ferney” road and west of the recently built eco-district in Ferney-Voltaire (indicated by blue dashed lines in the illustration) could lead to suitable scenarios. Three of the theoretically possible plots in this zone (indicated by numbers 1, 2 and 3 on Illustration 50) are located within the protected boundaries of Voltaire's château. One of them is also located in a nature protection zone (wetland) used for water collection and protection (number 2 on the Illustration 50).

Other sites are located in highly urbanised areas (plots 4, 5, 6 and 7 on Illustration 50), but their small size makes them unlikely candidates. Two sectors (plots 8 and 9 on Illustration 50) are reserved for construction projects and therefore became exclusion zones between 2014 and 2021. A vast zone to the north of the airport (zone 10 on Illustration 50) is considered to be the last natural sector of Ferney-Voltaire and is therefore excluded from the studies. This area is also concerned by the drilling ban and the water protection zone, which extends to the west and east of the zone on Swiss territory.

Potential sites have been identified close to the D35 road leading to the CERN Prévessin site. Zones 12 and 13 shown in the illustration are very close to Prévessin and are therefore given lower priority than zone 11, shown in Illustration 50. For scenarios involving a PA experiment site in this area, the PD, PF and PG sites would be in unfavourable locations, and access would be difficult for the PJ site. These scenarios were therefore abandoned.

Two zones (zones 14 and 15 on Illustration 50), located in the immediate vicinity of point 8 of the CERN LHC, lead to scenarios in which all other candidate locations for surface sites would be in zones that are theoretically compatible. They are also noteworthy because of the beneficial synergies they would generate with the existing CERN site. However, zone 14 is already developed (Espace Candide shopping centre and Leclerc hypermarket) and zone 15 is classified woodlands that the Ferney-Voltaire commune wishes to preserve.

4.1.3. layouts of interest in Switzerland (left bank of the lake)

Illustration 51: Locations in Switzerland, on the left bank of the lake. Border with France in Annemasse and Ville-la-Grand to the southeast, and in Veigy-Foncenex to the northeast.

The sector on the left bank of the lake in Switzerland (Illustration 51) is urbanised in the zone extending inland from the lake for around 2.5 km. Only one location (marked by the black dashed lines in the illustration) is suitable in the narrow corridor that must be respected due to the bathymetry of the lake and the geological boundary line over the entire perimeter.

The fringe to the west of the Pallanterie business park (blue zone no. 1 on Illustration 51) is a zone that could be considered for surface sites. However, traffic congestion in this area remains a challenge. Areas further inland are considered very challenging due to their close proximity to strictly protected areas, heritage sites, wetlands and renaturation projects. A selection of agricultural plots along the “Route de Compois” road (blue zone no. 2 on Illustration 51) can be considered to be suitable candidate zones for surface sites, provided that safety distances are respected to watercourses, wetlands, forests and trees, as well as to the archaeological zone. The entire zone between Meinier and Jussy, including the protected hamlets of Corsinge and Sionnet, is considered too difficult for the location of a surface site. Due to protected agricultural areas, the quality of the landscape and heritage sites, it is too difficult to find a sufficiently large open space at a reasonable distance from the constraints identified in this zone. No scenario could be found that included a surface site further east of this zone up to the French border in Annemasse, since all other surface sites, as well as the particle collider footprint, must remain within the geological boundary limit, and no surface sites are located in the lake. Scenarios were identified with surface sites between the Franco-Swiss border and the railroad line connecting Annemasse and Evian, but they exceeded the geological boundary line, and it was not possible to find suitable locations for all the other surface sites.

Technically suitable sites were found in the Presinge and Choulex sector, to the east of the Carre d'Aval protected areas and the Seymaz watercourse, and to the west of the “Haute école du paysage, d'ingénierie et d'architecture de Genève” university (HEPIA) in Jussy, on the “Route de Jussy” road (blue zones no. 3 and no. 4 in Illustration 51). However, particular attention will be paid to the protected zones in the village of Presinge and to the protected Presinge archaeological zone. The État de Genève (government of Geneva) owns a large tract of land in this zone, making it an attractive location for a surface site. This would create direct synergies with the university, the Domaine de l'Abbaye organic farm and the visitors centre located on the same plot for the recovery and reuse of residual heat (heating the school and greenhouses) and for the sharing of infrastructures such as electricity, water, and telecommunications.

4.1.4. Layouts of interest in France, in the Arve River Valley

Illustration 52: Zones of interest in the Arve River valley.

Illustration 52 above sheds some light on the Arve River valley zone. Surface site locations must remain west of the geological boundary line (red dashed line) and east of the blue dashed curve that indicates the limit of suitable configurations for the particle collider. To the north, the entire zone from Annemasse to Cranves-Sales is unsuitable due to its high rate of urbanization. There are several isolated sites of limited size (3 to 4 ha) along the D903 road and close to the A40 motorway that appear to be suitable (circled in blue in the illustration). The Arve River zone is classified as Natura 2000 and ZNIEFF (Natural Zone of Interest for Ecology, Flora, and Fauna), and must therefore be avoided. Many of the areas to the west of the A40 motorway appear to be suitable, but access to them would ultimately be difficult. The zone including Reignier, L'Éculaz and Scientrier, to the north of the A410 motorway, is urbanised and contains farms, isolated and scattered houses, and forested areas. The zone to the south of the A410 motorway and to the west of the A40 motorway is more suitable. From a topographical standpoint, the area closest to the A40 motorway is the most favourable. It is not possible to define large target zones, as the presence of small villages, and scattered houses and farms requires a more detailed search. The suitable zone ends north of La Roche-sur-Foron, at the Cornier electrical distribution substation.

4.1.5. Layouts of interest in France, in the sector from Bornes plateau to Fillière

Illustration 53: Zone south of La Roche-sur-Foron, as far as Charvonnex.

Illustration 53 shows the zone from south of La Roche-sur-Foron to Charvonnex. The path of the collider must remain north of the red geological boundary line. To achieve a sufficiently large collider circumference, i.e. greater than 89 km, with feasible locations for the surface sites to the north, it is necessary for the collider footprint to remain well below the black dashed line, ideally to the south of the A410 motorway (scenarios with a circumference greater than 90 km). South of La Roche-sur-Foron, sites located before the railroad line, represented in the illustration by the dashed purple line, are in principle possible (zone circled in blue no. 1 on Illustration 53). However, the slope is steep, and the zone is only accessible via a single narrow road that runs through the hamlets to the south of the town. Isolated houses and farms make it difficult to define a sufficiently large surface area. This zone is therefore only considered for technical sites whose location would have to be moved northwards along the footprint of the particle collider in order to place them at a lower elevation. A single zone north of the A410 motorway and south of the RN203 road in Eteaux, away from housing, wetlands and the ZNIEFF, has also been identified as suitable for relocating sites. However, the areas to the north of the RN203 road cannot be selected due to the high density of urbanization and the presence of steep slopes.

The entire zone to the south of the railroad line connecting Annecy to La Roche-sur-Foron cannot be considered due to its high elevation. In general, these zones are inaccessible, and roads are largely unsuitable. However, certain isolated areas (e.g. zones no. 5 and no. 6, circled in blue on Illustration 53) are close to the D1203 road and the A40 motorway, and will need to be examined on a case-by-case basis. On the other hand, their surface area is generally quite limited.

The Fillière valley is too narrow for a surface site. The first suitable location would be on a flat field outside Thorens-Glières (zone no. 4 circled in blue on Illustration 53), close to a heritage farm. Although this location was considered highly suitable for a surface site, local development policy, difficult site access and the likelihood of disturbances for the local population have considerably affected the site's suitability. There are vast sectors of mixed woodland and grassland south of the Fillière (zone no. 3 circled in blue on Illustration 53) which could in principle be considered for a scientific site (experiment site). However, their high ecological value, lack of roads, and restrictive development policies raise questions about their suitability.

Closer to Charvonnex, a few small, isolated sites appear to be suitable along the A410 motorway (for example, zone no. 7, circled in blue on Illustration 53). Further east, other zones on the outskirts of Villy-le-Pelloux (zones no. 8 and no. 9 on Illustration 53) appear to be suitable. However, the presence of experiment sites in these zones would mean crossing the geological boundary in the Vuache zone, which would be problematic due to the presence of active faults and karstic limestone formations with risks of water penetration, as well as risks of seismic instability.

Locations to the south of Villy-le-Pelloux cannot be considered due to the dense urbanization and the presence of forests. Only a few isolated locations along the A41 and D1201 roads could be suitable for relocating the technical sites in certain scenarios, which would otherwise be located in mountainous and forested zones to the east of Charvonnex (e.g. zone no. 10 on Illustration 53).

The most suitable location in this zone for a PG scientific site (experiment site), opposite the PA site, would be to the north of Charvonnex, on the "Route d'Annecy" D1203 departmental road (zone no. 11 on Illustration 53). This location would avoid disturbances for the local population and benefit from access via the local departmental road and even the Groisy motorway service area. Zone no. 11 (circled in blue on Illustration 53) covers a sector of approximately 15 ha. A surface site on this location would also provide easy and rapid access from the LAPP of CNRS/IN2P3, north of Annecy, offering opportunities for sustainable operation of the site.

4.1.6. Layouts of interest in France, between La Mandallaz and Les Ussets

Illustration 54: The Mandallaz Mountain zone, between the A41 motorway to the east and the Ussets Valley to the west.

The zone to the west of Charvonnex and Villy-le-Pelloux (west of the A41 motorway, Illustration 54) quickly rises to elevations of 900 m or more. It has several protected areas, including natural zones and forests. Even if it is not possible for the tunnel to avoid this zone, the zone to the east of Choisy is, as a whole, unsuitable for the location of surface sites due to the risks entailed by crossing through difficult limestone rock. Candidate locations are, in certain cases, only defined in isolated, carefully selected areas (e.g. zones no. 1 and no. 2 in Illustration 54). Other more suitable locations would be to the west of Choisy. Care must also be taken to respect heritage sites, such as the Château de la Balme, located between zones no. 1 and no. 3 on Illustration 54. To the north of this zone, the elevation again rises rapidly above 700 m, and the area is covered by dense forest. Closer to the Ussets Valley further north (zones no. 4 and no. 5 on Illustration 54), suitable locations would be between the D203 and D2 departmental roads. In this zone, there is a strategic exclusion zone, forests and drinking water protection zones that must be avoided.

Accessibility is a problem throughout the sector. The proximity of the departmental road would reduce disturbances, provided that hamlets are not crossed through. The proximity of industrial and agricultural production facilities in this area means that synergies can be anticipated, for example the supply of residual heat. Closer proximity to the Ussets River would also mean shallower shaft depths. Consequently, the most suitable area in this sector would be to the south of the D2 departmental road and to the west of the Marlioz forest area.

4.1.7. Layouts of interest in France, in the Vuache and Rhône zone

Illustration 55: Area extending from the Vuache to the Rhone in the north.

Illustration 55 shows the zone extending from north of Marlioz to Pougny. This zone is bounded by the Vuache mountains to the west, while the north mainly consists of the vast Rhone River zone. The particle collider scenarios must be as far away from the Vuache Mountain as possible to reduce risks crossing known faults, to avoid crossing through the molasse/limestone interface and areas characterised by seismic activity, and also to avoid high elevations and steep slopes. At the same time, the layout must be as close as possible to the Vuache to ensure that the collider ring is sufficiently large, to avoid crossing the geological boundary line in other sectors (e.g. to the east) and to avoid unfavourable zones to the south (Bornes plateau, Fillière valley). This makes the search for suitable scenarios particularly difficult.

In addition, there are numerous restrictions on the zones to the north and south of the A40 motorway, such as the protection of agricultural activities of particular regional interest (e.g. fruit tree cultivation) and the presence of numerous drinking water protection areas, residential homes, and farms in highly valued countryside.

The zone north of Vulbens includes a protected forest and a strategic water reservoir. Although the zone along the riverbanks could in theory be considered, it is less favourable due to the likelihood of local opposition and the creation of potentially unacceptable disturbances in a sensitive zone with many visitors (leisure activities, equestrian facilities, campgrounds, migratory bird observation zone).

The entire Rhone sector and the area north of the Rhone are exclusion zones due to Natura 2000 protection status and the presence of peatland, wetlands (Étournal marsh) and numerous strategic drinking water protection sites.

Suitable isolated zones are located near small villages to the east of the Vuache (blue zones no. 1 and no. 2 on the Illustration 55, Savigny and Murcier sectors).

More suitable locations would be north and south of the A40 motorway, west of the Valleiry service area, west of the drinking water protection zone and east of the entrance to the Vuache tunnel. This zone, for which access is relatively easy via the D1206 road, meets the criterion for railway access or proximity to existing railway access, and could potentially generate synergies with the existing motorway service area.

4.1.8. Layouts of interest in the Jura zone of France

Illustration 56: Zone north of the Rhone, south and east of the Jura.

Illustration 56 above shows the zone north of the Rhone, east and south of the Jura Massif. The right-hand side of the illustration shows the various protection zones to be avoided in the Jura-Rhone-Vuache region. The black box indicates the area shown in greater detail on the left-hand side of the illustration. The dotted red line represents the geological boundary line. The footprint of the particle collider must remain south and east of this line. The zone to the north of this geological boundary is characterised by the presence of karstic limestone formations at shallow depths. As a result, there are several artesian wells with high-pressure water all the way to Challex. These wells are frequently used to collect drinking water and are subject to water protection restrictions. The zone to the southwest of Challex is part of the Haut-Jura regional park and should therefore be avoided altogether. One potential candidate zone, located on the Swiss border to the south of Challex, is considered unsuitable due to difficult access and the fact that Challex would be subject to major disturbances if a road were to be built to access this area.

There are suitable zones to the north of the regional park and to the southwest of Challex, at the D76B road (blue zones no. 1 and no. 2 on Illustration 56). Another, less suitable zone (blue zone no. 3 on Illustration 56) would be located to the south of Challex, west of the D89 road, but would require the building of a bypass road around Challex to avoid disturbances. The most suitable zone (blue zone no. 4 on Illustration 56) would be to the north of Challex and to the south of the Bois de Gambet, which includes a forest and wetlands. The zones located on protected fields would enable the creation of access to the D89 road leading to the four-lane D889 departmental road and to the 400 kV power line currently supplying CERN. Care must be taken to ensure that the site is well integrated into this zone, while maintaining a distance from residential areas and respecting the various natural zones and ecological wildlife corridors that connect the forest to the Rhone river zone.

4.2. INVARIABLE CRITERIA AND VOLUNTARY OBJECTIVES

The initial work on the configuration and layout, the subsequent development of methodologies; and the examination of the entire region all led to the definition of invariable criteria for the creation of a balanced project scenario (territorial compatibility, project implementation, scientific performance).

4.2.1. Invariable criteria for scenario

Table 14 below summarises all the invariable criteria that absolutely must be respected in order for the project to be acceptable from a scientific research and project implementation standpoint.

Table 14: Conditions and limits of invariable criteria for the scenario.

Subject	Conditions	Limits
Geological conditions	Avoid limestone, karst, unstable soils, high-pressure water areas, seismic activity, and fault lines, as well as significant overburden.	Optimise vertical alignment in the molasse layer. Remain 100 m below the lake bed (it may be possible to relax this requirement, subject to geophysical and geotechnical verification).
Exclusion zones	Avoid all conflicts with established protection zones and strategic infrastructures, as well as developed areas, in both host countries.	Avoid areas classified as red in the territorial sensitivity grid.
Total length of curved sections (arcs)	For the initial configuration, the acceptable reduction in total arc length must not exceed 10% of the initial total arc length (i.e. the total length must be at least 91% of the initial total length), in order to maintain a balance between luminosity, energy obtained, and energy lost.	A total arc length greater than 76.2 km (91% of 83.75 km) would result in an acceptable total circumference that would not be significantly less than 91 km, compared with the initial circumference of 97.75 km.
Connection with existing CERN accelerators	Avoid configuration and layout scenarios that would result in scenarios with non-viable transfer lines between the FCC and the SPS and LHC accelerators.	Each scenario requires at least one high-level analysis of transfer line compatibility.
Distance between surface sites	The distance between two access sites must be less than 12 km to ensure the feasibility of civil engineering and an efficient and affordable supply of resources to the accelerator (water, air, cryogenics, electricity), while making it possible to develop a convincing concept for individual safety.	Distance between access shafts of surface sites of less than 12 km.
Number of surface sites	The minimum number of surface sites is determined by a) the minimum distance required between access shafts, and b) the need for a reliable and efficient supply of cryogenics for the hadron collider. Additional constraints arise from the need to provide efficient, reliable ventilation.	8 sites.

Minimum size of surface sites	<p>The minimum size of the land required for a scientific site (experiment site) must be enough to install the equipment needed for the infrastructures and to ensure access for transportation. 400 kV electrical substations, each requiring 1.5 ha, must be foreseen at three of the sites. For all other electrical substations, a size of 0.4 ha is sufficient.</p>	<p>5 ha for a scientific site (experiment site), or even less if an existing CERN site can be reused or used jointly.</p> <p>4 ha for a technical site, 5 ha if a 400 kV substation is required on the site, except for a site holding technical infrastructures for particle acceleration.</p> <p>Fenced area of 3 ha for a technical site with no electrical substation, no buffer zone, and no renaturation measures.</p>
Cross-border access	<p>Reduce legal and administrative issues relating to cross-border access between the two host states as much as possible. State treaties on cross-border issues can cause major delays in project implementation, or even blocking points.</p>	<p>Exclude scenarios that would require surface sites on both sides of the border.</p>
Number of scientific sites	<p>Four locations are required for the scientific sites (experiment sites) of the hadron collider.</p> <p>At least two scientific sites are required for the lepton collider, and an option for two additional sites must be foreseen.</p>	<p>4 sites required.</p>
Access roads	<p>Access roads must be compatible with equipment installation requirements.</p>	<p>Roads 7 m wide, with two lanes, curve radius of 20 m, gradient of less than 10%, minimum height clearance of 4.4 m, weight requirements to be studied on a case-by-case basis.</p>
Accessibility of surface sites	<p>Scientific sites must be within a 30-minute drive of CERN headquarters or an equivalent service centre to ensure efficient installation, servicing, maintenance and repair work.</p> <p>It is acceptable for the technical sites to be slightly further apart.</p>	<p>Distance between CERN and PA and between CERN and PJ or PD: less than 30 km.</p> <p>Distance between LAPP and PG or PD or PJ: less than 30 km.</p> <p>Distance between LAPP and PF or PH: less than 30 km.</p> <p>Distance between CERN and PL and CERN and PB: less than 30 km.</p> <p>Accessibility via standard two-lane roads.</p>

<p>Number of access shafts at surface sites</p>	<p>Access to the experiment site is required from two sides inside the ring, so that systems can be installed, maintained, and upgraded without having to cross the particle accelerator and bypass the detector.</p> <p>Access to technical sites from inside the ring is required to avoid crossing the particle accelerator.</p>	<p>At least 2 shafts per experiment site, with preferably 3 shafts.</p> <p>1 shaft per technical site, inside the ring.</p> <p>Subject to detailed study and case-by-case analysis, 1 shaft directly above the ring, at radiofrequency sites.</p>
<p>Relocating access shafts at technical sites</p>	<p>Access shafts at technical sites can be moved along the straight sections, but they must remain well within the boundaries of these straight sections to avoid any interference with equipment and operating conditions at interfaces between straight sections and arcs.</p>	<p>For each technical site, relocation is limited to a distance of 900 m from the site's nominal point. The closer the access is to the nominal point, the better.</p> <p>Relocating of shafts towards the inside the machine is limited to 400 m for technical sites.</p>
<p>Topography</p>	<p>Ensure that surface sites can be built reliably and operated in complete safety.</p>	<p>Exclude unstable soils and slopes in excess of 30%. Avoid discontinuous terrain (more than 5 m deep or wide). Avoid zones with flooding risks.</p>
<p>Elevation</p>	<p>Give preference to scenarios with low-elevation surface sites.</p>	<p>Shaft location at elevation below 750 m. Accept relocations, within established limits, at elevations below 750 m if the nominal point is above this elevation.</p>
<p>Shaft depth</p>	<p>Give preference to scenarios with deep shafts.</p>	<p>Less than 250 m for experiment sites, with a strict limit of 400 m for technical sites.</p>

4.2.2. Voluntary objectives for creating scenarios

The multi-year study also identified voluntary objectives that would help make the project more balanced and achievable in terms of territorial acceptance. These objectives are outlined in Table 15 below. They have been taken into account in the modifications made to the scenario and in the development of a preferred layout scenario, presented in later sections of this document.

Table 15: Voluntary objectives for creating scenarios.

Subject	Objectives	Consequences for scenarios
Sustainable operation and maintenance	Ensure that the scenario can be used and maintained sustainably. To achieve this, the relevant technical centres (high-tech workshops, offices) must be in close proximity.	Give preference to scenarios that take advantage of synergies with existing CERN sites and are close to the LAPP of CNRS/IN2P3.
Protecting farmland	Reduce the need to use farmlands in both host states.	Avoid protected agricultural areas/SDA surfaces (crop rotation areas), unless they are decisive for feasibility.
Road access to surface sites	To limit the need to build new roads and to avoid wasting land, surface sites must either be located directly on existing departmental roads, or require only an improvement to existing access roads, or minimise the need to create new access roads.	Upgrading of existing roads or rural roads limited to 1 km per site. Creation of new roads limited to approx. 800 m.
Disturbances	Avoid direct disturbances for local inhabitants.	Avoid proximity to residential areas, visibility, and shared visibility. Avoid locations on roads passing through residential areas. Avoid proximity to natural and historical heritage sites. Provide means of evacuating spoil by conveyor belt, to avoid truck traffic.
Landscape integration	Work to preserve views and landscape protection zones wherever possible.	Specific studies by landscape architects are required for a preferred scenario.
Protection of water	Avoid water protection zones, rivers, and streams.	Avoid having to stabilise or modify riverbanks. Specific studies are required for a preferred scenario.
Forests	Respect protected forest zones and trees. Avoid clearing forests or felling trees in both host countries to maintain biodiversity.	Avoid high quality forest zones wherever possible. Improve climate resilience by restoring impaired forests.

Synergies	<p>Give preference to locations that can create synergies with nearby customers and public infrastructures.</p>	<p>Prioritise proximity to schools and hospitals, provided that disturbances can be avoided (distance of 300 m).</p> <p>Seek out proximity to industrial and commercial facilities, highway service areas and railroads.</p> <p>Identify the possibility of supplying residual heat within a 5 km radius.</p> <p>Develop a safety concept in cooperation with local fire departments and first-aid services.</p> <p>Discuss with local authorities whether or not they are willing to host a visitors' centre.</p>
Reduced need for electrical infrastructure	<p>To limit the effects and impacts of infrastructure development for electrical power, give preference to scenarios located near substations and power lines.</p>	<p>225 kV and 400 kV lines and substations nearby.</p>
Volume of excavated material	<p>Limit the volume of materials excavated annually and reduce road transport wherever technically and economically feasible.</p> <p>Facilitate local reuse.</p>	<p>The aim is to keep the volume of materials excavated annually to less than 10% of the volumes generated in each region (Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region, canton of Geneva).</p>
Issues with landowners	<p>Work on an efficient implementation scenario that avoids negotiations with many private landowners, which can lead to unsatisfactory compensation for these owners.</p>	<p>Give preference to public rather than private land.</p> <p>Avoid areas with known development projects.</p>
Biodiversity and nature	<p>Give preference to sites with low-quality environmental characteristics.</p>	<p>Through the ERC approach, preserve as much as possible the elements of interest in terms of biodiversity and nature within the perimeter. Study, together with design offices, the existing and projected conditions of the concerned sites, and carry out environmental, flora and fauna surveys on the proposed site to identify valuable elements and the site's role in the ecological infrastructure. Propose appropriate restoration, replacement and compensation measures based on the impacts identified with a specialist consultant. Maintain or reinforce ecological infrastructure, particularly wildlife corridors.</p>

5. DEVELOPMENT OF SCENARIOS

"I have gotten a lot of results! I know several thousand things that won't work."

(« J'ai obtenu beaucoup de résultats ! Je connais quelques milliers de choses qui ne fonctionnent pas. »)

Thomas Edison, *Edison: His Life and Inventions*, 1910.

Chapter 5 explains how the scenarios have changed over time according to the iterative Avoid-Reduce-Compensate approach. First of all, it emphasises the constant evolution of the region, and the ever-increasing constraints, which limit the opportunities for new layouts. The main characteristics of the scenario now selected as the preferred scenario, PA31-1.0, are outlined, followed by a historical overview of how the main scenario types were developed. Three scenarios with twelve sites are presented first, followed by four scenarios with eight sites, which offer a more favourable layout. Section 5.5 compares all the scenario types detailed above, and shows that this iterative approach has resulted in the selection of a balanced scenario. Finally, the micro-improvements made to the preferred PA31-1.0 scenario are described, which, through an iterative process, led to the development of versions 2.0, 3.0 and finally 4.0, the most accomplished and well-balanced scenario.

5.1. TERRITORIAL CHANGES

Illustration 57: Around one hundred different layout scenarios were studied between 2014 and 2022.

Around a hundred different configuration and location scenarios were studied between 2014 and 2022 (Illustration 57). Great care was taken in the study to analyse the balance between scientific performance, technical feasibility, and territorial compatibility, following the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) approach. Several scenarios do not meet the established geological compatibility limit. However, the work carried out to date has shown that, in all the cases considered, the scenarios that have been optimised from the point of view of territorial constraints would encounter unacceptable subsurface conditions in terms of the risks associated with underground construction. The advantages were very limited for the small number of surface sites in the best locations, and they did not outweigh the other drawbacks.

What's more, territorial constraints changed significantly between 2014 and 2022, and continue to do so⁵¹, resulting in significant losses of suitable land. As a result, the working hypothesis for a configuration with twelve sites has been completely abandoned. These changes also represent real risks concerning the possibility of maintaining the hypothesis to carry out a project. Due to the need to group three sites together to the north and three to the south, with symmetry constraints, it became impossible to find a solution compatible with geological, topographical and territorial constraints, while satisfying minimum requirements in terms of acceptable scientific performance.

These changes include, but are not limited to, the creation of around 300 ha of protection zones in the Rhone sector to the southeast of Collonges, the inclusion of new water protection zones to completely avoid any potentially negative repercussions on the territory's drinking water resources, the DDT 74 recommendation to avoid the Fillière valley with its high ecological value, and the need to protect this zone as a quiet, residential area. Cerema has drawn attention to difficulties with road access from the La Roche-sur-Foron conurbation to the Bornes plateau zone. Continued urbanization to the west and east of the Arve River and the A40 motorway between Annemasse and La Roche-sur-Foron has resulted in the gradual loss of various plots of land over the years. Zones in the canton of Geneva and the neighbouring department of Ain, in France, have also been progressively reduced, notably through various projects, such as: renaturation projects on Swiss territory in the zone between the lake and the French border; residential construction projects in the Bellevue zone reported by the Département du territoire (work started in 2020); public development projects in the Bellevue zone (sites reported in 2021); construction and nature protection projects in Ferney-Voltaire, Ornex and Prévessin-Moëns and transportation and urbanization projects launched in Saint-Genis-Pouilly. Geological investigations related to geothermal projects (such as the GEothermies program) have made it possible to better locate aquifer zones between Bellevue and Challex and to characterize significant water tables (e.g. Illustration 58 shows the superposition of the Montfleury aquifer and the Rhône aquifer). This has also reduced the potential areas for the implementation of the project.

The FCC study conducts geotechnical and geophysical investigations in areas with uncertainties to confirm the presence of water and to optimize the depth level of the tunnel in order to avoid areas with significant challenges.

⁵¹ For example, while optimizing the location of the PF site, a project for an inert waste storage facility was discovered by a service provider in La Roche-sur-Foron in December 2022:

<https://www.haute-savoie.gouv.fr/content/telechargement/40848/236838/file/AP%20ouverture%20consultation.pdf>

Date d'impression: 13.10.2023
SITG - Tous droits réservés

0 5km N

Illustration 58: Water tables and water protection zones in Geneva. Source: SITG⁵²

As a result, efforts have been focused on developing a scenario that would:

- reduce land ownership needs for surface sites;
- accept land that is less suitable from a topographical standpoint;
- accept access shaft depths of up to 300 m for experiment sites;
- accept access shaft depths of up to 400 m for sites that do not need detectors for experiments;
- accept significant displacements of non-interaction points of up to 900 m along the ring and up to 700 m inside the ring;
- ensure adequate road access to the sites, so as to keep disturbances as low as reasonably possible in the surrounding region;
- connect to the national electrical grid with as minor impact as possible on the territory;
- give preference to access to railway infrastructure;

while respecting existing territorial constraints in both host countries.

This chapter lists a certain number of scenarios that ultimately led to the currently preferred working hypothesis scenario, PA31-1.0, which is described in further detail in the following sections of this document. This table also presents the main characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages of these scenarios, which have been studied in greater detail.

⁵²https://map.sitg.ch/app/?mapresources=GEOLOGIE_MODELE_GEOL_PROFOND%2CGEOTHERMIE%2CGEOLOGIE&hidden=GEOLOGIE_MODELE_GEOL_PROFOND%2CGEOTHERMIE

5.2. BASIC WORKING HYPOTHESIS PA31-1.0

Illustration 59 summarises the multi-criteria analysis of the PA31-1.0 scenario, which is the working hypothesis proposed for the in-depth studies. This scenario, based on a collider with a circumference of 91.1 km, appears to be advantageous; it meets scientific needs, is compatible with territorial constraints and presents acceptable construction risks (the three factors are considered to weight equally in order to achieve a balanced scenario). Since four scientific sites are possible, this scenario has greater scientific potential than the scenario in the preliminary conceptual design report (PA0-0.1).

Illustration 59: Summary of the multi-criteria analysis of the PA31-1.0 scenario with eight surface sites. Proper integration with the RD 903/A40 project remains to be developed for the PD site.

5.3. RESULTS OF THE SCENARIO OPTIMIZATION PROCESS

Table 16 below describes the conditions of the current scenario (2023) compared with the initial hypotheses postulated in 2014.

Table 16: Overview of the changes in territorial requirements resulting from the optimization process.

Project element	Initial conditions between 2014 and 2018	Conditions after changes in 2024
Total number of surface sites	12	8
Sites that can reuse or profit from existing CERN sites and infrastructures	1	2 Synergy maintained with point 8 of LHC in Ferney-Voltaire Synergy with the CERN Prévessin site for the construction of the pre-injector (Linac) and an optimised transfer line using site 4 of the SPS.
Total land area used by surface sites	Year 2014 , 12-site configuration: 12 x 9 ha = 108 ha	Year 2017 , 12-site configuration: 62 ha = 18 ha (2 x 9 ha) + 12 ha (2 x 6 ha) + 32 ha (8 x 4 ha) Year 2024 , 8-site configuration: Approx. 48.9 ha = 5.2 ha (PA) + 4.5 ha (PB) + 4.9 ha (PD) + 4 ha (PF) + 10.5 ha (PG) + 8.2 ha (PH) + 6.1 ha (PJ) + 5.5 ha (PL)
Proximity of sites to major road transport infrastructures	4 out of 12 (33%)	7 out of 8 (87%)
Total length of site access roads to be built or upgraded	Approximately 3,500 m	Approximately 2 950 m: PA (0 m), PB (0 m), PD (300 m), PF (0 m), PG (750 m), PH (0 m), PJ (600 m), PL (1,300 m)
Possibility of designing railway access from site	2 out of 12 (16%)	3 to 4 out of 8 (37%)
Number of access shafts	20 (12 service accesses, 8 experiment accesses)	12 (8 service accesses, 4 experiment accesses)
Estimated total volume of material excavated per year	Around 7 million m³ in place (18.5 Mt) in 7 years of construction	Around 6 million m³ in place (16.4 Mt) in 7 years of construction
Surface area with ecological interest or affected forestland	Approximately 23 ha total 6 ha (PD), 8 ha (PG), 3 ha (PH), 6 ha (PK)	Approximately 8 ha total (including 4 ha for an ecological corridor at PA and PF sites)

Possible synergies with public infra-structures (schools, public buildings, healthcare providers)	2 out of 12 (16%) (PA, PB)	5 out of 8 (62%) (PA, PB, PD, PF, PJ)
Possible synergies with private infra-structures (farms, industries, businesses, and residential areas)	5 out of 12 (41%) (PA, PC, PG, PH, PI)	8 out of 8 (100%) (PA, PB, PD, PF, PG, PH, PJ, PL)

5.4. SUMMARIES OF SELECTED SCENARIOS

5.4.1. PB17-0.8 (twelve sites; not selected)

Illustration 60: Configuration of PB17-0.8 scenario with twelve surface sites.

The scenario shown in Illustration 60 includes twelve surface sites for a collider with a circumference of 96 km. The two straight sections at sites PD and PJ are extended by 900 m to position the PE, PF, PG, PH, PI, PJ and PK sites in locations that are theoretically feasible. The total length of the curved sections is 81.2 km, 3% less than the 83.75 km of the baseline scenario in the preliminary conceptual design report (CDR, PA0-0.1). Despite this change in configuration, the PF and PH sites have been moved 1 278 m and 700 m, respectively. Access to the PF site would be too difficult, and the elevation of 850 m would be unacceptable. The PH site would be in the middle of a village (Les Chapalliers) or would have no access, on a hillside at an elevation of 700 m to the west of Charvonnex.

From a geological point of view, the scenario remains within the limits established to avoid the karstic zones of the Jura and the risk of faults in the Vuache zone. Difficulties with the topography and the elevations remain for this scenario.

<p>PA: scientific site on an existing CERN site.</p>	<p>PB: scientific site in Bellevue, Switzerland.</p>	<p>PC: technical site in Meinier, north of Carre d'Aval in Switzerland.</p>
<p>PD: technical site in Cranves-Sales, near the D 903 (FR).</p>	<p>PE: technical site in Arenthon, near the A40 and the Arve River (FR).</p>	<p>PF: technical site moved 1200 m to La Roche-sur-Foron (FR).</p>
<p>PG: scientific site in Thorens-Glières, north of the Fillière (FR).</p>	<p>PH: technical site moved 700 m to Saint-Martin-Bellevue (FR).</p>	<p>PI: technical site in Choisy (FR).</p>

Illustration 61: Layout for surface sites of scenario PB17-0.8

Illustration 61 shows the possible location for each surface site in this scenario.

The PA scientific site is located entirely within the existing perimeter of the CERN site, enabling maximum use of existing infrastructures. The FCC-ee technical site and the FCC-hh PB scientific site are in Bellevue. The site is characterised by severe subsurface constraints due to the presence of the strategic Montfleury water table, superimposed on a shallower water table, and surface water. The situation is complex with the landowners of the various private plots, and requires an acquisition process well in advance. Only one plot, which would be used for surface construction, belongs to the État de Genève (government of Geneva). This situation, together with the environmental issues at the site (Gobé stream) and the immediate proximity of the airport and the A1 motorway interchange, would cause a number of constraints for the project.

The PC technical site in Meinier is also subject to agricultural and landscape constraints.

The PD technical site in Cranves-Sales is located right next to the D903 departmental road, on a plot of farmland. However, due to urban constraints (a hamlet) and environmental constraints (river, forest, stables), the available space is very limited.

The PE site in Arenthon is located in a vast protected agricultural area. The proximity of the Arve River represents an opportunity for the project.

The nominal point for the PF site has difficult access and too high of an elevation (850 m). Moving it 1,300 m to an elevation of 700 m on agricultural land in La Roche-sur-Foron could solve this problem. The site's proximity to a railroad line is an opportunity for the project. However, the topography, the limited size of the available field and road accessibility are still major challenges.

The main PG scientific site, located at the eastern entrance to Thorens-Glières and close to the D2 departmental road, is on a large agricultural plot within the perimeter of a listed farm (heritage building). A 100 m access road from the D2 could be considered, but this would pass through a zone with flood risks and a natural and forested area. If this option is not feasible, the only possible access would be through Thorens-Glières and the hamlet of Biot, which could cause significant disturbances to residents during the construction phase.

The PH technical site must be moved 700 m to the west to a plot of farmland between two forests, as the nominal point is located precisely in the village. Moving it to Charvonnex to the east is not possible, as the site is not accessible by road, the topography in the wooded area is not favourable, and the location is on a hill at an elevation of 700 m.

The PI technical site in Choisy and the PJ technical site in Minzier are located on farmland. The sites are fairly isolated. Apart from a 225 kV power line close to the PJ site, there are no other notable features.

The PK technical site is located on the south bank of the Rhone, in the forest in Vulbens. This site is located outside the Natura 2000 perimeter, and is subject to severe environmental constraints. A clearing near the banks of the Rhone offers an opportunity for the project if a water catchment station for cooling can be considered for this site. Despite the need to create a 1 500 m road through the forest along an existing forest road, the possible access to the railroad line to the south of the forest could be an advantage. It is not possible to move this site within a perimeter of less than 1 300 m.

The secondary PL site, north of Challex, is in an agricultural zone, south of a forest, with access possible to the 4-lane D884 departmental road. Disturbances for villagers could be avoided via this direct access to the site, which also benefits from close proximity to the CERN sites in Meyrin and Prévessin. The 400 kV line that currently supplies CERN is located nearby.

PB17-0.8	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP			RF			EXP			RF			96 km	C
FCC-hh	EXP	EXP	Cryo		Cryo	Col		RF	Cryo	Col	Cryo	EXP		
Site														
Score	96	52	44	61	63	43	42	63	58	51	54	70	79	60

Illustration 62: Results of multi-criteria analysis of scenario PB17-0.8.

This type of scenario has several advantages: high scientific value, compatibility with geological features and the possibility of developing synergies with existing CERN infrastructures. Three scientific sites are located close to existing CERN infrastructures.

It also has its drawbacks: the problems with designing a scientific site in the Fillière valley; the elevation and difficult access to the PF and PH sites; the subsurface, urban planning and environmental constraints for the PB site; and the density of urbanization in the zone for all the PD site options. The environmental constraints of the Rhone riverbanks zone (PK) also raise questions concerning the feasibility.

The multi-criteria analysis (Illustration 62) shows the theoretical feasibility of this scenario, but it also includes a multitude of territorial constraints at the limit of acceptability, which must be better understood and overcome.

5.4.2. PB19-0.3 (twelve sites; not selected)

Illustration 63: Configuration of PB19-0.3 scenario with twelve surface sites.

The scenario shown in Illustration 63 includes twelve surface sites for a collider with a circumference of 91.3 km. The two straight sections at sites PD and PJ are extended by 340 m to position the PD, PE, PF, PG, PH, PJ and PK sites in locations that are theoretically possible. The total length of the curved sections is 77.8 km, 7% less than the 83.75 km of the baseline scenario (CDR, PA0-0.1). Despite this change in configuration, the surface sites PE, PF, PH and PJ must be moved 550 m, 700 m, 530 m and 750 m, respectively.

From a geological point of view, the scenario goes well outside the established limits (Illustration 64) to avoid the karstic zones of the Jura (2 100 m between Péron and Saint-Jean-de-Gonville) and the risk of faults in the Vuache zone (1 400 m at Cortagy), with a footprint directly under the Vuache Mountain (elevation of 1 101 m). Given that the tunnel would be at an elevation of around 200 m, the overburden of roughly 1 300 m of rock over a tunnel with a length of at least 5 000 m would cause major technical and financial difficulties, calling the feasibility of the project into question. The topography, elevation and difficult access to several surface site locations represent other major challenges for this scenario.

Illustration 64: Zone covering the geological limit of acceptability (represented by a red line) and layout of scenario PB19-0.3 in yellow. Areas close to the Vuache and Jura mountains with particularly difficult aspects are indicated by a thin red line. Known faults are shown in blue (data from 2019).

<p>PA: scientific site close to a CERN SPS site and an electrical substation.</p>	<p>PB: scientific site in Bellevue (CH), see also PB17-0.8.</p>	<p>PC: technical site in Choulex (CH), to be moved 350 m to the southeast.</p>
<p>PD: technical site in Arthaz-Pont-Notre-Dame, near the A40 motorway (FR).</p>	<p>PE: technical site in Eteaux (FR), the shaft is moved 550 m.</p>	<p>PF: technical site in Fillière (FR), moved 700 m, close to the A410.</p>
<p>PG: scientific site near the A 410 in Villy-le-Pelloux (FR).</p>	<p>PH: technical site in Choisy (FR), moved 530 m.</p>	<p>PI: technical site in Contamine-Sarzin (FR).</p>

Illustration 65: Location of surface sites for scenario PB19-0.3.

Illustration 65 shows the possible location for each surface site in this scenario.

The PA scientific site is located in Prévessin, France, opposite the existing CERN SPS BA4 site, close to the RD35 and the Bois-Tollot electrical substation. This location makes it possible to benefit from synergies with existing infrastructures. The drawback of this site is that it would be separated into two parts, on either side of the departmental road.

The FCC-ee technical site and the FCC-hh PB scientific site are located in Bellevue, Switzerland. The layout is the same as in scenario PB17-0.8. The site is characterised by severe subsurface constraints due to the presence of the strategic Montfleury water table, superimposed on a shallower water table, and surface water. The situation is complex with the landowners of the various private plots, and requires an acquisition process well in advance. Only one plot, which would be used for surface construction, belongs to the État de Genève (government of Geneva). This situation, together with the environmental issues at the site (Gobé stream) and the immediate proximity of the airport and the A1 motorway interchange, would cause a number of constraints for the project.

The PC technical site in Choulex, Switzerland is located on a plot of land housing a building complex, and should be moved 350 m to the southeast on a plot of land belonging to the État de Genève (government of Geneva). The site is located between a small forest and the protected natural area of the Nant du Paradis stream. This location is also in the preferred PA31 scenario, which comprises eight sites. Moving the site outside the ring represents a technical challenge that would entail additional costs and difficulties, the scale of which is unknown at this stage.

The PD technical site, in Arthaz-Pont-Notre-Dame (locality known as “Les Crottes”), is close to the A40 motorway, about 100 m from the Arve River, and close to the Natura 2000 protected area and the Nangy motorway service area.

The nominal point for the PE site in Eteaux is located on a steep slope in a forest with no access, at an elevation of 725 m. The site would therefore have to be moved 550 m north along the footprint to an elevation of around 650 m, close to the 400 kV line connected to the Cornier substation, which is near the Élevage de la Madeleine farm. Access via a small road through hamlets and farms is still a major challenge. The 19% gradient is also a significant difficulty.

The nominal point for the PF site near the A410 motorway is close to a hamlet and a forest, in a zone of ecological and agricultural importance. A bed & breakfast (Domaine Les Trois Biches) is just a few dozen meters away. The site would therefore have to be moved 700 m to the east, and would once again be close to the A410 motorway. The site behind a farm building is classified as an inert waste storage area. It would be located at an elevation of 685 m, with temporary access for the time being via a rural road running alongside the motorway.

The main PG scientific site is located in Villy-le-Pelloux, between the A410 and the D2 departmental road, close to the sorting centre. This is an agricultural zone in a sector with landscape features of interest.

The PH technical site in Choisy, on the Crêt de Charave, is at an elevation of 750 m on a slope behind the Domaine de Charave occupied by the GAL TP construction company, in a field. Due to the unfavourable location and lack of access, the site would have to be moved at least 530 m westwards to another agricultural plot near the “Route d'Arthaz” road, at an elevation of 700 m. This location is problematic, as there is a protected zone around the Mounaz stream. Access remains difficult.

The PI technical site is located near the town of Contamine-Sarzin, in an agricultural area very close to the “Route de Musièges” road. Access is difficult, and only possible by going through the village (RD123). An advantage of this site is the 400 kV line connecting Cornier to Génissiat, which passes over the land.

The PJ technical site, to the south of Vulbens, is on developed land and will therefore have to be moved roughly 750 m, either northwards towards Vulbens, or southwards, close to the A410 motorway. The latter location would be close to the entrance to the tunnel through the Vuache mountain at an elevation of 700 m. Access would be via a rural road running alongside the motorway, which would have to be upgraded to link up with the RD7 road leading to Vulbens.

The PK technical site is located south of the RD884 departmental road in Péron, on farmland. A short move of 200 m is required to bring the site closer to the existing intersection between the RD884 and RD884a. The site is easily accessible from CERN.

The PL secondary scientific site, near the Val Thoiry shopping centre, may have direct access via the D884 and the shopping centre. The site is very close to CERN on farmland, close to a protected German zone. The 400 kV line runs nearby, to the south of this site. Obtaining this site would be difficult, as the area is already highly urbanised and frequently has traffic problems. In addition, agriculture and natural areas would need to be preserved, and the artificialisation of undeveloped areas should be avoided.

PB19-0.3	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP			RF			EXP			RF			91 km	C
FCC-hh	EXP	EXP	Cryo		Cryo	Col		RF	Cryo	Col	Cryo	EXP		
Site														
Score	86	52	69	85	43	67	79	54	68	56	77	87	48	67

Illustration 66: Results of multi-criteria analysis of scenario PB19-0.3.

This type of scenario offers several advantages. Potential locations for the PA, PL, PB and PG scientific sites are favourable and have acceptable shaft depths. The PC and PD sites are also in accessible locations that seem compatible with territorial constraints. Two sites are at acceptable locations, subject to minor adjustments (PI and PK). However, four sites (PE, PF, PH and PJ) need to be moved to increase feasibility. Access to the sites will still be difficult after they have been moved.

The scientific value is lower than in the baseline scenario and the PB17-0.8 scenario. The scientific excellence that a project such as this should offer cannot be guaranteed, as the scenario is close to the lower limit of acceptability.

Synergies with existing CERN infrastructures are possible on the PA site, but remain limited. Three scientific sites are located close to existing CERN infrastructures.

The biggest drawback of this scenario is its incompatibility with the geological situation, due to the tunnel crossing through the Vuache mountain and the presence of known faults and a limestone zone in the Jura region (Illustration 67). A quarter of the sites in the scenario are located in limestone areas and could be subject to hazards that are currently unknown.

Illustration 67: Longitudinal profile of footprint for PB19-0.3. Red lines indicate areas with hazards that make the scenario infeasible in terms of the risks and costs involved in building underground structures.

The unavailability of the PB site in Bellevue, Switzerland, where the zone was set aside for another public project, is **another obstacle for this scenario and for all scenarios of this type**. This makes any scenario involving a site in this location infeasible.

Several surface sites would have to be moved several hundred meters, with no noticeable improvement of the situation. This constraint takes precedence over the favourable location of the PA, PL and PG scientific sites.

The multi-criteria analysis (Illustration 66) shows that the territorial compatibility of this scenario is better than in scenario PB17-0.8. However, the scenario cannot be considered feasible because the project entails too many risks, and fails to strike a balance between scientific performance and territorial compatibility.

5.4.3. PA21-0.3 (eight sites; not selected)

Illustration 68: Configuration of scenario PB21-0.3 with eight surface sites.

Scenario PA21-0.3 shown in Illustration 68 includes eight surface sites for a collider with a circumference of 95.85 km. The scenario complies with the required minimum length of 1 400 m for the straight sections at the points of interaction (PA, PD, PG and PJ), but is 100 m short (2 000 m instead of 2 100 m) for the technical straight sections (PB, PF, PH and PL), which represents an initial challenge. In addition, due to the constraint concerning the long distances between access points (10.25 km) and the difficulties in developing transfer lines between the collider and the existing CERN accelerators (LHC and SPS), the scientific value of this type of scenario is considered low to medium. This assessment remains unchanged, even though the total length of the curved sections of 82 km is higher than in the PB17-0.8 scenario with twelve sites, and almost identical to the 83.75 km of the baseline scenario (CDR, PA0-0.1).

The possible surface sites are all favourable. Only the PF technical site would have to be moved 400 m because of its location in a zone to be avoided. The PH technical site can be relocated if necessary to avoid clearing forested land and to be at a lower elevation, close to a departmental road.

From a geological point of view, the scenario is incompatible due to the presence of faults in the Vuache area and the degree of risk caused by crossing through limestone zones containing karst in the Jura (see Illustration 69 and Illustration 70). The likelihood of this type of scenario being completed is therefore considered low, given the risks involved in carrying out the project (risks for workers, risks associated with the stability of the tunnel and caverns, costs, and lead times).

Illustration 69: Scenarios such as PA21-0.3 require long passages through the Vuache and Jura limestone formations, which seriously compromise feasibility.

Illustration 70: View of difficulties caused by the footprint's proximity to the Vuache zone (PJ, to the west) and to the Jura (zone between the Rhone, the PL site and the PA site).

<p>PA: scientific site on existing CERN land (Prévessin).</p>	<p>PB: technical site in La Pallanterie (CH).</p>	<p>PD: scientific site in Bonne, near the D903 (FR).</p>
<p>PF: technical site moved 400 m to Eteaux (FR).</p>	<p>PG: scientific site in Groisy, south of the A 410 (FR).</p>	<p>PH: technical site at Marlioz (FR).</p>
	<p>--</p>	
<p>PJ: scientific site in Dingy-en-Vuache (FR).</p>	<p>PL: technical site in Péron (FR).</p>	<p>--</p>

Illustration 71: Location of surface sites for scenario PB21-0.3.

Illustration 71 shows the possible location for each surface site in this scenario.

The PA scientific site is located entirely on CERN land (Prévessin) in France, and therefore makes maximum use of existing infrastructures.

The PB technical site for FCC-ee is located in La Pallanterie, an industrial and urbanised zone in Switzerland. There could be a conflict with a road tunnel and/or bridge project for Lake Geneva ("Traversée du lac"), but there are currently no certainties.

A PD scientific site (Bonne) is located alongside the D903 departmental road on farmland and on a site used for gravel extraction on the banks of the Menoge. The location offers potential synergies with a commercial zone to the east of the main road.

The nominal point for the PF site is located in an urbanised, developed area near the A410 motorway. It therefore needs to be moved. Several options are possible, either 150 m to the north, 70 m to the west (on the left side of the motorway), or 400 m to the south, which would avoid disturbance of local residents. There are several possibilities for creating synergies with Eteaux. The presence of the "Cornier" electrical substation 1 800 m to the north and the railway line 1 000 m away are advantages.

The main PG scientific site is just south of the A410 motorway, 350 m east of the Groisy motorway service area. There is access to the D2 departmental road to the east, serving the motorway service area. Many types of synergies are possible with the commercial and artisan zone 650 m to the east. The Groisy railway stop is nearby, but requires crossing the A410.

The PH technical site is located in a mixed agricultural and forestry zone in Marlioz. An access road needs to be created for the site. Moving the site 550 m to the west, to Cercier, would place it in a field close to the departmental road, at an elevation of less than 50 m.

The PJ scientific site is in Dingy-en-Vuache, north of the A40 motorway and south of the municipality of Vulbens. The site is located on farmland with a gradient of around 15%, sloping down towards Vulbens. The site is isolated and has a protective boundary to the north for a drinking water zone, which cannot be built on. There is access from the D7 departmental road.

The PL technical site is located in Péron in a field. A hamlet lies 100 m to the east, and the hamlet of Greny must be crossed to reach the D884 4-lane road to the south. The proximity of the 400 kV power line that currently supplies CERN, between Bois-Tollot and Génissiat, is an advantage.

PA21-0.3	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP						EXP						96 km	B
FCC-hh	EXP			EXP			EXP			EXP				
Site														
Score	92	85		92		79	77	82		52		80	54	77

Illustration 72: Results of multi-criteria analysis of scenario PA21-0.3.

The advantage of this type of scenario is its high level of territorial compatibility compared with other types of scenarios, and the possibility of benefiting from synergies with the existing CERN infrastructure in Prévessin.

However, this type of scenario must be ruled out because of the geological difficulties in the Vuache and Jura zones (faults, karst, limestone). Its scientific value also remains limited, even though the configuration with eight surface sites is more advantageous than the one with twelve, and the collider circumference is close to that of the baseline scenario. The project has its limitations: the length of the technical straight sections and the difficulties planning and building connections with the existing LHC and SPS accelerators of CERN. However, it is conceivable that these difficulties can be managed through optimization of the configuration and technical approaches.

The multi-criteria analysis (Illustration 72) shows the low feasibility of this scenario, even if the layout of the above-ground sites seems favourable.

5.4.4. PA38-0.1 (twelve sites; not selected)

Illustration 73: Configuration of PA38-0.1 scenario with twelve surface sites.

The scenario shown in Illustration 73 includes twelve surface sites for a collider with a circumference of 90 km. This scenario is based on scenario PB17 but with a smaller collider circumference in order to find ways to improve the location of surface sites and, above all, to find a location for the PK site outside the Rhone Natura 2000 zone. The length of straight sections at the PD and PJ sites is the same as in the baseline version CDR-PA0-0.1. The PA scientific site (CERN, Meyrin, Switzerland) and the PB technical site (Bellevue, Switzerland) are the same as in version PB17-0.8.

The total length of the curved sections is only 76 km, 9% less than the 83.75 km of the baseline scenario. Despite efforts to find solutions for surface sites, three sites require an access tunnel from outside the ring. This is a technical complication for which the impact has not yet been quantified, but which is undoubtedly significant (one of the access tunnels will be 500 m long).

The scenario is favourable from a geological point of view, but the PF shaft is in the same location as in scenario PA31 and is very deep (370 m). What's more, the shaft at the main scientific site is 400 m deep, which poses an even greater challenge. This is at the limit of technological acceptability. The need for two shafts at a scientific site entails very high costs.

This scenario was ultimately rejected because of its low scientific performance and the poor territorial compatibility of the PC site (technical site) and PG site (main scientific site) on the surface, in addition to difficult site access and technical complications.

<p>PA: scientific site on an existing CERN site, see also PB17-0.8.</p>	<p>PB: scientific site in Bellevue (CH), see also PB17-0.8.</p>	<p>PC: technical site in Meinier (CH), with a 360 m access tunnel.</p>
<p>PD: technical site in Cranves-Sales (FR), with a 500 m access tunnel.</p>	<p>PE: technical site in Scientrier (FR), with a 100 m access tunnel.</p>	<p>PF: technical site in Eteaux (FR), see also PA31-1.0.</p>
<p>PG: scientific site in Fillière (FR).</p>	<p>PH: technical site in Villy-le-Pelloux (FR).</p>	<p>PI: technical site in Cercier (FR).</p>

Illustration 74 : Layout for surface sites of scenario PA38-0.1

Illustration 74 shows the possible location for each surface site in this scenario.

The PA scientific site and the PB technical site are similar to those in the PB17 scenario. The PA site is located entirely within the existing perimeter of the CERN site, enabling maximum use of existing infrastructures. The technical site for the FCC-ee and the PB scientific site for the FCC-hh are in Bellevue. The site is characterised by severe subsurface constraints due to the presence of the strategic Montfleury water table, superimposed on a shallower water table, and surface water. The situation is complex with the landowners of the various private plots and requires an acquisition process well in advance. Only one plot, which would be used for surface construction, belongs to the État de Genève (government of Geneva). This situation, together with the environmental issues at the site (Gobé stream) and the immediate proximity of the airport and the A1 motorway interchange, would cause a number of constraints for the project.

The PC technical site in Meinier, in the Carre d'Aval sector, is located on the site of the La Touvière organic farm. This site, surrounded by exclusion zones, has to be moved at least 360 m outside the ring, which creates technical complications. Even if the surface site is moved, it will still be located in a wetland area with major ecological, agricultural and landscape constraints.

The PD technical site is in the middle of Cranves-Sales and has to be moved at least 500 m outside the ring, creating technical complications. A 500 m long underground connection will entail significant costs. The moved site would be close to the D903, which offers a number of advantages in terms of access. What's more, the area already appears to be earmarked for urban development or other public interest projects (PLU zones UH and UE).

The PE technical site in Scientrier is too close to residential areas and requires an underground tunnel approximately 100 m long to provide access to a site opposite the existing road, north of the A410 motorway, in an agricultural zone.

The PF technical site is in the same location as in scenario PA31, in the immediate vicinity of the RD1203. The site includes two wetlands, which are to be avoided. A location further to the west is therefore necessary.

The main PG scientific site is located in Fillière, at an elevation of 767 m. This elevation, combined with difficult access to the RD1203 (the small "Route des Régalets" road) and the immediate proximity of residential areas (Le Régalet), makes this location practically infeasible. Extensive farming facilities seem to be present in the surrounding area.

The PH technical site is located in Villy-le-Pelloux, near the RD2 departmental road and the A41 motorway toll booth. The site's proximity to residential areas and a hotel could cause disturbances. The site is also located in zone of significant interest for its landscapes.

The PI site is located in Cercier, at the end of the Falpot rural road, where there is a livestock shed and grasslands.

The PJ site in Savigny lies to the north of the hamlet of Nyoux, on the Chemin du Moulin rural road. There is a house at the end of the road. The site would therefore need to be well integrated into its surrounding environment. The hamlet would suffer from disturbances if a new access road were not built for the site, as the site would be almost as large as the hamlet itself.

The PK technical site, moved 350 m outside the Natura 2000 area, is on the south bank of the Rhone, in a clearing in the Vulbens forest. An access road leading to Vulbens would need to be created, close to a private property (chemin de Moisse). This would most likely create disturbances.

The PL secondary scientific site is in the same location as in scenario PB17, to the north of Challex. It lies in an agricultural zone, to the south of a forest, close to possible access to the 4-lane RD884 departmental road. Direct access to the site would prevent disturbances for village residents, and also benefit from the nearby CERN sites in Meyrin and Prévessin. The 400 kV line that currently supplies CERN is located nearby.

The advantages of this type of scenario are the favourable locations of the PA, PL, PB and PG scientific sites, and better compatibility with geological constraints (Illustration 75) than the baseline PA0-0.1 version and the PB17-0.8 scenario. The difficulties caused by the location of the PK site in the Rhone sector and the PF site on the Bornes plateau are also minimal. Opportunities for synergy with existing CERN infrastructures are of great value to the PA site. Three scientific sites are located close to existing CERN infrastructures.

However, the PG scientific site is at a depth of over 400 m, in a mountainous location with difficult access, and entails the risk of creating major disturbances. This is a major difficulty in the scenario. Several other sites are also subject to severe environmental and urban planning constraints, including the PC technical site in Switzerland, the PD technical site in Cranves-Sales in France, the PH site in Villy-le-Pelloux in France, the PJ technical site in Savigny in France, and the PK site in Vulbens in France. The PF technical site in Eteaux should be optimised to avoid the two nearby wetlands. A solution seems possible.

The scientific value is the lowest of all the scenarios presented as examples in this report, as the total length of the curved sections of the accelerator is only 76 km, **the lowest limit of acceptability**.

Illustration 75: The longitudinal profile of PA38-0.1 is further away from the Jura and Vuache mountains than scenario PB17-0.8. It is comparable to the PB31 scenario.

The location of the PB site in Bellevue, Switzerland, is problematic because another public project could be launched. It is **currently a blocking point for this and other scenarios**. Any scenario including a site at this location is therefore infeasible. Placing the PC site in Meinier, in a vast wetland area around the lake of Rouelbeau with strictly protected natural areas, also seems unrealistic. A similar situation exists at the PK site on the banks of the Rhône.

The multi-criteria analysis (Illustration 76) indicates that the scientific value of this scenario is lower than that of scenario PB17-08. Territorial compatibility and the value of the implementation remain unchanged, despite efforts to improve them. This is due to the fact that any improvements to the footprint entail additional costs and complications for the construction of surface sites. The location of the main PG scientific site brings lowers the score, despite some improvements to the site locations. As a result, this less balanced scenario was not taken into consideration.

PB38-0.1	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP			RF			EXP			RF			90 km	C
FCC-hh	EXP	EXP	Cryo		Cryo	Col		RF	Cryo	Col	Cryo	EXP		
Site														
Score	96	49	40	61	63	77	34	61	61	41	34	70	72	59

Illustration 76 : Results of multi-criteria analysis of scenario PA38-0.1.

5.4.5. PA33-0.13 (eight sites; not selected)

Illustration 77 : Configuration of scenario PA33-0.13 with eight surface sites.

Scenario PA33-0.13 shown in Illustration 77 includes eight surface sites for a collider with a circumference of 93.377 km. It complies with the required minimum length of 1 400 m for the straight sections at the points of interaction (PA, PD, PG and PJ) and of 2 100 m for the technical straight sections (PB, PF, PH and PL).

With a total length of curved sections of 79.377 km, compared with 81.193 km in the PB17-0.8 scenario (2.2% shorter), the two scenarios are virtually comparable in terms of scientific performance. However, transfer lines between the collider and the existing CERN accelerators (LHC and SPS) are more difficult to build for a scenario with eight surface sites, and the access points are far apart (9.9 km).

Potential surface sites are almost all in locations with severe constraints, many of which are highly unlikely to be feasible. This is the case for five of the eight sites (almost two-thirds): the scientific site PA in Prévessin (France), the PB technical site in Meinier (Switzerland), the PD scientific site in Fillinges (France), the PF technical site in La Roche-sur-Foron (France) and the PG scientific site in Fillière (France).

From a geological point of view, this scenario is less compatible than PB17-08, as it is closer to the Vuache mountain (Illustration 78).

This scenario is considered infeasible, mainly because of its low territorial compatibility.

Illustration 78: View of the geological situation for scenario PA33-0.13. The red polygon indicates the limits of a scenario's acceptability from a geological point of view.

<p>PA: scientific site in Prévessin (France).</p>	<p>PB: technical site in Meinier (CH).</p>	<p>PD: scientific site in Fillinges (FR).</p>
<p>PF: technical site in La Roche-sur-Foron (FR).</p>	<p>PG: scientific site in Fillière (FR).</p>	<p>PH: technical site in Cercier (FR).</p>
		<p>--</p>
<p>PJ: scientific site in Dingy-en-Vuache (FR).</p>	<p>PL: technical site in Challex (FR).</p>	

Illustration 79 : Location of surface sites for scenario PA33-0.13.

Illustration 79 shows the possible location for each surface site in this scenario.

The PA scientific site is located in Prévessin, on the outskirts of the municipality of Ferney-Voltaire. The site would be located entirely in an urbanised area. New urban development projects are now planned for the two plots of land to the west and southeast. From 2014 to 2018, this location could still be considered feasible. Currently, this location seems unrealistic, given the number of projects underway, the lack of any realistic prospect of creating access, and the presence of future housing and a healthcare centre.

The PB technical site in Meinier, Switzerland, is located in a vast protected natural area. These are wetlands close to the Sionnet marsh (Les Prés Pourris), owned by the État de Genève (government of Geneva). Despite this administrative advantage, the zone to be avoided is considered to be infeasible due to direct and nearby constraints.

The PD scientific site in Fillinges, close to the RD9 and RD903, benefits from good road links. However, it is located in the middle of an urbanised area. Currently, the site is located on a protected plot of farmland, next to a plot of land indicated as "For urban development". The field is surrounded by residences and will result in shared visibility, and therefore would appear to be a difficult location to use.

The PF technical site to the south of La Roche-sur-Foron, close to the RD2, is located in an agricultural area near a large farm shed. Access would only be available through the hamlets to the south of the town, and would cause disturbances. The impact on the farm appears to be significant. There is a sharp contrast with the identity of the site.

The PG scientific site in Fillière is located close to the RD74, which is actually a small mountain road, making access very difficult. The site is located in an area of high ecological value, close to single-family homes and a forest with high ecological value. The topography and elevation (640 m) are highly unfavourable for this site. There is a sharp contrast with the identity of the site. The site is very remote and would be difficult to develop.

The location of the PH site is the same as the PI site in scenario PA38-0.1. It is in Cercier, at the end of the "Chemin de Falpot" rural road, where there is a livestock shed and grasslands.

The PJ scientific site is located in Dingy-en-Vuache, south of the A40 motorway, 500 m east of the principal town. This is an agricultural zone characterised by the presence of ecological corridors.

The PL technical site in Challex is included in several other scenarios, such as PB17, and in the preferred working hypothesis PA31. It lies to the north of Challex in an agricultural zone, to the south of a forest, close to a possible access point to the 4-lane RD884 departmental road. The disturbances to village residents could be avoided thanks to direct access to the site, which would also benefit from the nearby CERN sites in Meyrin and Prévessin. The 400 kV line that currently supplies CERN is located nearby.

The advantage of this scenario is its good scientific performance, comparable to that of the CDR and PB17-0.8 scenarios, but with a configuration of eight surface sites. The scenario remains compatible with known geological constraints. However, it does have some weaknesses in terms of territorial compatibility, as most of the surface site locations are on land subject to natural and town-planning constraints, and some of the plots of land are quite small. Some of the plots initially considered have been allocated to other projects. This scenario also offers very few opportunities to develop synergies with existing infrastructures and the surrounding region.

The multi-criteria analysis (Illustration 80) therefore shows that such a scenario is considered infeasible, even if the scientific performance is good and compatibility with geological conditions likely.

PA33-0.13	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP						EXP						93 km	D
FCC-hh	EXP			EXP			EXP			EXP				
Site														
Score	70	40		45		41	30	57		50		70	83	54

Illustration 80 : Results of multi-criteria analysis of scenario PA33-0.13.

5.4.6. PA35-0.6 (eight sites; not selected)

Illustration 81: Configuration of scenario PA35-0.6 with eight surface sites.

Scenario PA35-0.6, shown in Illustration 81, includes eight surface sites for a collider with a circumference of 92.637 km. It complies with the required minimum length of 1 400 m for the straight sections at the points of interaction (PA, PD, PG and PJ), and with the requirements for the technical straight sections (PB, PF, PH and PL).

With a total length of curved sections of 78.637 km (3% less than in the PB17-08 scenario with 81.2 km, and 6% less than in the baseline scenario CDR/PA-0.01 with 83.75 km), the scientific value of this type of scenario can be considered satisfactory. Transfer lines between the collider and the existing CERN accelerators (LHC and SPS) seem feasible, although their design would be more difficult than in scenarios involving twelve surface sites.

From a geological point of view (Illustration 82 and 83), the scenario itself with no adaptations is difficult to reconcile with the presence of faults in the Vuache zone and karstic formations in the Jura sector, which still represent risks at this stage.

Illustration 82: All scenarios similar to PA35-0.6 have to pass through the Vuache limestone rock and an area with unknown constraints in the Jura sector. This is considered a risk to the feasibility.

Illustration 83: View of difficulties caused by the PA35-0.6 footprint's proximity to the Vuache zone (between the PH site and the PJ site to the west) and to the Jura (zone between the Rhone, the PL site and the PA site).

Three potential surface sites are quite favourable (PC, PH and PJ), but five others (PA, PD, PF, PG and PL) pose difficulties. The PA scientific site is located in Prévessin, on a site surrounded by urbanised or soon-to-be urbanised areas in Ferney-Voltaire, with no access, and the PD scientific site conflicts with the RD903 development project because the footprint is too close to the road. Moving the ring to the west to resolve these problems would make the project incompatible with the geological constraints already found in this scenario, and would create an incompatibility with the topography at the PG site in Charvonnex. The PF technical site in La Roche-sur-Foron has to be moved due to the presence of housing and the high elevation. This appears to be feasible with a 600-700 m long underground connection, although the technical challenges (depth of 400 m) and additional costs would be considerable. The PG scientific site in Charvonnex is located in an area that is difficult to develop, and is close to a deep and wide ravine in the forest, on a sloping rural road. It is not considered to be infeasible, but it remains a challenge. The PL site, which is in a field, is theoretically feasible. However, it is surrounded by strict protection zones (Ramsar zones, vineyard protection, water protection area, zone with significant landscape and historical value, no access). No realistic solution could be found, as the environmental constraints in both areas are too severe to be acceptable.

The probability of this type of scenario being used is therefore considered to be very low, mainly for the following two reasons: the uncertainty of the risks involved in carrying out the project (passing through karstic formation zones) and the lack of solutions for the PA and PD scientific sites and the PL technical site.

<p>PA: scientific site in Prevesin (FR).</p>	<p>PB: technical site in Meinier (CH).</p>	<p>PD: scientific site in Nangy (FR), in conflict with RD903.</p>
<p>PF: technical site in Eteaux (FR), moved north.</p>	<p>PG: scientific site in Charvonnex (FR).</p>	<p>PH: technical site in Marlioz (FR).</p>
		<p>--</p>
<p>PJ: scientific site in Dingy-en-Vuache (FR).</p>	<p>PL: technical site in Dardagny (CH).</p>	

Illustration 84 : Location of surface sites for scenario PA35-0.6.

Illustration 84 shows the possible location for each surface site in this scenario.

The PA scientific site is located in Prévessin, on the outskirts of the municipality of Ferney-Voltaire, as in scenario PA33-0.13. The entire site would be located in an urbanised zone. New urban development projects are now planned for the two plots of land to the west and southeast. From 2014 to 2018, this location could still be considered possible. Currently, this option seems unrealistic, given the number of projects underway, the lack of any realistic prospect of creating access, and the presence of future housing and a healthcare centre.

The PB technical site in Meinier, Switzerland, is located in a vast protected natural area. These are wetlands south of the Sionnet marsh along the bank of the Seymaz. The site could be moved to an adjacent field, but proximity constraints would remain, making this difficult.

The PD scientific site in Nangy is located beside the D903 departmental road, on a plot of farmland. The location would offer a great deal of synergy with a commercial zone to the east of the departmental road, and with the Alpes-Léman hospital complex (CHAL). Unfortunately, the footprint is very close to the departmental road, and a development project approved in 2022 makes this location infeasible. A westward shift of the ring is only possible by decreasing the total circumference of the collider, which leads to the currently preferred working hypothesis PA31.

The PF technical site is in the same location as in scenario PA31, very close to the RN203. The site is characterised by the presence of two wetlands that should be avoided. A location further to the west is therefore necessary. An underground tunnel 600-700 m long would be needed to connect a shaft, which would be 400 m deep, to the accelerator tunnel. A location closer to the footprint no longer seems possible, as a site further south was earmarked for an inert waste disposal facility (ISDI) at the end of 2022.

The PG scientific site is located to the north of Charvonnex on a plateau to the south of a classified wooded area. At first glance, the location seems possible, but the difficult topography and the presence of a deep, wide trench nearby to the west presents a challenge. The site would cut across the existing rural road linking Charvonnex to the forest and the motorway service area to the north.

The PH technical site is located in a mixed agricultural and forestry zone in Marlioz, close to a hamlet. A specific access route through the hamlet would have to be created, without which the site would have to be moved several hundred meters.

The PJ scientific site straddles the municipalities of Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens, to the north of the A40 motorway and south of the municipality of Vulbens. The site is on farmland in a landscape preservation zone. An access road avoiding the hamlets on the edge of the municipality should be created in the direction of Vulbens.

The PL technical site is in Dardagny, on farmland that is theoretically usable but undesirable, with crop rotation areas. This is the only location without protection zones, as the field is operated on the French-Swiss border, with access from France. This point already constitutes an administrative difficulty. In addition, on the Swiss side, it is necessary to maintain a certain distance between developments and protected areas, as is the case for the Ramsar site in the adjacent forest. The site is surrounded by vineyard protection zones in Switzerland and France, with no possibility of land being reassigned. There is no direct access to the site. Any use of this small plot of unprotected land seems unrealistic, as it is surrounded by a water protection zone, nature protection zones, and an ecological corridor with high-value historical heritage and landscapes.

PA35-0.6	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP						EXP						93 km	C
FCC-hh	EXP			EXP			EXP			EXP				
Site														
Score	70	46		58		77	55	46		55		27	80	57

Illustration 85: Results of multi-criteria analysis of scenario PA35-0.6.

The advantage of this type of scenario is that the footprint of the collider makes good use of the space determined based on geological constraints, and has eight surface sites. This scenario includes optimizations to improve the territorial compatibility of this configuration, which ultimately led to the preferred working hypothesis PA31-1.0.

This type of scenario should be ruled out for the following reasons: the severe constraints on the only possible site in Dardagny; the location of a site in Préveessin that is "landlocked" in the municipality of Ferney-Voltaire; the incompatibility with the RD903 development project in Nangy; the difficult access and development needs for the site in Marlioz; and the difficulties creating the site in Charvonnex.

The multi-criteria analysis (Illustration 85) shows the low feasibility of this scenario, even though the overall value of the multi-criteria analysis is slightly above the acceptance limit.

5.4.7. PA37-0.3 (eight sites; not selected)

Illustration 86: Configuration of scenario PA37-0.3 with eight surface sites (different approach).

The PA37 scenario type was developed to evaluate an alternative approach to the layout by rotating the entire ring 45 degrees. In this scenario, the scientific sites are located where the technical sites are found in the other scenarios. The PA37-0.3 scenario shown in Illustration 86 is an example of this approach. It includes eight surface sites and a collider circumference of 94.823 km. It complies with the required minimum length of 1 400 m for the straight sections at the points of interaction (PA, PD, PG and PJ), and of 2 100 m for the technical straight sections (PB, PF, PH and PL).

With a total length of curved sections of 80.823 km (comparable to the PB17-08 scenario with 81.2 km and only 3% less than in the baseline scenario CDR/PA-0.01 with 83.75 km), the scientific value of this type of scenario can be considered to be excellent. However, this value is greatly reduced by technical difficulties. The design and construction of transfer lines between the collider and the existing CERN accelerators (LHC and SPS) continue to pose problems, with long lines likely to be required. Injecting the beam lines at the PA and PD scientific sites would appear to be impractical.

With regard to geological conditions (Illustration 87 and Illustration 88), the scenario is slightly incompatible due to the potential presence of karstic and limestone formations in the Jura sector.

Illustration 87: Scenario PA37-0.3 remains compatible with the Vuache zone, but has some uncertainties in the Jura zone.

Illustration 88: Geological difficulties due to the close proximity of the PA37-0.3 footprint to the Jura zone.

Regarding the location of surface sites, the aim of this approach was to check whether the 45-degree rotation of the ring could bring about improvements in site location that would justify accepting additional technical difficulties. This is not the case. The PA, PD, PG and PJ scientific sites no longer create synergy with existing CERN infrastructures or other known infrastructures, and the technical sites still need to be adapted based on the existing constraints and possibilities. For the PJ site, the topography is particularly unfavourable and entails the construction of two shafts, each one over 411 m deep. The PH technical site in the Fillière valley, near the RD2 in the direction of Thorens-Glières, poses a particular challenge.

Ultimately, the arguments in favour of this type of scenario were not sufficient to continue studying them, as the scenario is of mediocre value in terms of the project's three pillars: scientific excellence, territorial compatibility and the risks associated with project implementation.

Illustration 89 : Location of surface sites for scenario PA37-0.3.

Illustration 89 shows the possible location for each surface site in this scenario.

The PA scientific site is located to the west of Challex, in an agricultural zone close to the forest. The location becomes advantageous with a connection to the “Route de Pougny” road, and disturbances for local residents can be largely avoided. The site is close to CERN, the 400 kV power line and the RD884, a major road link.

The PB technical site is located in a strictly protected area in Meyrin, Switzerland (Terrain Jakob⁵³) and is not accessible. Moving the site 300 m to the east at Prévessin, near the RD35, enables us to generate many different synergies, such as the use of infrastructure, the presence of the CERN SPS BA4 site and the connection to the 400 kV line of the Bois-Tollet electrical substation.

The PD scientific site is located on farmland in La Pallanterie, in Collonge-Bellerive, and is owned by the État de Genève (government of Geneva). The constraints do not appear to be significant, apart from the need to ensure proper integration in an urbanised setting and to respect neighbours. Numerous synergies would be possible, such as supplying heat to a botanical centre and to the many offices located in the vicinity.

The PF technical site in Bonne is located in a zone that cannot be considered because it is a densely urbanised residential area, and its relocation would have serious consequences for an equestrian estate. The site could be moved to a location between the Menoge river and the RD903 road. However, an underground access tunnel 650 m to 700 m long would be required, representing a major challenge.

The PG scientific site is located to the north of La Roche-sur-Foron, in Amancy, in a mixed industrial and commercial area with single-family housing. This location benefits from a good connection to the RD1203 and good landscape integration, and seems feasible. It could even lead to synergies with the municipality and its developments.

The PH technical site is located in the Fillière valley, close to the RD2, at the entrance to Thorens-Glières. There is not enough space for a technical site, and it does not appear possible to move the site due to the presence of steep slopes to the north, the river and forest to the south, and a hamlet and single-family homes along the RD2. If the site were to be built, there would be a strong contrast with the landscape. There is currently no obvious solution for the acceptability of a technical site in this area.

The PJ scientific site is located in Choisy, a small village at an elevation of 710 m. The two shafts on this site would have a depth of 411 m each. This represents a major challenge. What's more, the site would be larger than the hamlet it runs alongside and would contrast sharply with its surrounding environment.

A similar situation exists for the PL technical site in Savigny. The site would be larger than the municipality, and the buildings opposite the church and town hall would be too imposing. Moving the site 240 m to the north would be possible, thereby avoiding disturbances by means of a separate connection to the main road. However, the entire agricultural and forestry zone, which includes fruit trees, is classified as an "agricultural zone with a role in the identity of the municipality". As a result, it currently seems unlikely that stakeholders and local players would accept the establishment of such a site in this area.

⁵³ https://www.meyrin.ch/sites/default/files/inline-files/Histoire%20du%20Terrain%20Jakob_2009.pdf

PA37-0.3	PA	PB	PC	PD	PE	PF	PG	PH	PI	PJ	PK	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP						EXP						95 km	D
FCC-hh	EXP			EXP			EXP			EXP				
Site														
Score	75	81		74		57	65	19		37		27	57	54

Illustration 90: Results of multi-criteria analysis of scenario PA37-0.3.

The advantage of this type of scenario is the favourable location of the PA and PD scientific sites and the PB technical site. The PG scientific site would still be in an urbanised zone of La Roche-sur-Foron and would be feasible under certain conditions.

However, the locations of the PF, PH and PL technical sites are still problematic, and having the PJ scientific site in a very isolated area would create difficulties. It should be noted that there is currently no solution for a PH technical site in the Filière valley, and it cannot be moved due to the topography.

Finally, it would appear that it will not be possible to connect the collider to the existing CERN accelerator complex. Numerous technical complications also affect the potential cost of civil engineering structures and make operations more complex.

The multi-criteria analysis (Illustration 90) shows that such a scenario is considered to be quite infeasible. One site is infeasible, and several technical challenges remain unresolved: the two 411 m-deep shafts at the PJ scientific site, the connection to the CERN accelerators and the length of the underground link for the PF site.

5.5. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SCENARIOS

Around a hundred different scenarios have been developed and analysed as part of the FCC study since 2015. This section examines a sample of these scenarios, presents the studies that were carried out, and presents their results in a clear, concise manner. These scenarios can be found in Table 17.

The PA0-0.1 scenario, known as the CDR (*Conceptual Design Report*), developed to demonstrate the technical feasibility of the FCC in the first phase of the study (2014-2018), is the benchmark for the performance of the other scenarios.

The table shows a variety of scenarios: with a configuration based on eight or twelve surface sites, and different collider circumferences.

Note that a circular collider is made up of curved and straight sections. The straight section on either side of an interaction point must be at least 700 m long to focus the beam lines before they cross. Each straight section housing technical equipment must be longer than 2,000 m to accelerate, modulate, inject, and extract beam lines. The total length of the curved sections is essential for attaining the electron-positron collider luminosity (FCC-ee) and proton collision energies (FCC-hh) required to accomplish the scientific research program: a length of at least 90 km is considered the strict acceptable limit, compatible with the defined research program.

The twelve-site configuration has four interaction points for the FCC-hh, with three scientific experiment sites in close proximity and one on an opposite side. This configuration has only two interaction points for a lepton collider (FCC-ee). The configuration with eight sites also has four interaction points for FCC-ee, and could achieve, or even exceed, the originally foreseen scientific performance levels. However, the four sites will be far apart from each other, and the creation of four experiments for the lepton collider depends on available funding, and will only be possible if its relevance to the research program is demonstrated.

Table 17: A sample of the scenarios presented in this report, with their key characteristics.

Scenario	Sites	Arc length [km]	Total circumference [km]	Energy c.m. (FCC-hh) [TeV] ¹⁾	Luminosity ²⁾ (FCC-ee) in % of CDR scenario with 2 i.p.	Luminosity ³⁾ (FCC-ee) in % of CDR scenario with 4 i.p.	Feasibility risks ⁴⁾
1 PA0-0.1 (CDR)	12	83.750	97.750	101 (100%)	100%	Not feasible	Territory, geology
2 PB17-0.8	12	81.193	96.093	99 (98%)	96.9%	Not feasible	Territory
3 PB19-0.3	12	77.784	91.324	95 (94%)	92.9%	Not feasible	Geology
4 PA21-0.3	8	82.045	95.845	100 (99%)	98.0%	196%	Geology
5 PA38-0.1	12	75.228	89.228	92 (91%)	89.8%	179 %	Territory, performance
6 PA33-0.13	8	79.77	93.377	97 (96%)	94.8%	189.6%	Territory
7 PA35-0.6	8	78.637	92.637	96 (95%)	93.9%	187.8%	Territory, geology
8 PA37-0.3	8	80.823	94.823	99 (98%)	96.5%	193.0%	Territory, geology
9 PA31-1.0	8	76.932	91.172	94 (93%)	91.9%	183.8%	No blocking points
10 PA31-3.0	8	76.929	90.658	94 (93%)	91.9%	183.8%	No blocking points
11 PA31-4.0	8	76.929	90.658	94 (93%)	91.9%	183.8%	No blocking points

¹⁾Centre-of-mass (c.m.) energy of the FCC-hh at each interaction point (i.p.) for proton interactions, using bending magnets with 16 tesla fields and a filling factor of 80% of the magnets contained in an arc. In brackets, the performance (in %) of the most powerful reference scenario, PA0-0.1 (CDR).

²⁾ Loss of luminosity at each interaction point (i.p.) compared with reference scenario PA0-0.1 (CDR).

³⁾ Luminosity loss or gain with four interaction points (i.p.) instead of the two interaction points of the reference scenario PA0-0.1 (CDR). A configuration based on twelve sites does not allow for four interaction points. Its value to the scientific program is therefore generally lower than that of scenarios based on an eight-site configuration, which offer the possibility of having four interaction points, subject to funding and respect for socio-economic sustainability.

⁴⁾ The elements with the greatest impact, and which most likely make the scenario infeasible.

The various scenarios were analysed in detail using the multi-criteria methodology. The results of the ranking according to the three pillars, (T) territorial compatibility, (I) ease of implementation and (S) scientific performance, are presented in the table below. The score for each criterion (T, I, S) and the summary of scores do not make it possible to establish the probability of feasibility because in the multi-criteria analysis, the scores obtained for the different criteria are simply added together and averages are calculated. Low scores on some criteria (which rule out feasibility) are therefore offset by higher scores on others. This approach therefore only allows us to see whether the three pillars are represented in a balanced way. For two of the scenarios (PB19-0.3 and PA21-0.3), the incompatibility with geological conditions is so significant that a detailed analysis is not necessary to establish their infeasibility. The scientific value is not only calculated on the basis of the circumference, but also considers the connection to CERN's existing infrastructure and accelerators, and the difficulty of designing, building, installing and operating the technical systems. This explains, for example, why scenario PA38-0.1 (a version of PB17-0.8 with a smaller collider circumference) has a lower scientific value than the PB17-08 scenario but is above the acceptance threshold, even though the arc lengths are considered far too short. However, the PA38-0.1 scenario has not been retained. This shows that the multi-criteria approach remains incomplete and is only an aid for analysis. A detailed analysis is still essential to assess the acceptability and feasibility of each scenario.

Table 18: Summary of multi-criteria analysis.

#	Scenario	Number of sites	Arc length [km]	Total circumference [km]	Results of multi-criteria analysis							
					T ¹⁾	I ²⁾	S ³⁾	T ¹⁾	I ²⁾	S ³⁾	Summary ⁴⁾	VIKOR ⁵⁾
1	PA0-0.1	12	83.750	97.750	53	75	83	D	B	B	D	7
2	PB17-0.8	12	81.193	96.093	58	81	79	C	B	B	C	4
3	PB19-0.3	12	77.784	91.324	69	25	63	C	E	C	C	11
4	PA21-0.3	8	82.045	95.845	80	37	65	B	E	C	B	5
5	PA38-0.1*	12	75.228	89.228	57	81	67	C	B	C	C	9
6	PA33-0.13	8	79.377	93.377	50	81	83	D	B	B	D	8
7	PA35-0.6	8	78.637	92.637	54	75	83	D	B	B	C	6
8	PA37-0.3	8	80.823	94.823	54	62	53	D	C	D	D	10
9	PA31-1.0	8	76.932	91.172	74	87	80	B	A	B	B	3
10	PA31-3.0	8	76.929	90.658	76	87	78	B	A	B	B	2
11	PA31-4.0	8	76.929	90.658	78	87	78	B	A	B	B	1

¹⁾ Territorial compatibility, ²⁾ Ease of project implementation, ³⁾ Scientific performance,
⁴⁾ Ranking according to multi-criteria analysis, ⁵⁾ Value of multi-criteria analysis according to the VIKOR method.
^{*}) The total length of the curved sections is considered to be too short.

The detailed analysis of each scenario presented in this report leads to the conclusion that only versions of the PA31 scenario type can be considered potentially feasible. All the other developed scenarios are no longer considered feasible, either because of the loss of site locations during the study years, because of unacceptable incompatibilities with territorial or geological conditions, or because their scientific performance is not sufficient to attract researchers from all over the world over the long term.

To complete the analysis, a synthesis was made of the criteria using the VIKOR method⁵⁴, which is a benchmark for decision-making processes based on lists of criteria. However, this method does not address whether or not the scenario is feasible. It only ranks the merits of the scenarios in descending order. To estimate the merits of a scenario according to the VIKOR method, we used the parameters presented in Table 19 below.

Table 19: Parameters for the ranking based on the merits of each scenario (VIKOR method).

Criterion	Weight of criterion	Optimization	Comments
Number of sites	5%	Minimise	An eight-site configuration offers four interaction points for FCC-ee, compared with just two interaction points for the twelve-site configuration.
Total length of curved sections	5%	Maximise	A longer circumference length provides higher scientific performance or simpler design.
Territorial compatibility	30%	Maximise	Territorial compatibility, ease of implementation and scientific performance are given equal weight. These three pillars must be balanced to ensure the feasibility of the scenario. The feasibility of each scenario can only be determined through detailed analysis.
Compatibility of technical implementation and construction with geological constraints, configuration, and layout	30%	Maximise	
Scientific performance taking into account the configuration and technical difficulties of the scenario	30%	Maximise	

⁵⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/VIKOR_method

The ranking results (Table 20 below) confirm that the PA31 scenario versions are preferable to the other scenarios. On the left side of the table, the different scenarios are listed in descending order by arc length. On the right side of the table, the scenarios are ranked in descending order using the VIKOR method.

In fact, only the configuration and layout shown in the PA31 type of scenarios can still be considered truly feasible.

Table 20: Scenario ranking by arc length and VIKOR method.

Scenario ranking by arc length					Scenario ranking per the VIKOR method				
#	Scenario	Arc length [km]	Arc length [%]	VIKOR	#	Scenario	Arc length [km]	Length of arcs [%]	VIKOR
1	PA0-0.1	83.750	100%	7	11	PA31-4.0	76.929	91.8%	1
4	PA21-0.3	82.045	97.9%	5	10	PA31-3.0	76.929	91.8%	2
2	PB17-0.8	81.193	96.9%	4	9	PA31-1.0	76.932	91.8%	3
8	PA37-0.3	80.823	96.5%	10	2	PB17-0.8	81.193	96.9%	4
6	PA33-0.13	79.377	94.7%	8	4	PA21-0.3	82.045	97.9%	5
7	PA35-0.6	78.637	93.9%	6	7	PA35-0.6	78.637	93.9%	6
3	PB19-0.3	77.784	92.8%	11	1	PA0-0.1	83.750	100%	7
9	PA31-1.0	76.932	91.8%	3	6	PA33-0.13	79.377	94.7%	8
11	PA31-4.0	76.929	91.8%	1	5	PA38-0.1	75.228	89.8%	9
10	PA31-3.0	76.929	91.8%	2	8	PA37-0.3	80.823	96.5%	10
5	PA38-0.1	75.228	89.8%	9	3	PB19-0.3	77.784	92.8%	11

The best-case scenario, PA31-4.0, is one of the micro-optimizations of the working hypotheses PA31-1.0 and 3.0 presented in this report (PA31-2.0 is an intermediate working version and is not presented). There are only slight differences between the various PA31 class optimizations (1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0). Following discussions with stakeholders and local players in 2023, version 4.0 became the reference scenario. This shows that, even if one scenario is preferred and the margin for adjustment is small, it is still possible to optimise the territorial layout of the FCC. Other examples of possible avenues for optimization are presented in the next section.

5.6. PREFERRED SCENARIO PA31 AND ITS ITERATIVE DEVELOPMENT

5.6.1. Description of scenario PA31 (selected)

The working hypothesis PA31 version 1.0, created in the first quarter of 2021 and presented here, was the preferred scenario determined through a multi-criteria analysis, which was then examined in detail by experts in civil engineering and geology, together with accelerator design specialists and theoretical and experimental physicists. Consultations were also held with numerous local players at various administrative levels (municipal, inter-municipal, department, canton, region).

Once working hypothesis PA31-1.0 had been selected for the feasibility study, CERN and its partners continued to investigate optimizations of this scenario to improve its territorial compatibility and scientific performance, while taking into account constraints, opportunities and additional information gathered. Illustration 91 below shows micro-optimizations of the footprint (PA31-2.0, 3.0 and 4.0), developed from June 2022 onwards. In 2023, these working hypotheses evolved to become the reference scenario, PA31 version 4.0. In 2024, the work continues with local authorities likely to host surface sites to optimise the shape of the perimeter of these sites.

The optimizations carried out from version 1.0 to version 3.0 did not simply consist of moving the sites. This would not have been possible because the configuration of a circular accelerator imposes strict symmetry, and all the sites are interdependent: moving one site means moving all the others. Optimization of the PA31 scenario, from version 1.0 to version 3.0, is achieved by simultaneously adjusting five parameters:

- 1) **displacement** of the nominal PA point in Ferney-Voltaire 23 m to the east;
- 2) **rotation of the ring** by 0.25 degrees around the displaced PA nominal point in a counterclockwise direction;
- 3) **shortening of the technical straight sections** by 128 m, or 512 m in total (4 x 128 m), as further shortening of the curved sections would no longer be acceptable;
- 4) **adjustment of PB, PF, PG, PH, PJ and PL site locations;**
- 5) **reduction of land use at the PA, PB, PD and PF sites.**

Version 4.0 represents a micro-optimization of version 3.0, consisting of a slight displacement of the ring by a few meters, a slight rotation of 0.03 degrees and the optimization of shaft positioning at the sites following meetings with local stakeholders. In addition, a **shortening of the straight sections at the interaction points** from 1 400 m to 961 m compensates for the widening of the tunnel between the straight sections and the arcs, which improves compatibility between the lepton collider (FCC-ee) and the hadron collider (FCC-hh).

The optimizations described in Table 21 are intended to progressively refine the technical concept to enable the design of equipment and technical infrastructures while also finding solutions to difficulties not resolved during the feasibility study in order to propose a scenario that is attractive to all stakeholders.

Illustration 91: Development of working hypothesis PA31 (from version 1.0 to version 4.0) from 2021 to 2023. Overall, there are only slight differences in the footprint and location of the nominal points. In detail, site optimization represents approximately 200 m for scientific sites and 800 m for technical sites. On this scale, the PA31-3.0 footprint is covered by the PA31-4.0 footprint, which is very similar.

Table 21: Developments and impacts of iterative modifications to the preferred working scenario.

Scenario	Date	Actions	Changes and impacts
PA31-1.0	April 2021	Working hypothesis selected for in-depth analysis.	-
PA31-2.0	June 2021	Correction of geodesic calculations and adjustment of straight sections.	Improvement of the nominal PG point to avoid the southern slope and correction of each point to estimate the theoretical land use of the surface sites.
PA31-3.0	December 2022	PA nominal point moved, rotation of the ring and shortening of straight technical sections.	PG and PJ scientific sites moved more than 150 m. Optimization of PA, PD and PG site locations. Additional options for PB, PF, PH and PL technical sites.
PA31-3.1	January 2023	Development of an integrated footprint for the FCC-ee and FCC-hh colliders.	Nominal points of PA, PD, PG and PJ scientific sites moved 10 m towards the exterior of the ring.
PA31-4.0	August 2023-August 2024	Optimization of surface site land use and access. Technical design of the FCC-ee and FCC-hh colliders taken into account for development of a single civil engineering project.	This baseline scenario was established on the basis of working version PA31-3.1, and optimised the location and footprint of surface sites in order to: confirm technical feasibility and initiate land freeze procedures; plan and implement subsurface investigations in locations where data was lacking; plan and initiate analyses of the initial surface conditions; and thereby provide an initial cost estimate for the construction project.

Illustration 92 and Illustration 93 show the changes made to the PA31 scenario over the course of 2023 from version 1.0 to version 4.0, which was adopted as the reference scenario. We can see that the improvements brought about by micro-optimization concern scientific performance and territorial compatibility.

Illustration 92: Summary of the multi-criteria analysis of the PA31-3.0 scenario with eight surface sites.

Illustration 93: Summary of the multi-criteria analysis of the PA31-4.0 scenario with eight surface sites.

5.6.2. Changes made to the PA scientific site in Ferney-Voltaire, France

In version 1.0 of scenario PA31, the footprint and, consequently, the two required access shafts, are very close to the D35 road (Illustration 94). This may compromise the feasibility of the construction of an above-ground assembly hangar, and represents a challenge for landscape integration. It was therefore advisable to move the ring to the southeast, while maintaining the required distance between the site and the exclusion zone identified to the east (existing ecological compensation wetland). The access shaft to the experiment cavern was 40 m from the departmental road in version 1.0. In the optimised version 3.0, the shaft is 60 m from the road, making it easier to integrate the site. In version 4.0, the distance is 40 m, which is also feasible. However, the other sites along the footprint have better locations.

Illustration 94: Optimization of the scenario with a slight shift in the nominal point PA in Ferney-Voltaire to make the construction of the access shaft and the development work around the shaft more feasible. The exclusion zone marked in red to the east of the nominal point remains intact and will be avoided.

5.6.3. Changes made to the PD scientific site in Nangy, France

The nominal point of the PD scientific site in Nangy is at the southern end of the plot (Illustration 95), just 20 m from the “Chemin de la Courbe” rural road. Beyond this road, the land is to be avoided as it is within the perimeter of the motorway and will be needed to accommodate the structures associated with the RD903 development work. The displacement of the PA point, combined with the rotation of the ring, the shortening of straight technical sections and the work on geodesic calculations, moves the PD nominal point 120 m northwards. As the plot of land widens progressively to the north, this modification offers more flexibility to design the site properly and avoid incompatibilities with the motorway and the RD903 road, and also allows for better integration of the site into the landscape. Access is still from the north, as originally planned. Compared with version 3.0, the reference scenario is 10 m further north, to gain space between the A40 and the service cavern shaft.

Illustration 95: Result of scenario optimization for the Nangy scientific site. By optimizing the layout, potential conflicts can be avoided with the zone reserved for the motorway and with the RD903 development project.

5.6.4. Changes made to the PG scientific site in Groisy and Charvonnex, France

In scenario PA31 version 1.0, the nominal point of the PG scientific site was on a plateau, straddling the municipalities of Charvonnex and Groisy (Illustration 96). In version 3.0, the adaptation of the ring moved the nominal point to the “Bois de la Forêt” forestland, in Groisy. The site is bounded to the southeast by a steep slope that must be avoided to ensure the stability of the buildings.

In version 4.0, the site would straddle the forest (Groisy) and the plateau (Charvonnex), which is currently undeveloped; this location considers the analysis of the initial state, and the recommendations made by the relevant government departments, stakeholders and local players. The changes made from version 1.0 to version 3.0 avoid impacts on grazing and the landscape, but would use a portion of land in a classified wooded area that would have to be compensated for. The reference scenario strikes a balance between impacts, and includes the possibility of compensating for the loss of 1.6 ha of forest around the site with brownfields in the vicinity.

Illustration 96: The changes made to scenario PA31 from version 1.0 to version 3.0 move the nominal point PG and its two shafts 160 m north and 150 m east into the forest. This facilitates landscape integration and avoids the existing grasslands. However, version 3.0 has an impact on a classified wooded area. Version 4.0 achieves a balance between impacts.

5.6.5. Changes made to the PJ scientific site in Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens, France

In version 1.0 of scenario PA31, the PJ scientific site lies between two branches of the Nant d'Hiver watercourse, straddling the municipalities of Dingy-en-Vuache to the south and Vulbens to the north (Illustration 97). This area is hampered by a lack of available space between the two branches of the watercourse, which are incised and bordered by wooded strips. The zone is characterised by its high ecological and agricultural value, which should be preserved and remain integrated into its surroundings. It is therefore advisable to optimise the layout of this site to improve its territorial compatibility. As a result of the three-fold operations (moving of the PA site, rotation of the ring and shortening of the straight technical sections) the PJ nominal point and its two shafts were moved 165 m to the east. The site still straddles the two municipalities, but offers many advantages:

- 1) the new location has less agricultural and ecological value;
- 2) the new location benefits from simplified access via an existing road to be widened to the north;
- 3) in its updated version, the site is closer to the Valleiry motorway service area;
- 4) by moving the site, a new ecological continuity is created for wildlife and the north-south wildlife corridor is safeguarded, thus achieving a net ecological gain.

Illustration 97: Optimizing the scenario leads to the PJ scientific site being moved to the east, with advantages for territorial compatibility.

5.6.6. Changes made to the PB technical site in Switzerland

In scenario PA31-1.0, the nominal point of the PB technical site is located directly under the Nant du Paradis watercourse in Choulex (Illustration 98). This configuration only allows for a single working hypothesis for a surface site to the south of the point, as the access point can be moved slightly along the footprint but must remain within the ring. In version 3.0 of the scenario, the nominal point is moved slightly north of the watercourse, to Choulex. This location could facilitate access and the management of excavated materials on adjacent plots of farmlands. This scenario could also improve site access. As far as administrative procedures are concerned, the site would be on a private plot of land in version 3.0 instead of the public plot in version 1.0. However, a technical analysis of the feasibility of underground structures showed that it was not feasible to build in this location. A distance of at least 35 m between the tunnel and the service cavern is required, which would place a shaft directly on the Nant du Paradis. In the reference scenario, only one site, south of the Nant du Paradis, in Presinge along the “Route de Jussy” road, was found to be suitable and therefore retained in version 4.0 of the scenario PA31. The surface site should preferably be in the municipality of Presinge, along the “Route de Jussy” road, to minimise interference with natural protection zones.

Illustration 98: Location of nominal points for scenarios PA31-1.0, 2.0, 3.0 and 4.0. Reference scenario PA31-4.0 calls for the site to be located in Presinge, displaced from the nominal point, at the “Route de Jussy” road, north of L'Avenir.

5.6.7. Changes made to the PF technical site in Eteaux or La-Roche-sur-Foron, France

The PF site (Illustration 99) must be located away from the nominal point inside the ring due to the topography, elevation, urbanization constraints and accessibility choices. Two locations were selected: one to the south of the RD1203 road, in the municipality of Eteaux, and another in the locality known as "Champ d'Arrière" between the watercourse and the railroad line, in the municipality of La Roche-sur-Foron. At first glance, a location close to the railroad line seems preferable, as it has low soil quality, the site would not be visible, access would not cause disturbances to local residents and the ecological impact would be limited. However, the location to the north, close to the RD1203 road, offers extremely easy access from the departmental road, and is directly opposite a public works and earthmoving company with construction equipment and facilities for its activities nearby, and can take advantage of the existing infrastructure in the vicinity (e.g. two 20 kV ENEDIS substations, sewage and drinking water). The site would not add to the existing disturbances (traffic noise). The location is characterised by the presence of higher quality agricultural land than that to the south in La Roche-sur-Foron, the proximity of wetlands, and direct visibility from the departmental road. Mountain views can be preserved by constructing semi-underground buildings on the existing slope.

The study phase involved site visits for visual inspections between autumn 2022 and autumn 2023. During these visits, the service providers for the civil engineering and environmental study learned of a proposed inert waste storage facility (ISDI) at the location of the PF site in La Roche-sur-Foron, north of the railroad line. At this stage, preliminary analysis shows that the FCC technical site and the ISDI are not directly compatible without prior planning for their integration. As a general rule, construction waste disposal can lead to long-term ground instability. What's more, these waste deposits frequently conflict with subsequent constructions if there are no prior planning or preparation measures. Using the land as farmlands or grasslands cannot be ruled out. The feasibility of building the shaft and creating stable landscaping around it through a 10 m layer of inert waste is questionable. CERN has already had experience drilling through a much shallower layer of inert waste during the HL-LHC and ITER projects. It is advisable to anticipate additional costs for civil engineering works representing tens of millions of euros, with no guarantee of lasting success if the ground is not sufficiently stable, as shown by several examples in the literature⁵⁵. In order to build along the perimeter of the ISDI, CERN would need to reach an agreement with the landowners and the ISDI operator before the start, in 2027, of phase 2 of this facility, which would involve backfilling the intended space for the surface site with inert waste. A location for the ISDI on land in La Roche-sur-Foron would also require the construction of an access road approximately 2.4 km long, with the creation of a new bridge to cross the railroad line from Aix-les-Bains-Le Revard to Annemasse. The passage under the A410 motorway should also be improved or renovated. These developments represent an additional cost of around 4.5 million euros.

The La Roche-sur-Foron site is closer to the footprint of the collider than the site alongside the RD1203, requiring a tunnel 340 m long at the bottom of the shaft to connect to the collider (compared with around 600 m for the Eteaux site). A cost analysis of the underground structures shows that a deeper shaft with an underground access tunnel for a site to the north, in Eteaux, which is further away from the accelerator tunnel, would cost 5 million euros more than the construction of a shorter shaft and access tunnel to the south, in La Roche-sur-Foron. The wetlands to the north can be avoided, and the development of a technical site creates the possibility of enhancing the natural environment, which is currently degraded. As a result, the option along the departmental road is chosen for the location of the PF site in reference scenario PA31-4.0.

⁵⁵ Cerema, *Ce qu'il faut savoir sur les installations de stockage de déchets inertes (ISDI)*:

https://www.auvergne-rhone-alpes.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/190621_guide-dechets-inertes-cerema-hd_1_.pdf

Illustration 99: Layout options for the PF technical site (January 2023). Compatibility with a planned ISDI on site and wetlands is currently being studied. The option along the departmental road would avoid the wetlands. The site location in scenario PA31-4.0 would be directly beside the departmental road in Eteaux. The exact location of the is to be optimised based on environmental analyses.

5.6.8. Changes made to the PH technical site in Cercier and Marlioz, France

Development of scenario PA31 from version 1.0 to version 4.0 results in the PH nominal point being moved approximately 190 m to the northeast (Illustration 100). The nominal point is now located directly beside the D203 road and is not within sight of the single-family homes to the south, because the site would be in the middle of the forest. In version 1.0, the site was partly forest, partly farmland, with road access opposite the roadside houses. Optimization would appear to be possible for better integration in the landscape, with a shorter access route and less impact on agricultural and forestry areas, even if part of the site would then be in a classified wooded area. The exclusion zone to the north of the site, due to the presence of a gas pipeline, must be respected. As in version 1.0, the site in version 4.0 straddles two municipalities, Marlioz to the west and Cercier to the east. An analysis of the environment while taking into account the sloped topography will make it possible to more precisely determine the exact location of the site perimeter.

Illustration 100: Location of PH site (January 2023) between Cercier and Marlioz along the D203 road.

5.6.9. Changes made to the PL technical site in Challex, France

The changes made to scenario PA31 from version 1.0 to version 4.0 moves the nominal point of the PL technical site approximately 80 m to the east (Illustration 101). The point is now closer to two single-family homes. However, the general surroundings remain the same. Thanks to cooperation with stakeholders and local players, with assistance from the relevant government departments, it was possible to propose acceptable siting options in this sector, which has territorial, geological, hydrogeological and environmental constraints.

Illustration 101: The general surroundings of PL site layout remain the same, even though the nominal point is within a radius of roughly 80 m in versions 1.0, 3.0 and 4.0 of scenario PA31.

6. INTEGRATING THE PA31 SCENARIO IN THE TERRITORY

Chapter 6 describes the major constraints for the overall ring in France and Switzerland, and reviews the regulations in force. The main issues relating to the layout are presented according to different subject areas: topography, surface water and groundwater, biodiversity, risks, populations, landscapes, town planning documents, noise, networks (potential residual heat networks, water and electricity needs of the FCC), access, site requirements in terms of land area and site use. The chapter takes a closer look at some of the needs of the FCC in terms of resources, such as water and electricity, while drawing attention to potential opportunities such as residual heat networks. Lastly, it provides details about the surface sites (required land areas and site use).

6.1. FOOTPRINT OF PA31

The footprint of PA31 (Illustration 102) is a working hypothesis resulting from the iterative process described in Chapter 1. Among the many scenarios analysed based on the different types of data (existing literature, terrain, environment), this is the most promising one to retain for in-depth studies (in all subject areas). It is by no means the definitive footprint, but offers a balanced compromise between territorial constraints, scientific performance, and technical feasibility. It will make it possible to gather more information and knowledge about local projects, so that the project can be continuously improved.

Illustration 102: Map of footprint of PA31 working hypothesis.

The map (Illustration 102) shows the theoretical layout of the sites. Adjustments are then made according to territorial constraints (within the limits defined in Chapter 1).

This report presents the considered layouts, which have made it possible to formulate hypotheses and gather feedback and comments from local authorities and stakeholders. To date, no layout has been decided on. Two types of adjustments are possible:

- for scientific sites, access shafts must be vertical with respect to the experimental cavern, which determines the shaft position at the theoretical point. On the surface, however, the perimeter around the shaft can be adapted;
- for technical sites, it is possible to modify the polygon and move the shaft a certain distance around the theoretical point, in order to find a site with fewer constraints.

As part of the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate approach, a major effort to reduce the amount of land required has been carried out and is continuing, with particular emphasis on:

- studies to reduce the number of facilities required: for example, as the result of a study that was conducted, the number of shafts required for scientific sites was reduced from three to two;
- constant efforts to optimise the technical facilities required for surface sites and to reduce their size.

The analysis of each site (chapters 7 to 14) provides a detailed presentation of each proposed location and possible adjustments.

6.2. ANALYSIS OF THE OVERALL PA31 FOOTPRINT

6.2.1. Introduction

The purpose of this section, based on available bibliographical data, is to identify the main environmental and human issues that could be major challenges for the project.

This section presents and prioritises the main environmental issues to be taken into account when applying the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) approach as part of the environmental assessment of the project. These issues will guide the choice for the footprint, particularly with regard to the location of surface sites.

The analysed issues are based on those to be taken into account for an environmental assessment (article R122-5 of the French environmental code and OEIE/ROEIE⁵⁶ in Switzerland). However, not all the elements listed in article R122-5 of the French environmental code are analysed in this summary. At this stage of the project, before the initial assessments are carried out, the subject areas are analysed based on the bibliography and the use of available databases. Consequently, the analysis is incomplete at this stage, and will need to be supplemented with knowledge from local players, in particular the various local authorities involved in the project and the government departments responsible for regulations and issuing permits.

With the aim being to propose realistic layout scenarios in the light of known constraints, laws and regulations, the ERC approach examined a range of key issues, including:

- **Topography:** the depth of the shafts is a major constraint for project feasibility and cost. On a technical level, experiment shafts should not exceed a depth of 300 m (400 m for technical shafts).
- **Groundwater:** bodies of groundwater are likely to be present along the FCC footprint. Boreholes will have to be drilled to determine their depth and characteristics, particularly at the locations of the various sites. An in-depth geological analysis is also required.
- **Biodiversity:** the FCC footprint is affected by the existence of ZNIEFF types 1 and 2 zones (Natural Zone of Interest for Ecology, Flora, and Fauna), ZICOs (zone important for bird conservation), Natura 2000 zones, ZSCs (special area of conservation), ZPSs (special protection areas), wetlands, and zones protected by biotope protection orders, which all will require detailed environmental analyses beforehand to define the conditions for site layouts. In Switzerland, biodiversity is also protected at the cantonal level by priority flora and fauna sites, and at the federal level by the inventory of listed sites for amphibian breeding.
- **The risks:** existing risks such as clay shrinkage-swelling, flooding and seismic and technological risks should be taken into account as early as possible, and should be brought to the attention of project owners for determining the size of infrastructures. The proven presence of gas pockets in molasse formations represents a risk that should be analysed during subsurface investigations. The OCEV-GESDEC (cantonal office for environment-geographic information system) is currently mapping the risks of gas present in the molasse in Switzerland, but it is not yet available. Potentially significant water circulation in the molasse, at certain faults, cannot be ruled out either.
- **Population density:** the FCC footprint covers a zone that is, in general, sparsely populated but highly sensitive. Surface sites must be located away from residential areas.
- **Landscape:** the FCC is to be integrated in highly valued landscapes already affected by the presence of numerous infrastructures. Particular attention must be paid to the architecture of the sites to ensure harmonisation with each unified landscape.

⁵⁶ Swiss environmental impact assessment regulation (OEIE) and Regulations for application of the federal ordinance on environmental impact assessment (ROEIE).

- **Town-planning:** most of the municipalities affected by the surface sites have approved town-planning documents: in France, a local urban plan (PLU) for most municipalities, and an inter-commune local urban plan (PLUi) for two municipalities. A single municipality, which has very limited development and no urban planning document, is subject to the national urban planning regulations (RNU). It would be advisable to monitor any changes made to these urban planning documents as part of the process for developing the layout scenario. In this context, particular attention will also be paid to the territory's current and future SCoTs (territorial coherence schemes) and the frameworks they will define for its urbanization.

The FCC sites concern (as of September 2022) six SCoTs: Annemasse region, Pays Rochois, Annécien basin, Usses et Rhône, Pays de Gex, Genevois⁵⁷.

Overall, all the SCoTs have recently been revised (or will be) to incorporate the rules of the SRADDET (regional scheme for planning, sustainable development and territorial equality), in particular rule number 7 on preserving farmland ("identify strategic agricultural areas, in particular based on the agronomic quality of the soil"; "in parallel, identify areas of agricultural decline").

In practical terms, this means carrying out an agricultural diagnosis for all SCoTs and integrating guidelines to be applied in the PLU/PLUi plans: the obligation to carry out in-depth agricultural diagnoses and to take appropriate measures to preserve soil, or even to safeguard it, in application of ZAN objectives (zero net artificialisation).

In Switzerland, the project must comply with various regulations at different levels of the Confederation:

- federal plans like sector plans⁵⁸;
- cantonal plans⁵⁹ for land-use, infrastructure and protection plans (cantonal master plans, currently being revised to take account of the cross-border territorial vision, district master plans, local neighbourhood plans, tree protection measures and building permits);
- cantonal strategic plans, focusing on specific subject areas;
- municipal master plans⁶⁰ (PDCom): approved by the "Conseil d'Etat" in Choulex; Presinge is exempted from having one.

⁵⁷ Information and links to the relevant SCoTs :

SCoT Région Annemasse, approved on 15 September 2021. Document available on website of the urban area:

<https://www.annemasse-agglo.fr/actions-et-projets/amenager-la-ville/revision-scot>

SCoT Pays Rochois, approved on 11 February 2014. Perimeter under consideration:

<https://www.ccpaysrochois.fr/mon-territoire/les-documents-cadre/scot/>

SCoT du bassin annécien, approved on 26 February 2014, currently under review:

<https://www.scot-bassin-annecien.fr/>

SCoT Usses et Rhône, approved on 11 September 2018:

<https://www.usses-et-rhone.fr/6204-scot.htm>

SCoT Pays de Gex, approved on 19 December, 2019:

<https://www.paysdegexagglo.fr/9294-le-schema-de-coherence-territoriale-scot.htm>

SCoT du Genevois, approved on 13 December 2013:

<https://www.cc-genevois.fr/fr/la-collectivite-et-son-territoire/le-scot/les-grands-objectifs>

⁵⁸ <https://www.are.admin.ch/are/fr/home/developpement-et-amenagement-du-territoire/strategie-et-planification/conceptions-et-plans-sectoriels/plans-sectoriels-de-la-confederation.html>

⁵⁹ <https://www.ge.ch/consulter-plans-amenagement-adoptes/plan-directeur-cantonal>

⁶⁰ <https://www.ge.ch/dossier/amenager-territoire/planification-communale/plans-directeurs-communaux-2e-generation>

All work on the FCC project will have to take these developments and the resulting protection tools into account. At this stage, the available information is not directly usable at the project level.

- **Noise:** the project will have to comply with regulatory thresholds during the construction and operation phases, particularly in the vicinity of dwellings.
- **Networks:** known networks (e.g. transportation, water, electricity, gas, etc.) in the vicinity of the FCC footprint are listed and presented. Further studies will need to assess the extent to which these networks can meet the needs of the future FCC. In any case, the distribution of resources will have to be covered by specific agreements between France and Switzerland.

6.2.2. Topography

The footprint lies between the Jura Massif and the Subalpine chains. The elevation can vary from 422 meters for the PA site to 760 meters for the PF site (elevation of the theoretical point). The tunnel is about 200 m above mean sea level. Its location is currently being optimised.

The depth of the shafts is a key factor in determining feasibility (Illustration 103).

Illustration 103: Elevation of nominal points, corresponding to the centre of straight sections, in meters above sea level. These points do not always correspond to the location of the shafts.

Any positioning or displacement of shafts in relation to the nominal points in the middle of the straight sections must therefore be studied in the light of this issue, particularly with regard to site PF in the municipality of Eteaux.

6.2.3. Bodies of groundwater in France

The following bodies of groundwater are known (Illustration 104).

Illustration 104: Mapping of groundwater bodies in France. Source: SDAGE 2022.

Groundwater bodies are mapped by breaking down each water body according to the vertical organization of the entities. On the map, level 1 water bodies are located above level 2 water bodies, with no metric depth indicated.

To the west of its footprint and for roughly 60% of its circumference, the FCC is affected by the presence of a fully confined water table. By definition, this is a volume of groundwater separated from the soil surface by an impermeable geological formation, at a pressure higher than atmospheric pressure. Its piezometric surface is greater than the roof of the aquifer that contains it. The water circulates very slowly and under pressure, and is protected from potential pollution from the surface if there is no connection to the surface or other aquifers (either naturally via faults, or through drilling).

The FCC is also affected to the east, for roughly 5 km, by the presence of an unconfined water table in the Arve valley. An unconfined water table is a groundwater table whose upper level can vary without being blocked by an upper impermeable layer. It flows under permeable soil, at generally shallow levels, and its surface is at atmospheric pressure. It is more sensitive to pollution.

Bodies of groundwater are therefore present in the area covered by the FCC footprint. However, the information currently available does not allow us to determine their depth and, consequently, the probability of encountering them during tunnel excavation and shaft construction. Consequently, detailed hydrogeological studies will be required to accurately assess the impact.

Preserving these aquifers is a major challenge. The framework directive for water sets quantitative and qualitative objectives for each body of water. Programming documents (SDAGE Rhône-Méditerranée-Corse) and SAGEs (water planning and management schemes) for the region also specify the local issues relating to the area's water resources, as well as the rules to be taken into account.

The Rhône-Méditerranée-Corse master plan for water development and management (SDAGE RMC) was approved on March 18 2022⁶¹. It draws particular attention to the drinking water supply issue. Studies on strategic resources are available or underway⁶². They could prove decisive for the FCC.

The SDAGE defines the groundwater bodies and aquifers with the greatest stakes for satisfying drinking water (AEP) supply needs, in which safeguard zone boundaries are to be defined (or have already been defined) (provision 5E-01 of fundamental guideline no. 5E of the SDAGE RMC 2022-2027):

1. If strategic resources for drinking water supply have been identified and their safeguard zone boundaries defined, the corresponding safeguard zones require specific actions to control withdrawals and protect against point/non-point source, accidental, chronic or seasonal pollution. Actions to preserve the quality and availability of water from strategic resources in safeguard zones are designed to meet the priority given to these resources for drinking water supply over other uses, as stipulated in article L. 211-1 of the French environment code.
2. While strategic resources remain to be identified and their safeguard zone boundaries defined, once the safeguard zone boundaries have been defined, the same objectives as those indicated above will be pursued. The map distinguishes between the situation of water bodies (or aquifers) that have already been covered by strategic resource characterization studies, as required by SDAGE 2010-2015, but for which safeguard zones have yet to be defined, and the situation for water bodies that have not been covered by studies.

In the vicinity of the study area, several bodies of groundwater have been identified as being of major concern in the SDAGE RMC 2022-2027 of the Rhone Mediterranean basin. They concern the 1) Pays de Gex, 2) Arve and 3) Genevois areas.

The breakdown of the map (Illustration 105) shows that:

1. sites PJ and PL are affected by the presence of a deep body of water with a safeguard zone to be defined;
2. the PA site is affected by the presence of a deep-water body with a safeguard zone to be defined and a deep water body with a defined safeguard zone;
3. the PD site is affected by the presence of a body of water reaching the surface, with a defined safeguard zone.

⁶¹ <https://www.rhone-mediterranee.eaufrance.fr/gestion/sdage2022/etapes-delaboration-du-sdage-2022-2027>

⁶² Strategic resources for drinking water supplies (AEP): <https://www.rhone-mediterranee.eaufrance.fr/eau-potable-et-assainissement/eau-potable/ressources-strategiques-pour-laep#quest-ce-quune-ressource-strategique-et-une-zone-de-sauvegarde>

Illustration 105: Location of water bodies with safeguard zones around PA31 (SDAGE RMC 2022-2027).

6.2.4. Bodies of water in Geneva

The water tables in the canton of Geneva are mapped according to whether they are confirmed or presumed to be the main (deep), surface (shallow) or temporary water table (Illustration 106).

The footprint mainly avoids groundwater, and the PB site borders the Puplinge surface water table.

In addition, surface sites avoid water protection areas (Illustration 107).

Compatibility with the hydrogeology in the Challex area (France) for the PL surface site at the nominal point of scenario PA31 remains to be clarified by means of already planned subsurface investigations. The site is not located within a water protection zone. These investigations will take into account cross-border aspects, such as the confirmation or not of the presence of a temporary water table indicated by GESDEC in Switzerland in 2023. If a shaft is incompatible with a water table, the shaft or the entire surface site can be moved westwards, out of the affected area. The technical feasibility of the entire scenario therefore remains unchanged.

Illustration 106: Mapping of water table in the canton of Geneva. Source: SITG.

Illustration 107: Water protection sectors in the canton of Geneva. Source: SITG.

6.2.5. Biodiversity and water

Inventories of Natural Zone of Interest for Ecology, Flora, and Fauna (ZNIEFF)

On the PA31 footprint, no surface sites are directly concerned by ZNIEFF inventories.

However, three of the sites are located close to a ZNIEFF:

The PD site is close to the type-1 ZNIEFF "Gravières de l'Arve" to the east and "Plaines des rocailles" to the west, which are included in the type-2 ZNIEFF "Ensemble fonctionnel de la rivière Arve et de ses annexes" (functional area of the Arve River and its extensions). As the PD site will be located outside the alluvial forests and away from the Arve River, it should have minor impact on these zones. However, it is interesting to note that the type-2 ZNIEFF mentions natural flood expansion zones and water resource protection zones. It may therefore be useful to take into account the permeability and topography of the area to avoid affecting its ecological functions.

The PF site is close to the type-1 ZNIEFF "Ensemble des zones humides du plateau de Bornes" (collection of wetlands of the Bornes plateau) and "Ruisseau du Couche", which are included in the type-2 ZNIEFF "Zones humides du plateau de Bornes". Some of the proposed plots are adjacent to the type-2 ZNIEFF. It is characterised in particular by its ecological functions of a hydraulic nature and for the preservation of animal populations as a feeding or breeding area for numerous species. Some of the proposed plots of land include wetlands listed in the departmental inventory, which will need to be taken into account in this context.

Finally, the PG site is located in the immediate vicinity of a type-1 ZNIEFF "Friches et pinèdes à molinies à la gare de Groisy" (brownfields and pine forests at Groisy train station), which concerns a wooded parcel very close to one of the proposed plots. In particular, its description mentions the connections between wooded areas on the plateau. The site requires a transport infrastructure that passes between classified wooded areas. However, as the selected plots are not wooded, the impact of the site on this area should be low.

6.2.6. Protection of Natura 2000 sites and biotope protection orders

No site is located in a Special Protection Area (ZPS) or Special Area of Conservation (ZSC) as part of the Natura 2000 system, or in an area subject to a Biotope Protection Order (APB) (see Illustration 108).

The PD site is also close to a ZPS and Natura 2000 SAC, requiring further study to assess the extent to which these Natura 2000 sites are likely to be affected by the project.

Illustration 108: Map of biodiversity protection in France.

In Switzerland, different levels of biodiversity protection exist, at federal (Illustration 109) and cantonal (Illustration 110) levels.

The PB surface site borders on a nationally important protection zone for amphibian breeding sites (in accordance with OBat, the amphibian ordinance), as well as a cantonal priority site for flora and fauna. All these protections are linked to Nant du Paradis, which borders the sector identified in the PB site.

Illustration 109: Map of federal inventories in Switzerland.

Illustration 110: Map of cantonal inventories in the canton of Geneva.

6.2.7. Ecological continuities of the SRADDET Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes⁶³.

The "protection and restoration of biodiversity" component of the SRADDET Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes must be incorporated into local urban planning documents (SCoT and PLU) in order to be enforceable for the plots of land.

The biodiversity map in the SRADDET Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes shows that the PA31 footprint is mostly located in "natural permeable zones".

On some sites, notably PJ, there are "ecological corridors to be restored".

The analysis carried out at this stage provides an indication of the potential ecological importance of the sectors concerned. For each PLU (urban development plan), it will be necessary to check that the SRADDET has been taken into account in this respect.

The study of each site (chapters 3 to 10) provides detailed information on the various components of the green and blue grids (TVB, terrestrial and aquatic ecological continuities). Each site will have to be adapted to local conditions, in particular by analysing the green and blue grid integrated into local urban planning documents.

Illustration 111: Ecological continuities identified under the "protection and restoration of biodiversity" component of the SRADDET Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes.

⁶³Formerly SRCE, (regional scheme for ecological consistency).

6.2.8. Ecological continuities identified in Geneva's ecological infrastructure

Illustration 112: Ecological infrastructure at 200 m scale in 2020 (cantonal scale). Source: SITG.

The ecological infrastructure makes it possible to identify the sectors in the territory that are the best from an ecological point of view (Illustration 112). This approach maps biodiversity reservoirs and biological corridors.

The PB site is bordered by biodiversity reservoirs and functional corridors. It is essential to preserve and even strengthen them.

6.2.9. Surface water

Illustration 113: Rivers, wetlands, and spawning grounds.

Spawning grounds:

They are inventoried at the departmental level. As they overlap classified watercourses, they are not shown on the map (Illustration 113). They are, however, listed in the constraints.

Wetlands:

Regional wetland inventories are used as a methodological tool and as a warning system for examining the potential presence of wetlands in a project location area. A meticulous study of each surface site is necessary to gain detailed knowledge of the location area, by cross-referencing cartographic indices and additional field inventories.

Watercourses:

The master plan for water development and management (SDAGE RMC) establishes a hierarchy of watercourses and their status. There are two lists:

1. Rivers classified in list 1 are in very good ecological condition and require full protection for migratory fish between salt and fresh water. In order to avoid damaging aquatic environments, no authorization or concession may be granted for the building of new structures if they constitute an obstacle to ecological continuity (see article R214-109 of the Environment Code).
2. Rivers in list 2 require action to restore ecological continuity (sediment transport and fish circulation). Any obstructions to this must be managed, maintained, and equipped in accordance with rules defined by the administrative authority, in coordination with the owner or, failing that, the operator.

Scenario PA31 is affected by both types of lists. These elements provide an initial indication of a potentially important "watercourse" issues at this site.

6.2.10. Drinking water supply (AEP) catchments and protection perimeters

The list below shows the AEP water catchments potentially affected by the PA31 scenario, which should therefore be kept in mind during further studies.

Data provided by the Agence régionale de santé Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (regional health agency).

The information in this paragraph is confidential and not publicly available. Its use is strictly limited to the present study in order to take these issues into account and avoid them. The document containing this data is online on Zenodo with restricted access: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10184739>.

During the detailed technical development phase, additional hydrogeological investigations may be required for the protection of AEP catchments and protection perimeters in France. Water protection zones in Switzerland are also shown in the following illustration. No protected areas in Switzerland are concerned.

6.2.11. Natural and technological hazards

6.2.11.1. Clay swelling

Along the entire footprint, there is a low to medium risk of clay shrinkage/swelling at sites PG, PH and PJ (Illustration 114). This risk must be taken into account by adopting specific construction measures where necessary. The project owner must factor this risk into the design and technical choices made for all types of infrastructure: e.g. access roads and surface buildings, whose foundations must be able to withstand the consequences of clay shrinkage/swelling.

Illustration 114: Natural hazards: clay shrinkage/swelling. Similar data for Switzerland available in the SITG (layer: “sols de fondation”⁶⁴).

⁶⁴ SITG, layer « sols de fondation » : https://map.sitg.ge.ch/app/?portalresources=GOL_SOLS_FONDATION

6.2.11.2. Natural risks of unstable terrain and flooding

The PF and PD surface sites are covered by a natural hazard prevention plan, and more specifically by a flood risk prevention plan (PPRI, see Illustration 115).

They are also defined as territories at significant risk of flooding (TRI). A map is drawn up for each shaft in a TRI. In areas where the TRI is a priority, it requires the development of a concerted flood strategy, including a PPRI.

Illustration 115: Natural risks of unstable terrain and flooding.

In Switzerland, the sector is located in a low-risk zone for flooding of the Seymaz. However, this hazard is considered to be residual only. A non-constructible safety perimeter must be maintained at the edge of the pre-identified sector (Illustration 116). In addition, the forestland zone bordering the Seymaz to the west of the zone is a sector to be preserved, first because of its “forestland” status, and second because it is considered a "minimum space" ensuring the management of the watercourse. It overlaps with nature protection zones, thus ensuring consistency between territorial issues.

Illustration 116: Water-related natural hazards in the canton of Geneva. Data from SITG (minimum watercourse space and flood hazard zones).

In Switzerland, the PA31 footprint crosses zones with deep and shallow unstable terrains. There are no zones with unstable terrains at the PL, PA and PB surface sites (Illustration 117).

Illustration 117: Natural hazards associated with the risk of deep and shallow unstable terrains in the canton of Geneva. Data from SITG.

6.2.11.3. Earthquakes

In general, the FCC footprint is affected by a moderate to medium seismic risk on the French side (Illustration 118). On the Swiss side, the foundation soils are classes A, B, C, D and E (Illustration 119). This seismic risk must be taken into account by adopting specific construction measures where necessary.

This information is brought to the attention of infrastructure and building owners and contractors.

Surface buildings will have to withstand the detected seismic risks.

Illustration 118: Seismic risk in France.

Illustration 119: Seismicity of foundation soils in Switzerland.

6.2.11.4. Technological risks

On the French side, the PA31 footprint (Illustration 120) features a large number of facilities classified for environmental protection (ICPE).

The other sites are located close to various ICPEs. None of these ICPEs are classified as “Seveso” (industrial sites presenting major accident risks, requiring a high level of prevention). The closest proximity between an ICPE and a surface site is at the PD site.

An ICPE is a facility operated or owned by a natural or legal person, public or private, which may present hazards or disturbances for local residents, health, safety, public hygiene, agriculture, the protection of nature and the environment, and the conservation of sites and monuments.

The law defines and governs the procedures relating to ICPEs, as well as the way in which these facilities are to be managed, in order to reduce the risks and impacts relating to these facilities and to assess the technological hazards they present.

Illustration 120: Technological risks in France. Source: Géorisques.

Switzerland has a legal framework for protection against major accidents (Illustration 121). The transport, handling, and storage of large quantities of chemical or biological substances must comply with all the safety measures required to prevent a major accident. The purpose of the ordinance on protection against major accidents (OPAM) is to protect the population and the environment from the serious consequences of major accidents. Facilities subject to the OPAM are:

- companies using or storing large quantities of substances, preparations, or special wastes, as well as those using pathogenic, genetically modified, or exotic organisms in a contained environment for Class 3 or 4 activities according to the ordinance of 9 May 2012 on contained use;
- major transit routes;
- railway facilities transporting or transshipping goods;
- gas and oil pipelines.

Each of these installations is a potential source of risk, assessed in a specific context. A map lists all facilities subject to the OPAM and indicates the consultation perimeter within which risk assessments are to be carried out, in parallel with coordination with the competent cantonal or federal authority. In the case of a construction project located within the consultation perimeter, the risk analysis will define what is feasible, subject to the adoption of specific protective measures or constraints on use, when necessary. The coordination required for this purpose is covered by a planning guide (*Coordination aménagement du territoire et prévention des accidents majeurs*⁶⁵).

⁶⁵ <https://www.are.admin.ch/are/fr/home/media-et-publications/publications/strategie-et-planification/planungshilfe-koordination-raumplanung-und-stoerfallvorsorge.html>

Illustration 121: Technological risks in the canton of Geneva. Swiss data relating to the perimeter of companies with major risks and transit routes are confidential and cannot be disclosed.

6.2.11.5. Polluted soils in France

There are no polluted soils listed in the BASOL database at any of the proposed sites. The BASIAS database does not identify any polluted sites at the site locations. If polluted sites exist, they could present a risk for tunnel excavation and the management of excavated material.

6.2.11.6. Polluted soil in Switzerland

Illustration 122: Polluted sites in Switzerland. Source: SITG.

The PB site in Switzerland is not located near any operating area, accident site or storage site listed by the canton of Geneva. The same applies to the PA and PL sites in France. The footprint passes close to certain operating areas.

6.2.12. Population density

Although many of the communities crossed by the footprint are sparsely populated, there are nevertheless a few towns with highly sensitive architectural and landscape contexts. Iterations to determine surface sites have therefore sought to keep them away from residential areas.

The FCC concerns a dynamic area with high economic attractiveness (Illustration 123). The map shows a relatively dense urban fabric compared with the French average, and a relatively dispersed habitation pattern throughout the area. The issue of proximity to residences and human activities appears to be significant throughout the sector.

Illustration 123: Population density in France.

Illustration 124: Map of population density in Switzerland. Source: SITG.

© IGN - Insee 2022

*Illustration 125: Map of average annual population growth between 2014 and 2020 in France.
Source: INSEE 2022.*

*Illustration 126: Variations in Switzerland's permanent resident population over the period 2010-2021.
Source: Office fédéral de la statistique.*

Demographic trends in Switzerland and France (Illustration 125 and Illustration 126) show relatively strong regional growth over the last ten years, particularly in the border area and to the south (Saint-Julien-en-Genève sector).

6.2.13. Demographics and employment

The demographic situation in the areas concerned (Pays de Gex and Haute-Savoie département in France, Geneva canton in Switzerland) is shown in the table below.

Table 22: Demographic situation in the concerned sectors.

	Pays de Gex⁶⁶	Haute-Savoie Department (74)	Canton of Geneva⁶⁷
Population	98 257 (in 2019)	826 094 (in 2019)	508 774 (in 2020)
Population density	242.7 per km ² (in 2019)	188.3 per km ² (in 2019)	1 793 per km ²
Growth rate	2.3% per year	1.2% per year	0.8% per year
Number of households	42 030 (in 2019)	366 281 (in 2019)	206 000 (in 2014)
Percentage of foreigners	32% ⁶⁸ (in 2017)	12.7% ⁶⁹	41%
Number of jobs	20 004 (in 2019)	305 756 (in 2019)	276 000 ⁷⁰ (in 2018)

In both France and Switzerland, the previous maps and the analyses carried out by the Greater Geneva⁷¹ and the Greater Annecy⁷² agglomerations show how dynamic the sector is in terms of population growth forecasts for 2040. Compared with this growth, the number of residents involved in CERN research programs is likely to remain fairly constant.

At present, some 8 800 people from France and Switzerland work in the region for one of the CERN research programs (Illustration 127). Around two-thirds of them live in France, and one-third in Switzerland.

Even taking into account a total workforce of around 15 000 people, including both permanent residents and visiting researchers temporarily present on the campus and sites, this number may seem relatively low compared to the total population of the area, i.e. nearly 1 400 000 inhabitants (Pays de Gex, Haute-Savoie, and canton of Geneva).

⁶⁶ <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/1405599?geo=EPCI-240100750>

⁶⁷ <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/asset/fr/21904077>

⁶⁸ <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3569308?sommaire=3569330&geo=EPCI-240100750>

⁶⁹ <https://www.linternaute.com/ville/haute-savoie/departement-74>

⁷⁰ <https://www.grand-geneve.org/habitants-et-emplois/>

⁷¹ https://www.grand-geneve.org/wp-content/uploads/cahier_19-4_projections_population_et_emplois_pa4.pdf

⁷² Grand Annecy - Projet de territoire, <https://omnibook.com/library/77afe73c-392b-43d8-abad-b5992029a0f4>

Illustration 127: Number of people working at CERN (all levels) by municipality in the FCC region.
Source: CERN.

For the operating phase of FCC-ee, the number of active residents at CERN can be expected to remain stable. However, the split between France (75%) and Switzerland (25%) is likely to be different, as more activities move to Haute-Savoie. Business centres will be more scattered than they are today. Between the end of the LHC operating phase and the start of the FCC-ee operating phase, the number of residents will be temporarily reduced. This will probably be offset by the arrival of employees from the companies completing the underground structures. Only once a layout scenario has been validated can reliable forecasts be made, enabling the development of a civil engineering project at a later stage.

The economic impact will be considerable, even if the number of residents working in scientific research is small in relation to the territory's total population. During the operating phase of FCC-ee, household spending alone will generate an economic impact of around 3.5 billion euros⁷³. This amount can therefore be considered as a potential loss for the regional economy if the FCC program does not go ahead.

⁷³ L. Alix (CNRS) and J. Gutleber (CERN), *La contribution du Future collisionneur circulaire (FCC) à l'économie locale : la valeur des dépenses de consommation*, V3.0, 24 January 2023, FCC-2202071530-JGU : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7564634>

Thanks to the FCC program, nearly 14 500 jobs will be filled or created in France and Switzerland⁷⁴: 6 000 direct project-related jobs in science, engineering, administration, and site management; 8 500 indirect and induced jobs in the two host countries. Around 1 200 jobs are expected to be created in France and 200 in Switzerland during the investment phase (construction and implementation). Nearly 3 400 jobs could be linked to the operating costs of the research infrastructure in the region. Around 1 200 sustainable jobs are planned in the supply sector for the necessary operational resources, such as green energy.

Over the lifetime of the FCC program, some 2 800 sustainable jobs are expected to be linked to tourism (around 250 000 to 300 000 visitors to CERN and FCC per year). With respect to the vitality of the French and Swiss national economies, the creation of 14 500 jobs linked to the FCC would not be insignificant in relation to the total number of jobs in the region, i.e. 600 000. The business sectors that would benefit most would be:

- construction activities;
- general industry;
- manufacturing of materials and products;
- manufacturing of machinery and electrical equipment;
- wholesale and retail trades;
- transport and storage;
- professional, scientific and technical services;
- administrative and support services.

⁷⁴ G. Streicher, “Building CERN’s Future Circular Collider. An Estimation of its Impact on Value Added and Employment”, WIFO, 9 January 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7382706>

6.2.14. Landscape units

Examination of the landscape units (Illustration 128) provides instructive elements that can be incorporated into planning and development projects at an early stage. These initial elements of landscape analysis from an environmental standpoint are very useful for clarifying the analysis of the initial state and will guide future impact studies.

The footprint is integrated in "emerging landscapes", "agrarian landscapes" and "landscapes marked by major facilities" according to the seven types of landscapes defined by the Rhône-Alpes regional landscape observatory⁷⁵.

The architectural design of the sites will take into account the specific landscape features of each of these zones.

Illustration 128: Landscape units in France.

In Switzerland, landscape units are not defined at the cantonal level. A document on the cantonal conception of the landscape, currently in progress, will provide additional insight in later phases of the study.

⁷⁵ <http://www.auvergne-rhone-alpes.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/observatoire-des-paysages-en-rhone-alpes-a10298.html>

6.2.15. Landscape protection

There are no classified or listed sites either along the FCC footprint or in the vicinity of surface sites (Illustration 129). Furthermore, none of the sites are located in the Haut-Jura regional nature park (RNP).

Illustration 129: Landscape protection in France.

In Geneva, a multitude of protected sectors and entities make up the canton's landscape that is of importance to its natural and cultural heritage and its identity.

The PB site is directly impacted by historical routes. Other protected or classified areas are not concerned by the PB surface site (Illustration 130).

Illustration 130: Landscape protection in the canton of Geneva.

6.2.16. Urban planning documents

6.2.16.1. Provisions relating to the “Montagne” (mountain) law in France

The entire footprint of the FCC, in all municipalities, is subject to the “Montagne” (mountain) law and the provisions of the French urban planning code (articles L 122-5 to 7).

Illustration 131: Urban planning regulations in municipalities and territories subject to the “Montagne” law.

The table above (Illustration 131) shows the regulations governing urban planning in the municipalities and territories concerned by the “Montagne” law:

- urbanisation consistent with currently urbanised areas;
- preservation of land necessary to maintain and develop agricultural and forestry activities;
- preservation of spaces, landscapes, and environments characteristic of the natural and cultural mountain heritage.

Regulatory exceptions

Subject to confirmation by the DDT (Departmental directorate of the territory), CERN would be concerned by two clauses of exception to the “Montagne” law. These regulations do not apply to ⁷⁶:

- public installations or facilities incompatible with the neighbouring inhabited areas;
- installations and works required for scientific establishments (...) and public services other than ski lifts, if their location in these areas corresponds to an imperative technical need (article L122-3 of the French urban planning code).

Consequently, the DDT will determine whether or not the urban planning regulations set out in articles L 122-5 to 7 of the French urban planning code should apply to FCC surface sites.

Illustration 132: Current status of urban planning documents in France (2020) and Switzerland.

⁷⁶ https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/fiche_1_le_champ_d_application_des_dispositions_d_urbanisme_specifiques_aux_zones_de_montagne_v1.pdf

In France, the majority of the sites are in municipalities with approved urban planning documents: PLU or PLUi (see Illustration 132).

A close eye needs to be kept on any changes to urban planning documents (revisions, modifications). Similarly, a close eye will be kept on developments in SCoTs, as they can influence the orientation of PLUs.

6.2.16.2. Territorial development in Switzerland

In Switzerland, the cantonal master plan (PDCn), the central instrument of cantonal land-use policy, is the reference document for Geneva. Its aim is to coordinate activities that influence the organization of the territory. It serves as a reference for the canton's territorial development objectives, the coordination of sectoral policies and the actions required to implement them. It defines the desired territorial development and determines the necessary planning measures in terms of urbanization, mobility, management of rural areas and natural environments, and resource management.

The PDCn is binding for the authorities. It regulates the coordination of the planning policies of the Confederation, neighbouring cantons, and adjacent regions. It provides the framework for local planning and activities that are under the responsibility of the municipalities.

The cantonal master plan for 2030 was adopted by the Grand Conseil on 20 September 2013, and approved by the Federal Council on 29 April 2015.

It underwent an initial update adopted by the Grand Conseil on 10 April 2019, and approved by the Confederation on 18 January 2021.

A second update (minor) was adopted by the Conseil d'État on 1 March 2023, and approved by the Confederation on 23 August 2023⁷⁷.

The cantonal master plan will shortly be undergoing a complete revision, and include an outlook to the year 2050. It is scheduled to come into force in 2027. The revision of the cantonal master plan focuses on cross-border cooperation and the ecological transition⁷⁸.

An FCC construction project should be mentioned for information purposes, as it is a project of federal importance that will be taken into account in the 2050 cantonal master plan, as well as in the municipal master plans revised in light of this new version of the cantonal master plan.

⁷⁷ <https://www.ge.ch/dossier/amenager-territoire/planification-cantonale-regionale/plan-directeur-cantonal-2030>

⁷⁸ <https://www.ge.ch/document/vision-territoriale-transfrontaliere-2050>

6.2.17. Noise

6.2.17.1. French regulations

The following values (Table 23) are taken from French regulations and are of general application. Compared with the initial noise levels (background noise), the project owner is required to respect the maximum values for the additional noise generated by the project (emergence) at dwellings located near noise sources, whether they be temporary (construction sites) or permanent (in operation). These maximum values depend on the period (day or night), duration and composition of the frequencies. Where necessary, the project owner will carry out initial acoustic measurements to characterise the background noise before the project is carried out.

Table 23: Noise reference values in France.

Permissible emergence values: + 5 dB(A) during the day (7am-10pm) + 3 dB(A) during the night (10pm-7am) Corrective term based on cumulative duration: + 0 dB(A) if D>8h + 6 dB(A) if D<1mn Regulatory emergence by frequency bands: + 5 dB(A) for 125 and 250 Hz + 7 dB(A) for 500 to 4 000 Hz			
CUMULATIVE DURATION onset of the noise in question: T	CORRECTIVE TERM In decibels A	Limit value for overall emergence, in dBA	
		At night	During the day
T ≤ 1 minute	+ 6	+ 9	+ 11
1 minute < T ≤ 5 minutes	+ 5	+ 8	+ 10
5 minutes < T ≤ 20 minutes	+ 4	+ 7	+ 9
20 minutes < T ≤ 2 hours	+ 3	+ 6	+ 8
2 hours < T ≤ 4 hours	+ 2	+ 5	+ 7
4 hours < T ≤ 8 hours	+ 1	+ 4	+ 6
T > 8 hours	0	+ 3	+ 5

6.2.17.2. Swiss Regulations

To assess and limit noise pollution, noise protection legislation defines planning values⁷⁹, immission limit values and alert values for different types of noise. These values are adapted to the degree of sensitivity of the exposed area, and are lower at night than during the day.

Exposure limit values are set down in the noise protection ordinance (OPB) and are based on the environmental protection law (LPE). It defines three types of exposure limit values:

- The planning values apply to the construction of new noise-emitting facilities and roads, and to the demarcation and equipping of construction zones for noise-sensitive buildings (housing).
- The immission limit values define the thresholds above which noise significantly disturbs the well-being of the population. They apply to existing noise-emitting installations and to building permits for noise-sensitive buildings (housing).
- Alert values are a criterion used to define the urgency of remediation and the installation of noise-proof windows.

Exposure limit values are more stringent for purely residential areas than for those where handicraft activities are also permitted (degrees of sensitivity shown in table). These values must be measured/modelled at sensitive receivers (frame of open window).

The following exposure limit values (Table 24) are expressed in dB(A).

Table 24: Exposure limit values of the noise protection ordinance (OPB). Source: Federal office for the environment (FOEN), Switzerland.

Degree of sensitivity		Planning value (VP) in dB(A)		Immission limit value (VLI) in dB(A)		Alert value (VA) in dB(A)	
		Day	Night	Day	Night	Day	Night
I	Leisure	50	40	55	45	65	60
II	Home	55	45	60	50	70	65
III	Housing/handicraft	60	50	65	55	70	65
IV	Industry	65	55	70	60	75	70

According to the land registry, RDPPF (degree of sensitivity to noise of canton of Geneva, <https://ge.ch/sitg/fiche/0576>), the PB surface site in Presinge is located in a sensitivity level III zone (zones accepting businesses generating moderate annoyance).

⁷⁹ <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/fr/home/themes/bruit/info-specialistes/exposition-au-bruit/valeurs-limites-pour-le-bruit/valeurs-limites-dexposition-au-bruit.html>

6.2.18. Networks and Systems

6.2.18.1. Hydrology

The FCC needs water for the accelerator equipment cooling systems. The technical solutions will not be known until shortly before the construction of this research infrastructure, so that we can take full advantage of technical developments and improvements in cooling system efficiency. A rough estimate of maximum water requirements, based on consumption by CERN's existing accelerator cooling systems, provides a first estimate. The water supply scheme for cooling is based on the assumption that the water drawn from Lake Geneva by Services Industriels de Genève (SIG) in Switzerland, which CERN currently uses, will continue to be available. This was confirmed by an exchange between CERN and SIG in 2022. Then, in August 2023, SIG confirmed the technical feasibility of the link to point 8 of the LHC for the PA site of the FCC. To make the distribution of water along the entire length of the accelerator technically easier and economically more advantageous, two additional water supply points are planned in France. To this end, a specific territorial study during the technical development phase is planned, which will integrate in particular the available quantitative management plans for water resources (PGRE).

6.2.18.2. Electricity

The specific needs of the FCC will only be known after the detailed technical development phase, so that we can take advantage of technical developments in systems designed to improve energy efficiency. According to the results of the preliminary technical feasibility study carried out by RTE⁸⁰ (which manages France's electrical grid), the FCC's connection to the high-power electrical infrastructure calls for three supply points in France at this stage. A power supply point in Switzerland is also foreseen to improve reliability and optimise operation, with the possibility of obtaining renewable energy from additional sources, but its technical and administrative feasibility remains to be studied.

At this stage, the PA31 footprint is crossed by various power lines, mainly 63 kV and 225 kV. Two 400 kV lines cross the PA31 footprint from west to east (Illustration 133). The 400 kV lines pass close to the PL sites (Ain department) and the PF and PH sites (Haute-Savoie department). A major distribution station (Cornier) is located close to the PD and PF sites.

Electricity needs are higher at the PL and PH sites, as these are designed to house the radiofrequency systems that accelerate particles in the collider. These are the two locations foreseen for connection to the 400 kV network. A third supply point is planned for the PD site, to provide a balanced supply of electricity to other infrastructures and equipment.

RTE, which was entrusted with the task of managing the electricity transmission grid in France⁸¹ through a public service contract dated as of 24 October 2005⁸², which includes, among other things, the environmental integration of the grid (consultation, protection of landscapes and natural and urbanised environments) and safeguarding the public grid, is responsible for analysing the connection while taking into account technical choices; overseeing the hook-up process; and carrying out the necessary administrative procedures (connection agreement, grid access contract). RTE also carries out the work once the hook-up agreement has been signed⁸³.

⁸⁰ RTE, *Étude exploratoire N. 22-1022 pour le raccordement du FCC*, 15 July 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13364463>

⁸¹ Decree no. 2005-1069 of 30 August 2005 approving the status of the company RTE EDF Transport: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000000812363>

⁸² Public service contract between the French State and EDF: https://cpdp.debatpublic.fr/cpdp-epr/docs/pdf/dossier_mo/contrat-service-public-etat-edf-oct2005.pdf

⁸³ RTE, *Instruction des demandes de raccordement, version 2*, 17 octobre 2019, https://www.services-rte.com/files/live/sites/services-rte/files/documentsLibrary/DTR%201.4.1%20Proc%C3%A9dure%20Racc%20Conso%20L342-2%20v19%2010%2017_fr

For the supply of electricity during the construction phase, requests for hook-ups to local networks will be made directly to the relevant national distributors (e.g. Enedis in France and SIG in Switzerland). According to the information provided by Herrenknecht, the TBM manufacturer, electricity requirements are 3.7 MVA for a construction site using a single TBM and 7.4 MVA for a construction site with two TBMs. The working hypothesis presented below in Table 25 still needs to be fine-tuned with the civil engineering companies, who will be selected shortly before the start of construction. The electrical power required during the construction phase will be determined using the hypothesis adopted for the organisation of the TBMs, which will only be known with certainty shortly before the launch of the public works contracts.

Table 25: Working hypothesis for temporary connection to regional networks during the construction phase.

Site	Location	Manager	Type of hook-up	Mains power
PA	Ferney-Voltaire, France	Enedis	Normal, with emergency line only	7.0 – 13.8 MVA (= 400 A in 20 kV)
PB	Choulex, Switzerland	SIG	Normal, with emergency line only	3 MVA – 7.0 MVA (= 200 A in 20 kV)
PD	Nangy, France	Enedis	Normal, with emergency line only	7.0 – 13.8 MVA (= 400 A in 20 kV)
PF	Eteaux, France	Enedis	Normal, with emergency line only	3 MVA (= 100 A in 20 kV)
PG	Charvonnex or Groisy, France	Énergie et Services de Seyssel	Normal, with emergency line only	13.8 MVA (= 400 A in 20 kV)
PH	Cercier, France	Enedis	Normal, with emergency line only	3 MVA (= 100 A in 20 kV)
PJ	Dingy-en-Vuache, France	Enedis	Normal, with emergency line only	13.8 MVA (= 400 A in 20 kV)
PL	Challex, France	Enedis	Normal, with emergency line only	3 MVA – 7.0 MVA (= 200 A in 20 kV)

*Illustration 133: Existing or planned electricity grids in France and Switzerland within the FCC perimeter.
Sources: SITG 2023 for Switzerland, available for consultation and extraction for free use (CAD_ELEMENT_CONDUITE layer); for France, Open Data Réseaux Énergies (ODRÉ, <https://opendata.reseaux-energies.fr/>).*

6.2.18.3. Rail and road transport

Illustration 134: Transport networks.

The road network is dense along the FCC footprint. Nonetheless, some areas are still far from major road networks (Illustration 134).

The site-by-site analysis presents an initial examination of possible road and rail links and their associated constraints.

This analysis will need to be supplemented by traffic studies and an analysis of possible routes to meet construction site requirements, in order to help characterise the extent of transport-related issues, including disturbances for local residents (dust emissions, noise, traffic jams).

6.2.19. Heat recovery and reuse

The FCC infrastructure cooling system will use non-potable water to cool many of the subsystems⁸⁴ of the particle accelerator, the experiments and the technical infrastructure. This water circulates in closed circuits, absorbs heat, then dissipates it in cooling towers, where some of the hot water evaporates. The water enters the cooling facility at a temperature of around 20°C, and exits at 50°C. This heat can be recovered for use in urban heating networks, for example for residential, tertiary or even industrial heating. Table 26 provides estimates of the amount of heat available year-round, at each site and according to the operating mode, as well as the potential heat consumption within a radius of around 5 km.

Table 26: Potential heat supply to each site according to the status of the studies in 2023.

Site	Heat production during accelerator operation, corresponding to capacity during first phase of operation (Z)	Heat consumption near sites
PA	138 GWh	1,678 GWh
PB	15 GWh	657 GWh
PD	138 GWh	49 GWh
PF	15 GWh	59 GWh
PG	138 GWh	49 GWh
PH	230 GWh	15 GWh
PJ	138 GWh	21 GWh
PL	25 GWh	34 GWh
Total	837 GWh	> 2 000 GWh

Heat production fluctuates from week to week. The indicated GWh is a cumulative total for one year.

A technical-economic study of heat recovery is underway with an industrial partner. The methodology followed is explained in the report written by this partner⁸⁵.

The potential consumption within a 5 km radius therefore justifies an analysis of the integration of a heat reuse concept into the design of the research infrastructure. However, heat reuse depends on the commitment and active cooperation of stakeholders in the concerned territories.

⁸⁴ Magnets, power converters, radiofrequency amplifiers, cryogenic refrigeration equipment, ventilation systems, etc.

⁸⁵ A. Guiavarch, *Étude de valorisation de la chaleur disponible du FCC, Partie I : Étude du potentiel de consommation*, Ginger Burgeap, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11192000>

6.2.20. Water resources: estimated needs and regulations

6.2.20.1. Estimated water needs

The non-potable water is mainly used to cool several of the particle accelerator's subsystems and experiments. These subsystems include, but are not limited to, the resistive magnets guiding the particle beam lines, the power converters supplying the magnets, the radiofrequency amplifiers supplying the radiofrequency cavities that accelerate the particle beam lines, the cryogenic refrigeration equipment for the superconducting radiofrequency cavities such as compressors and pumps, the electronic systems for the experiment detectors, the data processing infrastructures and the ventilation systems. The magnet water-cooling system also absorbs the heat generated by synchrotron radiation, i.e. the energy lost by the particle beam lines when they are forced by the magnetic fields to follow a circular path.

Cooling water is especially necessary during operation of the particle collider. The required flow rate depends on the technical design of the particle accelerator subsystems, the water cooling systems and the operating phase of the collider. Technical choices will generally be made at a later design stage (around 2035) or, depending on R&D, will only be validated a few years before the start of operation (around 2040). Water requirements vary significantly depending on the operating mode of the particle collider. Flow rates are low in the first few years, then gradually increase to reach peak rates in the last five years of operation, when particle collider performance is at its highest. At this early stage of scenario development, it is only possible to give a rough estimate of a high flow value, based on current technologies, to determine whether a water cooling system for the new particle collider is compatible in principle with territorial constraints.

Two different water-cooling system options are available. Depending on territorial constraints and environmental impacts, a combination of these two options may also be applicable (Illustration 135). In conclusion, there are three possible options, each offering different advantages.

The first option is an open-circuit cooling system in which water is extracted from a natural source (e.g. a river or lake) and pumped to a heat exchanger that removes heat from a separate cooling system, which in turn removes the thermal load from the particle accelerator equipment. Water from the external cooling system is cooled by evaporation in a cooling tower, then returned to a river or lake. This option requires the continuous flow of large quantities of water, but as almost all this water is returned to the watercourses, very low net consumption can be maintained. It requires the installation of large-diameter underground pipes, and energy consumption for pumping the water can be significant, depending on the distance between the surface site where the water is needed and the location where the natural water is extracted from the river or lake.

The second option is a closed-circuit cooling system. Natural water extracted from a river or lake is pumped into a heat exchanger, where it absorbs heat from a separate water cooling system for the particle accelerator equipment. The water is then directed to a cooling tower, where its temperature is reduced during the evaporation process. However, unlike in an open-loop concept, the water is not immediately returned to its original watercourse, but recirculated several times between the heat exchanger and the cooling tower. In so doing, the concentration of dissolved matter in the water gradually increases. To reduce this concentration, the circuit is drained and filled with make-up water. Most of the extracted water eventually evaporates, and only a small quantity is discharged into the sewer system after treatment. Water supply and drain flow rates can be further reduced by demineralisation processes. These techniques can be applied either on the make-up water or when draining. In the latter case, the treated water can be reused as make-up water. Compared with an open-loop recirculation system, the closed-loop system consumes less electrical energy and requires smaller pipe diameters and fewer buried pipes outside surface sites. The waste heat produced by the process can be recovered and used as a valuable energy source for public and residential heating, as well as for agricultural and industrial uses.

Illustration 135: Open-loop (left) and closed-loop with recirculation (right) water-cooling concepts. These two systems use two separate water cooling systems: the water system that extracts the thermal load from the particle accelerator systems transfers the heat to a second water system that passes through a cooling tower. In the open-loop scenario (left), water is extracted from a river or lake, flows freely through the cooling tower and is discharged back into the source. In the closed-loop scenario (right), water is extracted from a river or lake and circulated several times in the cooling tower. The system is drained into the sewage system and filled with make-up water when the concentration of dissolved solids in the water becomes too high.

For the closed-loop recirculation scenario, and based on the known characteristics of the existing pumping station currently supplying CERN with cooling water⁸⁶, all the water needed to cool a particle collider such as the FCC can in principle be supplied from Lake Geneva in a single location, via the current connection from Switzerland to the LHC Point 8 surface site, close to the PA site of the FCC in Ferney-Voltaire, France. However, such a scenario would require large-diameter, long stainless steel pipes capable of handling high volumes, flows and pressure levels, and would entail additional costs. In addition, large components corresponding to the pressure and volume characteristics would be required around the entire circumference of the particle accelerator. This scenario therefore presents difficulties for the implementation of the project in terms of investment and operating costs and, above all, severe constraints in terms of underground space (Illustration 136).

Illustration 136: A system that relies on a single water intake point requires larger pipes, made from higher-quality materials and more expensive than a system with three water intake points. The drawback of this system, in addition to its higher cost and complexity, is that it leaves much less available space for installing particle accelerator equipment in the tunnel.

⁸⁶ Meeting between CERN and SIG (Geneva, Switzerland), 5 October 2022.

For this reason, three additional water extraction points are planned (see also Illustration 137):

- 1) In Lake Geneva, via the existing Services Industriels de Genève (SIG) water supply connection to Point 8 of the CERN LHC;
- 2) In a new water intake to be planned and built in cooperation with the STEP in Scientrier, in the Nangy zone;
- 3) In a new water intake to be planned and built in the Rhone, in the zone between Pougny and Vulbens.

Illustration 137: Initial working hypothesis for water supply. The hourly flow rates shown are valid only during operation of the collider, i.e. around 270 days a year. The maximum water needs correspond to a "ttbar" operation mode and "full load".

The initial scenario (2018) indicated a total maximum water extraction of around 5.6 million m³ per year, of which 725 000 m³ would be discharged, corresponding to a net consumption of around 4.9 million m³ per year spread over around 270 days.

Further study led to the design of a system that requires only around 2.8 million m³ of water per year, of which 325 000 m³ is discharged, corresponding to a **net consumption of around 2.5 million m³ per year**. This scenario (Illustration 138) would also enable supply via a single extraction point from Lake Geneva, or water distribution from three extraction points with significantly lower flows and pressure levels, and therefore far fewer constraints (Illustration 139). This approach also makes it possible to foresee seasonal water storage reservoirs.

Illustration 138: Scenario for supplying water to the FCC-ee, with a single existing extraction point ("reduced" scenario) in Lake Geneva (Switzerland) connected to Point 8 at the CERN LHC in France (May 2024). Option 1. The maximum water needs correspond to a "ttbar" operation mode and "full load".

Illustration 139: Water distribution scenario with three extraction points (one existing point in Switzerland and two to be created in France) for reference scenario PA31-4.0 (May 2024). Option 2. The maximum water needs correspond to a "ttbar" operation mode and "full load".

By way of comparison, CERN extracted 3.2 million m³ of water from Lake Geneva in 2022⁸⁷. As a result, the **FCC-ee water consumption scenario indicates water needs that are lower than CERN's water consumption in 2022**. Moreover, the provided figures are for a high estimate of needs. Most of the time, FCC-ee operating methods will require much less water extraction. Heat recovery and supply will further reduce consumption.

For Switzerland, these scenarios were discussed with Services Industriels de Genève (SIG) on 30 August 2023 in Geneva. Water cooling based on current closed-circuit technology has been deemed compatible with territorial conditions for the particle collider operating phase with the highest performance (see Table 27). Water can be supplied within the existing contractual framework either by building a new, short connection of around 200 m with a 500 mm nominal diameter between the Tuileries-La Berne pipe and Point 8 of the LHC, or by using two internal CERN lines which would require upgrading.

In France, the scenario was presented to the Haute-Savoie department and the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region at a special meeting held on 29 August 2023 in Annecy. The scenario with two extraction points in the Rhone and Arve rivers is preferred.

Table 27: Water extraction needs in the worst-case scenario and available capacity for make-up water supply. The indicated hourly needs are for the machine's highest performance level and for the operating phase, i.e. around 270 days a year.

Option	Site	Water needs in worst-case scenario (rounded average in m ³ /h)	Available volumetric water flow (in m ³ /h for 365 days a year)	Water flow consumption limit (in m ³ /h for 365 days a year)	Overcapacity factor (available/need)	Water source
Overall need		Between approx. 353 m ³ /h and 630 m ³ /h for 270 operating days per year.				
2	PA	143 m ³ /h	5 400 m ³ /h	1 080 m ³ /h	8	Lake Geneva ⁸⁸
1	PA reduced	630 m ³ /h			2	
2	PD	201 m ³ /h	232 200 m ³ /h	11 610 m ³ /h	57	Arve ⁸⁹ or STEP in Scientrier
1	PD reduced	No water intake			None	
2	PJ	286 m ³ /h	1 288 800 m ³ /h	64 400 m ³ /h	225	Rhone ⁹⁰
1	PJ reduced	No water intake			None	

⁸⁷ <https://hse.cern.fr/rapport-environnement-2021-2022>

⁸⁸ Technical limitation due to the capacity of the Vengeron pumping station and the allocation of pumping capacity to CERN.

⁸⁹ <https://www.hydro.eaufrance.fr/sitehydro/V0205422/synthese>

⁹⁰ <https://www.hydro.eaufrance.fr/sitehydro/V1000010/synthese>

The hourly intake flow required in the worst-case scenario (see table above) refers to the "ttbar" operating mode over the last five years of a 15-year scientific research program. The hourly or per-second needs cannot be directly compared with the hourly or per-second volumetric capacities of the water sources, since the particle collider is only operated for a limited period each year, and consumption during other operating modes is significantly lower than indicated (for example, consumption for operating modes Z, WW and HZ would be one-third lower than for operating mode "ttbar").

The water needs described above include four experiments at points PA, PD, PG and PJ, in case the particle physics community should call for the scientific research program to be expanded. **Actual water flow may be lower than the peak values indicated.** Nor is water consumption constant throughout the year, as cooling water is mainly needed for particle collider operation and not for maintenance, upgrades and repairs. Consumption also varies according to weather conditions and the possibility of providing residual heat.

The reference scenario calls for a closed-circuit recirculating water cooling system with evaporator towers. This approach limits water extraction, but imposes constraints on the use of the water passing through the cooling system. Depending on the technical feasibility, the discharged water can be reused to supply watercourses and reservoirs in the vicinity of the sites. In this approach, the infrastructure brings additional water to the zones where the surface sites are located. Studies should be carried out in cooperation with local players to develop these synergies between the FCC and the territory, particularly on the left bank in Geneva and in the Rhone sector.

The final technical choice will therefore also be made according to possible territorial opportunities.

The **maximum annual volume of water withdrawn** during the highest performance operating mode is **around 2.8 million m³**, 50% less than the initial hypothesis of 5.6 million^{m³}. Approximately **325 000 m³ of water**, or **11% of the total, is returned**. This also represents an improvement on the initial working hypothesis of a discharge of 725 000 m³, **or 13% of the total quantity of water returned**.

By way of comparison, **the peak annual net water consumption in the reference scenario is around 2.5 million m³ for the operating mode with the highest performance level**. This also represents a 49% reduction compared with the initial working hypothesis.

By way of comparison, 544 million m³ of water evaporate from Lake Geneva every year^{91,92} and 7.4 billion m³ of water flow out of the lake via the Rhone every year. The average flow of the Arve River in Bonneville is 232 200 m³/h, whereas operation of the FCC would require 100 to 200 m³/h (supply option 2). The Bellecombe/Scientrier wastewater treatment plant (Syndicat des Eaux de Rocailles et Bellecombe) discharges a flow of treated water ranging from approximately 200 to 500 m³/h into the Arve River. A study is underway to assess whether it would be possible to reuse this treated water, provided that a pre-treatment is in place before use to reduce the residual dissolved calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) in the water.

Overall water consumption will be further reduced if residual heat recovery systems are foreseen from the outset, and if heat consumers can be reliably identified and connected to such a system, as less evaporation will be required.

⁹¹ https://www.epfl.ch/schools/enac/education/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/34_Fourrier_Karpushov.pdf

⁹² Hydrological Atlas of Switzerland: <https://atlashydrologique.ch/?language=switch>

The first ten years of operation are characterised by significantly lower cooling needs. In addition, it should be pointed out that the particle collider is not in operation for around a third of the year, that technological advances in cooling will take place over the next 20 years before the collider is commissioned, that hybrid systems with lower evaporation needs (closed/open loop, open-air cooling, process optimisation) can be implemented, and that residual heat supply systems for public and private heat consumers can be foreseen in the vicinity from the outset.

At this stage, from a quantitative point of view, the reference scenario for water consumption is technically, financially and territorially feasible, since water extraction and consumption represent quantities lower than CERN's actual consumption in 2022. The availability of a supply representing twice the total needs was confirmed by SIG in 2023.

However, during the subsequent phases of the studies, it will be necessary to verify aspects relating to the sharing of water with the other players who use these same water sources, particularly with regard to related catchment areas that currently experience chronic deficits (Pays de Gex, La Roche-sur-Foron and possibly the Usses). Numerous synergies can be considered with local authorities in the vicinity of surface sites in terms of reuse of residual heat and discharged water.

6.2.20.2. French regulations on water extraction

Regulatory procedure:

The potentially concerned subject areas in the list of operations subject to authorisation or declaration under articles L214-1 to L214-3 of the French environment code⁹³ are described below. Regulations vary depending on whether water is extracted from **groundwater** or **surface water**.

The following elements from the list are available online⁹⁴.

For all the subject areas described below, in application of article R214-42 of the French environment code, it is necessary to examine the **water extraction points for the entire project on French territory, on Swiss territory and in all the territories concerned**, to determine whether the project requires an authorisation or a declaration per the regulations.

If the extractions are from groundwater, the potentially concerned subject areas are:

Article R.214-1, 1.1.1.0. Boreholes, drilling, including pumping tests, creation of shafts or underground works, not intended for domestic use, carried out with a view to **search for or monitor groundwater**, or **with a view to temporarily or permanently extract groundwater**, including accompanying water tables of watercourses (**declaration**).

Comment: this point concerns the drilling of exploratory boreholes and pumping tests to study the borehole's production capacity without overuse of the resources concerned by the extractions.

Article R.214-1, 1.1.2.0. Permanent or temporary extractions from a borehole, shaft or underground structure in an aquifer system, not including accompanying water tables of watercourses, by pumping, drainage, diversion or any other process, the total extracted volume being:

1° **Greater than or equal to 200 000 m³/year (authorisation);**

2° Greater than 10 000 m³/year but less than 200 000 m³/year (declaration).

If extractions are made from surface water, the relevant subject areas to be considered, depending on the situation, are as follows:

Article R.214-1, 1.2.1.0. With the exception of extractions covered by an agreement with the beneficiary of the allocated flow as set forth in article L. 214-9, **extractions and the facilities and works enabling the extraction, including by diversion, of water from a watercourse, its accompanying water table or a body of water or canal fed by this watercourse or water table:**

1° **With a total maximum capacity greater than or equal to 1 000 m³/hour or 5% of the flow rate of the watercourse** or, failing which, of the total supply rate for the canal or water body (**authorisation**).

Comment: at present, the FCC is not affected by this situation, as the total extraction for the project will be significantly less than 1 000 m³/h (needs of around 650 m³/h for a period of around 270 days) and significantly less for extractions from the Rhone (maximum need of 290 m³/h) and the Arve (maximum need of 200 m³/h) if additional extraction points are available.

⁹³ Commonly known as the "water law" list.

⁹⁴ https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_lc/LEGIARTI000043136646/

Article R.214-1, 1.2.2.0. With the exception of extractions covered by an agreement with the beneficiary of the allocated flow as set forth in article L. 214-9, **extractions and the facilities and works enabling the extraction of water, from a watercourse, its accompanying water table or a body of water or canal fed by this watercourse or water table, when more than half of the watercourse's flow in low-water periods results from artificial replenishment.** However, in the case of the Seine, Loire, Marne and Yonne, authorisation is only required when the extraction capacity exceeds 80 m³/h (**authorisation**).

Comment: this covers special cases, if applicable.

Article R.214-1, 1.3.1.0. With the exception of extractions covered by an agreement with the beneficiary of the allocated flow as set forth in article L. 214-9, constructions, facilities and works enabling the **total extraction of water in a zone where permanent quantitative allocation measures instituted**, notably under article L. 211-2, have foreseen the lowering of thresholds:

1° Capacity greater than or equal to 8 m³/h (**authorisation**).

Comment: the FCC is not currently concerned by this situation. It would be concerned by at least one PH abstraction carried out in the water distribution zone (ZRE) for surface water and groundwater in the Usses basin. Any groundwater extractions from the Genevois water table would also fall within the scope of a ZRE.

Lastly, procedures concerning water are part of an **overall approach involving a single authorisation for an indivisible, cross-border project.**

Illustration 140: Examples of existing dams in the Vulbens and Pougny sectors between France and Switzerland.

Water treatment and draining scenarios must be agreed on with the relevant administrative departments in the host countries. Scenarios for the supply of waste heat from cooling systems should be drawn up in cooperation with local public administration departments. A co-construction of this type with the region on this specific subject would be the most effective approach to designing and implementing the presented scenario.

6.2.21. Electricity needs and supply

6.2.21.1. Electricity needs

The FCC-ee scientific research program is based on different collider operating modes. Each mode uses a different equipment configuration. This equipment (acceleration systems via superconducting radiofrequency cavity, electrical energy conversion systems and cryogenic cooling systems) will be installed progressively, in line with the multi-year operating schedule, during the maintenance and upgrade phases planned for these activities. Each configuration is characterised by different electrical power needs (see Table 28), which serve as the basis for average consumption estimates.

Table 28: Electrical power supply needs. During each operating mode (Z, W, H, ttbar, HH), particles are accelerated to different energy levels as part of the research program's scientific investigations. As a result, energy consumption varies according to operating mode. Technical feasibility studies have enabled us to reduce power requirements by almost 45% between 2020 (initial hypothesis) and 2023.

Phase	Beam line energy	Duration of phase	Minimum and maximum power needs	
			Initial estimates	2024 estimates
Construction	No operation	9 years	20 MW - 50 MW	16 MW - 64 MW
Z operating mode	45.5 GeV	4 years	65 MW - 240 MW	30 MW - 222 MW
WW operating mode	80 GeV	2 years	70 MW - 265 MW	33 MW - 247 MW
ZH operating mode	120 GeV	3 years	70 MW - 294 MW	34 MW - 273 MW
"ttbar" operating mode	175 GeV	5 years	80 MW - 350 MW	40 MW - 350 MW
HH operating mode	182.5 GeV	1 year (optional)	50 MW - 384 MW	41 MW - 357 MW
		Total	20 MW - 384 MW	16 MW - 357 MW

The collider operates on a yearly schedule, with a limited period of beam line operation for physics research. The program also includes phases for equipment testing and start-up, machine performance optimisation and routine maintenance (Table 29). Depending on the operating mode, electrical energy consumption varies from year to year.

At this stage of the study, it is only possible to put a figure on approximate, not optimised, consumption. It has been possible to commission grid connection studies in Europe and Switzerland, which have provided the relevant entities (such as RTE⁹⁵ in France and Swissgrid⁹⁶ in Switzerland) with elements in order to specify feasibility conditions, including: available and required transmission line capacities; the planning for the high-capacity substations upstream of distribution within the research infrastructure; national and international energy supply options; the integration of the project into national and cross-border power distribution; and the development of the necessary measures to guarantee stable energy supply during the operating program.

Table 29: Research infrastructure operations during the year are characterised by different situations. Each situation requires different energy consumption.

Activity	Number of days	Energy needs
Maintenance and regular updates	120	Minimum infrastructure level
Stops following incidents, for necessary machine access and between operating cycles	46	Minimum infrastructure level + standby systems
Equipment testing, preparation for operation and system optimisation	60	Minimum level of infrastructure + a certain number of standby systems and systems required at reduced power (20-50% depending on equipment installed)
Beam line in operation for scientific research	139	100% depending on operating mode and equipment installed

Following these preliminary and exploratory studies, the project participants will develop concepts to optimise the energy performance of the accelerator's equipment and to improve operations based on information provided by electricity infrastructure operators and energy suppliers.

⁹⁵ <https://www.services-rte.com/fr/decouvrez-nos-offres-de-service/raccorder-une-installation-de-production.html>

⁹⁶ <https://www.swissgrid.ch/fr/home/projects/approval-process.html>

This approach will be based on the usual Avoid-Reduce-Compensate methodology.

- **Avoid:** the overriding goal is to limit consumption according to a cost-benefit analysis, which includes, for example: the research infrastructure layout with two or four experiments; the limiting of maximum power, which will have impacts on luminosity and extending the duration of the research program; and ensuring that systems do not consume energy when not in use.
- **Reduce:** this means to optimise system efficiency and reduce losses. This includes, for example, improving the efficiency of electrical energy conversion for radiofrequency, reducing losses in internal distribution and equipment, energy recovery and storage, smart consumption based on needs (e.g. for ventilation and cooling), and developing systems that can switch more easily and quickly between operating modes (standby or operating mode).
- **Compensate:** lastly, the goal of compensating is, on the one hand, to recover, store and supply renewable energy for society, and on the other hand, to develop synergies for the transition to green energy in Europe, increase renewable energy capacity and cooperate internationally for the supply of renewable energy. Examples of compensation, with direct local economic benefits, include the use of waste heat in industrial processes (cheese production, etc.), for greenhouse operations, crop cultivation and the heating of public establishments such as hospitals, schools and shopping centres.

All these measures will need to be improved over the fifteen years of the technical design and construction phases. They are an effective way of limiting electricity consumption and its impact.

With regard to the various phases of the collider throughout the research program, the initial electrical power needs, before optimisation, are presented in Illustration 141. Maximum needs are only necessary during the "ttbar" operating phase, and during an optional phase at the end of the program (HH) when all the radiofrequency equipment is installed. On average, during the scientific research phase, the FCC-ee **would consume approximately 1.3 TWh per year. Over its entire lifetime, its average electricity consumption would be around 1 TWh per year.** By way of comparison, medium-sized offshore wind farms with a capacity of 600 MW, such as Kriegers Flak⁹⁷ (Denmark) or Dunkerque⁹⁸, produce around 2.5 TWh of electricity per year at a cost of 44 euros/MWh (2021 prices), which corresponds to the electricity needs of around 500 000 households.

⁹⁷ https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Parc_éolien_de_Kriegers_Flak

⁹⁸ <https://www.edf-renouvelables.com/poursuite-du-developpement-du-projet-eolien-en-mer-de-dunkerque-et-de-son-raccordement-electrique-suite-au-debat-public/>

Illustration 141: Initial estimate of FCC-ee electricity needs over the years, including the construction phase, in TWh per year. Consumption figures are for informational purposes and will evolve as technical systems are designed.

6.2.21.2. Energy supply

With the aim of establishing an energy sobriety plan in line with the regional climate plans of France and Switzerland, the international community leading the FCC study is committed to seeking solutions to supply the research infrastructure with sustainable energy. To this end, at this stage in the study, studies have been carried out with industry partners with expertise in the field (McKinsey and Accenture) to select renewable energy supply options. Another goal of these studies is to develop an energy supply scenario with competitive prices, which is possible given the predictability of consumption and CERN's willingness to make a very long-term commitment, supported by many countries.

The analysis carried out by Johannes Gutleber⁹⁹ shows that, in principle, it is already possible to supply the FCC with renewable energy at affordable prices for 60% to 80% of its needs. In fact, in 2023, electricity production from wind turbines and photovoltaic installations, representing 27% of total electricity production, surpassed production from gas or coal for the first time in the European Union (Illustration 142). This choice of energy supplies will have no undesirable effects on the availability of energy in France and Switzerland.

An analysis carried out by RTE in 2023 confirmed the availability of the capacity needed to operate the FCC¹⁰⁰. Given the increased capacity for renewable electricity production in Europe, a nearly total supply of renewable energy for the FCC by 2045 seems feasible and likely, as forecasts for green electricity production capacity indicate coverage of 70-80% of total EU needs as early as 2035 (Illustration 143).

Illustration 142: Annual electricity production in the EU by method.

Source: Annual electricity data, Ember, <https://ember-climate.org/insights/research/european-electricity-review-2024/>.

⁹⁹ J. Gutleber, *Renewable Energy Supply Feasibility Analysis*, 2023. Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10023947>

¹⁰⁰ RTE, *Étude exploratoire N. 22-1022 pour le raccordement du FCC*, 15 juillet 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13364463>

Illustration 143: Forecast scenarios for electricity production (in GW) from wind turbines and photovoltaic installations in the EU by 2035.

Source: <https://ember-climate.org/insights/research/new-generation/>

As far as the planning for electricity supplies is concerned, the study assumes a long-term, sustainable commitment through the direct sale of electricity from renewable sources (power purchase agreement - PPA). It is possible to conclude several PPAs either directly with energy suppliers, or through an intermediary. France is particularly well placed to harness wind power¹⁰¹, which is also a cheap and renewable source of energy. The strategy therefore relies on a supply based primarily on electricity from offshore wind turbines, supplemented by photovoltaic installations.

Illustration 144: Lazard’s unsubsidized Levelized Cost of Energy Analysis Version 16.0, in USD/MWh in 2024.

Source: <https://www.lazard.com/media/xemfev0k/lazards-lcoeplus-june-2024- vf.pdf>

¹⁰¹ H. Eerens, E. de Visser, “Wind-energy potential in Europe 2020-2030” ETC/ACC Technical Paper 2008/6, European Topic Centre on Air and Climate Change, December 2008: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu>

The feasibility analyses carried out at this stage are based on the costs and options for supplying renewable energy in 2023. They cannot anticipate technological improvements, the strengthening of networks facilitating the energy trade in Europe, or future decisions concerning the construction of production capacity for renewable energy. Already, at this early stage, taking into account contractual conditions and market exposure risk, the percentage of contractually accessible renewable energy is around 60%, at prices between 60 and 90 euros/MWh (Illustration 145). This percentage takes into account the possible risk of having to compensate for a lack of renewable energy over the course of the year. From a technological point of view, this percentage can even reach 95% with energy storage. The aim now is to achieve total coverage 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. To make up for energy shortfalls, the use of energy produced from decarbonised sources and surplus renewable energy could be considered (excess capacity, which will be made available to the market, could be added to the contract). Another possibility is to store energy in the form of batteries, either as part of a PPA that includes energy storage, or by energy distribution to FCC sites.

Illustration 145: Actual price of PPAs from auctions in Europe (2012-2021). The most recent prices for wind power range from 60 to 90 euros/MWh.

Source: AURES II RES auction database, created through a project co-funded by the European Union under the H2020 program, GA 817619¹⁰².

The cost estimates, based on technological and economic conditions in 2023, include the additional costs arising from the purchase of electricity outside the PPA to cover renewable energy needs not met under the PPA. In the long term, the price of electricity approaches the *levelized cost of electricity* (LCOE) which, for wind farms, is roughly 60 euros per MWh in 2023.

¹⁰² AURES II auction database, created as through a project co-funded by the European Union under the H2020 program: <http://aures2project.eu>

Total cost per Mwh =

- LCOE (wind, photovoltaic)*
- + 5% margin for PPAs*
- + 5% PPA management fee*
- + purchase of missing quantity of electricity on the market*
- sale of planned excess capacity*
- sale of purchased by unused contracted energy capacity*

At this stage of the study, the supply strategy recommended by the consultants is to conclude a specific supply contract for CERN, including the needs of the FCC, with one or more energy suppliers in France who have an interest in acquiring additional offshore wind turbines to ensure production of approximately 1 GW, with CERN as a preferred customer for a capacity of around 350 MW for around fifteen years.

The FCC's operational needs may require the purchasing of additional electricity on the open market if the quantity of electricity available is insufficient, or allow unused renewable energy capacity to be made available to other consumers. It would also be possible, from the outset of the contract, to provide for the resale of surplus capacity to compensate for any need to purchase electricity generated from other sources. However, simulations carried out by McKinsey for a "conventional" operating period for FCC have shown that the amount of surplus electricity that could be supplied would correspond to the amount that would have to be purchased in the event of temporary unavailability of renewable electricity. Even in the absence of surplus electricity, the additional cost of purchasing electricity on the market without a guarantee of its source remains acceptable. The volume covered by the power purchase agreement for electricity from renewable sources therefore truly corresponds to the total volume that would be used by the FCC. This total cost is included in the cost estimate presented here. The introduction of storage systems, yet to be designed, would increase the rate of coverage by renewable sources.

Illustration 146: Changes in electricity demand in TWh over the course of the year in the EU (2019-2022).

Source: Ember, <https://ember-climate.org/insights/research/european-electricity-review-2023/>.

However, the possibility of "transferring" FCC operating days from the summer to the winter period, when wind power production is higher, should be studied. As demand for electricity is higher in the winter (Illustration 146), an additional quantity of electricity would have to be purchased, at an extra cost of 10 to 20 euros/MWh compared with summer prices (Illustration 147), if the PPA contract covers average consumption rather than maximum demand. Selling the surplus in summer would not cover the additional costs in winter, as the summer selling price per MWh would be around ten euros lower than the average purchase price in the contract, representing a net loss of 10 euros per MWh of electricity sold to CERN. This would affect how well the demand for waste heat could be met during the heating season between October and March. Accepting an additional cost of around 10 euros/MWh opens up the possibility of supplying large quantities of heat in the winter. An in-depth economic analysis based on a more precise timetable, a rigorous quantification of the potential number of consumers of waste heat, and an estimate of the value of this heat supplied over the fifteen years of operation, can be useful information for decision-making. For the time being, however, the working hypothesis remains that the collider will operate from April to September.

Illustration 147: Average monthly electricity price in France based on the listed price the day before the auction (day ahead auction) during an ordinary year (2019). Source: www.energy-charts.info from Fraunhofer ISE.

A wind power contract for 350 MW supplies around 1.2 TWh of electricity per year¹⁰³. A PPA of this type would already cover the average needs of the FCC over its lifetime. This alone would cover up to 60% of green energy needs for 2024, at a price of around 77 euros/MWh¹⁰⁴ including contract management costs. It would be necessary to purchase additional electricity to supplement requirements when there is not enough wind. It is estimated that it would take around five years to conclude a PPA of this type, due to the need to create new production capacity. Given that the collider only operates for scientific research purposes for around 140 days, and that the research infrastructure requires less electricity for the rest of the year, a supply contract of this type also makes it possible to sell green electricity not used by the FCC to other consumers at a very attractive price.

Concerning the development of renewable energies, and in particular offshore wind farms, a much larger capacity of around 1 GW is more attractive for energy suppliers. It offers the potential for greater efficiency and lower prices, and opens up the prospect of even more sustainable benefits for the economy and society. The mere fact that CERN is the main customer for at least a third of this capacity would be sufficient motivation to set up a wind farm of this size. The supplier would offer unused capacity for sale on the market, either according to demand, or as part of other PPAs. In the case of a long-term PPA, for a period of fifteen to twenty years, the supplier would not ask for participation in the form of co-financing. Construction of the wind turbines would begin as soon as the PPA is signed, which guarantees the sale of the electricity. Currently, ten to twenty players in the French market have expressed interest in a project of this type.

For suppliers, the biggest challenge is obtaining an option for the location of this type of wind farm. Expert consultants in this field point out that strong support and a partnership with the concerned state would be necessary to develop this strategy. The construction and operation of a new wind farm would bring CERN

¹⁰³ According to WindEurope (windeurope.org) and DUKES (<https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/renewable-sources-of-energy-chapter-6-digest-of-united-kingdom-energy-statistics-dukes>), in section 6.3 published in 2022, the load factor for offshore wind farms is approximately 40 % in Europe.

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.montelnews.com/fr/news/1531140/kallista-signe-3-ppa-pour-100-gwhan-avec-les-mousquetaires#>

additional economic benefits through a net profit of 400 to 700 million euros, depending on production capacity, and the creation of 5 000 to 8 000 sustainable jobs.

Concerning the energy needs of the FCC-hh proton collider, scheduled for construction in the second half of the 21st century, the ability to make forecasts is very limited at this stage. The technical feasibility of the FCC-hh was studied between 2014 and 2018, based on the use of Nb₃Sn superconducting magnet technology operating at a very low temperature of 2 K (-271.15 degrees Celsius). At this temperature, the electricity needs for the cryogenic cooling systems would be higher than those of the FCC-ee collider systems. As a result of the reduction in circumference of almost 10% between the PA0-0.1 (CDR) reference scenario and the PA31 scenario, the magnetic field of the magnets required to maintain the collision energy of the particles should also be greater than 16 Tesla¹⁰⁵. These two constraints led to the launch of basic research in materials science to design magnets with very intense magnetic fields (between 15 and 20 Tesla) that can operate at more "conventional" cryogenic temperatures, and which require much less electricity than NbTi and Nb₃Sn technologies. Thanks to the FCC-ee program, this research into high-temperature superconducting materials can be carried out over a 40-year period.

At present, it is only possible to say that electricity needs in 2065, which will be met exclusively from sustainable and renewable energy sources, will remain more or less the same as those of the CERN FCC-ee infrastructure, since this new technology makes it possible to imagine an upper limit for energy consumption.

This technology will pave the way for significant industrial innovations because, for the first time, superconductors would be used on a sufficiently large scale to create an industry dedicated to their production, and to enable technology transfers in fields that, today, only use very low-temperature superconductors, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). This scenario is credible, as it has clear parallels with the Tevatron program in the United States in the late 1970s, which led to the industrialisation of MRIs¹⁰⁶ based on NbTi superconductor technology¹⁰⁷.

The use of renewable energy is also being considered for the construction phase. To this end, each site would be connected to regional power distribution grids with different capacities, depending on the needs of the construction activities on site (e.g. no TBMs, one TBM or two TBMs). The required capacities are mentioned in section 6.2.18.2 "Electricity" in this report.

¹⁰⁵ In a circular synchrotron, particle energy is linearly dependent on the magnitude of the magnetic field B of the magnets that maintain the particles on a curved trajectory, and on the radius rho of curvature of these dipole magnets: $E = B \times rho$.

¹⁰⁶ <https://news.fnal.gov/2017/12/ieee-honors-game-changing-tevatron-technology/>

¹⁰⁷ <https://cds.cern.ch/record/796105/files/CERN-2004-006.pdf.pdf>

6.2.22. Residual magnetic field at the surface of scientific sites

Static magnetic fields will be used to track the trajectory of particles in the detectors of the four experiments, which will be located at different depths beneath the ground, between 180 m and 250 m. The residual magnetic field created by a 4 Tesla superconducting solenoid included in the standard detector planned for the second phase, for the FCC-hh (Illustration 148), will be a magnetic field twice as strong as that generated by a detector from the first phase of FCC-ee.

Illustration 148: Cross-section of a standard detector for the second phase of the FCC program (FCC-hh), after the year 2065. The detectors in the first phase (FCC-ee) will be smaller, comparable to the CMS or ATLAS detectors in the current LHC program.

The residual magnetic field has been calculated to protect the facilities and to deduce the maximum observable value on the surface in the immediate vicinity of the scientific sites. The magnetic field density is shown in Illustration 150. The earth's natural magnetic field (Illustration 149) in the region is 0.000047 Tesla (47 μ T). The magnetic field decreases rapidly with respect to the detector axis in meters (r), eventually reaching a value of less than 0.0001 Tesla (100 μ T) at a distance of around 180 m, which is the foreseen depth of the shallowest experiment cavern at the PD site in Nangy, France. At a distance of 45 m from the shaft, this residual field will merge with the earth's natural magnetic field, and will no longer be detectable beyond that. For the other three scientific sites, as the cavern is located at a depth of over 200 m, the value of the residual magnetic field at the surface will be less than 0.00007 Tesla (70 μ T). At the PA site (Ferney-Voltaire), the residual magnetic field will be lower than the earth's natural magnetic field at more than 30 m from the shaft. At the PG site in Charvonnex and the PJ site in Vulbens, the detector's residual magnetic field will always be lower than the earth's magnetic field.

Illustration 149: Intensity of the earth's magnetic field in the FCC region.

Illustration 150: Decay of residual magnetic field B (in Tesla) as a function of distance r (in meters). The residual magnetic field at each scientific site (PA, PD, PG and PJ) is shown for the most penalising situation, i.e. for a detector without magnetic shielding during the second operating phase (FCC-hh). The residual magnetic field for a detector during the first phase of operation (FCC-ee) will be weaker than the earth's natural magnetic field. At more than 45 m from the PD shaft and 30 m from the PA shaft, the residual field will be entirely "hidden" by the earth's natural field.

The value of 0.00007 Tesla can be put into perspective by comparing it with some of the magnetic field density values generated by everyday electrical appliances, as well as with the regulatory limit values for the public established by the host countries. The regulatory limit values are as follows:

- exposure limit set at 0.04 Tesla (i.e. 570 times more) for the population in France¹⁰⁸ and Switzerland¹⁰⁹ set at 0.04 Tesla;
- exposure limit set at 0.005 Tesla (i.e. 70 times more) for wearers of active implantable medical devices (AIMD) in Europe.

The magnetic field generated by a decorative magnet is 200 times higher than the maximum residual magnetic field that will be observable on the PA and PD shafts (Illustration 151). This field can be further reduced with shielding. Outside the FCC surface sites, the residual magnetic field will be weaker than the earth's natural magnetic field. So there will be no adverse effects.

¹⁰⁸ In France, decree no. 2002-775 of 3 May 2002 in application of paragraph 12° of article L. 32 of the French post and telecommunications code and relating to limit values for public exposure to electromagnetic fields emitted by equipment used in telecommunications networks or by radio installations in France.

¹⁰⁹ In Switzerland, ordinance on protection against non-ionizing radiation (ORNI) of 23 December 1999.(last modification dated as of 29 September 2023).

Illustration 151: A few magnetic field references.

6.2.23. Compatibility with geothermal borehole probes

A heat pump system with vertical geothermal borehole probes or fields of probes consists of circulating water, often with added antifreeze, in a closed circuit through a network of polyethylene tubes laid vertically in boreholes roughly 100 m deep (Illustration 152).

This allows energy to be exchanged by heat transfer and then transported to the ground-source heat pump.

On the surface, the ground-source heat pump transfers heat extracted from the ground to the building to be heated, raising its temperature (heating mode), or injects heat from the building into the ground, lowering its temperature (cooling mode).

Illustration 152: Ground-source heat pump on borehole field. © ADEME-BRGM.

Vertical geothermal boreholes for probes are generally drilled in molasse at depths of between 100 and 400 m, and are therefore at risk of being severed and rendered inoperative during tunnel excavation.

The location of geothermal borehole probes for which data is publicly available was taken into account when developing scenario PA31-4.0.

A minimum distance of 35 m between public underground structures and the FCC tunnel or caverns is considered adequate to rule out any mutually negative effects (see scale diagram in Illustration 153).

The available map data shows that the PA31-4.0 reference scenario does not appear to conflict with existing boreholes for probes. However, as boreholes for geothermal probes sometimes deviate significantly from verticality, locations and depths are not always accurate and, as a result, map values may differ from reality.

Illustration 153: Scale drawing of safety perimeter and geothermal boreholes. Source: CERN.

The assistance of the departments of the host countries, France and Switzerland, has been requested in order to verify the compatibility of the reference footprint, taking into consideration the following details:

- the elevation of the tunnel has not yet been defined, but it is likely to be between 150 and 250 m above sea level;
- in molasse, a safety distance of 50 m around the tunnel (with a diameter of around 6 m) and other underground infrastructures is considered adequate to ensure compatibility between these facilities and a geothermal borehole;
- in Switzerland, two boreholes were located within the 35 m minimum safety strip, and three boreholes within the 50 m safety strip that extends above ground on either side of the PA31-4.0 footprint in the canton of Geneva (see map in Illustration 154). The two boreholes less than 35 m away are located 27 and 32 m respectively from the centreline and at a depth of around 100 m below the surface, i.e. around 330 m above sea level. The 50 m safety distance around the tunnel seems to be respected;
- in France, the location of existing or authorised boreholes for geothermal probes within the 50 m safety perimeter should be indicated.

Illustration 154: Geothermal boreholes for probes located within 50 m of the tunnel in the canton of Geneva, Switzerland. Source: SITG, layer CTSS_CHAUFFAGE_SONDE (ID: 6867).

The services of the host countries are requested to:

1. Verify that existing boreholes for geothermal probes are located at a safety distance of 50 m from the FCC tunnel in accordance with reference scenario PA31-4.0;
2. To confirm that an adequate safety distance greater than 50 m from the tunnel and caverns is maintained in cases where the location, depth and verticality of an existing borehole for a geothermal probe are not precisely known;
3. Ensure compliance with the 50 m safety distance for geothermal probes already authorised or to be authorised in the future, particularly with regard to verticality and depth;
4. Indicate the location of existing or authorised geothermal probe boreholes, in France only.

It would be prudent to maintain the underground space occupied by the tunnel and caverns, as well as a safety zone 50 metres from the tunnel and other underground infrastructure as described in the PA31-4.0 reference scenario (Illustration 155), bearing in mind that the exact depth of the tunnel will only be defined once the results of the underground investigations have been analysed, i.e. towards the end of 2026.

Illustration 155: French and Swiss plots of land within the 50 m safety strip extending aboveground on either side of the PA31-4.0 footprint.

6.3. SUMMARY OF TOOLS FOR IDENTIFYING ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN FRANCE

6.3.1. Introduction

The environmental issues defined at this stage of the study are constantly changing due to:

- possible changes in public policies and national and/or local environmental ambitions to which the project will have to respond;
- possible changes in regulations (environmental code, urban planning code, etc.), in particular to meet increasingly ambitious environmental goals;
- changes in the local context: environmental pressure affecting the territory (demographics, economic activities, transport, etc.) and the way in which each region responds to this pressure change over time.

This section summarises the tools identified in the FCC study area (in particular, inventoried or protection zones) in order to:

- identify sectors where environmental issues are present;
- characterise the nature of these issues (intensity and nature of the issue).

An analysis of the territory where the project is located, based on these tools, provides an initial assessment of the situation in order to:

- avoid locations in sectors with the most significant issues with regards to the known characteristics of the FCC project and available environmental data;
- define the sectors where the issues will require more in-depth studies, so that the FCC layout can be planned under conditions that cause the least possible damage to the environment. In particular, the environmental analysis will make it possible to use the "avoid", "reduce" and, where appropriate, "compensate" approach for any environmental harm caused by the project during the construction and operation phases.

6.3.2. Inventories of Natural Zone of Interest for Ecology, Flora and Fauna (ZNIEFF)

The ZNIEFF inventory is a knowledge-based tool that indicates the presence in certain areas of an ecological interest requiring special attention and more in-depth studies. The inventory has no direct legal value in itself, and does not constitute an instrument for the regulatory protection of natural areas. ZNIEFF inventories are nevertheless proof of the ecological richness of natural areas and the need to protect them.

There are two types of ZNIEFF, with a type-1 ZNIEFF presenting the most significant nature preservation issues.

6.3.2.1. Type-1 ZNIEFF

A type-I ZNIEFF is a sector of generally limited surface area, characterised by the presence of "decisive" species, associations of species or environments, i.e. rare, remarkable or characteristic of the national or regional natural heritage.

The risk of the presence of legally protected species is very high, but not systematic.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid being located in a type-1 ZNIEFF:

If a project is to be carried out in a type-1 ZNIEFF, it must be demonstrated that it cannot be avoided under acceptable economic conditions. A "fauna, flora and habitats" inventory must be carried out over a full biological year, including a search for the existence or not of protected species. The absence or inadequacy of such an inventory is likely to call the project into question due to a "manifest error in assessment".

If the presence of protected species is confirmed, damage to these species and their habitats is subject to prior authorisation from the prefect, after a decision from the national council for the protection of nature (CNP).

6.3.2.2. Type-2 ZNIEFF

A type-2 ZNIEFF is a large natural area (forests, valleys, plateaus, estuaries, etc.) that are rich and largely intact, or which have significant biological potential. They may include one or more type-1 ZNIEFFs.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid being located in a type-2 ZNIEFF:

In these zones, it is important to respect the major ecological balances, taking into account, in particular, the home range of sedentary and migratory fauna. As in the case of a type-1 ZNIEFF, a "fauna, flora and habitats" inventory must be carried out over a full biological year, including a search for the existence or not of protected species.

6.3.3. ZICO (priority zone for bird preservation) inventory

ZICOs (priority zones for bird preservation) are high-priority sites that host wild bird populations deemed to be of Community or European importance. This inventory was carried out by the French "Ligue pour la protection des oiseaux" (LPO) and the French national history museum (MNHN) on behalf of the French ministry of ecology, with the help of regional ornithological groups.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid being located in ZICO:

As with ZNIEFFs, the project owner must explain why the project cannot avoid a ZICO. An inventory of bird populations must be carried out, and the impact study must include measures to avoid, reduce and compensate for any negative impacts of the project on these populations.

In the case of protected species, prefectural authorisation may be required following the opinion of the CNPN. As far as the construction site is concerned, requirements may be imposed, such as a ban on disturbances, and therefore on work being carried out, during the nesting period (period to be defined during the inventory phases).

6.3.4. Inventory of peatlands and wetlands

An inventory of peatlands, entrusted to the “Conservatoire d'espaces naturels”, was carried out between 1997 and 1999 under the aegis of the Rhône-Alpes region. Other wetland inventories have also been carried out by the French departments: this is notably the case for Haute-Savoie, which has made available to the public a wetland map updated annually since 2010.

In addition to existing inventories, other indicators of the any wetlands or peatlands affected will need to be used for the project impact study phase (water development and management master plans, water development and management plans, field surveys, etc.).

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a site that might affect a peatland or wetland:

If a peatland and/or wetland is affected, the project is subject to a declaration or authorization procedure under the "water law", depending on the surface area in question, for land areas of 1 000 m² or more (article R214 of the environment code). As part of the authorization application, the project owner must indicate all the measures planned to eliminate, reduce or, if technically impossible, compensate for the project's impact on the aquatic environment. Authorization or declaration applications must therefore propose effective corrective or even compensatory measures if the impact cannot be avoided or sufficiently reduced.

In addition, as the probability of damage to protected species or their habitats is very high in wetlands, the project can only be authorised by a prefectural decree, with the prior approval of the “Conseil national de la protection de la nature” once an application has been submitted for a "protected species" exemption.

6.3.5. Natura 2000 network

The Natura 2000 network, made up of a series of natural sites, aims to ensure the long-term survival of particularly endangered species and habitats of significant conservation importance in Europe. The aim is twofold:

- the maintaining or re-establishment of good conservation status for habitats and species through specific management measures;
- the supervision of development projects and human activities, which must be compatible with the conservation objectives for the habitats and species that led to the site's inclusion in the network.

In concrete terms, the Natura 2000 network is the result of the application of two European Union directives:

- directive 79/409/EEC, known as the "Wild birds" Directive;
- directive 92/43/EEC, known as the "Natural habitats and wild fauna and flora" directive.

This network is the result of the merger of SPAs and SACs (see below).

6.3.5.1. Natura 2000: Special Protection Areas (SPA)

The “Wild birds” directive calls for the protection of habitats necessary for the reproduction and survival of birds considered rare or threatened on a European scale. Within this framework, each country of the European Union must classify as a Special Protection Area (SPA) the sites best suited to the conservation of the habitats of these species, taking into account their number and size.

In France, a significant number of ZICO sites have been recognised as SPAs.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid an SPA:

The project owner must explain why zones classified as SPAs could not be avoided. A Natura 2000 impact study must be carried out (specifically targeting the natural heritage that led to the site's designation), which specifies in particular how the project's negative impacts on bird populations have been avoided, reduced or compensated for.

It should be noted that a Natura 2000 impact study is mandatory, even if the project is not in an SPA, when direct or indirect impacts, be they temporary or definitive, are likely to affect the bird populations concerned.

6.3.5.2. Natura 2000: Special Areas of Conservation (SAC)

The "Natural habitats and wild fauna and flora" directive aims to:

- strengthen nature conservation measures and, in particular, help to maintain biological diversity;
- maintain or re-establish good conservation status for certain natural environments or certain plant and animal populations.

A list of habitats appears in Annex I of this directive, and a list of plant and animal species in Annex II. These elements are considered to be of European Community interest, and those that are considered to be threatened are defined as priorities.

The first stage, in each country, involved establishing inventories and proposing spaces or sites to be selected as sites of European Community importance, following approval by the European Union. In a second stage, each member country undertook to maintain these areas in a good state of conservation. On the basis of these government commitments, these Sites of European Community interest were designated Special Areas of Conservation (SAC) by decree.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a SAC:

Any damage to priority species or habitats is prohibited, except for reasons relating to human health or safety.

For non-priority species and habitats, the project owner must explain why zones classified as SACs could not be avoided. As is the case with SPAs, a Natura 2000 impact study must be carried out (specifically targeting the natural heritage that led to the site's designation), which specifies how the project's negative impacts on habitats and species of European Community interest have been avoided, reduced or compensated for.

It should be noted that a Natura 2000 impact study is mandatory, even if the project is not in an SAC, when direct or indirect impacts, be they temporary or definitive, are likely to affect the natural heritage that led to the site receiving the SAC designation.

6.3.6. Protected agricultural zones (ZAP)

The French agricultural policy law of 9 July 1999 created a tool that makes it possible to classify certain agricultural areas as "protected agricultural zones" if their preservation is in the general interest due to:

- the quality of their production;
- their agronomic quality;
- or their geographical location.

This special zoning is defined in article L112-2 of the "rural code".

The demarcation of the protected agricultural zone (ZAP) is defined by prefectural decree and consists in the creation of a public utility easement applied within a given perimeter, and which is appended to the urban planning document.

It provides greater protection for farmlands in response to the changing nature of urban planning documents. This protection ensures that the plots of land within its scope will continue to be used for agricultural purposes over time, which is essential for the sustainability of farms.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a ZAP:

ZAP regulations are the same as those for agricultural zones in the urban planning document. However, any change in the land use or occupation that permanently alters the agronomic, biological or ecological potential of the ZAP may be subject to an amendment by prefectural decree, subject to prior approval by the chamber of agriculture and the "Commission départementale d'orientation de l'agriculture" (CDOA).

6.3.7. Protective perimeters for peri-urban natural and agricultural areas (PAEN)

The PAEN is a tool used to preserve agricultural and natural areas, which can be implemented by departments or through a territorial cohesion scheme (SCoT).

They provide long-term protection for farmlands¹¹⁰.

Although rarely used at the present time, they may be used in the future by local authorities in their zero net artificialisation (ZAN) initiatives.

¹¹⁰ For more information on this tool: <http://outil2amenagement.cerema.fr/la-protection-des-espaces-agricoles-et-naturels-r467.html> ou https://www.isere.fr/sites/default/files/fiche_paen.pdf

6.3.8. Hazard prevention plans (PPRN, PPRI)

The natural hazard prevention plan (PPRN), created by the law of 2 February 1995, is today one of the essential instruments used for government actions in natural hazard prevention in order to reduce the vulnerability of people and property.

The PPRN is a public utility easement that carries penal sanctions in the event of non-compliance with its rules, as well as the possibility of compensation for natural disasters. The PPRN file contains a note presenting the context and the procedure that has been carried out, one or more regulatory zoning maps that demarcate the regulated zones, and the regulations corresponding to this zoning. It is approved through a prefectural decree.

The PPRN makes it possible to take account of all hazards, including flooding, earthquakes, landslides, forest fires, avalanches and more. The regulations cover both new projects and existing properties. The PPRN can also define, and make mandatory, general measures for the prevention, protection and safeguarding of property and populations.

When the hazard is specifically related to flooding, the plan is called PPRI (natural hazard prevention plan for flooding).

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a natural hazard prevention zone:

Construction in PPRN red zones is strictly prohibited. In other areas (blue or white zones), construction may be authorised when the building permit is applied for if it does not worsen the phenomena (risk factors) and has no vulnerabilities in the event of a natural disaster.

6.3.9. Technological hazard prevention plans (PPRT)

The areas under study are not affected by any PPRT plans.

6.3.10. SRCE and SRADDET

The regional ecological coherence scheme (SRCE) is now part of the regional scheme for planning, sustainable development and territorial equality (SRADDET) of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region

The regional ecological coherence scheme¹¹¹ was set down in article 121 of the French law of 12 July 2010 relating to the national commitment to the environment (known as the "Grenelle II" law) (see also articles L.371-1 et seq. of the French environment code). It is the cornerstone of the regional "green and blue grid" (TVB) approach, one of the aims of which is to maintain and reconstitute a network across the national territory so that animal and plant species can interact, circulate, eat, reproduce, rest, etc., i.e. ensure their survival, by facilitating their adaptation to climate change.

The SRCE has become the **"protection and restoration of biodiversity" component of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes SRADDET plan.**

A distinction is made between:

- **biodiversity reservoirs**, which concentrate most of a region's biodiversity;
- **ecological corridors** that enable plant, animal and fungi species to move between reservoirs.

The combination of biodiversity reservoirs and ecological corridors is referred to as **"ecological continuity"**.

The "protection and restoration of biodiversity" component of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes SRADDET plan must be incorporated into local urban planning documents (SCoTs and local urban plans) in order to be enforceable for individual plots of land.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a SRADDET zone:

If the ecological continuity of the SRADDET is affected, the project owner must demonstrate that it has taken into account the biodiversity reservoirs and ecological corridors concerned.

This implies an obligation of compatibility, with a possible concession for justified reasons. It requires "not to deviate from the fundamental orientations of the SRADDET (e.g. serious harm to a biodiversity reservoir; disruption of an ecological corridor) except for a reason based on the interest of the project and insofar as this interest justifies it".

In concrete terms, the project owner must demonstrate in the impact study how ecological continuity has been taken into account, i.e. biodiversity reservoirs and ecological corridors.

¹¹¹ https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sch%C3%A9ma_r%C3%A9gional_de_coh%C3%A9rence_%C3%A9cologique

6.3.11. Classified wooded area (EBC)

Article L130-1 of the urban planning code stipulates that local urban plans (PLUs) can classify woods, forests and parks to be preserved, protected or created as wooded areas. This classification can also apply to isolated trees, hedges or hedge networks, or to certain plantations along streets.

The classification prohibits any change of land use or occupation that might jeopardise the conservation, protection or creation of woodlands.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid an EBC:

Any construction in a classified wooded area is prohibited. This could only be achieved by downgrading the classification of the area, with a land-clearing permit issued by the prefect if the government is not the project owner. The PLU (local urban plan) would still need to be brought into accordance as part of the procedure for the declaration of public interest. It must include a justification for the downgrading of the classified wooded area and the corresponding measures to avoid, reduce or compensate for the environmental impacts of this downgrading of the concerned area.

6.3.12. Protection of water catchments

Catchment protection perimeters are established around water catchment sites intended for human consumption, to ensure the preservation of the resource (article L1321-2 of the French public health code). The aim is therefore to reduce the risk of point-source and accidental pollution of the resource at these specific points.

Three types of perimeters exist:

- **the immediate protective perimeter**, within which all construction is prohibited. Its purpose is to prevent deterioration of the works and avoid the discharge of polluting substances in the immediate vicinity of the catchment;
- **close protective zone**: this is a larger sector (generally a few hectares) where any activity likely to cause pollution is prohibited or subject to special regulations (construction, deposits, discharges, etc.). Its purpose is to prevent the migration of pollutants into the catchment;
- **remote protective perimeter**: this perimeter is created if certain activities are likely to cause significant pollution. This sector generally corresponds to the catchment area for a collection point, or even the entire watershed.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a water catchment protection:

All construction within the immediate perimeter of the catchment is prohibited. Construction within the close or remote protective perimeter is prohibited, unless the project owner can demonstrate that it will comply with any special requirements stipulated for the project.

6.3.13. Environmental and river contracts to protect aquatic environments

Schémas d'aménagement et de gestion de l'eau (SAGE) and contrats de milieu¹¹² are two complementary tools, one establishing a "common project for water" with rules of good conduct, the other enabling the financing of actions (in the service of this common project when a river contract follows on from a SAGE).

Within the FCC perimeter, there are three potential environmental contracts¹¹³.

6.3.14. Listed historic monuments / buildings protected by local urban plan (PLU)

A historic monument is a building (built or not built: park, garden, cave, etc.) or a tangible movable object (movable or immovable due its nature or purpose) with a special legal status to protect it on account of its historical, artistic, architectural, technical or scientific interest, so that it can be preserved, restored and enhanced.

Protection of the surrounding area is a public easement whose purpose is to protect, conserve and enhance cultural heritage.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a protection zone:

An urban planning permit is required for works located in the vicinity of a historic monument, particularly when the project is within sight of a historic monument (if it is visible from the monument or visible together with the monument) and less than 500 m from the monument, or when the project is located within an adapted or modified protective perimeter that has become a demarcated perimeter.

Authorization is granted by the prefect, subject to a decision in favour of the project by the Architecte des Bâtiments de France (ABF).

¹¹² Information sheet:

<https://www.rhone-mediterranee.eaufrance.fr/gestion-de-leau/gestion-locale-de-leau/sage-et-contrats-de-milieu>

¹¹³ <https://www.gesteau.fr/contrats#9/45.9874/6.3281/sdage,contrats>

6.3.15. Listed and classified sites

Listed site

This is a natural area or a built area of an artistic, historical, scientific, legendary or picturesque nature that needs to be preserved.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a listed site:

In listed sites, the authorities must be informed at least four months in advance of any planned works. The Architecte des Bâtiments de France issues an advisory opinion only, except for demolition permits, which require approval.

Classified site

This is a site of an artistic, historical, scientific, legendary or picturesque nature, the quality of which requires in the general interest that it be preserved in its current state and protected from any serious harm. The classification applies to nature and built areas of any size. This procedure is widely used to protect landscapes considered remarkable or exceptional.

Consequently, if a project cannot avoid a classified site:

In classified sites, all work likely to alter the condition of the site or its appearance (e.g., work requiring a building permit) is subject to special prior authorisation from the ministry responsible for sites, based on the decisions of the DREAL (regional directorate for the environment, development and housing), the DRAC (regional directorate for cultural affairs and the territorial architecture and heritage service of the concerned department) and the departmental commission for nature, landscapes and sites (CDNPS). Authorisation is decentralised to the departmental prefect for smaller-scale projects.

6.3.16. Easement PT1 – Protection of radio reception centres against electromagnetic interference.

In order to ensure the proper operation of networks, easements are instituted in application of articles L57 to L62-1 of the French post and telecommunications code to protect radio reception centres from electromagnetic disturbances that may result from the operation of certain equipment, particularly electrical equipment.

There are two types of easements:

- easements introduced for radio reception centres relating to national defence or public safety;
- easements for radio reception centres owned by private operators.

There are two zones: protection zones and radio buffer zones.

The FCC does not appear to be affected by these regulations.

Consequence:

In buffer zones, it is forbidden to operate or modify electrical equipment likely to interfere with radio reception without authorisation from the minister responsible for operating the centre.

The easement does not specify any maximum permissible quantitative value for the electromagnetic field. It requires the project owner to ask the minister in charge of operating or monitoring existing facilities to clarify this point. This is therefore a point of interest for the impact study.

6.4. SUMMARY OF TOOLS FOR IDENTIFYING ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN SWITZERLAND

6.4.1. Introduction

All the legal aspects and environmental issues presented in this section are taken from the report entitled *FCC Layout review in Switzerland*, delivered in 2017 by the engineering firm Ecotec Environnement SA. These elements were updated in 2022 by Latitude Durable.

6.4.2. Protection of air quality

Federal legislation:

- Environmental protection act (LPE, 814.01) of 7 October 1983.
- Reduction of CO₂ emissions act (Law on CO₂ emissions 641.71) of 23 December 2011.
- Protection of air quality ordinance (OPair, 814.318.142.1) of 16 December 1985.

Cantonal legislation:

- Regulations for protection of air quality (RPAir, K 1 70.08) of 22 February 2012.

Directives and recommendations:

- OFEV, 2016. *Directive on operational and technical measures to limit emissions of air pollutants from construction sites (Directive Air Chantiers)*¹¹⁴, supplemented edition. The practical environment. 32 p.
- OFEV, 2018. *Minimum height of chimneys on roofs. Recommendations for minimum chimney heights.* The practical environment. 21 p.
- OFEV, 2003. *Particulate filters for construction machinery. Cost-benefit analysis.* Environmental documents no. 148 - Air. 52 p.
- OFEFP, 2001. *Combating air pollution from construction site traffic.* The practical environment. 70 p.
- SABRA, 2018. *Plan de mesures OPair 2018-2023.* Geneva air quality remediation plan, approved by the Conseil d'État in January 2018.
- OCEV, 2016. *Air Protection Strategy 2030*, approved by the Conseil d'État in December 2015.

¹¹⁴ OFEV, *Directive Air Chantiers*. Completed edition, February 2016.

https://www.bafu.admin.ch/dam/bafu/fr/dokumente/luft/uv-umwelt-vollzug/luftreinhaltung_aufbaustellenergaenzteausgabe.pdf

Consequence:Construction site phase:

Pollutant emissions (nitrogen oxides, fine particles) from truck traffic for work on the project are the main factors to be taken into account during the construction phase. Construction of the tunnel will generate extremely large volumes of excavated material, which will have to be transported to storage areas, landfill sites or other construction sites.

Operational phase:

The project will have an impact on regional air quality due to the increase in industrial activities such as road traffic and the ventilation and cooling processes. These activities and the corresponding pollution risk will have to be defined.

Mobility is one of the main sources of air pollution, particularly in terms of individual motorised transport. CERN has provided an initial estimate of the number of staff members present at each site, in order to assess traffic levels:

- during operation, there would be approximately 30 people per shift, with three shifts per day;
- during technical interventions, up to 60 people would be on site, with four shifts per day.

However, some of the planned sites are located far from public transport infrastructures, and the last part of the daily transit is usually on roads with little traffic. To limit the impact on these roads, it would be necessary to consider suitable means of transport from the nearest public transport facilities, in order to limit daily and night-time traffic. One solution would be for the CERN vehicle fleet to be gradually modernised, by promoting electric vehicles for example.

6.4.3. Protection against noise

Federal legislation

- Noise protection ordinance (OPB, 814.41) of 15 December 1986.

Cantonal legislation

- Noise and vibration protection regulations (RPBV, K 1 70.10) of 12 February 2003.

Directives and recommendations

- OFEV, OFROU, 2006. *Road noise manual. Guide for sanitation work*. The practical environment. Status: December 2006.
- OFEV, 2006. *Directive on construction and operation measures aimed at limiting construction site noise according to Article 6 of the Noise protection ordinance*¹¹⁵. État : 2011.
- SABRA, OCEV, DT, 2021, BRUIT 2030 - Cantonal strategy for noise protection, adopted by the Conseil d'État on 26 May 2021.

Definitions

The relevant limit values for buildings, as defined in the OPB, are the exposure limit values. They are of several types: planning values (VP), immission limit values (VLI) and alert values (VA). They are set according to the type of noise and the time of day (for traffic noise: daytime: 6 a.m.-10 p.m. / night time: 10 p.m. to 6 a.m.), the use of the building and the level of protection for the area in question (degree of noise sensitivity).

Degrees of noise sensitivity (DS) are assigned to the various zones according to the protection required and the authorised activities. The following are considered to be premises whose use is sensitive to noise (article 2, paragraph 6 OPB):

- rooms in dwellings, excluding kitchens without habitable areas, sanitary rooms and storerooms;
- agricultural premises where people regularly stay for long periods of time; this excludes premises where livestock are kept and premises where the activity itself generates considerable noise.

¹¹⁵ <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/dam/bafu/fr/dokumente/laerm/uv-umwelt-vollzug/baulaerm-richtliniestand2011.pdf>

Consequence:Construction site phase:

The construction of surface sites must take into account the following noise-generating parameters:

- site-related road traffic (truck transport of excavation and construction materials);
- noise generated by the construction site machinery itself;
- noise due to the construction of shafts and infrastructures.

Noise emissions caused by project-related traffic will also have to be estimated. In the event of non-compliance with Article 9 of the Noise protection ordinance (OPB), remediation measures will have to be taken to comply with the legislation.

Sensitive receptors are mainly residential areas close to the sites.

*** Foreseen measures:**

The use of excavated materials and earth materials for the creation of noise barriers will be considered to limit the noise exposure for these sensitive receptors.

Operational phase:

-Noise from surface installations

The surface site is considered a new industrial facility and will have to comply with local urban planning limits for nearby sensitive receptors.

A specific study will have to be carried out at an early stage of the project to determine the noise emissions of the facilities (machines, turbines, ventilation systems, generators, use of parking lots, etc.). As the facilities also operate at night, compliance with night-time exposure limit values will have to be verified.

According to data supplied by CERN, refrigeration systems produce noise emissions of 50-55 dB(A) outside the building. These levels are acceptable during the day, but could cause problems and require the adoption of certain measures to reduce noise at night, depending on the distance from the nearest sensitive receptors.

- Induced traffic noise during the operating phase

Noise emissions caused by project-related traffic (employees, tourists, delivery trucks, etc.) will also have to be estimated. In the event of non-compliance with Article 9 of the OPB on certain roads, remediation measures will have to be taken to comply with the legislation.

CERN has provided an initial estimate of the number of staff members present at each site, in order to assess traffic levels:

- during operation, there would be approximately 30 people per shift, with three shifts per day;
- during technical interventions, up to 60 people would be on site, with four shifts per day.

*** Foreseen measures:**

To limit noise pollution from surface sites, the project will have to assess the option of underground or semi-underground buildings or components in certain cases. Exterior landscaping, such as the installation of vegetated mounds along the edges of the sites, would also help reduce these impacts.

6.4.4. Protection against vibrations and structure-borne sound propagation

The federal law on the protection of the environment (LPE, 814.01, dated 7 October 1983) obliges the "polluter" to limit vibratory emissions with respect to neighbouring residents. On the other hand, there is no law limiting the vibration and structure-borne sound levels in newly-built homes. Nevertheless, in the absence of regulations in force, it is useful to consider the LPE as a basis for study. Article 15 of the LPE stipulates that "emission limit values for noise and vibration shall be set in such a way that, based on current scientific knowledge and experience, emissions below these values do not significantly affect the well-being of the population". In accordance with the law, limit values should be set through an ordinance, which is currently being created.

In the present context, it is interesting to note that the LPE contains a so-called "prevention" article (article 11): "Independently of existing disturbances, it is important, as a preventive measure, to limit emissions to the extent permitted by the current state of the art and operating conditions, and insofar as this is economically viable".

The law therefore requires us to go beyond simple compliance with limit values, provided this is economically viable. This mindset should also be adopted in this case, because while the law only speaks of "appreciable disturbance", here it is more a question of comfort; and ensuring "reasonable" comfort based on a given standard is more restrictive than simply avoiding "appreciable disturbance".

Consequences:

Construction site phase:

Depending on the methods selected for the drilling and retaining walls, a study of the vibrations associated with the construction of the tunnel, galleries and shafts will have to be carried out during the preparatory phase to ensure that vibration levels remain below thresholds likely to cause damage to certain buildings or generate disturbances for users and any local residents.

Operational phase:

Not concerned.

6.4.5. Protection against non-ionising radiation

Federal legislation

- Ordinance on protection against non-ionizing radiation (ORNI, 814.710) of 23 December 1999.

Definitions

The ORNI defines emission limits and preventive measures (facility limit values) for electric and magnetic fields created by fixed installations.

Consequence:

Construction site phase:

Not concerned.

Operational phase:

CERN houses equipment containing potential sources of non-ionizing radiation: magnetic and electromagnetic fields, infrared radiation (e.g. power supply circuits, transformers, lasers).

According to data supplied by CERN, the foreseen particle accelerator is a synchrotron that causes collisions between electron and positron beam lines at energies between 45 GeV and 175 GeV at two separate interaction points in France (PE and PJ), and high-energy proton beams with a maximum energy of 50 TeV (maximum centre-of-mass energy of 100 TeV) at four separate interaction points (PA, PD, PG and PJ experiment sites).

A low magnetic stray field will emanate from the experimental detectors located inside the caverns and connected to the surface via vertical access shafts.

A potential leakage field from the powerful 16 T dipole magnets of the proton-proton accelerator will not go beyond the tunnel. Magnetic stray fields remain at tolerable levels at all times.

CERN estimates that:

- at a distance of 100 m from the centre of the detector, the magnetic field is about 1 mT;
- at a distance of 250 m from the detector, the residual magnetic field is weaker than the earth's natural magnetic field outside surface sites, and will therefore produce no undesirable effects.

The ORNI does not regulate the limitation of radiation emissions from sources on company premises to which employees are exposed. In this case, it is the SUVA (Swiss national accident insurance fund) that defines a threshold limit of 500 μ T (0.5 mT) for workstations. The project will therefore have to ensure compliance with this limit value at surface sites by providing appropriate mitigation measures to further limit the stray field (e.g. suitable liners for access shafts).

On the surface, outside the footprint of the sites, a limit value of 1 μ T will be respected in sensitive zones (a. premises located inside a building in which people regularly stay for an extended period; b. public or private playgrounds, defined in an urban development plan; c. parts of undeveloped land on which activities as defined in a. and b. are permitted) and 100 μ T for non-sensitive areas.

The new power lines connecting to the existing grid and the transformer stations must also comply with the installation limit value (1 μ T) for spaces with sensitive uses.

6.4.6. Protection of water

Federal legislation

- Environmental protection act (LPE, RS 814.01) of 7 October 1983.
- Water protection act (LEaux, RS 814.20) of 24 January 1991.
- Water protection ordinance (OEaux, RS 814.201) of 28 October 1998.
- Ordinance for the protection of water against potentially polluting liquids (OPEL, 814.202), of 1st July 1998.
- Ordinance for protection against hazardous substances and preparations (OChim, RS 813.11) of 5 June 2015.
- Ordinance on reduction of risks related to the use of particularly hazardous substances, preparations and objects (ORRChem, RS 814.81) of 18 May 2005.
- Fisheries act (LFSP, RS 923.0) of 21 June 1991.
- Ordinance on the federal fisheries act (OLFP, RS 923.01) of 24 November 1993.

Cantonal legislation

- Water act (LEaux, L2 05) of 5 July 1961.
- Subsurface resources act (LRSS, L 3 05) of 7 April 2006.
- Regulations for implementing the water act (REaux, L2 05.01) of 15 March 2006.
- Fisheries act (LPêche, M 4 06) of 20 October 1994.
- Regulations for implementing the fisheries act (RPêche, M 4 06.01) of 15 December 1999.
- Regulations for use of surface water and groundwater (RUESS, L 2 05.04) of 15 September 2010.

Directives and recommendations

- OFEFP, 2001. *The state of the art in water protection*. Information on water protection. 16 p.
- Directive for the treatment and disposal of construction site water (based on SIA/VSA 431:2022), June 2023.
- Water protection map of the Canton of Geneva, 1:25,000, 13 March 2003.
- Hydrogeological map of the canton of Geneva 1:25,000.

The works of SN and VSS could also be cited, which summarise the problems concerning road drainage, as well as the SPAGE:

- *Road water drainage: current situation, proposals, safety, retention and infiltration structures* (Research mandate OFROU/VSS 22/96, September 2000).
- VSA directive on rainwater drainage in agglomerations, 2019.
- SPAGE, 2012. Cantonal tool for integrated watershed management. Water protection, development and management plan (2nd edition).

Consequence:Construction site phase:

a) Groundwater

It must be demonstrated that no surface water table, main water table or deep aquifer is affected, either in terms of flow or water quality (risk of water tables entering into contact, risk of water pollution). In general, all protective measures must be implemented to avoid any impact on groundwater.

b) Surface water

As in the operating phase, watercourses and their protection perimeters must be preserved during the construction phase.

c) Water drainage

A construction site water management plan must be drawn up by the civil engineering firm selected for the work. This management plan must be sent to the person in charge of environmental monitoring during the construction phase (SER) for validation, and then to the cantonal water office (OCEau) before the start of construction. Details (sizing of facilities, etc.) and the technical means employed (type of facility, etc.) will then be provided.

Operational phase:

a) Groundwater

In the case of the main Genevois water table used for public water supply, the ring is located at a minimum lateral distance of over one kilometre. The Genevois water table is therefore not considered to be affected. For the other main and surface water tables, the ring will be located between 90 m and 500 m below the saturated levels.

In addition to the water tables listed on the canton's hydrogeological map, deeper aquifers are known to exist in the Geneva basin. Given the location of the future accelerator, the aquifers potentially concerned are located in Tertiary and Cretaceous geological formations:

- The Tertiary molasse may have localised aquifers of limited size.
- In Tertiary geological formations, the lower freshwater limestone, when present, can sometimes be several tens of meters thick. Fractured and karstified aquifer levels have been observed within these limestones.
- The limestone series of the Cretaceous formations are also potentially aquifers. In most cases, these are fractured and/or karst aquifers.

Once the concept has been published, detailed hydrogeological studies will have to demonstrate that the project is not likely to have any quantitative or qualitative impact on groundwater tables. The results should be included in the optimisation of the ring footprint and surface site layout. In particular, surface sites and access shafts must take into account, where applicable, the presence of main and surface water tables, which must not be disrupted. In general, all protective measures must be implemented to avoid any impact on groundwater.

b) Surface water

The sector is located in a flood-risk zone due to the presence of the Seymaz River. However, this hazard is considered to be residual. A non-constructible safety perimeter borders the pre-identified area and must be respected. In addition, the forest zone bordering the Seymaz to the west of the zone is considered to be a "minimum space" perimeter for management of the watercourse.

c) Water drainage

The construction of surface sites means that most of the usable surface area is rendered impervious.

The rainwater management concept developed for the site should reduce impervious surfaces as much as possible, by integrating rainwater management principles into the buildings (roof gardens, semi-permeable pavements, retention basins, infiltration channels, etc.), which will increase retention surfaces and limit runoff. These water management measures could be integrated into the overall landscaping concept that will be essential for each site.

The FCC will require a significant amount of water, much of which will be used to cool machinery. Due to heat exchange, temperature differences between the inlet and outlet of the distribution systems can be up to 25°C. Systems for the sustainable reuse of this water (remote heating network, domestic hot water supply, etc.) will have to be studied during the technical development of the project.

6.4.7. Soil protection and territorial planning

Federal legislation

- Environmental protection act (LPE, RS 814.01) of 7 October 1983, articles 29, 33 paragraph 2, article 35 paragraph 1.
- Spatial planning act (LAT) of 22 June 1979.
- Federal ordinance of 1st July 1998 regarding soil pollution (OSol, 814.12).
- Federal ordinance on the limitation and treatment of waste (OLED, 814.600) of 4 December 2015.

Cantonal legislation

- Soil protection regulations (RSol, K 1 70.13) of 16 January 2008.

Directives and recommendations

- Directive for application of soil protection regulations (K 1 70.13 - RSOL), 24 January 2014.
- GESDEC, 2018. *Guide for construction site waste*. 116
- ECOMAT, 2016. *Guide for reuse of unpolluted excavation materials*. 48 p.
- OFEV, 2015. *Soils and buildings. State of the art and practices*. Knowledge of the environment. 113 p.
- OFEV, 2022. *Building without damaging soils*.
- OFEV, 2001. *Comments on the ordinance of 1st July 1998 regarding soil pollution (OSol)*. The practical environment. Updated in 2005. 46 p.
- OFEFP, 2001. *Instructions: evaluation and use of earth materials*. The practical environment. 22 p.
- OFEV, 1999. *Directive for reuse, treatment and storage of excavation materials and spoil* (Directive regarding excavation materials).
- DETA, DGE, GESDEC. *Plan for measures regarding soil protection 2015 – 2018*.
- Standard SN 640 581, 2017. *Terrassement, sol. Protection des sols et construction*.
- GESDEC, OCEV, DT, 2019, *Soil protection on construction sites - Minimum content of a soil management concept*

Note: The section covering soil protection focuses mainly on the management of surface layers A and B (topsoil and arable layer). Deeper layers are not considered soil.

Consequence:Construction site phase:

During the construction phase, all soil protection requirements must be met. In particular, soils must be stripped, stored and, where necessary, reintroduced in compliance with current legislation.

Stockpiles of earth materials will, wherever possible, be placed at the edge of the perimeter to act as noise barriers throughout the construction phase.

Operational phase:

The project will require permanent soil stripping on the land used for the surface sites, resulting in the permanent loss of soil over large surfaces, including crop rotation areas (SDA).

Crop rotation areas refer to arable lands that are best suited for agriculture. These areas are included in the cantonal master plan, which must guarantee a quota of 8,400 ha of SDA to meet the needs of the population in the event of supply disruptions.

Because of the agronomic value is likely high for the land removed from agricultural uses, the land used for the project constitutes a negative impact. Measures to minimise the impact of the sites' surface area will therefore have to be considered (foreseen construction of certain buildings).

The project must incorporate the maximum amount of reused earth materials (topsoil and sub-layer) for the landscaping of the sites.

6.4.8. Polluted sites

Federal legislation

- Environmental protection act (LPE, 814.01) of 7 October 1983.
- Ordinance on the remediation of polluted sites (OSites, 814.680) of 26 August 1998.
- Ordinance relating to the tax for the remediation of contaminated sites (OTAS, 814.681) of 26 September 2008.

Cantonal legislation

- Federal law for legislation relating to contaminated sites (LaLSC, K 1 71) in force since 27 March 2003.

Directives and recommendations

- OFEV, 2006. *Directive for the recovery of mineral waste from construction site*. The practical environment. 2nd updated version. 34 p.
- OFEV, 2016. *Construction projects and polluted sites. A module of the implementation aid "General management of polluted sites"*. The practical environment series. 28 p.

Consequence:

Construction site phase:

In principle, the project site does not include any plots of land listed in the cantonal register of polluted sites. However, the absence of any entry in the register of polluted sites does not mean that the excavated material is not polluted.

If the presence of polluted materials is detected during the construction phase, special investigations will have to be carried out. Depending on the nature of the pollutants and their concentration, these materials will have to be sorted and disposed of through appropriate and approved channels (recycling, treatment and/or final disposal), in accordance with OLED. Earthworks involving polluted materials will be subject to environmental monitoring by a specialised engineer.

Any construction project affecting polluted site areas listed in the cantonal register (access shafts, excavations, drilling, etc.) will only be authorized if the terms of Article 3 of OSites are met, meaning primarily that the project must not create a need for remediation.

Operational phase:

Not concerned.

6.4.9. Waste and environmentally hazardous substances

Federal legislation

- Environmental protection act (LPE, 814.01) of 7 October 1983.
- Federal ordinance on the limitation and disposal of waste (OLED, 814.600) of 4 December 2015.
- Ordinance on waste movements (OMoD, RS 814.610) of 22 June 2005.
- DETEC Ordinance on lists of waste movements (LMoD, RS 814.610.1) of 18 October 2005.
- Ordinance on reduction of risks related to the use of particularly hazardous substances, preparations and objects (ORRChem, RS 814.81) of 18 May 2005.

Cantonal legislation

- Waste management act (LGD, L 1 20) of 20 May 1999.
- Regulations for implementing the waste management act (RGD, L 1 20.01) of 28 July 1999.

Directives and recommendations

- OFEV, 2006. *OMoD and LMoD implementation guide*. As of March 14 2006. 41 p.
- OFEV, 2003. *Instructions: Waste and materials management for projects subject or not to an environmental impact study*. Waste. The practical environment series. 11 p.
- OFEFP, 2001. *Instructions: Evaluation and use of earth materials (earth materials guide)*. The practical environment series. 22 p.
- OFEV, 2006. Directive for the recovery of mineral waste from construction site. Bituminous and non-bituminous road demolition materials, demolition concrete, unsorted materials. The practical environment. 2nd updated edition. 34 p.
- OFEV, 1997. Waste. Directive for the recovery of mineral waste from construction site (bituminous and non-bituminous road demolition materials, demolition concrete, unsorted mineral materials). The practical environment series. 24 p.
- GESDEC, 2018. Guide for construction site waste. 116 p.
- ECOMAT, 2016. *Guide for the reuse of unpolluted excavated materials*, 48 p.
- GESDEC, *Waste management plan for canton of Geneva 2014-2017*, adopted by the Conseil d'État on 25 March 2015. 72 p.
- GESDEC, 2004. Directives for disposal of construction waste, of 27 February 2004.
- GESDEC, 2002. *Cantonal waste management concept*, 30 p.
- OCEV, DT, 2021, *Waste management plan 2020-2025*, adopted by the Conseil d'État. 166 p.
- Swiss Society of Engineers and Architects, 2023 *Limitation and management: of construction waste*. Standard SIA 430 28 p.

Consequence:Construction site phase:

The FCC project will generate a large amount of excavated material. Its reuse should be given priority. A management concept will have to be created for the excavation material. It will define, as precisely as possible, the nature of the rock formations and unconsolidated sediments concerned, so as to be able to assess the potential for reuse.

The canton of Geneva is particularly hard hit by a lack of landfill sites for the final disposal of excavated materials.

With this in mind, it will be necessary to forge partnerships with companies that own material processing sites to maximise reuse.

A waste management plan for the construction site must also be drawn up before the start of construction. It will specify the different types of waste, and the measures to be implemented to ensure optimal collection and reuse, treatment or elimination (disposal channels), in line with recommendations and legal requirements.

Operational phase:

The project will promote, as far as possible, the limitation and sorting of waste on operating sites.

6.4.10. Environmentally hazardous organisms*Federal legislation*

- Ordinance for protection against major accidents (OPAM, RS 814.012) of 1st June 2015.

Directives and recommendations

- ARE/OFEV/OFT/OFEN/OFROU/DETEC, 2022. *Planning guide - Coordination of land-use planning and prevention of major accidents*. The practical environment series. 64 p.
- OFEV, 2024. *Quantitative thresholds in accordance with the ordinance for major accidents (OPAM). A module from the guide for the ordinance for major accidents* (4th updated edition). 79 p.

Consequence:Construction and operational phases:

Impacts are related to the risk of colonisation by invasive species and, during the construction phase, to the risk of propagation through the importing of contaminated soil.

Industrial sites are particularly at risk from invasive species. The landscaping concept to be developed for the site will have to take account of this problem and include areas to promote biodiversity, which will be monitored to avoid any introduction of invasive species.

Where necessary, during the construction site phase, the usual preventive measures (growing grass on stockpiles of earth materials) and control measures for invasive species (removal of seedlings or young plants and disposal for incineration) will have to be implemented.

6.4.11. Major accident prevention and disaster protection

Federal legislation

- Ordinance for protection against major accidents (OPAM) of 1st June 2015.

Recommendations, standards and directives

- ARE/OFEV/OFT/OFEN/OFROU/DETEC, 2022. *Planning guide - Coordination of land-use planning and prevention of major accidents*. The practical environment series. 64 p.
- OFEV, 2024. *Quantitative thresholds in accordance with the ordinance for major accidents (OPAM). A module from the guide for the ordinance for major accidents*. (3rd updated edition).

Consequence:

During the technical development phase, CERN will study the nature and quantity of substances that are present on the site and potentially hazardous according to the OPAM. The risk studies produced by CERN will have to be reviewed in the light of any changes in the storage and management of these hazardous substances as part of the project.

6.4.12. Forest conservation

Federal legislation

- Environmental protection act (LPE, 814.01) of 7 October 1983.
- Federal forestry act (LFo, RS 921.0) of 4 October 1991.
- Forestry ordinance (OFo, RS 921.01) of 30 November 1992.

Cantonal legislation

- Forestry act (LForêts, M 5 10) of 20 May 1999.
- Regulations for implementing the forestry act (RForêts, M 5 10.01) of 22 August 2000.

Consequence:

The PB site is located near a forest, but is not affected by the project.

In accordance with the forestry act (LFo, article 17), buildings and installations in the vicinity of forests may only be authorised if they do not jeopardise their conservation, treatment or use. In Geneva, article 11 of the forestry act (M 5 10) sets the minimum distance between buildings and facilities and the forest edge at 20 meters.

The Département du territoire (DT) may, after consultation with the department, the municipality, the commission for monuments, nature and sites and the advisory commission on biological diversity, grant exemptions for:

- buildings or facilities of general interest whose location is dictated by their purpose;
- small-scale constructions adjoining the main building or renovations, reconstructions, conversions, and slight extensions to existing buildings;
- buildings that respect the alignment set out in a land-use plan or an alignment plan, or that form part of an alignment of existing buildings, provided that the new building is erected on land in a construction zone and located at least ten metres from the edge of the forest, and that it does not affect the biological value of the forest edge.

6.4.13. Flora, fauna and biotopes

Federal legislation

- Environmental protection act (LPE, 814.01) of 7 October 1983.
- Nature and landscape protection act (LPN, RS 451) of 1st July 1966.
- Ordinance on nature and landscape protection (OPN, RS 451.1) of 16 January 1991.
- Ordinance relating to the federal inventory of landscapes, sites and natural monuments (OIFP, RS 451.11) of 29 March 2017.
- Ordinance on waterfowl and migratory bird reserves of international and national importance (OROEM, RS 922.32) of 21 January 1991.
- Ordinance on the protection of amphibian breeding sites of national importance (OBat, RS 451.34) of 15 June 2001.
- Law on hunting and the protection of wild mammals and birds (Hunting act LChP, RS 922.0) of 20 June 1986.
- Ordinance on hunting and the protection of wild mammals and birds (Hunting ordinance OChP, RS 922.01) of 29 February 1988.
- Federal law on the protection of animals (LPA, RS 455) of 16 December 2005.
- Regulations for implementing the federal law on the protection of animals (RaLPA, M 3 50.02) of 15 June 2011.
- Ordinance on the protection of animals (OPAn, RS 455.1) of 23 April 2008.
- Ordinance on the protection of plants against particularly harmful pests (OPV, RS 916.20) of 31 October 2018.
- Ordinance on the use of organisms in the environment (ODE, RS 814.911) of 10 September 2008.
- Ordinance on the protection of alluvial plains of national importance (OZA, RS 451.31) of 28 October 1992.
- Ordinance on the protection of low marshes of national importance (OBM, RS 451.33) of 7 September 1994.
- Ordinance on the protection of dry grasslands and pastures of national importance (OPPS, RS 451.37) of 13 January 2010.

Cantonal legislation

- Biodiversity act (LBio, M 5 15) of 14 September 2012.
- Regulations for implementing the biodiversity act (RBio, M 5 15.01) of 8 May 2013.
- Law on the protection of monuments, nature and sites (LPMNS, L 4 05) of 4 June 1976.
- General regulations for application of the law on the protection of monuments, nature and sites (RPMNS, L 4 05.01) of 29 November 1976.
- Regulations for the protection of the landscape, natural environments and flora of 25 July 2007 (RPPMF, L 4 05.11)
- Fauna act (LFaune, M 5 05) of 7 October 1993 and amendment of 26 January 2024.
- Regulations for application of the fauna act (RFaune, M 5 05.01) of 13 April 1994.
- Regulations for the conservation trees (RCVA, L 4 05.04) of 27 October 1999.
- Law for the promotion of measures to enhance the biodiversity and quality of farming landscapes (LMBA, M 5 30) of 14 November 2014.
- Regulations for application of the law for the promotion of measures to enhance the biodiversity and quality of farming landscapes (RMBA, M 5 30.01) of 14 January 2015.
- Biodiversity act (Lbio) of 14 September 2012 and its regulations for implementation.

Directives and recommendations

- Conservatoire et jardins botaniques (CJBG). Red list of vascular plants in the canton of Geneva. Updated in 2019.
- Conservatoire et jardins botaniques (CJBG). Priority list of vascular plants of Geneva.
- Direction générale de l'agriculture et de la nature (DGAN), 2012. "Flora action plan" sheets.
- DGAN, 2006. "Invasive species" sheets.
- DGAN, 2016. Directive for pruning, trimming and felling.
- OCAN, 2020. Directive on compensatory planting (3rd version).
- Direction générale de la nature et du paysage (DGNP), 2013. Directive for tree planting and maintenance.
- DGNP, 2008. Directive on measures to be taken when working near trees.
- DGNP, 2008. Tree conservation directive. Retention criteria and reasons for felling.
- DGAN, 2008. Guidelines for tree transplanting.
- OCAN, 2018. Geneva Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (SBG-2030)¹¹⁶.
- OCAN, 2020. Biodiversity Plan 2020-2023 from the Geneva Biodiversity Strategy 2030¹¹⁷.

¹¹⁶ <https://www.ge.ch/document/7302/telecharger>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.ge.ch/document/7302/annexe/1>

Consequence:Construction site phase:

During the impact study phase, independent consultants will carry out inventories of the flora to identify protected species affected by the project. Inventories of fauna will also be carried out to define the species to be taken into account in the compensatory concepts.

Any cutting of plants will require authorisation from the Office cantonal de l'agriculture et de la nature (OCAN). The cutting request must be accompanied by an external landscaping plan showing the trees to be felled, those to be kept and those to be replanted as part of the building layout. Preservation is systematically given priority.

Operational phase:

Depending on the identified impacts, compensatory concepts will be drawn up for the site, incorporating a range of measures such as the installation of nesting boxes, the creation of surfaces conducive to biodiversity, rooftop vegetation, planting, etc., all of which can host the species to be enhanced.

6.4.14. Landscapes and sites

Federal legislation

- Environmental protection act (LPE, 814.01) of 7 October 1983.
- Territorial planning act (LAT, RS 700) of 22 June 1979.
- Ordinance on territorial planning (OAT, RS 700.1) of 28 June 2000.
- Nature and landscape protection act (LPN, RS 451) of 1st July 1966.
- Ordinance on nature and landscape protection (OPN, RS 451.1) of 16 January 1991.
- Ordinance relating to the federal inventory of landscapes, sites and natural monuments (OIFP, RS 451.11) of 29 March 2017.

Cantonal legislation

- Law on the protection of monuments, nature and sites (LPMNS, L 4 05) of 4 June 1976.
- General regulations for application of the law on the protection of monuments, nature and sites (RPMNS, L 4 05.01) of 29 March 2023.
- Regulations for the protection of the landscape, natural environments and flora (RPPMF, L 4 05.11) of 25 July 2007
- Cantonal law for implementing the federal territorial planning act (LaLAT, L 1 30), of 4 June 1987.
- Cantonal regulations for the conservation of trees (RCVA, L 4 05.04), of 27 October 1999.

Regulatory elements and directives

- Standard VSS 640577 Association Suisse des professionnels de la route et des transports. Earth-works/Protection of trees and shrubs. 1 March 2003.
- Recommendations for the protection of trees. Union Suisse des Services des Parcs et Promenades (VSGG/USSP).
- DGAN, 2016. Directive for pruning, trimming and felling.
- OCAN, 2020. Directive on compensatory planting (3rd version).
- DGNP, 2013. Directive for tree planting and maintenance.
- DGNP, 2008. Directive on measures to be taken when working near trees.
- DGNP, 2008. Tree conservation directive. Retention criteria and reasons for felling.
- DGAN, 2008. Guidelines for tree transplanting.
- OCAN, 2008. Guideline regarding the Landscape Development Plan (PAP)¹¹⁸.

¹¹⁸ <https://www.ge.ch/document/13695/telecharger>

Consequence:Construction site phase:

Where necessary, noise barriers should be incorporated, which will also to reduce the visual impact of construction work.

Operational phase:

The visual impact of the site should be integrated at an early stage in the architectural concept of the sites in order to be minimised. This is to take place during a public consultation phase before the technical developments are finalised.

6.4.15. Historical monuments and archaeological sites*Federal legislation*

- Ordinance relating to the federal inventory of landscapes, sites and natural monuments (OIFP, RS 451.11) of 29 March 2017.

Cantonal legislation

- Cantonal law on the protection of monuments, nature and sites (LPMNS, L 4.05) of 4 June 1976.
- Miscellaneous buildings and facilities act (LCI, L 5 05) of 14 April 1988.

Consequence:

No historical monuments or archaeological sites are affected by the project. This paragraph is not applicable.

6.5. PRIORITISATION OF EXAMINED CONSTRAINTS

The constraints identified in the area covered by the FCC study and their consequences have an impact on the sensitivity of the project layout.

Section 2.5 provides a detailed presentation of the constraints identified and their prioritisation.

6.6. GENERAL INFORMATION ON ACCESS ANALYSIS

Access is a major issue. It particularly concerns the construction phase, during which access will have to ensure it is possible to:

- remove the excavated materials;
- bring the necessary construction equipment and materials for the civil engineering work and the scientific machines.

For each potential site, an analysis of possible access points is carried out at three levels:

1. **Large scale:** to identify connections to the main road networks and railways,
2. **Medium scale:** to specify the roads used (mainly departmental roads) to reach the main road network,
3. **Local scale:** to specify the connection to the plot of land.

The access analysis presented in this document is a summary of detailed analysis sheets, which can be referred to for further details. The detailed data sheets include images of each of the described constraints to better understand them.

Cross-sections used for lane widening or new road sections:

Some sections of local and departmental roads have clearances that are clearly unsuitable for high volumes of heavy goods vehicle traffic. These portions have been identified and indicated in this report. On the other hand, certain necessary structural reinforcements have not yet been identified, and will require discussions with the various managing authorities (state government, departmental councils, municipalities). This is why a review of the foreseen routes will be carried out in due course with the managing authorities and stakeholders in order to confirm the design hypotheses and determine the structural reinforcements required on these road networks (roadway structures, engineering structures).

In certain cases, it is necessary to widen and reinforce sections of municipal or departmental roads which do not have a suitable clearance for high volumes of heavy goods vehicle traffic.

For the road widening work, in order for two heavy goods vehicles to pass each other at reduced speed, a minimum cross-section of 5.50 m of roadway with two 0.50 m shoulders is required (Illustration 156).

Illustration 156: Standard cross-section for widening of existing lanes.

Some plots of land are connected to the nearest road by new access routes. These lanes, which will be located on the plots of land obtained for the sites, may be smaller in size: widths of 4.00 m for the roadway and 0.50 m for the shoulders. This reduced section will require instructions to be given to the drivers of the vehicles concerned (Illustration 157).

Illustration 157: Standard cross-section for new access routes (on land taken for the construction site).

6.7. CONNECTION TO MOTORWAY SERVICE AREAS

This layout study examines the feasibility of connections to the motorway network for the removal of materials and the supply of equipment during the construction phase.

The possibility of obtaining direct connections is a goal in the general interest, aimed at limiting the impact of the project, particularly during the construction phase. The specific technical choices will be made later, during the project development and preparation phase, by CERN member states and the international scientific community.

To verify the technical, legal and financial feasibility of direct access to motorways, a file was compiled for this purpose and submitted on 14 September, 2022 to the competent authority for granting concessions: the Direction générale des infrastructures, des transports et des mobilités (DGITM):

Direction générale des infrastructures, des transports et des mobilités / Direction des mobilités routières / Sous-direction des financements innovants et du contrôle des concessions autoroutières / Chef du Bureau des services aux usagers et de la comodalité,

Direction générale des infrastructures, des transports et des mobilités / Direction des mobilités routières / Sous-direction des financements innovants et du contrôle des concessions autoroutières / Chef du Bureau du patrimoine et de l'aménagement,

The feasibility of four new connections to the motorway network was analysed for the following sites:

- PD site in Nangy (on the A40 motorway),
- PF site in Eteaux/La Roche-sur Foron (on the A410 motorway),
- PG site in Charvonnex/Groisy (on the A40 motorway),
- PJ site in Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens (on the A410 motorway).

Illustration 158: Map showing the location of the studied motorway connections (via service areas).

The conclusions of these discussions were as follows:

- the described concepts are acceptable to the DGITM, and loading off-area is preferred;
- discussions were focused on adjustments, with the final decisions to be made with the operator in the project phase;
- the procedure for submitting an application in the future was specified;
- the proposed justifications, in the general interest, are acceptable;
- entrances and exits will need to be equipped with detection devices to manage tolls.

The preferred solutions for connections to service areas are presented¹¹⁹ below in this report.

¹¹⁹ Detailed report: FCC-2204270900_Faisabilite_connexions_autoroutes_V0100

6.8. GENERAL INFORMATION ON SURFACE SITES

6.8.1. Elements relating to surface sites

The surface sites are used to:

- build underground tunnels and caverns;
- install the particle accelerators;
- assemble and install detectors for the experiments;
- provide resources to the machinery: electricity, cooling water, fresh air, cryogenic systems for cooling magnets and radio frequency systems, and communication and data transmission lines.

There are two types of surface sites:

- scientific sites,
- technical sites.

The FCC scenario can accommodate up to four experiments. Consequently, four surface sites can be scientific sites. The working hypothesis foresees an initial phase of operation with a lepton collider (FCC-ee) with two experiments, followed by a hadron collider (FCC-hh) with four experiments. A scientific site is different from a technical site due to the presence of additional elements, such as infrastructure for assembling, testing and installing the experiment detector, a computing centre, and facilities for researchers working on site to assemble, test, install and conduct the experiment (e.g. control room, meeting room, offices, workshops).

The type and size of surface constructions depend mainly on the employed technologies. As these technologies will only be known once the technical development of the accelerators and experiments has been finalised, in around 2035 for the lepton collider and around 2055 for the hadron collider, it is not possible to provide reliable specifications in 2024, one to three decades ahead of time. Concepts for surface sites and their layout are therefore based on technologies available today, and take into account assumptions that their efficiency will be optimised. This approach makes it possible to present possible perimeters. The hypotheses used for the surface sites are also based on the fact that electrical substations are located on the sites. This choice remains to be confirmed or adapted in coordination with RTE (France) and Swissgrid (Switzerland), while taking into account the technological choices for the power distribution configuration that best meets the needs of the particle accelerator. The surface area of the sites also takes into account the hypotheses selected to properly integrate the site in its environment. Depending on the final layout, the choice of building materials and the architecture may change. For example, it is also conceivable that certain systems, such as cooling infrastructures, may have to be relocated with respect to the shaft if this allows for better integration in the landscape and a simpler, more efficient supply of resources. Such developments will be covered through an iterative approach in later phases of the project, after the exploratory technical feasibility phase.

A single building can house several pieces of equipment. The following table shows the use of the concerned equipment (Table 30).

Table 30: Use of equipment on the sites.

Area	Description:
Site	Site features such as parking lots, roads, gates, entrances
Underground	Elements required above ground to build underground
Utilities	General operating services not strictly related to the accelerator or the experiment (sanitation, water and normal power supply)
Magnets	Components required for magnet testing and installation
Radiofrequency	Components required for testing, installation and operation of radiofrequency systems
Power supply	Systems needed to power the accelerator and the experiment
Electrical distribution	Above-ground systems for power conversion and transmission to the underground machinery
Experience	Systems required to build, test, install and operate the experiment
Cooling	Water and air cooling systems for the accelerator and the experiment
Ventilation	Ventilation systems for tunnels and caverns close to shafts
Vacuum	Systems to create a vacuum in the accelerator
Cryogenic	Cryogenic cooling systems for the accelerator and the experiment
Transport	Transport and management systems for equipment such as cranes, elevators and storage, loading and unloading areas
Safety	Personal protection systems such as first-aid equipment, firefighting equipment and access systems
ICT	Information and communications technology, e.g. computer centre

A scientific site where an experiment is installed usually includes the following elements:

- an assembly, test and installation hall for the experiment;
- a building at the main shaft site to install the experiment and provide access to the main cavern;
- a building at the secondary shaft site for access to the service cavern;
- a compressed air building;
- a building to store and supply working gas for the experiment;
- a building for electronic equipment, close to the shaft;
- a ventilation station close to the shaft;
- a water pumping station, with chillers to run the cooling water circuit;
- a cooling station (exchangers);
- a storage area (shed) and workshops that can be integrated in the experiment assembly hall;
- a site access building with offices, meeting rooms and, possibly, a computing centre;
- a building to transport equipment and materials between the surface and underground for radiological analysis;
- space to unload materials and equipment and to enable trucks to manoeuvre and turn;
- a site for waste sorting and collection facilities;
- an electrical substation.

A technical site usually includes the following elements:

- a building at the shaft site for access to the service cavern;
- a building to store and supply working gas for the experiment;
- a building for electronic equipment, close to the shaft;
- a ventilation station close to the shaft;
- a water pumping station, with chillers to run the cooling water circuit;
- a cooling station (exchangers);
- a storage area (shed);
- space to unload materials and equipment and to enable trucks to manoeuvre and turn;
- a site for waste sorting and collection facilities;
- an electrical substation;
- at two of the four technical sites, a cryogenic cooling system for radiofrequency systems.

The surface area for the constructed buildings and the storage and manoeuvring areas at a technical site generally does not exceed 25,000 m² (2.5 ha). A scientific site generally accommodates 40,000 m² (4 ha) of buildings. Taking into account the roads and access means required for the sites, buffer zones and the aim of integrating the site into the landscape, a technical site generally requires four hectares of land, compared with six for a scientific site.

Illustration 159 below shows the elements that can be found at a surface site, and indicates the distances required between constructions to ensure adequate access for the loading and unloading of equipment and for manoeuvring.

Illustration 159: Example of elements on a scientific site, highlighting the need for space to manoeuvre between buildings. This diagram serves only to illustrate the principle, and is not intended to be a hypothesis for possible implementation.

6.8.2. Iterative integration process

As part of the feasibility study, surface sites are specified through an iterative process:

- for the layout: theoretical surface areas of roughly five hectares for technical sites and seven hectares for scientific sites make it possible to examine the feasibility of a site;
- optimisations and shared usage opportunities are then developed wherever possible to reduce land take and impacts;
- indicative representations of surface sites are then produced, accompanied by a description when available (in progress);
- subsequent stages will focus on architectural and landscape integration.

The importance of architectural and design integration, as well as vegetation, should be emphasised (Illustration 160).

Illustration 160: This illustration of an existing building shows the importance of the process to be put in place right from the design phase.

6.8.3. Amount of personnel at sites during operation

The amount of personnel at the scientific sites (experiment sites) and technical sites varies according to the operating periods.

Estimates based on feedback from existing LHC sites are presented below.

Amount of personnel at a scientific site:

For informational purposes, Table 31 gives an estimate of the daily amount of personnel at the scientific sites.

Table 31: Estimate of amount of personnel at scientific sites.

Scientific site	Installation	Operation	Maintenance phase	Long shutdown
Period	5 years	10 months	2 months	every 3 years
Staff per day	200 to 300 technicians	4 to 8 team members and 12 to 16 technicians	100 technicians	200 to 300 technicians

Amount of personnel at a technical site:

Table 32 gives a rough estimate of the daily amount of personnel at the technical sites.

Table 32: Estimate of amount of personnel at the technical sites.

Technical site	Installation	Operation	Maintenance phase	Long shutdown
Period	5 years	10 months	2 months	every 3 years
Staff per day	100 technicians	0 to 10 team members or technicians depending on the system	15 to 30 technicians (+ 5 for fire safety intervention)	0 to 100 technicians depending on the system

7. THE PA SITE - FERNEY-VOLTAIRE (AIN, FRANCE)

Chapter 7 provides a detailed presentation of the location environment of the PA site in Ferney-Voltaire. The description of the site and its environment is followed by an urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (current constraints) and an analysis of access, particularly connections to the railway, highway and local road networks.

The site boundary presented in this chapter is a conceptual draft and does not necessarily correspond to the exact boundary currently being considered. Section 15.3 presents the latest version of this boundary in detail.

7.1. DESCRIPTION

The site is located in the municipality of Ferney-Voltaire in the Ain department, close to the Swiss border and Geneva (Illustration 161).

The site is in the immediate vicinity of Point 8 of the CERN LHC, which will enable synergy between the sites. The CERN site in Meyrin is also nearby, around 4 km away.

The site is bordered to the east by the "Espace Candide" shopping centre and to the west by a residential area under construction north of the "Route de Meyrin" (RD35) road.

The PA site is decisive for the whole scenario, as it is the base point for the footprint.

Illustration 161: Map of footprint: location of PA site.

The WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical point for scenario PA31-4.0 are:

- Latitude: 46.2480475° N,
- Longitude : 6.0986019° E.

The PA site is a scientific site. The main shaft is located approximately 30 metres to the left of the theoretical point, directly on the footprint.

The elevation is 422 m. Shaft depth is 201 m.

The following types of plots are foreseen (Illustration 162):

- main site (north): approx. 5.3 ha,
- optional site (south): approx. 2.5 ha.

The list of concerned cadastral plots is shown in Appendix 16.3.

Illustration 162: Map showing the location of the foreseen plots of land for the PA site (December 2023).

The **characteristics and constraints** of this site are as follows:

- small size: about 4 ha, 110 to 150 m x 280 m;
- single shaft to the experiment cavern west of the nominal point;
- single shaft for access to the service cavern inside the ring: either close to the experiment shaft, or 300 m inside the ring at the Point 8 site of the LHC;
- visibility constraints due to the presence of residential buildings and a planned construction project on the other side of the road:
 - assembly hall for the the experiment with the lowest possible height,
 - reuse of Point 8 of the LHC as much as possible,
 - possibility of extending Point 8 of the LHC southwards,
 - integration with Point 8 of the LHC via a 300 m long underground gallery or access tunnel to the collider and the “Chemin des Prés Jins” road,
- difficult integration in the urban setting:
 - alignment and architectural coherence with the shopping centre (height, volumes), visibility,
 - difficult traffic conditions requiring careful planning of construction activities.

The main **opportunities** offered by the site are as follows (Illustration 163):

- synergies and shared use of equipment with Point 8 of the LHC, including a heating network;
- visitors centre;
- close to the Espace Candide shopping centre;
- nearby residential area (eco-district) and new hospital project;
- a mixed development zone (ZAC) under construction and the “Cité internationale des savoirs” in the future;
- close to CERN campuses (Meyrin and Prévessin) and synergies with their services;
- wide range of housing, businesses, educational and public services offered by Ferney-Voltaire;
- supply of heat to Ferney-Voltaire, the airport and parts of Geneva;
- close to the GeniTerre and GeniLac heating networks;
- connection confirmed to the Lake Geneva water extraction station.

Illustration 163: Map of main opportunities near the PA site.

Land

The site is made up of (Illustration 164):

- mostly private plots of land,
- state-owned plots; Point 8 of the LHC at CERN,
- approximately 1 ha of municipal land to the south of Point 8 of the LHC.

Illustration 164: Map of land owners at the PA site. Source: anonymous parcel register.

Map of agricultural activities

Only one agricultural activity appears to be affected for both polygons (Illustration 165).

Illustration 165: Map of agricultural activities at the PA site. Source: Graphical parcel register.

7.2. URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

7.2.1. State of the premises

The site is located in the municipality of Ferney-Voltaire, close to the municipality of Prévessin-Moëns and the Swiss border. From an orographic point of view, the zone is flat, with the Jura mountain range behind it.

The zone is made up of a variety of elements: agricultural and forestry zones, commercial zones, residential areas, new eco-districts, areas close to the Swiss border and the presence of an airport. The presence of Point 8 of the CERN LHC is also worth mentioning.

It should be noted that, throughout this report, arrows are used on the maps to show where photos were taken. These arrows indicate the general direction of the photo, and not the angle.

Illustration 166: Map showing location of photos taken at the PA site.

View of the site, currently occupied by a field
(number 1 on Illustration 166)

Shopping centre near the site
(number 2 on Illustration 166)

Existing CERN site
(number 3 on Illustration 166)

Reception area for voyagers
(number 4 on Illustration 166)

Small residential area
(number 5 on Illustration 166)

New eco-district
(number 6 on Illustration 166)

Illustration 167: View of the site from the intersection, number 7 on the photo location map.

Illustration 168: View of the site alongside the Leclerc store, number 8 on the photo location map.

An eco-district is currently under construction near the site.

The architectural and landscape context is highly contrasting.

As far as the project's acceptability is concerned, the region already has a long history of cooperation with CERN.

7.2.2. Urban planning, architecture and landscape

Geneva's high economic attractiveness has led over the years to a steady increase in the cross-border population living in France. This unique economic and social context is reflected in the area, which is characterised by the presence of large residential blocks and by real estate speculation.

In terms of urban planning, there are many small villages, often with a small historic centre, next to large residential districts (due to the proximity of Geneva). In light of recent developments, the predominant architectural style in the area is contemporary. The CERN infrastructure (buildings, electrical equipment, etc.) has left its mark on the landscape.

It should be noted that the photographs presented here are intended to provide some context for the site's surroundings, and in no way indicate the future architecture of the sites.

Illustration 169: View of the plain, with the Jura in the background (left). Succession of residential areas (right).

7.3. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

Summary map of constraints

The following map summarises the environmental constraints (Illustration 170).

Illustration 170: Map of environmental constraints around the PA site.
An ecological corridor is present in the area (green line; source: SITG).

North polygon

The north polygon is located in a protected agricultural zone (Illustration 170): this protection imposed by prefectural decree could be lifted, also by prefectural decree, and would require the adoption of compensatory measures. A natural area protected because of its importance for ecological continuity extends along the north-eastern and south-eastern edges of the site. This continuity must be preserved. The sector is intended to become part of the artificialised areas of Ferney-Voltaire over the medium term. The proximity to urban projects on the other side of the RD road will need to be studied. In particular, the visibility constraints due to the presence of residential buildings and a construction project planned on the other side of the road will lead to the design of buildings as low as possible, especially for the experiment assembly hall. The site therefore seems feasible.

South polygon

Part of the South sector is located in a protected agricultural zone (Illustration 170): this protection, imposed by prefectural decree, could be lifted, also by prefectural decree, and would require the adoption of compensatory measures. Construction in this area would require the relocation of the reception area for voyagers, and verifications would need to be made to ensure that the wetlands system continues to function, as it would then be enclosed on at least three sides.

Ecological continuity also needs to be maintained (conservation of sufficiently large corridors). However, the site PA (considering both polygons, north and south) is not located in an ecological corridor identified in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes SRADDET.

Water resources

The proposed PA site is in the immediate vicinity of Point 8 of the LHC. In this context, synergy will be sought with regard to water supply. Illustration 171 shows how the site could be supplied from the existing Swiss network. The technical feasibility and necessary capacity were confirmed by SIG in 2023. There would be no adverse effects if connected to the existing line.

Illustration 171: Diagram of the current water supply to Meyrin, with a possible connection to Point 8 of the LHC to supply water to the FCC. Source: SIG.

The CERN 2019-2020 *Environmental Report*¹²⁰ mentions a consumption of 2 006 million litres (2 million m³), taken mainly from the lake (le Vengeron/GeniLac), and also says that this volume is approximately 47% lower than the years of operation of the accelerator.

¹²⁰ <https://hse.cern/fr/rapport-environnement-2019-2020>

7.4. ACCESS ANALYSIS

As the PA site is located close to the border, the possibilities of connecting to the main road networks in the vicinity were examined, both in France and Switzerland.

This document only describes existing networks, and in no way anticipates any subsequent choices. Detailed planning with the French and Swiss traffic authorities will be necessary to determine transport solutions, particularly for excavation materials.

7.4.1. Location in relation to the main road network and railways

Illustration 172: Map of main road network and railways.

Points of interest on map of main road network and railways (Illustration 172):

E5: interchange 5: Meyrin

E7: interchange 7: Grand- Saconnex on the A1

G1: ZI Gare de Meyrin

G2: ZI railway branch lines, south Meyrin

G3: Satigny train station

The following are the access points to the main road network:

1. **The RD 1005** road connects to the A1 motorway at interchange 7: Le Grand-Saconnex (E1),
2. **The A1.** The A1 motorway goes to Lausanne, or to the A41 motorway to Grenoble or Lyon,
3. **Railway:** a railroad track passes close to the site. Three train stations are close, but two seem to be more favourable.

7.4.2. Departmental roads connecting to the main road network

Illustration 173: Map of access routes to the PA site.

Constraints on routes to the main road network (Illustration 173)

Constraint 1: cross-section slightly reduced to 5 m + bicycle lanes (avenue de Mategnin over a 300 m section)

Constraint 2: French customs station

Constraint 3: Meyrin customs station

Constraint 4: close to residential areas

Red hatched constraint: Meyrin urbanised zone

Illustration 174: Cross-section of Avenue de Mategnin at customs (constraint 1).

To the railway for merchandise in an industrial zone

Two routes are represented:

- the most direct has many constraints because it crosses urbanised areas;
- the other route is longer, but crosses less urbanised areas.

Other access routes seem possible and could be studied.

Discussions with the current operators of these railroad hubs should make it possible to obtain a more detailed picture of the possibilities for access and use, and to select the best access.

The distance between the PA site and the potential railway connection point G1 in Switzerland (in Meyrin; see Illustration 175) is around 3.2 km (short route).

Illustration 175: Access to Meyrin train station. Coordinates N46.221460, E6.069372.

The distance between the PA site and the potential railway connection point G2 in Switzerland (Zimeysa, in Meyrin; Illustration 176) is around 4.4 km (long route).

Illustration 176: Access to the railway line in Switzerland. Coordinates N46.222621, E6.083971.

The distance between the PA site and the potential railway connection point G3 in Switzerland (Illustration 177) is around 6.5 km (long route).

Illustration 177: Access to Satigny train station (Switzerland). Coordinates N46.214889, E6.038429.

To A1 motorway via interchange 5

With the exception of constraint no. 1 (reduced cross-section) mentioned above, access to interchange 5 is not particularly difficult. It is located around 3.7 km from the PA site.

To A1 motorway via interchange 7

With the exception of constraint no. 2 (customs) mentioned above, the RD35 and RD 1005 roads do not present any particular constraints. Interchange 7 is about 4 km from the PA site.

7.4.3. Connection to local road network

Illustration 178: Connection of PA site to the local road network.

Connection to the local road network via the RD35 road

The connection to PA3 (Illustration 178) can be made via the existing access route to the RD35 road.

Access to the PA1 location is via the “Chemin des Prés Jins” road, 800 m from the RD35. The first 450 meters are probably large enough for heavy goods vehicles. The last 350 m will probably have to be reinforced and widened (width of less than 3.50 m) at an estimated cost of 280,000 euros.

7.5. SUMMARY OF THE PA SITE

The PA site is located in the municipality of Ferney-Voltaire, in an already highly urbanised area, where a new development could be considered that takes into account the nearby residential blocks to the north.

In environmental terms, the sectors under consideration are covered by orange protections (protected agricultural areas, protected natural areas) which do not appear to be insurmountable if concessions are granted following the application of a rigorous Avoid-Reduce-Compensate approach.

Access to the main road networks seems feasible with a few modifications. A connection to train stations seems technically feasible, but will require discussions with current operators to further define its feasibility.

8. THE PB SITE – PRESINGE/CHOULEX (CANTON OF GENEVA, SWITZERLAND)

Chapter 8 provides a detailed presentation of the location environment of the PB site in Presinge/Choulex. The description of the site and its environment is followed by an urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (current constraints) and an analysis of access, particularly connections to the railway, motorway and local road networks.

The site boundary presented in this chapter is a conceptual draft and does not necessarily correspond to the exact boundary currently being considered. Section 15.3 presents the latest version of this boundary in detail.

8.1. DESCRIPTION

The proposed PB site is located in the municipality of Presinge in the canton of Geneva, Switzerland. It is about 12 km from Geneva (Illustration 179). The municipality borders France.

The site borders the municipality of Choulex, which may be affected by certain areas depending on the polygon selected. Presinge and Choulex are preserved sectors of the canton, in a high-quality natural and agricultural environment.

Illustration 179: Map of footprint: location of PB site.

The WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical point in scenario PA31-4.0 are:

- Latitude: 46.2271027° N,
- Longitude : 6.2374818° E.

The elevation is 422 m. Shaft depth is 201 m. Site PB is a technical site. The shaft can be relocated to either side of the theoretical point to sites with fewer constraints.

Two areas of around 4 ha each were chosen for a site on a large plot of over 100 ha of land belonging to the State of Geneva.

Illustration 180: Cadastral plots taken into consideration to optimise the PB site location (December 2023).

Agricultural plot 2113 (5.7 ha) is located in the municipality of Presinge and is directly connected to the “Route de Jussy” road, in the Girec sector, at the exit from the “L’Avenir” locality (Illustration 180).

Agricultural plot 12530 is located in the municipality of Choulex. It would require the creation of an access point to the “Route de Jussy” road via plot 2113 in the municipality of Presinge, or from the north. Two municipalities would be directly affected if access were via the “Route de Jussy” road.

Both plots of land are partially occupied by woodland: the north-western part of plot 12530 and a wooded strip to the east for plot 2113.

Agricultural plot 2112 is privately owned.

The plots are bounded to the north and east by the Nant du Paradis stream. This zone is partially developed, with trees and reeds providing habitat for small wildlife such as amphibians (frogs and toads). This is a protected area to be avoided (red zone). To the south of the identified sector, a house is located on plot 2111 (4 206 m², 33 m long), separated from plot 2113 by plot 2112 (3 693 m², 27 m long). The distance between the house and the candidate site is 40 m.

Several other sites to the east of the “Route de Jussy” road were also considered, but eventually rejected because of their high ecological value, the risk of disturbances to neighbours and conflicts with planned renaturation and soft mobility projects.

The “Route de Jussy” road provides direct access to plot 2113 (Illustration 180). It is for this reason that this plot in Presinge, beside the road, is the ideal location.

The **characteristics and constraints** of this site are as follows:

- large plot of land belonging to the canton. The optimum location has yet to be determined with the cantonal authorities;
- major constraints on adjacent plots:
 - environmental protection zone in the forest and along the Nant,
 - biological and agricultural activities,
 - heritage buildings,
 - residential and leisure zones,
 - nature conservation and renaturation policy with local stakeholders,
 - requires excellent environmental and landscape integration.
- road access:
 - relatively narrow “Route de Jussy” road, with bicycle paths,
 - access only via downtown Geneva or Annemasse (border crossing),
- no infrastructure on the site at present.

The main **opportunities** offered by the site are as follows (Illustration 181):

- approximately 16 ha of land owned by the State of Geneva;
- proximity and possible synergy with the Choulex-Vandœuvres fire station;
- Geneva school of landscape, engineering and architecture (HEPIA) and Centre for vocational training in nature and the environment;
- presence of local services in the neighbouring municipalities (Jussy, Choulex, Presinge, Puplinge): possibility of creating partnerships with restaurant services;
- reinforcement of the ecological infrastructure supported by the Nant du Paradis;
- the possibility of setting up a heating network with potential consumers in the vicinity;
- the possibility of using public transport to get to the site (to be studied) and development of bicycle paths planned for 2030;
- the possibility of improving electrical network coverage in the region;
- opportunity for future synergy in terms of education and waste heat recovery with the planned renovation of the Champ-Dollon correctional institution;
- HUG - Hôpital des Trois-Chêne hospital complex nearby.

Illustration 181: Map of main opportunities around the PB site.

8.2. URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

8.2.1. State of the premises

The areas subjected to urban and landscape analyses are located in the Swiss municipalities of Presinge and Choulex.

The region including the Seymaz basin was once a marshy area. The large marshes (Choulex, Le Carre, Meinier, Corsinge and Sionnet) collected or released water, depending on the season, thus regulating the river's flow. Drained at the end of the 19th century to make way for agriculture, wet grasslands only remained at the confluence of the Seymaz and Chambet rivers, where the heart of the former marshes was located, and in the Jussy woods. The renaturation of the Haute-Seymaz, which began in the late 1990s, has rehabilitated these former marshes, which today act as a refuge for characteristic flora and fauna and are an important stopping point for migratory birds. Further downstream, the Seymaz and its wooded belt form an important biological corridor¹²¹.

The “Route de Jussy” road (RC 23, a primary road of the cantonal network) runs alongside the polygon, providing a link to Annemasse in the direction of France, or to downtown Geneva (Illustration 182).

Illustration 182: Map showing the studied areas for the PB site.

¹²¹ État de Genève, Fiche Rivière no. 10, La Seymaz, December 2009.

Illustration 183: Zone of countryside, on the left (number 1 on Illustration 182), Geneva school of landscape, engineering and architecture (HEPIA), on the right (number 2 on Illustration 182).

Illustration 184: View of the site from the forest looking east (number 3 on map showing the location).

Illustration 185: View of the site from “Route de Jussy” road looking west (number 4 on the map showing the location).

8.2.2. Urban planning, architecture and landscape

The area, preserved from urbanisation, retains its rural character. Most of the area is farmland. Residential hamlets with single-family homes, such as Presinge, are also present.

Nearby, a large area is occupied by the Geneva school of landscape, engineering and architecture (HEPIA).

Heritage

There are no heritage constraints relating to building protection measures or listed architectural sites in or near the identified sector. The nearest buildings are located on the Abbaye site and are not directly affected by the project.

On the other hand, the defined sector is surrounded by historical connecting roads (Illustration 186):

- of regional importance: historical route, e.g. “Route de Jussy” road,
- of regional importance: historical route with significant works (GE 100.1/pt.434 - Les Champs d'Arrhes),
- of regional importance: historical route with very significant works (GE 100.1/pt.434 - Les Champs d'Arrhes).

It will be necessary to cooperate with the cantonal authorities to complete the diagnosis and specify the consequences for site access.

Illustration 186: Historical communication routes and points in the analysed area. Source: SITG.

The photographs presented here are intended to provide some context for surroundings of the proposed site. They do not show locations in the immediate vicinity of the PB site.

Illustration 187: View of Domaine de l'Abbaye (700 m east of the site), number 5 on the map showing the site location.

Illustration 188: View of the grasslands around the Domaine de l'Abbaye from the "Chemin de Pré-Rojoux" road, number 5 on the map showing the site location.

Illustration 189: View of the landscape from the "Chemin du Chambet" road looking northeast number 6 on the map showing the location.

8.3. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

Taking into account the most important constraints, risks and developments set out in the 2030 cantonal master plan, a net surface area of roughly four hectares should be allocated to FCC surface facilities, with a constraint concerning crop rotation areas (SDA). The site also lies on an ecological corridor between the forest to the west and the Abbey zone to the east (Illustration 192).

Taking into account the protection zones to be avoided (Illustration 190, in red), a net space of around 4.4 hectares remains for a candidate site on the Presinge territory. If the site is not to be adjacent to the houses in the hamlet of L'Avenir, it could extend onto the lands of Choulex on the neighbouring plot to the west. The same surface space would be available for a site in Choulex, between the forest and the Nant du Paradis.

Illustration 190: Map of environmental constraints around the area analysed for site PB (May 2024). Red zones are to be avoided.

Agricultural plots identified in advance are subject to the federal sectoral plan for crop rotation areas (SDA). Construction could be authorised on the plots through zoning in accordance with local planning regulations and by weighing the benefits. It is also possible to modify the zone at cantonal level. Classification by the canton as a building zone is only possible if it complies with the conditions set out in the land planning ordinance (article 30, paragraph 1bis). While the first option is considered feasible within a ten-year time frame, the second is deemed unrealistic by the cantonal authorities (Département du territoire de l'État de Genève).

Illustration 191: Passage from rural road to farmland in Choulex, after the boundary limit between Presinge and Choulex, halfway between the “Route de Jussy” road and the forest.

The use of any crop rotation area (SDA) listed in a cantonal inventory will in theory need to be compensated for by areas of equivalent size, with their quality taken into account, and with the assistance of the concerned cantons (see principle 14 of the SDA sectoral plan).

Management of hazards

The Choulex plot (plot 12530) is subject to a residual flood hazard from the Seymaz according to the cantonal map or hazards. However, this hazard is considered to be negligible.

The south is bounded by the 100 m-wide gas pipeline exclusion zone on either side of the perimeter (Illustration 192, in blue), which requires an OPAM (major accident) risk study to be carried out in coordination with the relevant national and cantonal authorities.

Illustration 192: Map showing constraint, protection and hazard layers.

It shows a residual area of 3.3 ha (yellow polygon) on the Presinge plot of land. The green arrow indicates the presence of an ecological corridor, the areas with a flood risk are shown in dark green, and the gas pipeline exclusion area in dark blue.

Source: SITG.

Natural environment

The Nant du Paradis (Illustration 194) is located between the plot and a rural road. It is considered by the municipality of Presinge to be "an essential biotope for the region". No impact is foreseen for this site of high natural value (its watercourse, natural environments and habitats).

The ecological quality of this area is recognised at the cantonal and national levels (Illustration 193):

- Federal protection:
 - Federal inventory of fixed amphibian breeding sites. Amphibians are severely threatened. With the exception of the common frog, all the species still present in Switzerland are on the red list of rare and endangered species. The Ordinance on the protection of amphibian breeding sites of national importance is intended to conserve the specific habitats of particularly endangered species.
- Cantonal protection:
 - Priority flora site: These sites are subject to conservation measures and must be taken into account in regional land planning. Priority flora sites are considered at a minimum as species or biotopes worthy of protection as defined in the LPN and the "Règlement sur la protection du paysage, des milieux naturels et de la flore" (RPPMF) L 4 05.11.

Illustration 193: Protection of biodiversity near the area analysed for a site PB.

Illustration 194: View of the farmlands from the rural road running alongside the Nant du Paradis.

The forest to the northwest and southeast of the sector is included in the cantonal forestry register. A precise survey of the forest edges should be carried out as part of the diagnosis.

The ecological infrastructure determined in 2020 (Illustration 195) shows a sector of good quality that contributes to the connectivity of the different environments). The Nant du Paradis and the two forested sectors along the site have been identified as biological corridors and biodiversity reservoirs, for which the connectivity could be increased.

Illustration 195: Connectivity of the ecological infrastructure around the area analysed for a site PB, based on a map by OCAN. Source: SITG.

In addition, the sector in question is at the heart of a black belt (“*trame noire*”) designated by the canton as a “*continuum nocturne*”, or nocturnal continuum (Illustration 196). It will therefore be essential to limit light pollution from the site as much as possible.

Illustration 196: Nocturnal continuum around the area analysed for a site PB.

Illustration 197: View towards the fields of the candidate site and the forest at the end of the fields from the parking lot of the “Route de Jussy” road.

Projects planned or underway in the vicinity to be taken into consideration

The 2030 cantonal master plan (PDCn) identifies a biological corridor on either side of the “Route de Jussy” road at Nant du Paradis. The long-term goal is to ensure the continuity and reinforcement of this corridor in order to ensure a link between the natural areas along the Nant du Paradis to the Blanchard wood.

Possibilities for temporary storage and processing of excavated materials

Excavated materials will need to be temporarily stored on the surface site and, if necessary, on nearby plots for processing before being transported to other locations for reuse or final disposal.

Following a preliminary geomatic analysis and an initial approach, and subject to more specific studies, excavated material could be temporarily stored on around 5 ha of the two sites in Presinge and Choulex (roughly 500,000 m³ of material). Compensation for loss of income due to the impossibility of growing crops during the construction phase remains to be studied.

The two previously mentioned sites are only hypotheses that have not been verified. Detailed analyses will need to be conducted to further investigate those and any other possibilities, and to validate or dismiss them.

The roads leading away from the site are in good condition but not very wide (two lanes, sufficient for cars and ordinary-sized trucks). The “Route de Jussy” road is only one lane at the identified plot of land, as both sides of the road are reserved for bicycles (unmarked centre lane). The roads to the east (Jussy, Meinier and towards La Pallanterie) are narrow and have many traffic calming devices and traffic circles. Traffic is heavy in the mornings. Similarly, the road to Thônex and Chêne-Bourg is well maintained but not designed for heavy traffic. Consequently, careful traffic planning and a concept for transporting excavated material will be required for site activities.

The following section takes a closer look at access.

Opportunities

Two public bus lines (TPG 33 and 86) stop right at the location of the surface site (L'Avenir).

There are opportunities for building an energy network that includes a variety of players:

- HEPIA, located 1.2 km away by road, could benefit from the FCC residual heat for heating purposes, including greenhouses;
- the Abbaye organic farm, located 300 m away, offers the same opportunities (heating for greenhouses, cowsheds for cows and facilities for chickens, riding school, Presinge tennis club);
- the Presinge residence for migrants could also benefit from the supply of residual heat;
- the Puplinge correctional institution;
- the Trois-Chêne hospital in Thônex (a little further away).

With regard to the sharing of other technical infrastructures, such as electricity and telecommunications networks, a detailed analysis would be required to study potential synergy with HEPIA and the municipalities of Presinge and Choulex.

Local and economic sensitivity

This topic should be covered by further analysis, carried out in cooperation with local stakeholders.

Ecological sensitivity

The high ecological value of the land must be respected.

Landscape integration must be anticipated, and a study conducted by professionals who are aware of the particular issues for the sector (Haute-Seymaz).

It would be necessary to negotiate an agreement with the neighbouring houses in L'Avenir.

Existing infrastructures

Today, the plots of land have no technical infrastructure (water, electricity, telecommunications, sanitation). Consultation with the Services Industriels de Genève (SIG) is needed to ensure the best possible connection to urban infrastructure, and to find a way of supplying 6 MW for a tunnel boring machine (TBM) during the construction phase. As the site will have only one shaft and no large underground caverns, two TBMs at this location are ruled out for technical reasons. The feasibility of using a single TBM has been confirmed by SIG.

The site is close to the Meinier network, which has a 300 mm pipe. Distribution capacity is estimated at 100 l/s. A connection with a diameter of 300 mm and a length of 360 m is required for the construction phase. Connecting the PA site to the SIG water system opens up the possibility of supplying lake water to this sector. Agriculture can also benefit from this water supply.

Access to the site from CERN

The plot is directly accessible from the “Route de Jussy” road.

The site is 17.5 km from CERN (Esplanade des Particules, Meyrin) along the route passing through the city of Geneva. The site can be reached in 50 to 60 minutes, either via the “Quai de Coligny” road, along the lake, or via the “Rue de Genève” road passing through Eaux-Vives and Chêne-Bourg. These two roads are unsuitable for frequent work-related travel, and have numerous traffic constraints due to their urban environment (city centre, bridge over the Rhone and lake).

Another route, via the A1 and A40 motorways (France), takes around 40 minutes in good traffic conditions. However, traffic jams are frequent at the Bardonnex border crossing and in the Annemasse area. In addition, the Étrembières-Annemasse-Gaillard-Ville-la-Grand area presents numerous constraints, particularly for the construction phase.

As a result, an alternative solution needs to be found to service the site during construction, installation, maintenance and repair activities.

For the construction phase, local accommodation for workers in Switzerland and France is possible. On the other hand, this is impossible for maintenance, repair or installation activities, which require highly specialised personnel from CERN or LAPP (Annecy). Consequently, a transport system capable of reaching speeds of around 25 km/h in the tunnel is also the subject of a conceptual study.

8.4. ACCESS ANALYSIS

Cooperation with the Swiss and French traffic authorities will be required to determine transport options, particularly for excavated materials. The principle to be applied in this case is for each country to have exclusive responsibility for the materials in its territory.

As the PB site is located close to the border, the possibilities of connections to the surrounding main road networks were examined, and consequently, in both Switzerland and France.

The unique situation of the zone for the PB site should be noted, as it is bordered on the one hand by the lake and on the other by French territory.

8.4.1. Location in relation to main road network and railways

Illustration 198: Main road network and railways around the PB site.

Points of interest on map of main road network and railways (Illustration 198)

Gx: nearby accessible train stations

E1: nearby interchange to reach A411/A40

In Switzerland, there are two train stations (G2 and G3), which are currently used to remove materials from large construction sites. The main road networks are dense but very urbanised.

The site is close to Annemasse, with a dense road network and a railway line running close by the future site.

Future road project: the “Contournement Est” (eastern bypass) in Geneva

In addition to the main road network described above, the future eastern bypass project in Geneva (Illustration 199) should also be noted.

The latest discussions between the public services and CERN indicate a provisional opening date beyond 2045, if current studies confirm the feasibility of the eastern bypass. The study is underway. It will be important to monitor the project's progress and identify potential synergies.

Illustration 199: Eastern bypass project in Geneva. Source: Contournement Est et Traversée du Lac-Étude de projets-Rapport de Synthèse-République et canton de Genève-31.03.2021.

8.4.2. French departmental roads connecting to the Geneva main road network

Illustration 200: Geneva main road network and French departmental network around the PB site.

Constraints on access to the main road network (Illustration 200)

Constraint 1: highly urbanised sectors of Annemasse

Constraint 2: the “Route de Cornière” road, 4 m wide, to be widened over a section approximately 300 m long (estimated cost: approx. €240 000 excluding tax). Utility poles line the road. The cross-section widens as it nears residential areas. The structure of the road pavement will probably have to be reinforced to accommodate the heavy traffic.

Constraint 3: crossing of Vézenaz near residential areas

Constraint 4: route takes the “Quai de Cologny” and “Quai de Gustave-Ador” roads

Constraint 5: highly urbanised sector of Meyrin

To reach the railway (G1) (while avoiding the Puplinge crossing)

Access to the railway is approximately 4.8 km away.

The “Route de Presinge” road (route 2 to avoid Puplinge) has reduced cross-sections of around 5 to 5.50 m (Illustration 201). It should be noted that a study is currently underway to gain a better understanding of how this train station operates.

Illustration 201: Access to the railway line from rue Albert Hénon. Coordinates 46.202727, 6.240267.

To reach the RD 1206 and A411 roads (route 1)

The main road network is around 3.3 km away (RD1205, RD 1206 roads then the A40/A411 interchange).

The main and most significant constraint concerns the crossing of the Annemasse urban zone, with its nearby residential areas. There are raised safety platforms and central traffic islands that can be crossed by heavy goods vehicles.

Illustration 202: Raised safety platforms in the centre of Annemasse.

To reach train stations G2 and G3

These routes, which are 16.3 km long to reach G2 and 26.4 km long to reach to G3, have many constraints. They could be considered for occasional use, but would not be a long-term solution.

The G2 does not have any new available space to build a new branch line or storage area (Illustration 203). An agreement will have to be obtained for the use of an existing branch line.

Two loading platforms are normally used in the Geneva area: CFF and Ducret (few storage possibilities). Today, there are more than two platforms, but some of these are temporary sites and will only remain for as long as it takes to complete major construction projects.

Illustration 203: Location of the G2 platform in Geneva. Map provided by GESDEC.

As for G3, located in the municipality of Meyrin, the sites usually used as loading platforms are the companies SASSO Recyclage and GESA Rail (Illustration 204).

Illustration 204: Location of the G3 platform in Geneva. Map provided by GESDEC.

8.4.3. Connection to local road network

It should be pointed out that the options shown here are provisional. The construction of these access points, even if temporary, could have a major impact on the environment, and in particular on the protection of ecosystems. These environmental constraints will therefore be taken into account (see Illustration 205 and Illustration 206).

Illustration 205: Summary of environmental constraints stemming from options for a PB site in Choulex or Presinge (reference site at the time the study was conducted: October 2023).

Illustration 206: Ecological issues stemming from the PB site options in Choulex or Presinge (reference site at the time the study was conducted: October 2023).

Following the recommendation made by the canton of Geneva when the interdepartmental unit set up for this question provided its support, an exploratory analysis was carried out and a concept for road access to the PB site via Choulex or Presinge was drawn up by an engineering firm with the necessary expertise¹²².

Environmental aspects were analysed in the light of the various constraints. Aspects relating to site accessibility were developed.

The following criteria were analysed:

1. access distance to the plot,
2. the land take and number of owners affected,
3. nature protection (quantitative assessment),
4. ecological infrastructure (quantitative assessment),
5. impact on landscape,
6. disturbances for residents (noise, safety),
7. the impact on traffic management,
8. the impact on soft mobility,

¹²² RGR Ingénieurs Conseils, *Étude pour l'accès routier au site PB à Choulex et Presinge : Final Report*, V3.0, 6 March 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10788385>

A multi-criteria analysis was carried out to recommend one of the five analysed variants (see Illustration 207), taking into account new mobility issues. Several departments from the Republic and Canton of Geneva (cantonal office for transport, cantonal office of agriculture and nature, department of the environment and major hazards) were consulted and were able to comment on this analysis.

Illustration 207: Study of different variants for access to the PB site options.

Variant 4a would only pass through plot 2113 in Presinge. It would therefore not require any land take from private property. If the PB site were to be located on this plot, no land take would be required, including public property. In this respect, this variant is the most advantageous compared with the other variants.

8.5. SUMMARY OF THE PB SITE

The PB site is located in the Swiss municipality of Presinge, in an agricultural environment, with the presence of a few hamlets and the Abbaye de Presinge nearby, a manor house, classified as a historic building by the canton.

From an environmental point of view, the two proposed sites are located on agricultural plots with crop rotation (SDA) status and on the edge of sites of national or cantonal importance with regards to protecting natural environments. Particular care must be taken to protect the Nant du Paradis, even if the land take for the project is likely to avoid protected sectors.

Access to the main road networks is very difficult, as they cross highly urbanised areas.

9. THE PD SITE – NANGY (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE)

Chapter 9 provides a detailed presentation of the location environment of the PD site in Nangy. The description of the site and its environment is followed by a detailed urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (indicating the current constraints) and an analysis of access (particularly connections to the railway, motorways and local road networks).

The site boundary presented in this chapter is a conceptual draft and does not necessarily correspond to the exact boundary currently being considered. Section 15.3 presents the latest version of this boundary in detail.

9.1. DESCRIPTION

The site is located in the municipality of Nangy in the Haute-Savoie department (Illustration 208).

The environment is highly contrasted, with a mix of traditional residential hamlets and zones for activities that are primarily business-related.

A hospital (CHAL) is in the immediate vicinity, to the southeast of the proposed site (hamlet of Findrol).

The municipality is located near a main road/motorway hub, the A40/RD903 interchange. The widening of the RD903 road to 4 lanes (A40 - Chasseurs link), for which a consultation was launched on 4 May 2022, must be taken into account in the planning for the site and access points.

A cross-lane toll barrier on the A40 is located to the northwest, around 1.9 km away.

Illustration 208: Map of footprint: location of PD site.

The WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical point are:

- Latitude: 46.1453657° N,
- Longitude : 6.3169260° E.

The PD site is a technical site that could also be an optional scientific site during phase 1 (FCC-ee), but which must be a scientific site during phase 2 (FCC-hh). The shaft is therefore located directly along the tunnel footprint, about 30 m north of the theoretical point. A second shaft is required around 80 m inside the footprint to provide access to the cavern for technical equipment.

The elevation is 453 m. Shaft depth is 181 m.

The plots foreseen are shown on Illustration 209 and correspond to:

- main site, approx. 4.9 ha,

The list of the concerned cadastral plots for the site is shown in Appendix 16.3.

Illustration 209: Map showing the location of the foreseen plots of land for the PD site (August 2024).

The **characteristics and constraints** of this site are as follows (Illustration 209):

- the site has constraints to the south, west and east:
 - size: 300 m long and approx. 150 m wide, up to 6 ha;
- single shaft above the experiment cavern north of the theoretical point:
 - The theoretical point is within the exclusion zone, but the goal is to move the exclusion zone 18 m to the south (100 m from the motorway);
- single shaft above the service cavern inside the ring, as far north as possible:
 - A minimum distance will have to be maintained for the shaft, even after the prefectural concession, which means special care must be taken when determining the location of underground structures;
- difficult traffic conditions in the sector:
 - There are frequently traffic jams at the A40 toll plaza,
 - A major traffic hub between the roads, hospital, hospital campus, business activities and residential areas to the north and west of the site;
- problems of visibility from the north and northeast should be resolved through proper landscape and architectural integration;
- potential sites near the Arve were examined, but ruled out due to constraints linked to the presence of the nature reserve and a natural hazard zone (flooding).

The main **opportunities** offered by the site are as follows (Illustration 210):

- close to the CHAL hospital, business parks and industrial zones (comprising around 110 companies), possibility of setting up a heating network;
- waste water treatment plant (STEP) near a methanation plant, which offers the possibility of supplying waste heat. Another possibility is the recovery of waste water discharged by the plant (to be confirmed by analysis);
- close proximity to the Fromagerie de la Tournette (Verdannot) for the recovery of waste heat;
- nearby restaurants and hotels;
- close to the A40 motorway cross-lane toll barrier for conveyor transfer of excavated materials;
- possibility of using public transport to get to the site;
- project to link the 4-lane RD903 road from Findrol to the Annemasse agglomeration and, possibly, to Switzerland;
- potential synergy with the Arthaz-Pont-Notre-Dame first response centre,
- the possibility of improving access to high-voltage lines;
- as far as the urban heating network is concerned, residual heat could be supplied to the Alpes-Léman hospital complex (CHAL), less than 300 m away, accessible via an underpass on the D903 road. Heat can also be supplied to all medical services in the vicinity of the hospital and possibly to nearby homes;
- there is an urban heating network in the centre of Reignier, 3.5 km west of the PD site;

- A cheese producer (Fromagerie de la Tournette) to the north of the site on the D1205 road, approximately 500 m away, and the Bellecombe WWTP in Scientrier (2.3 km), could be potential heat consumers;
- Nearby companies specializing in machining and the manufacturing of concrete machines (Quadra 1) and micromechanics (such as AFT, for example) could generate synergy for the construction of the FCC-ee.
- The P+R (park-and-ride) site creates an opportunity to encourage public transportation to the major hubs that could serve the site (Annecy, Geneva).

Illustration 210: General map of the main opportunities around the PD site.

Description of the site and its surroundings

The candidate site is located on a field between:

- the A40 motorway to the west,
- the D903 to the east,
- the D1205 to the north in the municipality of Nangy.

The reserved place for the motorway (to the south of the site) is not included in the site polygon.

The currently proposed site is accessible from the “Route de Serves” road to the northwest, which continues along a farm track that circles the site and is only interrupted to the northeast for approximately 150 m. It then continues around a house close to the D903 road. Access to the farm is via the D903 road to the southeast. There is also a hydraulic structure that passes under the D903 roads and continues to the CHAL P+R (park-and-ride) in Nangy.

The zone for the site lies on a gentle slope (to the south).

A large, modest-looking old farmhouse 400 m away is only partially visible (roof and upper floor) from the highest part of the site. There is no other direct visibility. The only buildings visible from the site are those of a Reblochon cheese producer to the north and a funeral home to the east.

The entire area is exposed to significant noise from road and motorway traffic (instantaneous measurements between 75 dB and 85 dB).

The surface area is large enough to accommodate a technical and experiment site. However, due to the proximity of the interaction point with the zone to the south, which belongs to the motorway concession, only one access shaft to the experiment cavern is conceivable. The access shaft would be relatively close to the motorway service cavern, at a distance of 150 m, but still far enough away from the fenced-in zone for the motorway.

Land

The site consists of:

- mostly private plots of land,
- some municipal, departmental or inter-communal plots (Illustration 211).

Illustration 211: Map of landowners by type for the PD site. Source: anonymous parcel register.

There are two possible scenarios, depending on the selected access option:

- if an access point with a traffic circle is built to the north, on the RD1205 road, only a few plots of land will have to be acquired from private owners;
- if the existing access point via the rural lane and the road to the west is used, an easement would have to be requested, and potential disturbances to the homes bordering this road would have to be anticipated.

Section 9.4. entitled "Access analysis" provides more information on these elements.

Map of agricultural activities

There are four farmers on all these plots of land. They are relatively scattered over each plot (Illustration 212).

Illustration 212: Map of farmers for the PD site. Source: Graphical parcel register.

Possible sites to the south ruled out

Two other plots of land to the south of the junction between the “Route d’Annecy” road and the motorway were examined before being ruled out due to:

- the environmental sensitivity due to its proximity with the Arve River,
- the need to use two small plots on either side of the road (insufficient surface area with a single plot).

9.2. URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

9.2.1. State of the premises

The site is located in the municipality of Nangy, near the A40 motorway exit (Illustration 213), in the Arve valley, between the Salève and Voirons mountain ranges. The zone is characterised by two elements that pass through it: one natural (the Arve River), the other man-made (the motorway).

From an architectural point of view, it is very heterogeneous: traditional residential hamlets, business parks (mainly commercial) and a hospital.

Illustration 213: Landscape analysis map for the main site plot.

The land is very flat. There are no dwellings in the immediate vicinity, apart from a house to the northeast.

Illustration 214: View of the site from “Route de Serves” road to the southeast (number 1 on the map showing the location).

Illustration 215: Panoramic view from the south of the site facing the northeast. The motorway is visible on the left, with the D903 in the distance on the right (number 2 on the map showing the location).

Illustration 216: Top left: the hospital complex (number 3 on the map showing the location). Top right, the business park (number 4 on the map showing the location). Bottom left: the motorway, with the bridge leading to the hospital (number 6 on the map showing the location). Bottom right: the current access road through a residential hamlet (number 5 on the map showing the location).

9.2.2. Urban planning, architecture and landscape

This area, close to the A40 motorway (exit no. 5, “Vallée Verte”), is on the Geneva-Chamonix road: its privileged geographical location makes it an attractive zone. This attractiveness is reflected by the way the has changed; formerly an agricultural area, it is now home to a number of residential hamlets. Shops are concentrated in identified zones split between several municipalities (Nangy, Fillinges, Contamine-sur-Arve). In terms of urban planning, the area is characterised by a certain amount of urban sprawl, although in terms of architecture, the municipality of Nangy has made an effort to integrate contemporary and traditional styles. In terms of landscape, the mountains form the backdrop to the region. The industrial sector is present, concentrated in demarcated zones.

It should be noted that the photographs presented here are intended to provide some context for the site’s surroundings, and in no way indicate the future architecture of the sites.

Illustration 217: Residential hamlets and agricultural sectors.

9.3. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

Summary map of constraints

Illustration 218: Map of environmental constraints around the PD site.

The proposed site has the following protected zones (Illustration 218):

- protected agricultural zone: this protection imposed by prefectural decree could be lifted, also by prefectural decree, and would require the adoption of compensatory measures.
- an unclassified agricultural zone with, possibly, a protected agricultural sector to the north, impacted by a direct access road to the RD1205 road (0.5 ha in this case).

The farmland to the north of the plot is a valuable piece of land, with an exploitable horizon of around 70 cm. There are some isolated trees, which are of some value as they provide a micro-habitat on higher ground, but they are not located directly along the perimeter of the site.

It should be noted that a road project is currently underway to the east of the plot of land in question. It has been taken into account in the division of the proposed plot.

The regional ecological coherence scheme (SRCE, now part of the SRADDET) includes a red zone that is extremely spread out, mainly encompassing the motorway access and extending to the south of the plot planned for the main site. However, the SRADDET zoning is to be considered at a scale of 1:100 000. For the individual plot of land, it is the Nangy local urban plan (PLU)¹²³ that defines the zoning in line with the SRADDET. The maps of environmental constraints were therefore drawn up on the basis of the local urban plan.

The local urban plan defines the A40 motorway zone as an "Ur zone". This zoning does not apply to proposed perimeter of the PD site. For information, the regulations governing this surface are as follows (Text 1):

2. Sont admises les occupations et utilisations du sol suivantes si elles respectent les conditions ci-après :

- la reconstruction dans le volume d'un bâtiment détruit ou démoli depuis moins de 10 ans, à condition que sa destination soit conservée ou soit conforme aux occupations et utilisations du sol prévues dans la zone et dès lors qu'il a été régulièrement édifié. Le respect des autres règles de la zone n'est pas exigé, à l'exception de l'article 11 en vue d'assurer une meilleure insertion dans l'environnement naturel et bâti.
- les ouvrages techniques nécessaires au service public, sous réserve de prendre toute disposition pour limiter au strict minimum la gêne pouvant en découler, et pour assurer une bonne insertion dans le site.
- les bâtiments, ouvrages et installations nécessaires au fonctionnement de l'autoroute
- les centres d'entretien nécessaires au fonctionnement de l'autoroute.
- les installations nécessaires à la réalisation des travaux sur l'autoroute.
- les clôtures.
- les affouillements et exhaussements de sol à condition qu'ils soient strictement nécessaires aux activités existantes ou à la réalisation de constructions et installations nécessaires aux services publics ou d'intérêt collectif ou à la création de voirie et/ou de

Text 1: Ur zoning regulations in the Nangy PLU.

Possibilities for temporary storage and processing of excavated materials

According to an initial analysis, subject to more detailed studies, from 100 000 to 200 000 m³ of excavated material could be temporarily stored on the site.

The access analysis below provides details about the possibilities and constraints for evacuating materials by road.

The materials could also be transported by conveyor belt to the Nangy Nord toll gate, roughly 1 900 m away.

This option would require an agreement with the concessioning authority and the operator of the motorway to authorise:

- truck access to the motorway,
- the development of the large 1.3 ha area near the parking lot to manage the transfer of materials from the conveyor belt to the trucks.

¹²³ <https://www.mairienangy.fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Reglement-signé-PLU-Modif-1-2018-compressé.pdf>

9.4. ACCESS ANALYSIS

The plots of land planned for the PD site are located in Nangy, along the A40 motorway and the RD903 road, and close to the RD1205 road.

9.4.1. Location in relation to main road network and railways

The RD903 road connects to Annemasse and La Roche-sur-Foron.

The A40 connects to the A410, which passes near La Roche-sur-Foron via a route with less constraints than the RD903 road (no nearby residential areas). It is possible to reach Annecy via this main road network.

The railway line access is in La Roche-sur-Foron.

Illustration 219: Main road network and railways at the PD site.

Points of interest on map of main road network and railways (Illustration 219)

G1: possible access to a railroad line in La Roche-sur-Foron (13.3 km away via the A410).

G2: the Annemasse train station, 10 km away, is more difficult to reach because the route is through the city (proximity to housing, heavy traffic, speed bumps, raised safety platforms, etc.)

E15: Vallée Verte interchange 15 via the RD905 road on the A40

To the railroad line in La Roche-sur-Foron

This railroad line is located 1.5 km from junction 19 (A410/RD1203), in La Roche-sur-Foron (Illustration 220). There are no comments necessary about access via the RD1203 and RD2A roads. However, there are two speed bumps with central islands on the RD2A road.

Illustration 220: Route from the PD site to the railroad line in La Roche-sur-Foron.

Illustration 221: Aerial view of the La Roche-sur-Foron train station. Coordinates 46.067528, 6.303691.

With regard to access to the railroad line (Illustration 221), discussions with the current operators of these platforms should make it possible to obtain a more detailed picture of the possibilities for access and use, and to select the best access.

9.4.2. Feasibility of connection to the Nangy motorway area

The technical, legal and financial feasibility of direct motorway access was discussed with the concessioning authority, DGITM (Direction générale des infrastructures, des transports et des mobilités).

Illustration 222: Location of the PD site and the Nangy cross-lane toll barrier, where connection possibilities are being examined.

The two preferred solutions are presented below.

The DGITM indicates that ATMB (Autoroutes et Tunnel du Mont-Blanc, concession holder for the A40) is planning to convert the cross-lane toll barrier into a free-flow toll plaza, which would mean eliminating the approach zone. If necessary, a link between this free-flow toll project and the connection project would have to be defined, depending in particular on the timetable for the operations.

Nangy North

This solution involves loading outside the motorway area on a plot of land for storage purposes. This would require the installation of a fence and access gate on the 1.2 hectare plot. The empty truck coming from the motorway would then access this plot from the rest area. Loading would take place at a distance from this area of a conveyor is used.

Illustration 223: Nangy North: loading heavy goods vehicles on a plot of land away from the motorway area. Access is located away from the on-ramp.

Nangy South

This solution involves loading the heavy goods vehicle with excavated materials away from the motorway area, on a plot of motorway land with “Ur” zoning classification. This plot, estimated to be around 1.3 ha in size, can be used as a temporary storage area for materials and machinery during the construction phase.

The empty heavy goods vehicle uses the service entry lane before the toll gate, then enters the plot away from the motorway area via a gate to be built for this purpose.

Illustration 224: Nangy South: loading heavy goods vehicles on a plot of land away from the motorway area.

9.4.3. Departmental roads connecting to the main road network

Connections to the main road network via the departmental road network vary from one plot of land to another (Illustration 225).

Illustration 225: Main road network and departmental network around the PD site.

An access point to the RD903 road makes it possible to reach the A40 motorway via interchange 15 (la Vallée Verte), or to continue on the RD903 road towards Annemasse.

Routes to the main road network via the departmental network

Illustration 226: Map of access constraints to the main road network.

Access *constraints to the main road network (Illustration 226):*

Constraint 1: route close to residential areas

Constraint 2: check turning angles for semi-trailer access to the RD903 road

Constraint 3: access to the RD903 road not possible for heavy goods vehicles (safety conditions and ban on heavy goods vehicles)

To join the RD903 road to the north, which is roughly 1.1 km from the proposed site, the RD903B road crosses an urbanised area (constraint 1). There is a great deal of traffic in this sector and this point will require special attention (19 710 vehicles per day on the RD903 road and 8 658 vehicles per day on the RD1205 road in 2019, according to Inforoute 74).

Illustration 227: Close-up view of yield at traffic circle.

Illustration 228: Distant view of yield at traffic circle.

The intersection providing access to the RD903 road (constraint 2 to the north) is via a yield with no merge lane (Illustration 227 and Illustration 228). The turning angles for a semi-trailer need to be checked. Added widths may be necessary at certain points.

An alternative northbound access point to the RD903 road could have been considered a bit further south, which would have avoided the north bypass of the RD903B Findrol road near residential areas, however:

- the RD2503 bypass that passes close to residential areas between the usable traffic circle and the next traffic circle to the south is banned for vehicles over 3.5 tonnes;
- access is via a T junction with a stop sign (Illustration 229). This configuration is not acceptable for heavy goods vehicle access to a 2 x 2-lane road, and would require the creation of a merge lane (275 m long).

Illustration 229: View of access road via T junction and stop sign.

Access to the A40 motorway in the direction of Annemasse can be obtained about 2.1 km away with no difficulties. The same applies to the A40 motorway heading towards La Roche-sur-Foron, around 2.4 km away.

9.4.4. Connection to local road network

The site can be reached in three ways:

1. direct access to the D903 (north-south direction only), which is not an option,
2. existing access via the rural road and “Route des Serves” road to the west,
3. creation of an access road with a traffic circle to the north on the RD1205 road.

Illustration 230: Connection to the local road network at the PD site.

A40-Chasseurs road connections

The consultation concerning the A40-Chasseurs road connections^{124,125,126} launched on 4 May 2022 gave details about the routes being considered by the Haute-Savoie departmental council, the project owner for the connections (Illustration 231).

Illustration 231: Map for consultation on the A40-Chasseurs road connections project affecting the PD site.
Source: Conseil départemental de la Haute-Savoie, dossier de concertation de la liaison A40 - Chasseurs.

Discussions between the Haute-Savoie departmental council and CERN have made it possible to analyse the

¹²⁴ <https://actu.hautesavoie.fr/explorez-actu/rd-903-lancement-de-la-concertation-publique-de-la-liaison-a40-chasseurs>

¹²⁵ <https://www.ledauphine.com/politique/2021/12/21/c-est-parti-pour-la-concertation-de-la-rd-903-a-2x2-voies-entre-l-a40-et-le-carrefour-des-chasseurs>

¹²⁶ <https://www.sage-environnement.com/references-amenagement-du-territoire-urbanisme/42-amenagement-de-la-rd903-entre-l-a40-et-annemasse-74>

interfaces between the two projects. The proposed layout of the PD site is compatible with the layout of the future A40-Chasseurs road connections. Close coordination between the two projects should be pursued.

A detailed drawing of the layout for the A40-Chasseurs road connection is shown below for informational purposes (Illustration 232 and 233).

Illustration 232: Drawing of the A40-Chasseurs road connections for informational purposes, with the maximum land take for the PD scientific site.

Illustration 233: Detailed drawing of the A40-Chasseurs interface with the PD site.

A connection to the plot of land is possible without an interface with the RD903 development project by using the “Route de Serves” road, which is connected to the RD1205 road (Illustration 234). The connection via the “Route de Serves” road, to the west of the plot, is 750 m long. It needs to be widened and reinforced over the first 450 m, which have already been paved starting at the junction with the RD1205 road. A paved structure will have to be built over a distance of 300 m to reach the PD site, as it is currently an unpaved road (estimated cost: €660 000 excl. tax).

Illustration 234: Connection to the road network via Route de Serves.

Illustration 235: Aerial view of the junction with the RD1205 road. Coordinates 46.150638, 6.313643.

The junction with the RD1205 road (Illustration 235) has a central lane configuration that enables a left-hand turn lane on to municipal road no. 27 and the “Route de Serves” road. It will be necessary to ensure that the left-hand turn lane is long enough to accommodate existing traffic and heavy goods vehicles that will travel to the plot of land. If this is not the case, the lengthening of this lane appears to be possible. Visibility is sufficient when turning left on to the “Route de Serves” road because the RD1205 road is a straight stretch at this point. However, it will be necessary to ensure visibility when exiting the “Route de Serves” road and to review the right-of-ways.

Illustration 236: Route through the hamlet on the “Route de Serves” road. Coordinates 46.150594, 6.313587.

In addition, the “Route de Serves” road runs through a small hamlet (three to four houses and a farm, Illustration 236) which would suffer additional disturbances from the traffic (constraint 9). This option therefore seems inappropriate.

Another way of connecting the plot of land would be to build a new intersection with the RD1205 road to the north of the plot:

A junction with the RD1205 road is to be built in order to:

- manage the heavy goods vehicle (HGV) traffic to the PD site during construction,
- manage the regular flow of HGVs to the commercial zone across the road (HGV driving school and HGV dealership),
- enable safe access to the site after the construction work has been completed.

A second left-hand turn lane (Illustration 237) is not an option. It is not a safe solution due to the heavy HGV traffic in the left-hand turn lanes on both sides of the RD1205 road, near the works. Creating a second left-hand turn lane would require a widening of the cross-section under the works, meaning it would have to be rebuilt.

Illustration 237: Hypothetical connection to road network rejected.

The creation of a traffic circle would appear to be an appropriate solution. Illustration 238 represents the traffic circle with a radius of 20 m at the present time. This radius will need to be adjusted according to transport constraints.

Illustration 238: Solution with a traffic circle providing a connection to the road network.

It should be noted that this hypothesis, which was defined prior to discussions with the Haute-Savoie departmental council, corresponds precisely to the layout planned by the same departmental council.

Coordination between the Haute-Savoie departmental council and CERN in this sector will ensure the interface between the two projects.

The conditions for the access route to the site from the traffic circle are as follows (Illustration 239 and Illustration 240):

- minimum radius: 54 m
- maximum gradient: 2.3%
- access route with little spoil or backfill.

An access route approximately 100 m long needs to be built in a protected agricultural zone (estimated cost: €100 000 excl. tax). Proper visibility must be ensured at the junction with the RD1205 road (constraint 7).

Illustration 239: Overall route with traffic circle.

Illustration 240: Longitudinal profile of project and natural terrain.

Scenario after in-depth study by WSP/BG Ingénieurs Conseils SAS:

Following this preliminary analysis, the design office working on the RD903 development project (WSP/BG) drew up several access scenarios. The scenario based on the approach presented in Illustration 239 is demonstrated in Illustration 241 below.

This scenario is characterised by less use of farmlands.

Illustration 241: PD site access scenario developed by the WSP / BG design office in synergy with the RD903 development project in 2023.

9.5. SUMMARY OF THE PD SITE

The PD site is located in the municipality of Nangy, close to a motorway traffic hub, hamlets and business parks. A location at a suitable distance from residential areas appears to be feasible.

The various sectors under consideration present agricultural issues (farmlands included in a SRADDET ecological corridor) but have no other environmental protection.

Access to the main road networks seemed feasible, provided that the crossing of urbanised areas and the high level of traffic in the sector were taken into account. The A40-Chasseurs road connection project requires close coordination with the Haute-Savoie departmental council. However, designing a new road access to the PD site by connecting the “Route de Bonneville” road and the RD903 roads may help relieve traffic in Findrol.

Direct connections to the motorway via the Nangy cross-lane toll barrier area have been discussed with the concessioning authority, DGITM. Northbound and southbound connections are possible.

A connection to the La Roche-sur-Foron train station seems possible, but will require discussions with the current operators to further study its feasibility.

10. THE PF SITE - ETEAUX/LA ROCHE-SUR-FORON (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE)

Chapter 10 provides a detailed presentation of the location environment of the PF site. The description of the site and its environment is followed by an urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (current constraints) and an analysis of access, particularly connections to the railway, motorway and local road networks.

The site boundary presented in this chapter is a conceptual draft and does not necessarily correspond to the exact boundary currently being considered. Section 15.3 presents the latest version of this boundary in detail.

10.1. DESCRIPTION

The two options under consideration for a technical site are located in the municipalities of Eteaux, to the north, and La Roche-sur-Foron, to the south, in the Haute-Savoie department (Illustration 242).

They are located along the RD1203 departmental road, and north of the A410 motorway.

The proposed site to the north (Eteaux) runs alongside the RD1203 road across from a public works and earth-moving company. In this sector, the RD1203 road to the north is lined with industrial and commercial activities.

The plot of land to the south (La Roche-sur-Foron) is fairly isolated. Access is difficult. An existing rural road that is 2 400 m long runs alongside the motorway to the south, and would have to be upgraded. A bridge would also have to be built over the railroad line.

A recent development should be noted: an application was submitted for the creation of an inert waste storage facility (ISDI) on the proposed southern site (public inquiry held from 12 December 2022 to 8 January 2023, the submitting company is SARL Luc Maulet).

Illustration 242: Map showing the location of the PF site.

The WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical point are :

- Latitude: 46.0490317° N,
- Longitude : 6.2865850° E.

The elevation of the nominal point is 760 m. Shaft depth is 380 m for the northern site and 400 m for the southern site.

The PF site is a technical site. The shaft was relocated to a more suitable zone on the land of the northern site, as described below. The possible coordinates of the relocated shaft would be as follows:

- Latitude: 46.051720,
- Longitude: 6.284373.

It should be noted that the PF site has the option of partially using wooded areas rather than farmland.

The following options are under consideration (Illustration 243):

- north site (Eteaux): approx. 4 ha,
- south site (La Roche-sur-Foron): approx. 4.1 ha.

The list of cadastral plots affected by the site is shown in Appendix 16.3.

Illustration 243: Map showing the location of options for the PF site (May 2024).

The **characteristics and constraints** of this site are as follows:

- a potential surface area of around 4 ha for the main site along the RN 203 road (RD1203);
- the plots of land concerned by the project (see map of the north site) are located within this potential surface area to avoid environmental issues;
- the “south site” polygon is affected by the recent ISDI application (zone Ax of the PLU - local urban plan). An analysis of this surface area is presented below;
- a 558.5 m long horizontal tunnel between the access shaft on the north site and the collider tunnel (at the same elevation as the collider);
- according to the optimised footprint, the deepest shaft has a depth of 400 m;
- optional zone for a possible railway connection to the south:
 - between the nature protection zone, the creek and the motorway/railway,
 - access to this area is difficult (a rural path 2 400 m long must be transformed into a road and a bridge must be built),
 - the possibility of transferring materials between the site to the south and the RD1203 road via conveyors needs to be studied.

It should be noted that the technical infrastructure is difficult to install on this site, which will therefore be equipped with the minimum amount of functional elements.

A plot of land to the south of the railroad line was studied (Illustration 243) but had to be ruled out, mainly because of:

- the proximity of the hamlet,
- the depth of the shaft,
- the difficult access to the plot.

The main **opportunities** offered by the site are as follows (Illustration 244):

- proximity of several business parks and public facilities in Eteaux and La Roche-sur-Foron, offering the possibility of providing a heating network;
- proximity of the Société fromagère d'Eteaux (Lactalis group) for potential recovery of waste heat;
- presence of a large number of grade schools, middle schools and high schools;
- presence of Enedis electrical substations;
- presence of a sewage system;
- connection to the 400 kV line in Cornier is possible;
- nearby restaurants and hotels;
- business tourism (Rochexpo, the Haute-Savoie exhibition centre), many tourist sites for leisure activities;
- possible to use public transport to get to the site and to improve accessibility to the site via the Eteaux/Évires A410 motorway service area;
- potential synergy with the Pays Rochois rescue centre in Eteaux.

Illustration 244: General map of the main opportunities for the PF site.

Land

Private plots of land are primarily concerned (Illustration 245).

Illustration 245 : Map of the foreseen plots of land for the PF site. Source: anonymous parcel register.

10.2. URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

10.2.1. State of the premises

The sites are located in an area that includes both the municipalities of Eteaux and La Roche-sur-Foron, depending on the plot of land under consideration. But all the locations are quite far from agglomerations. This area is characterised by the railroad and motorway that pass through it, but remains relatively preserved. The railroad line runs through an enclosed route and is not very visible. Nearby, the Foron river runs alongside the railroad line and the Vuaz stream runs alongside the motorway (Illustration 247).

Illustration 247: Map showing location of photos taken around the PF site.

Agricultural fields and single-family homes
(number 1 on the location map).

Bridge over the railroad line
(number 2 on location map).

Enclosed railroad line
(number 3 on location map).

Motorway
(number 4 on location map).

10.2.2. Urban planning, architecture and landscape

The zone to the southeast of the motorway is characterised by the presence of old single-family houses, grouped together in small hamlets, and fields. Dwellings include residential homes and agricultural farms. The landscape is quite hilly. The mountains in the background are part of the Aravis range. The architecture of the buildings is in the traditional Haute-Savoie style or with a contemporary touch. The landscape is pastoral, offering a sense of peace and tranquillity.

North of the motorway, however, the atmosphere is different. The local highway, which runs along the base of a large hill, is lined with a variety of businesses and companies. There are no homes. The location is quiet, but the high volume of traffic on the RD1203 departmental road generates a fairly high amount of background noise. A small wood hides the motorway from the valley floor, and the Aravis mountains rise in the background.

It should be noted that the photographs presented here are intended to provide some context for the site's surroundings, and in no way indicate the future architecture of the sites.

Contemporary architecture incorporating traditional elements.

Traditional farmhouse.

Companies along the D1203 road.

400 kV power line passing to the west of the site.

10.2.3. The PF site (north)

The ground is slightly sloped.

The elevation is 738 m.

Illustration 248: View of the road to the north of the site (number 5 on the map showing the location).

Illustration249: View of the north site from the local highway (number 5 on the map showing the location).

Illustration 250: Urbanised area with a public works company opposite the north site, on the opposite side of the road from the previous photo (number 5 on the map showing the location).

The site is connected to the RD1203 and RN203 roads.

The departmental road and the local highway are transit routes in an environment where farming and other economic activities are mixed.

There are no homes in the immediate vicinity.

Basic facilities for electricity, drinking water and sewage systems are located nearby.

10.2.4. The PF site (south)

The elevation is 742 m.

Illustration 251: View of the south site (number 6 on the map showing the location).

It is a remote site and access is more difficult than for the site to the north (see the “access analysis” section).

There are no basic facilities nearby (electricity, drinking water, sewage system).

10.3. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

The sites are located on the borders of the municipalities of Eteaux and La Roche-sur-Foron, between the RD1203 road and the A410 motorway.

Summary map of constraints

Illustration 252: Map of environmental constraints around the two options under consideration (north and south) for the PF site.

North site

The site has a number of constraints, particularly environmental (Illustration 252):

- Two wetlands have been inventoried by the department^{127,128,129}. The land used for the site will have the appropriate demarcation to avoid these wetlands (Illustration 253 below),
- A protected zone (wildlife corridor) is identified in the PLU (local urban plan). For this sector, this classification is probably taken from the regional ecological coherence scheme, or SRCE (to be verified). In this context, maintaining the ecological continuity (conservation of sufficiently large corridors) and free movement of species must be integrated into the project.
- The option for the site location is on a single property.
- The site requires an access tunnel 400 m deep and 450 m to 558.5 m long, depending on the position of the shaft, to connect the surface site to the underground accelerator tunnel.

Illustration 253: Wetlands in Eteaux (south of the “Route de Faverges” road), wet grasslands and pastures of normal importance for flora and fauna (no known species of high value).

Source: Direction départementale du territoire de la Haute-Savoie, most recent visit in 2013.

¹²⁷ Préfet de la Haute-Savoie, Les services de l’État en Haute-Savoie, DDT 74, Inventaire des zones humides : <https://www.haute-savoie.gouv.fr/Actions-de-l-Etat/Prevenir-le-risque-et-se-proteger/Eau/Zones-humides/>

¹²⁸ Zones humides du département de la Haute-Savoie, data set updated on 19 May 2024 by the DREAL: <https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/zones-humides-du-departement-de-la-haute-savoie/>

¹²⁹ https://piece-jointe-carto.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/DEPT074A/zone_humide/74ASTERS3197_24-06-2024_fiche.pdf

South site

- The south site is located on an inert waste storage facility (ISDI) site with ICPE status (facility classified for environmental protection) that is to be built in 2023, and which will be operated for ten years in two phases (zone Ax in the PLU - local urban plan).
- A ruined single-family home stands at the western end of the site. It appears to have recently undergone renovations, but no further information is available.
- An ecological corridor listed in the SRCE crosses the plots of land.
- Maintaining the ecological continuity (conservation of sufficiently large corridors) and free movement of species must be integrated into the project.
- The ecological value of the plots of land for the south site is less than for the north site.
- The plots belong to a farm located on both sides of the motorway (GAEC La Roche Parnale, “Route de Lavillat” road). However, the land take is not being used due to the creation of the ISDI.

Illustration 254: Map of natural hazards for La-Roche-sur-Foron at the nominal site location.

It should be noted that the zone to the south of the motorway is located close to a natural hazard zone due to steep slopes and the presence of water in the ground (risk due to unstable terrain, see illustration 254). This zone was therefore ruled out for a surface site.

The ISDI application has been submitted for the south site under consideration (public inquiry held from 12 December 2022 to 8 January 2023, the submitting company is SARL Luc Maulet).

Illustration 255: Sector concerned by the ISDI project. The land take in phase 2 of this ISDI, which has ICPE status (facility classified for environmental protection), could be the location for the PF site (south option). Source: IGN.

10.4. ACCESS ANALYSIS

The north site option is in the municipality of Eteaux, and the south site option in the municipality of La Roche-sur-Foron¹³⁰. The sites are located along the RD1203 road or the A410 motorway.

10.4.1. Location in relation to the main road network and railways

Illustration 256: Map of access to main road network and railways.

¹³⁰ The situation of the PF site presented corresponds to what was valid at the time when the access analysis was conducted. Since then, the situation has changed, but this has no impact on the results presented.

Points of interest on map of main road network and railroads (Illustration 256):

G1: access possible to a railway line in La Roche-sur-Foron

G2: railway branch line to be considered

E19: interchange 19 (La Roche-sur-Foron) on the A410 motorway

AR: rest area on the A410 motorway

Two sites are being studied as possible locations for the PF site. They are located close to the RD1203 road and A410 motorway, and to a railway line. The A410 connects the A40 and A41 motorways.

The main difficulty is connecting the south site to the local road network in the department. The possible solutions are presented in paragraph 10.4.4.

There are several access routes from the RD1206 road or the A410 motorway.

Routes to the A410 motorway or a railway line

Illustration 257: Map of routes to the motorway or railway line.

Points of interest on map of routes to the motorway or railway line (Illustration 257):

G2: railway branch line to be considered

Access to a railway line is 4.6 km from the PF site via the RD1203 road. There are no particular constraints, apart from two speed bumps with central islands in the direction of the train station.

There is access to the A410 motorway at the E19 interchange (approx. 2.8 km from the main site) heading southwest (Annecy). Going northeast on the A410 increases the travel distance by 3 km, for a total of 6 km. There is no direct access to the A410 on-ramp, and it is necessary to make a U-turn at the first traffic circle.

G1: La Roche-sur-Foron train station (Illustration 258)

Illustration 258: Aerial view of access to the La Roche-sur-Foron train station. Coordinates 46.066159, 6.30428.

G2: a railway branch line could be considered, provided there is sufficient alignment. Technical studies should clarify the feasibility (Illustration 259).

Illustration 259: Zone under consideration for a railway branch line. Coordinates 46.048538, 6.278127.

A farm path connects the plots of land to the south, but there may be severe constraints for crossing the motorway (Illustration 260).

Illustration 260: Route not selected. Coordinates 46.048134, 6.283501.

If a railway branch line to the north is not possible, it would be possible to study the feasibility of a branch line to the south (Illustration 261).

Illustration 261: Aerial view of the railway line passage beneath the motorway. Coordinates 46.048134, 6.283501.

10.4.2. Feasibility of connection to the Eteaux/Évires motorway area

The technical, legal and financial feasibility of direct access to motorways has been discussed with the concessioning authority, DGITM

Illustration 262: Location of PF site and of Evires/Eteaux motorway areas where possible connections are being studied (December 2023).

The two preferred solutions are presented below.

Évires motorway area (north)

Regardless of which location is selected for the plot of land for storage, heavy goods vehicles exit the motorway from the off-ramp, go to the rest area, then use the two service gates to obtain access to the “Chemin de la Croix Rouge” road and, finally, one of the plots of land. The gate located between the zone with the AREA buildings and the rest area appears to be far enough from the motorway off-ramp to be used by heavy goods vehicles.

The loading is performed in the storage area, outside the motorway. The HGVs then take the same route in the opposite direction; they cross the rest area on the side with the HGV parking lot, and then enter the motorway in complete safety via the rest area exit ramp.

Illustration 263: Connection to the Evires motorway area.

Eteaux motorway area (south)

The service access point at the Eteaux motorway area is close to the motorway off-ramp. As a result, a new access point is proposed for this connection, further away from the access ramps, to limit interference between the manoeuvring of the HGVs and traffic entering and exiting the motorway area. It should be noted that this access is located close to the parking lots for light vehicles.

Illustration 264: Connection to the Eteaux motorway area.

10.4.3. Departmental roads connecting to the main road network

Routes from site 176-03

Illustration 265: Map of routes to the main road network via the departmental roads.

A route to the rest area to connect with the A410 motorway (Illustration 265 and Illustration 266) appears possible from a top view, but is in fact not feasible (steep terrain, passage under the railway line, environmental constraints, proximity of motorway and railroad).

However, this route could be used for a conveyor belt, transporting materials directly from the PF site to the Eteaux/Evires motorway areas.

Illustration 266: Rejected route to the A410 rest area. Coordinates 46.048037, 6.278147.

Route 1 (yellow): access to the RD1203 road (Illustration 265)

A new road could be built that connects to the RD1203 road. The zone has a severe constraint due to the sloping terrain. This would probably have to be a winding road after it crosses the creek. The road will be 650 m long, at an estimated cost of around €650 000 excluding tax. A bridge will have to be built over the Vuaz stream, the cost of which will be determined after a field visit. However, it will have a lower environmental impact than the creation of access to the rest area.

Route 2 (ochre): access to the railway line (Illustration 265)

This route involves creating a branch line on the railroad. Given the short length of the straight alignment, its feasibility needs to be verified.

10.4.4. Connection to local road network

North site

Direct access to the main site is from the RD1203 road. An engineering firm with the necessary expertise was commissioned in 2024 to carry out a feasibility study and develop a concept with access via the RD1203 road. Five variants were considered (Illustration 267), including two with a T-junction (C1, C2) and three with direct access (A1, A2, A3).

Illustration 267: Five variants for access to the the north PF site option, including two with a T-junction (C1, C2) and three with direct access (A1, A2 and A3).

The analysis revealed that, taking into account concerns about road safety and maintaining traffic flow, as well as environmental constraints, the best variant is direct access (A2) opposite the Maulet public works company. The most suitable concept is a T-junction with a left-hand turn lane (see Illustration 268).

Illustration 268: Access to the PF site from the RD1203.

The detailed concept is shown in Illustration 269.

Illustration 269: Concept for access to the PF site opposite the Maulet public works company.

South site to RD1203 road: direct connection option

The site is located on a slope with a gradient of roughly 15%. Depending on site constraints, it is likely that, to provide access, a winding road will have to be built that respects turning angles for heavy goods vehicles with added widths in the turns. More precise topographical data will be required to obtain a more detailed road layout.

A hydraulic structure that crosses the Vuaz stream (Illustration 270) would be required (cost not estimated).

Illustration 270: Map of the hydraulic structure to be built over the Vuaz stream.

The diagram below (Illustration 271) shows a winding route based on contour lines, including turning manoeuvres for a "dump truck" type of heavy goods vehicle, with a constant 5 m cross-section. It runs alongside the forest to have as little impact as possible on it, but is still in an undesirable zone. The precise topography of the terrain must be taken into account when designing the road layout.

Illustration 271: Map of a possible route based on topography of the terrain.

The direct connection to the RD1203 road is therefore very tricky due to:

- the presence of steep slopes;
- the need for a winding route after crossing the creek;
- the ecological continuity objectives that must be maintained (wildlife movement area protected by the PLU - local urban plan). A connection here would in fact disrupt the ecological continuity.

South site to RD1203 road: option with connection via the “Route de Thorens” road

Illustration 272: “Route de Thorens” road along the motorway to the south.

Illustration 273: Longitudinal profile of the “Route de Thorens” road.

The “Route de Thorens” road is roughly 1.5 km long up to the rest area. It has slopes of up to 14%.

10.5. SUMMARY OF THE PF SITE

The PF site is located either in the municipality of Eteaux (north option) or in the municipality of La Roche-sur-Foron (south option).

The main northern site is located along the RD1203 road near a small business park. In theory, it is suitable for a site location. It has easy access from the RD1203 road. On the other hand, the plot of land is subject to various environmental constraints (SRCE corridor, area protected by a PLUi urban plan, wetlands nearby but not directly on the plots under consideration), which will require the implementation of a meticulous ERC (Avoid-Reduce-Compensate) approach. The layout selected for the site should avoid particularly sensitive sectors.

The plot of land for the south site option is in a rural, remote environment on the site of an inert waste storage facility (ISDI) with ICPE status (facility classified for environmental protection) that is under construction and will be operated for ten years. It does not present any major environmental challenges (agricultural plots in an ecological corridor of the SRCE), but access to the plot for the south site is very complex and costly. It would be difficult to install a surface site with a shaft at the ISDI.

Direct connections to the motorway via the Eteaux/Evires service areas have been discussed with the concessioning authority, DGITM. The north and south connections are both possible.

11. THE PG SITE - CHARVONNEX/GROISY (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE)

Chapter 11 provides a detailed presentation of the location environment of the PG site in Charvonnex and in Groisy. The description of the site and its environment is followed by an urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (current constraints) and an analysis of access, particularly connections to the railway, motorway and local road networks.

The site boundary presented in this chapter is a conceptual draft and does not necessarily correspond to the exact boundary currently being considered. Section 15.3 presents the latest version of this boundary in detail.

11.1. DESCRIPTION

The site straddles the municipality of Charvonnex and the southern part of the municipality of Groisy, in the Haute-Savoie department (Illustration 274).

The main site is located north of Charvonnex, on a plateau overlooking a hill. The RD1203 road runs along the foot of the hill. The environment (uncultivated grasslands and a forest) is far from any dwellings. To the north lies the A410 motorway and its Groisy service area, which can be accessed from the site via a forest road.

Near the motorway, plots of land should enable equipment to be brought in and materials to be removed, subject to the necessary approvals.

The railroad lies to the east of the site. The feasibility of a transfer zone for the evacuation of materials near the railroad should be examined.

The PG site is a special scientific site that is diametrically opposite the PA site, making it particularly important. There will be more staff activity than at other sites, and collaboration may be necessary with teams from CNRS/IN2P3 LAPP (Annecy particle physics laboratory), under conditions still to be defined.

Illustration 274: Map showing the location of the PG site.

The WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical point are :

- Latitude: 45.9938019° N,
- Longitude : 6.1693009° E.

The elevation is 592 m. Shaft depth is 226 m.

As the PG site is a scientific site, both shafts are positioned at the theoretical point. However, it should be noted that there is room within the perimeter of the PG site to adapt the layout according to the analysis of environmental issues.

The following types of plots are foreseen (Illustration 275):

- main zone to the south: approx. 6.9 ha. The polygon indicated as "plot of land 1" corresponds to the location initially defined in working scenario PA31-1.0. The polygon indicated as "plot of land 2" has become the preferred location following optimisation of the collider and its overall layout in version PA31-4.0. This scenario would use classified wooded areas and a portion of grassland that is currently unused. Lastly, the polygon indicated as "plot of land examined but not selected" was ruled out due to its steep slope and the presence of a farm. The analysis is given for reference purposes only,
- access zone to the north: approx. 3.6 ha. Located close to the motorway, it will be used to house technical infrastructures in ancillary buildings and for the temporary storage of excavated materials.

The list of cadastral plots affected by the site is shown in Appendix 16.3.

Illustration 275: Map of the foreseen plots of land for the PG site (May 2024).

The **characteristics and constraints** of this site are as follows:

- possibility of a large 7 ha site, 300 m x 250 m;
- a single shaft above the experiment cavern due to topographical constraints;
- part of the installation in the forest;
- 15% to 30% slope starting to the east of the site location;
- single shaft above the service cavern, about 80 m inside the ring;
- careful planning required for optional access from the “Route d'Annecy” road;
- 70 m drop, 20% slope to be avoided;
- potential access to the Groisy motorway service area, about 800 m long and at the same elevation;
- possible access to the railway line to the west via a zone of approximately 2 ha, at a distance of 500 m through the forest;
- very low agricultural value of grasslands on the plateau, not conducive to planting;
- a little-used but valuable forest in terms of biodiversity.

The main **opportunities** offered by the site are as follows (Illustration 276):

- no shared visibility, flat terrain if the site remains limited to the part straddling the plateau in Charvonnex and the forest in Groisy, away from dwellings, close to the LAPP laboratory in Annecy;
- potential for joint development of railway access (e.g. reopening the Doucy train station for commuters to Annecy and for use of the Léman Express to the Geneva region);
- proximity of Groisy train station and discussions to reopen the Saint-Martin-Bellevue train station as part of the Greater Annecy “*Plan de mobilité*” (Mobility Plan);
- access to the Groisy motorway service area: can be used for transporting materials;
- close to a small business park (Longchamp) and restaurant services;
- supply of residual heat to the Longchamp commercial zone, about 1 800 m to the northeast, and possibly to the residential buildings of Charvonnex;
- close proximity to two middle schools (one existing, one planned);
- nearby Argonay business park, offering accommodation and restaurant services;
- nearby Dassault Aviation and Pfeiffer Vacuum, offering training opportunities;
- improved access to high-voltage lines;
- supply of electricity to the Groisy motorway service station for operations and recharging of electric vehicles (if this is still relevant in 2045);
- possibility of developing the scientific site as a tourist attraction with a visitor centre;
- possibility of opening shops and restaurants at the Groisy train station;
- possibility of opening shops and restaurants at the bottom of the slope;
- close to the Groisy-Thorens fire station;
- improved fibre optic coverage in Charvonnex and the surrounding towns;
- potential recycling of cooling water for agriculture, wetlands or for feeding the Fattes stream towards Fillière.

Illustration 276: General map of the main opportunities for the PG site.

Land

The site consists solely of private plots of land (Illustration 277):

Illustration 277: Map of landowners at the PG site. Source: anonymous parcel register.

Map of agricultural activities

Illustration 278: Map of agricultural activities at the PG site. Source: Graphical parcel register.

The farmland plots are used by various operators (Illustration 278).

Topography

Illustration 279: Topographic map (5 m scale) of the PG site (December 2023).

The area to the west of the farm road that runs up the slope from the RD1203 road cannot be used due to unfavourable topography (Illustration 279) and the presence of a deeply incised stream (over 10 m deep).

The rural road running up the slope has a very steep gradient (17% to 20%) around 200 m from the bottom of the slope. It is not paved. However, it could easily be enlarged and turned into an access road for light vehicles.

The area immediately to the east of plots 1 and 2 slopes steeply down to the RD1203 road, in a protected forest zone that should be avoided.

The forest road to the Groisy service area of the A410 motorway leads to a loading/unloading area on flat ground that appears to be suitable. The forest road is wide, but unpaved.

11.2. URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

11.2.1. State of the premises

The site straddles the Charvonnex municipality and part of the Groisy municipality, to the south of the motorway, away from any inhabited areas. Charvonnex is characterised by its development around a hill. The historic centre is on top of the hill, as are a number of residential districts. The local highway to Annecy, which is very busy at rush hour, runs along the foot of the hill, and there are a variety of businesses and industrial activities in the surrounding area. The hillsides are wooded (Illustration 280).

Illustration 280: Map showing location of photos taken at the PG site.

Illustration 281: View from the south of the proposed, then rejected, plot to the north (number 1 on the map showing the location).

Illustration 282: View of the hilly landscape around the site (number 2 on the map showing the location).

”Route d’Annecy” road. Economic activities at the foot of the Charvonnex hill (number 3 on the map showing the location).

Historic centre of Charvonnex at the top of the hill (number 4 on the map showing the location).

Wooded areas near the site (number 5 on the map showing the location).

Residential districts along the “Route d’Annecy” road (number 6 on the map showing the location).

11.2.2. Urban planning, architecture and landscape

The village of Charvonnex is characterised by its dual nature: at the top of the hill is the historic centre, with its traditional buildings and residential districts of single-family homes; in the valley, along the “Route d'Annecy” road, economic activities have developed. More specifically, the zone around the proposed site is heterogeneous and lacks continuity. The FCC and its centre of excellence could turn this zone into a recognised scientific sector,

It should be noted that the photographs presented here are intended to provide some context for the site’s surroundings, and in no way indicate the future architecture of the sites.

Business parks
around the “Route d'Annecy” road.

A few isolated houses
around the “Route d'Annecy” road.

11.3. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

The sites are located to the south of the A410 motorway and to the northwest of the RD1203 road.

Summary map of constraints

Illustration 283: Map of environmental constraints around the PG site.

Main zone (surface site)

- Unused agricultural zone of grasslands, for the proposed polygon 1. This also concerns the southern part of polygon 2.
- Classified wooded area (EBC): for the northern part of polygon 2.
- The forest is unsuitable for harvesting, except possibly for carpentry, but is more suitable for firewood production. The zone is also valuable from a biodiversity point of view, as it is classified in category 4 of a five-category classification for the quality of its biodiversity. Wetlands in the forest also cover a portion of the plateau. The presence of a classified wooded area requires a revision of the PLUi local urban plan and the adoption of compensation measures if it is destroyed.
- On the plateau, the grassland soil is relatively wet and not fit for crops. The soil is gravelly and unsuitable for farming, with a layer of around 30 cm above clay and rock. It has very low value.

Access area (near the motorway service area)

- Agricultural zones and classified zones for the storage of inert waste.

The following points should also be noted with regard to the environment:

- the site is surrounded by forests: to the north, west and east;
- the lane running through the forest towards the motorway service area must be well integrated and respect natural constraints;
- the surface site, which would be located on the plateau to the north, would not be visible from the municipality;
- it should be noted that if the surface site were located at the bottom of the slope, the architectural approach would have been more problematic to ensure proper integration into the landscape;
- acoustically, the upper part of the plateau is quiet, while the lower part and base of the slope are subject to noise from the RD1203 road.

The forest to the west of the site is in principle not affected by the hunting bans¹³¹ in the Charvonnex zoning plan.

Urbanism regulations

Charvonnex has prepared a PLU urban plan. The agricultural areas in Chavonnex are not protected (zone A), and part of the surface site would be located in Groisy in the forest (zone N, EBC). The directives of the Sustainable Planning and Development Plan (PADD) are online on the website for the consultation¹³². The directives of the PADD are as follows: strictly limit urban sprawl and protect existing wetlands, water run-off, continuous green spaces within the village perimeter and undeveloped land (also known as the "trame verte et bleue" (green and blue grid)). The proposed area for the surface site is considered to be "other farmland, strategic for agriculture".

The plots of land near the Groisy motorway toll station, in Groisy, are unprotected farmland. In the forest, there are Nm zones¹³³ intended for the storage of inert materials for a limited period (Text 2).

2-3-3- EN SECTEUR NM UNIQUEMENT :

- Sont aussi autorisés les activités de dépôts temporaires ou recyclages de matériaux inertes issus ou destinés à des activités agricoles, artisanales ou de BTP, sous réserve de prendre les dispositions nécessaires, afin d'éviter les impacts négatifs sur l'environnement. Une fois l'activité terminée, la remise à l'état initial des terrains est obligatoire.
- Les constructions autorisées seront obligatoirement non clos
 - Nota : on entend ici par non clos les constructions qui présentent au moins la moitié de ces façades totalement non closes (hors poteaux de soutènement).
- La mise en place de clôtures de sécurité est obligatoire, avec une hauteur limitée à 2m en limite séparative et en respectant un recul de 2m par rapport aux limites du domaine public.

Text 2: Extract from the Groisy local urban plan (PLU) regulations concerning Nm zones.

¹³¹ https://www.haute-savoie.gouv.fr/var/ide_site/storage/images/media/files/01_loisirs/chasse/reserve/reserve-chasse-charvonnex/129458-3-fre-FR/Reserve-chasse-Charvonnex.jpg

¹³² <https://en.calameo.com/read/0043200637aa7416e5025>

¹³³ data.geopf.fr/annexes/gpu/documents/DU_74137/4cce54d5467428f919201b8b514fdf34/74137_reglement_20220517.pdf

Numerous apartment buildings and single-family homes are planned in Charvonnex, mainly along the railroad line to the west of the target zone in the Doucy sector. The stated aim is not to use up any more existing agricultural areas.

A supermarket project in La Culaz was abandoned in 2021.

A cycle path to Annecy is under study.

The reopening of a railway stop in Doucy, which ran from 1955 to 1992, is considered desirable.

Noise levels in the vicinity of the RD1203 road are high, but as the entire area is not intended for residential use, no protective or development measures appear to be planned. However, additional safety measures and speed limits are planned for Doucy.

Possibilities for temporary storage and processing of excavated materials

At first glance, and subject to further study, there appear to be storage possibilities:

- the large 2-hectare plots of land in Groisy, near the motorway service area in zones A and Nm appear to be suitable for storing excavated material;
- depending on the location of the surface site, a large 2-hectare zone with an A classification, close to the RD1203 road and at the bottom of the slope, could also be suitable.

In the study on excavated materials, various options were examined, including on-site reuse of materials. However, various options for transporting the excavated material seem feasible:

- conveyor to the A410 North motorway (550 m in a straight line through the forest, which would require a 10 m wide cut through the forest);
- trucks to the A410 North motorway (700 m of forest road);
- trucks weighing up to 40 tonnes on the road leading to the Groisy service area via the “Route de Lecy” road, which passes through Charvonnex: this last option does not appear to be acceptable, given the restrictions on the road's capacity and the potential disturbances to the residential zones in Charvonnex.

Excavated materials, construction materials and construction equipment could preferably be transported to the A410 motorway via the “Route des Tavernettes” rural road, which is a forest road. The road is flat, sufficiently wide and could be resurfaced. It could accommodate a conveyor connecting the construction site zone to the temporary storage area for excavation materials: 2.3 ha of temporary storage space for inert waste near the Groisy motorway service station, currently used to store materials from forestry operations and road maintenance.

To facilitate visitor access during the operating phase and to improve accessibility from Annecy (from the LAPP laboratory, for example), upgrading and resurfacing of the “Route des Tavernettes” road, which climbs up from the RD1203 road (“Route d’Annecy” road), will be considered.

Further details about access and transport are in the following paragraph.

Social aspects and local sensitivity

It will be important to take into account the existing directives of the PADD, to seek to develop the railway connection in cooperation with the municipality, and to create synergy with a commercial centre that benefits the local population.

Selected option: at the top of the slope on the plateau

As a reminder, an optional site on the southern part of the slope, on relatively flat ground close to the RD1203 road, was examined but rejected because the topographical conditions made it impossible to build the accelerator.

Doucy railway stop (see paragraph about this stop below)

The Doucy (Charvonnex) railway stop, which formerly existed, is 2.5 km away (4 minutes by car, 9 by bicycle). The existing railway stop in Groisy is 3.7 km away, but the passageway under the A410 motorway has a height limitation (farm vehicles can pass through).

Illustration 284: Layout of train stations on the railway line between Annecy and La Roche-sur-Foron.

The characteristics of the railway line (Illustration 284, see [railsavoie.fr](https://www.railsavoie.fr)) are as follows:

Table 33: Characteristics of the RFF railway line.

RFF line no.	897.000 (Aix les Bains - Annemasse)
Chaix line no.	533 (Aix les Bains - Annemasse)
Date of construction	1883-1884
Length	39 km
Type of track	Single track
Date of electrification	1951
Electrification method	Overhead line
Voltage	20 kV 50 Hz then, in 1953, 25 kV 50 Hz

Site of the former railway stop

Illustration 285: Map showing location of the former Doucy railway stop.

Close-up of the former railway stop

Illustration 286: Aerial view of the former Doucy railway stop, showing locations where photographs were taken.

Illustration 287: Site of the former Charvonnex stop. The train stop was located where the strip of grass now separates the village street from the track (number 1 on the photo above).

Illustration 288: View of the railway gate house at the former Charvonnex train station (number 2 on the photo showing the location).

Illustration 289: The railway line to Aix-les-Bains (number 3 on the photo showing the location).

Illustration 290: The railway line to La Roche-sur-Foron (number 4 on the photo showing the location).

The goal of reopening the Doucy train station (Illustration 286) is included in the PADD document and in the minutes of the municipal meetings concerning the PLU (local urban plan). No further information is available at this stage. The distance between Saint-Martin-Bellevue and Charvonnex train stations is around 3.5 km.

11.4. ACCESS ANALYSIS

11.4.1. Location in relation to the main road network and railways

Illustration 291 : Map showing access to main road network and railways.

Points of interest on map of main road network and railroads(Illustration 291):

E18: Interchange 18 on the A41 motorway

EA Crêts Blancs motorway service area

ED: Beginning of the 70 km/h section of the D1203 road, isolated from the surrounding environment, and with grade separated intersections

G1: Branch line to be built on plot 179.03

G2: Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train station

Connection to railways

2 connections are possible to the railway line near the PG site. These options are:

- the creation of a branch on this line to the west of shaft G, on the plot located to the west of the main site (G1);
- the Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train station (G2).

Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train station

Illustration 292: Aerial view of access to the Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train station. Coordinates 46.011380, 6.175406.

The Groisy train station (G2, Illustration 292) is located along the D2 road, which also leads to interchange 18 of the A41 motorway. This departmental road does not have any major difficulties for heavy goods vehicles, but it does cross long stretches of inhabited zones. One of the closed branch lines between the industrial site and the railway line could be reopened to allow for material transfers. Discussions with the concerned industrial partners may be necessary to ensure that this is the case if this station is chosen. This train station can also be used for the PH site.

Railway branch to be built on plot 179.03 to the west of the PG site

Illustration 293: Map of the railway branch to be built to provide access from the west to the PG site.

The branch (Illustration 293) would be built along the existing line within the perimeter of the plot to the west of the main site. It could be connected to the PG site via a conveyor approximately 800 m long. Its layout on the drawing is for informational purposes only. The location of the conveyor will depend on the constraints of the terrain and the exact point to be connected along the railway line. Even if a conveyor is installed in this location, it will still be necessary to create access via road to the selected plot for deliveries of equipment and for employee traffic. Discussions with SNCF Réseau will be necessary to examine the feasibility of such a project.

Connection to the road network

The main road network can be reached via three access points:

- interchange 18 on the A41 motorway (E18)
- the D1203 road to Annecy, after Argonay (ED)
- the Crêts Blancs service area (EA)

Access to interchange 18 and to the RD1203 road in Argonay is described in the following section.

11.4.2. Feasibility of connection to the Crêts Blancs motorway area

The technical, legal and financial feasibility of direct access to motorways has been discussed with the concessioning authority, DGITM.

Illustration 294: Location of the Crêts Blancs motorway area and access points. Coordinates 45.999476, 6.166723.

The Crêts Blancs motorway area is the nearest point of access to the motorway network. Access is possible to both the south area (900 m) and the north area (2.4 km via the “Route de Lécy” road). Service entrances already exist to enter and exit the motorway areas.

Crêts Blancs North

This is the preferred solution, and would involve loading and unloading heavy goods vehicles directly on the plot identified as a storage/loading zone. Heavy goods vehicles on the motorway would then need a new gate, to be built between the motorway area and the plot of land, for entry to and exit from the plot and the motorway area.

In this case, heavy goods vehicles would only use the lanes currently used by trucks, and access could be provided with good visibility and safety conditions. The proposed location for the gate is in principle the most favourable in this respect, but it could be placed anywhere along the parking lot for the heavy goods vehicles.

Illustration 295: Preferred solution for Crêts Blancs North: loading of heavy goods vehicles on a plot away from the motorway area.

Crêts Blancs South

This is the preferred solution, and would involve loading and unloading heavy goods vehicles directly on the plot identified as a storage/loading zone. Heavy goods vehicles on the motorway would then need a new gate, to be built between the motorway area and the plot of land, for entry to and exit from the plot and the motorway area. The room for turning manoeuvres does not appear to be problematic. It should be noted, however, that the difference in elevation between the plot of land and the motorway area is considerable, and that ramp access will have to be provided across the existing embankment.

Illustration 296: Preferred solution for Crêts Blancs South: loading of heavy goods vehicles on a plot away from the motorway area.

11.4.3. Departmental roads connecting to the main road network

Illustration 297 : Map of routes to the main road network via the departmental roads.

Routes to the main road network (Illustration 297):

The **RD1203** road (in magenta and orange on the map, constraint no. 4) has, in theory, suitable characteristics. However, there are three long village crossings, some with central islands. It appears that they can be crossed.

Constraint 1: crossing through portions of the village of Charvonnex over a distance of 1.8 km. Presence of a few central islands;

Constraint 2: crossing through portions of the village of Saint-Martin-Bellevue over a distance of 1 km. Presence of two central traffic islands and a short, raised safety platform;

Constraint 3: crossing through portions of the village of Argonay over a distance of 1.5 km. This crossing is a more urban setting, with a very long island separating the two directions of traffic;

RD2 (remainder of the orange route) appears to have suitable characteristics. The following is worth noting, however:

- steep slopes: 6% over 1.9 km between the hamlet of Le Plot and the Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train station, 7% over 900 m between Villy-le-Pelloux and interchange 18,
- the presence of hamlets and villages: three crossings of villages and hamlets (including 3 km in Groisy), sometimes with central islands.

Constraint 4: crossing the hamlets of Longchamp (about twenty houses near the departmental road) and Le Plot (about fifteen houses near the departmental road);

Constraint 5: constant gradient of 6% between Le Plot and the Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train station over 1.9 km (Illustration 298).

Illustration 298: Aerial view and elevation profile of constraint 5. Coordinates 46.005737, 6.178771.

Constraint 6: crossing through the village of Groisy (town centre and various hamlets) over a distance of 3 km. Small industrial site adjacent to the train station. There are a few traffic islands along this route, but they do not hinder the passage of heavy goods vehicles;

Constraint 7: crossing through the village of Villy-le-Pelloux over a distance of 800 m. A 7% gradient that is 900 m long begins in the village centre and continues to interchange 18;

The “Route de Lécy” road (cyan route) appears to have suitable characteristics. However, several points should be noted:

- the presence of hamlets and villages: there are several groups of dwellings that are part of the municipality of Groisy along the “Route de Lécy” road;
- its structure needs to be verified given the low number of heavy goods vehicles currently using it;
- the width of the carriageway is 4 m between the south motorway area and the underpass, and 4.5 m to 6 m between the underpass and the D2 road to the north. In the south section, crossings by heavy goods vehicles can be regulated, bearing in mind that this portion only connects the service area, a basin and a small storage area. In the north section, extending the width of the carriageway to at least 5.50 m should be considered for the narrower portions to facilitate the passage of local cross traffic at low speeds (see cross-section below).

This road also passes by the structure with unknown clearances that is detailed in constraint 10 in the section concerning the Crêts Blancs motorway area.

11.4.4. Connection to local road network

Illustration 299: Map showing road connection to local road network.

Connecting routes to local road network (Illustration 299):

Yellow route (to Groisy motorway area): existing forest road (Illustration 300)

This route has no particular technical constraints. The following clarifications should be considered:

- length to the “Route de Lécy” road: 850 m (100 m of road to be built for shaft access and 750 m of road to be widened and reinforced);
- cross-section: approx. 3 m, to be widened to at least 4 m;
- intersections: edges to be widened when road is widened.

Illustration 300: Aerial view and diagram of access to the motorway via the forest road.
Coordinates 45.993844, 6.165104.

Route reusing the existing road from Tavernettes to Groisy (in direction of the RD1203 road, Illustration 301 and Illustration 302)

Illustration 301: Chemin des Tavernettes (forest road), looking north. Coordinates 45.995323, 6.165502.

The main constraint is the very steep slope (17.6%, Illustration 303). The following clarifications should be considered:

- length of section to the RD1203 road: 750 m (100 m of road to be built for shaft access and 650 m of road to be widened and reinforced);
- cross-section: approx. 3 m, to be widened to at least 4 m;
- very steep slope: maximum slope 17.6%. It is possible to reduce the slope to 11% by keeping the existing path, but it would require significant excavation (over 10 m). The land take would be significantly reduced compared with the winding road solution. In both cases, the slope is too steep for transporting materials;
- Intersections: combined intersection at end of road to be redesigned;
- Estimated cost: €0.77 M excluding tax.

Illustration 302: Aerial view and access diagram via “Route des Tavernettes” road in Groisy.

Illustration 303: Constraint 8: Elevation profile between the D1203 road and the PG site.

Illustration 304: Example of a convoy of tow-tractor vehicles.

This solution, which uses the “Route des Tavernettes” road in Groisy to travel as close as possible to the PG site, would appear to be ruled out for material and equipment transport, unless it is possible to use tow-tractor vehicles (Illustration 304). This solution seems feasible for light vehicle access.

*Illustration 305: Constraint 9: existing double intersection, which would probably need to be redesigned.
Coordinates 45.985411, 6.166782.*

Junction with departmental road:

- an at-grade junction with a left-hand turn lane would appear to be the best solution;
- dead-end created on the “Route des Tavernettes” road to the southwest, at location indicated by the red cross on Illustration 305 (access to the hamlet is possible from the south).

This junction should be developed in the same way for all routes leading to the RD1203 road.

Cyan route (to the RD1203 road)

This route reduces the gradient to 6.5%, but significantly increases the length of new road to be built (Illustration 306). The construction site constraints will dictate the desired slope gradient. Assuming a slope of around 6.5%, the characteristics are as follows:

- length of section to the RD1203 road: 1 200 m (1 000 m of road to be built to provide shaft access and 200 m of road to be widened and reinforced);
- horizontal layout: numerous hairpin turns with a minimum radius of 20 m, with extra widths on curves;
- steep slopes: 6.5% slope over 1 000 m (followed by 100 m at 7% on the south side);
- estimated cost: €1.35 M excluding tax.

Illustration 306: Route not selected (too many impacts).

Illustration 307: Elevation profile between the D1203 road and the PG site for the cyan route (rejected).

This variant does not appear to be very realistic: it is longer, takes up much more space, and requires significant embankments (7 m maximum in certain cases, see Illustration 307).

Black route (to the RD1203 road, Illustration 308)

This route is an intermediate variant of the two previous ones, which reduces the **slope to 15%** and limits the amount of space used by making use of the “Chemin des Tavernettes” road in Groisy over the longest possible distance.

Its main features are as follows:

- length of section to the RD1203 road: 750 m (300 m of road to be built to provide shaft access and 450 m of road to be widened and reinforced);
- horizontal layout: minimum turn radius of 25 m, with extra widths on curves;
- steep slopes: maximum slope of 15% over 100 m (Illustration 309);
- estimated cost: €0.81 M excluding tax;
- apart from the south-north road running along the RD1203 road, this entire access route is on the plot of land foreseen for the main site.

Illustration 308: Aerial view of the black route.

Illustration 309: Elevation profile of the black route between the D1203 and the PG site.

Cross-sections to be foreseen on sections to be built or widened

On new roads, the cross-section to be created is 4 m of carriageway with 2 x 50 cm shoulders (Illustration 310). Heavy goods vehicles can't pass each other on these roads, but these situations can be avoided by following specified procedures.

Illustration 310: Cross-section diagram for roads to be built.

On roads to be widened, the minimum cross-section is 2 x 2.75 m of carriageway and 2 x 50 cm of drivable shoulder (Illustration 311). This cross-section allows two trucks to pass each other at low speed. On curves in the road, extra widths are required. The appropriate extra widths will need to be added in tight curves to facilitate turning for heavy goods vehicles.

Illustration 311: Cross-section diagram for roads to be widened.

11.5. SUMMARY OF THE PG SITE

The PG site is located in the municipalities of Groisy and Charvonnex, along the RD1203 road, on a sloped site with heterogeneous architectural styles in the surrounding area. A new layout is conceivable and could give a more coherent style to the sector.

From an environmental standpoint, there is a classified wooded area on one of the plots, in Groisy. The sectors under consideration are mainly agricultural.

Access to the main road network is easy via the RD1203 road.

The connection to the Crêts Blancs motorway service area has been discussed with the concessioning authority, DGITM. Northbound and southbound connections are possible.

The creation of a railway branch seems conceivable, but will need to be studied in depth with the competent services.

12. THE PH SITE – CERCIER or MARLIOZ (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE)

Chapter 12 provides a detailed presentation of the location environment of the PH site in Cercier or Marlioz. The description of the site and its environment is followed by an urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (current constraints) and an analysis of access, particularly connections to the railway, motorway and local road networks.

The site boundary presented in this chapter is a conceptual draft and does not necessarily correspond to the exact boundary currently being considered. Section 15.3 presents the latest version of this boundary in detail.

12.1. DESCRIPTION

The theoretical point is located in the municipality of Marlioz, in a mixed zone of forest and farmland. This technical site can be moved approximately 800 m, for example to the municipality of Cercier along the RD2 road, in the Haute-Savoie department (Illustration 312).

The site is located in a preserved rural area, characterised mainly by the presence of agricultural and wooded zones and scattered dwellings. The sector is far from the main traffic arteries. There is little economic activity in the region.

Illustration 312: Map showing the location of the PH site.

The WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical point are :

- Latitude: 46.0146646° N,
- Longitude : 6.0309816° E.

The elevation is 559 m. Shaft depth is 235 m.

The PH site is a technical site, located on the theoretical point. It should be noted that an optimised location to the northwest was studied, but that site also had constraints. As this is a radiofrequency site, if the shaft is moved it must remain on the footprint. The coordinates for the proposed location are as follows:

- Latitude: 46.016411,
- Longitude: 6.019875.

The following types of plots are foreseen (Illustration 313):

- nominal zone to the southeast: approx. 3.4 ha,
- initially analysed zone to the northwest: approx. 4.8 ha.

The list of concerned cadastral plots is shown in Appendix 16.3.

Illustration 313: Map of the proposed plot of land for the PH site (December 2023).

Illustration 314: Map of environmental constraints around the PH site.

Illustration 315: The proposed location is to the south, close to the theoretical point from version PA31-1.0. The ERC (Avoid-Reduce-Compensate) approach led to another scenario being studied at a location to the northwest, but it also has constraints. The point for the PA31-4.0 version is 190 m further to the northeast. It avoids any impact on agricultural areas and remains entirely within the forest.

The ERC (Avoid-Reduce-Compensate) approach was used to examine the different possible layouts in order to reduce the impacts as much as possible.

The layout proposed at the theoretical point seems suitable, but still has two drawbacks: difficult access and the need to clear land. The constraint due to the presence of the forest is acceptable (yellow constraint zone). On the other hand, access must be closely examined, as it would have to pass through a small village to the west or through a hamlet to the east (possible disturbances for neighbouring dwellings). The creation of an access road to the nearest departmental road would likely cause disturbances to neighbouring residences, due to increased vehicle traffic to the construction site. Lastly, at least two farmers would be affected by the creation of the site in scenario PA31-1.0; one because of the use of land required for the site, the other because of the need to build an access road. The optimised PA31-4.0 scenario avoids these drawbacks.

As part of the ERC (Avoid-Reduce-Compensate) approach, other possible locations were examined in order to overcome these two constraints. The technical site for the radiofrequency systems can be moved, but only within certain limits. Moving the location about 800 m in a clockwise direction along the ring would be more favourable in terms of access, as this site is on the RD2 departmental road and access would not be through the hamlets. In addition, this location is closer to a 400 kV high-voltage line (see Illustration 133). On the other hand, this location makes use of farmland, which is a major constraint. In the end, the original location, with a slight northeast shift, was chosen as the best option in the PA31-4.0 reference scenario.

The final choice for the site location also took into account the advantages and disadvantages of this shift in terms of territorial layout, impacts on civil engineering and technical equipment, and effects on scientific performance.

The **characteristics and constraints** of the proposed site (to the south, close to the theoretical site) are as follows:

- land is at the nominal site and is relatively flat;
- clearing of unprotected forest to limit impact on farmland;
- close to the RD203 road, avoiding the municipality by creating access to the RD203 road to the east.

The main **opportunities** offered by the site are as follows (Illustration 316):

- close to the RD203 road;
- water treatment plants appear to be present nearby and will need to be analysed. In particular, a pumping station on the “Route de Chantepoulet” road (coordinates 46.023619, 6.025453) is located nearby, for which potential synergy with the PH site could be examined in detail;
- tourism: an educational farm and equestrian facilities are nearby;
- study the possibility of making industrial waste water from cooling systems available for fruit trees;
- possibility of developing activities that require a heat source, in conjunction with the supply of residual heat (e.g. aquaponics, wood drying);
- reforestation of unused brownfields in the forest (to be identified).

Illustration 316: General map of the main opportunities for the PH site.

Land

All plots are private land (Illustration 317).

Illustration 317: Map of landowners at the PH site (boundary from August 2024). Source: anonymous parcel register.

Map of agricultural activities

Illustration 318: Map of agricultural activities at the PH site. Source: Graphical parcel register.

Only one farmer is present on the proposed plot of land (Illustration 318).

12.2. URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

12.2.1. State of the premises

The site is located in the most rural and unspoilt region of Haute-Savoie. The region is mainly characterised by agricultural zones and wooded areas. The nearest village, Marlioz, is a small, rural village made up of several hamlets scattered around the area. Access is rather difficult, as the area is rural and off the main traffic arteries. Economic activities are underdeveloped. The site is part of a natural, agricultural landscape predominantly made up of apple and pear tree orchards.

Illustration 319: Map showing location of photos taken at the PH site.

Forest at location of nominal site
(number 1 on the map showing the location).

Location close to the nominal site
(number 2 on the map showing the location).

Site to be examined 800 m northwest of the nominal
site (number 3 on the map showing the location).

House along the access road to the nominal site
(number 4 on the map showing the location).

Illustration 320: View from the north of the proposed plot, with the departmental road on the right (number 5 on the map showing the location).

12.2.2. Urban planning, architecture and landscape

The village of Marlioz is made up of small, scattered villages. This is an agricultural region (orchards: apple and pear trees), so the predominant architecture is farmhouses and farm sheds. However, there are also single-family homes.

It should be noted that the photographs presented here are intended to provide some context for the site’s surroundings, and in no way indicate the future architecture of the sites.

Farm.

Single-family home.

Farm shed.

Rolling countryside, very natural and pristine.

12.3. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

Summary map of constraints

Illustration 321 : Map of environmental constraints around the PH site.

The proposed site around the theoretical point is in wooded and agricultural areas (Illustration 321).

It is bordered:

- to the north by forested land and an easement for a gas pipeline,
- to the east by a protected natural area.

12.4. ACCESS ANALYSIS

The plots of land proposed for the PH site are mainly located in the municipality of Cercier and partially in the municipality of Marlioz.

12.4.1. Location in relation to main road network and railways

Illustration 322: Map of access to main road network and railroads.

Points of interest on map of main road network and railroads (Illustration 322):

E11: interchange 11 on the A40 motorway **E18:** interchange 18 on the A41 motorway

E17: interchange 17 on the A41 motorway

G1: Valserhône train station

G2: Groisy- Thorens-La Caille train station

G3: Annecy train station

Constraint 1: 8% average slope for roughly 1.5 km and 30 km/h speed limit for heavy goods vehicles

A succession of zones with constraints: crossings through hamlets and villages, and steep slopes as detailed in the section on the D2 road.

Connection to railways

The most accessible railway lines are at the Valserhône and Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train stations.

The **Valserhône train station** (G1, Illustration 323) is 27.5 km away and has a marshalling yard and sidings in the immediate vicinity of the RD1508 road. Access is not easy, however, and requires crossing through narrow roads in the Valserhône town centre. The possible installation of a conveyor in this dense urban context would need to be analysed in greater detail.

Illustration 323: Aerial view of the Valserhône train station. Coordinates 46.107923, 5.822629.

The **Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train station** (G2, Illustration 324) is located 5 km east of interchange 18 on the A41 motorway and 17 km from the PH site. Access to the train station is relatively easy by continuing for 5 km on the D2 road after the interchange (this route is already used by heavy goods vehicles). This route goes through the villages of Villy-le Pelloux and Groisy, which are unavoidable. This train station is close to the PG site and can also be used for this site.

Illustration 324: Aerial view of the Groisy-Thorens-La Caille train station. Coordinates 46.011380, 6.175406.

The **Annecy train station** (G3, Illustration 325) is near the D1501 road and 23 km from the PH site. Access to the train station is relatively easy via the D1508, D3508 and D1501 roads, which are the main roads connecting Annecy to Valserhône. This route goes through several unavoidable urban areas (La Balme-de-Sillingy, Chaumontet).

Access to the train station from the D1501 presents no problems (same access as for heavy goods vehicles to nearby warehouses). The part of the train station that could be considered for transporting materials is the western part (the station's former freight area, with several sidings shown in yellow in the photo below).

Illustration 325: Aerial view and access diagram of the Annecy train station. Coordinates 45.901586, 6.117131.

Connection to the road network

The road network in the vicinity of the PH site is as follows: A41/A410, A40 motorways and the RD 1508 departmental road.

The main accessible motorway interchanges are:

- E11: via the RD1508 road heading northwest to interchange 11 on the A40 motorway, 21 km away. The A40 motorway connects Lyon to Geneva. The RD1508 road has a section with a slope of around 8% over 1.5 km, with a 30 km/h speed limit for heavy goods vehicles (constraint 1, detailed below);
- E18: interchange 18 of the A41/A410 motorway, 12 km to the east via the D2 road. The A41 motorway goes to Geneva and the A410 to Annemasse;
- E17: The RD 1508 road to the southeast, leading to interchange 17 on the A40 motorway 22 km away, with no topographical constraints.

12.4.2. Departmental roads connecting to the main road network

Illustration 326: Map of routes to the main road network via the departmental roads.

Constraints on routes to the main road network (Illustration 326):

Constraint 2: village of Cercier (about 40 houses, two raised safety platforms, two central traffic islands, zone 30)

Constraint 3: hamlet of 40 houses, (Cologney, two speed bumps)

Constraint 4: hamlet of eight houses (La Trossaz)

Constraint 5: hamlet of twenty houses (Avregny, raised safety platform and central traffic island)

Constraint 6: crossing through the village of Allonzier-la-Caille over a distance of 2 km (raised safety platforms and central traffic island)

Constraint 7: hamlet of twenty houses (Les Pratz)

Constraint 8: on the RD2 road, 200 m west of the RD203 road, 8% slope over 300 m on the S-curve

The RD2 road used to join the main road network has the following characteristics (Illustration 327):

- cross-section: two lanes about 3 m wide, some slightly reduced cross-sections through villages or hamlets on the eastern portion (approximately 2 x 2.50 m, in particular at the raised safety platforms and speed bumps), but which seem sufficient for heavy goods vehicles;
- steep slopes: starting at the RD1508 road, there is an 8% gradient over 300 m in the S-curve before the junction with the RD203 road (the section through Allonzier-la-Caille has an average slope of 5% for around 2 km);
- hamlets and villages: several along the RD2 road to the east of the RD203 road, with raised safety platforms and speed bumps;
- structure of the carriageways: to be assessed and reinforced if necessary.

Illustration 327: Constraint 8: 8% gradient over 300 m. Coordinates 46.023511, 6.038489.

12.4.3. Connection to local road network

Illustration 328 : Map showing road connection to local road network.

Constraints on routes to the RD2 road (Illustration 328):

Constraint 9: narrow intersection with limited visibility, 11% slope over 200 metres before the intersection

Constraint 10: narrow hamlet of 30 houses (Les Albens), narrow intersection, hedges close to the road

Constraint 11: narrow intersection

Existing roads used

RD203 road (blue route to be maintained)

- length of section to the RD2 road: 1.5 km of existing road (and 125 m to be built with a 13% slope on the plot of land);
- cross-section: approx. 4 m, to be widened to at least 5.5 m;
- horizontal layout: sharp turn right before the intersection with the RD2 road (radius of approx. 10 m, extra width already exists);
- slopes: none, except on the section to be built between the PH site and the RD203 road (125 m at 13%);
- structure of carriageways: will most likely have to be reinforced.

“Route des Albens” road (yellow route examined, but ruled out)

- length of section to the RD2 road: 1.1 km of existing road (600 m to be built with an 8% slope);
- cross-section: approx. 4 m, to be widened to at least 5.5 m;
- steep slopes: 11% over 200 m after the junction with the RD203 road, and 600 m at 8% on the existing section of road and the section to be built between the PH site and the “Route des Albens” road;
- intersections: narrow intersection to be widened, between two curves, with poor visibility and only limited modification possible due to the terrain;
- hamlets and villages: the hamlet of Albens must be crossed; narrow road with hedges close to the edge;
- structure of carriageways: will most likely have to be reinforced.

12.5. SUMMARY OF THE PH SITE

The PH site straddles the municipalities of Cercier and Marlioz along the RD203 road in a pristine rural sector far from major traffic arteries. However, the area is crossed by a 400 kV power line, which represents important potential synergy for the FCC. This location appears to be feasible, but special care would have to be taken to ensure its proper integration into the landscape.

From an environmental standpoint, no protected zones have been identified at the proposed plots of land. The preferred location for the site is in a forest, only a small part of which is protected under the PLU (local urban plan).

Due to the area's remote location, access to the main road networks is quite far away. Careful analysis of access points will be necessary during the planning phase for construction projects (widening, reinforcement, gradients, road safety, sewerage system, access to drinking water, electricity supply). Possible connections to train stations are quite far away and would require discussions with operators to better determine their feasibility.

13. THE PJ SITE - DINGY-EN-VUACHE/VULBENS (HAUTE-SAVOIE, FRANCE)

Chapter 13 provides a detailed presentation of the location environment of the PJ site in Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens. The description of the site and its environment is followed by an urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (current constraints) and an analysis of access, particularly connections to the railway, motorway and local road networks.

The site boundary presented in this chapter is a conceptual draft and does not necessarily correspond to the exact boundary currently being considered. Section 15.3 presents the latest version of this boundary in detail.

13.1. DESCRIPTION

The areas under consideration for the PJ site are in the municipalities of Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens, in the Haute-Savoie department, on the slopes of the Vuache and Sion mountains in northwestern Haute-Savoie (Illustration 329).

The site initially considered in scenario PA31-1.0, located between two streams, is a bit too small. Two additional areas to the north and east are also taken into consideration. There are no dwellings in the immediate vicinity. A hamlet lies to the west. The preferred location in scenario PA31-4.0 is a few dozen meters to the east of the area considered in scenario PA31-1.0.

The sector is accessible via the “Route de Vulbens” and “Route de Valleiry” roads. It is close to the A40 motorway, but there is no interchange nearby. However, there is a service area nearby. Accessibility to Dingy-en-Vuache is more limited.

Illustration 329: Map showing the location of the PJ site.

The WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical point are :

- Latitude: 46.0962036° N,
- Longitude : 5.9513024° E.

The elevation is 561 m. Shaft depth is 253 m.

The PJ site is a technical site that could also be an optional scientific site during phase 1 (FCC-ee), but which must be a scientific site during phase 2 (FCC-hh). The main shaft is therefore positioned at the theoretical point. A secondary shaft lies some 80 m inside the ring.

The following types of plots are foreseen (Illustration 330):

- the initial zone from scenario PA31-1.0: approx. 3.7 ha;
- north extension (option): approx. 2 ha;
- east extension (option), approx. 2.6 ha, of fruit trees to the south, particular attention required;
- the preferred zone in scenario PA31-4.0: approx. 5 ha.

It should be noted that environmental constraints pre-dating the February 2022 updates (presence of a protective perimeter for drinking water, see ARS databases) meant that it was not initially possible to consider an extension to the east.

This constraint no longer exists, which has made it possible to consider the move eastwards. This made it possible to decide in particular between agricultural zones and wooded zones with environmental issues.

Illustration 330: Map showing the location of the foreseen plots of land for the PJ site (August 2024).

The **characteristics and constraints** of the initial site (PA31-1.0), between the two streams, are as follows:

- very confined site between two streams, 340 m long and 110 m wide;
- the initial 4 ha site in scenario PA31-1.0 is too small to be used as an experiment site in phase 2;
- separate extension possible to the north (approx. 1.5 ha);
- environmental constraints and motorway to the south;
- hamlet to the west and steep slope;
- separate extension possible to the east (approx. 2 ha);
- no major utility networks (drinking water, sewage system, electricity);
- a single shaft above the experiment cavern is preferred;
- single shaft above the service cavern inside the ring;
- access to the existing rural road must be extended and stabilised. Possibility of resurfacing a road over a distance of 700 m as far north as Vulbens;
- access to the Valleiry motorway service area for activities during the construction phase, 900 m to the east;
- railway access 1,400 m to the north;
- soft mobility project between Vulbens and Valleiry to be taken into account and integrated into site planning;
- potential disturbances to dwellings (recently erected building at 663 Route de Saint-Julien-en-Genevois in Valleiry, and housing in Les Tattes), to be taken into consideration.

Consequently, the preferred site is on the eastern extension in scenario PA31-4.0.

The main **opportunities** offered by the site are as follows (Illustration 331):

- Proximity and possible synergies with the Vuache fire department and rescue centre in Vulbens;
- Close to a new middle school;
- Close to a future station of the French Gendarmerie national police;
- Potential for developing heating networks, particularly with the commercial and industrial zone to the northeast. The Vulbens/Valleiry ZAC (mixed development zone) is to expand and could therefore offer interesting possibilities;
- Possible connections to the railway line and Valleiry motorway service area;
- Possible connection to the motorway service area for electric vehicle recharging (if this is still relevant in 2045);
- Proximity to numerous public facilities in Dingy-en-Vuache, Vulbens and Valleiry, including the Vuache middle school;
- Development of services to accommodate site personnel with the municipalities of Vulbens, Dingy-en-Vuache and Valleiry;
- Zone opposite Grands Chavannoux with good development potential, which could accommodate a high school;
- Possibility of developing a restaurant system using products from nearby farms;
- Reinforcement of the electrical grid in Dingy-en-Vuache;
- Vulbens and Dingy-en-Vuache wish to develop high-quality tourism and scientific tourism. Potential development of tourism around the municipalities;
- Opportunity to participate in the development of soft mobility in the region;
- Possibility of studying the use of industrial waste water from the cooling system for urban needs, agriculture or feeding streams;
- Pumping station located in Vulbens.

Illustration 331: General map of the main opportunities for the PJ site.

Land

The site consists mainly of a municipal portion on the preferred location from scenario PA31-4.0 (Illustration 332) and includes a small private plot of land.

Illustration 332: Map of landowners at the PJ site. Source: anonymous parcel register.

Farmers

Illustration 333: Map of agricultural activities at the PJ site. Source: Graphical parcel register.

13.2. URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

13.2.1. State of the premises

The site is located in the most rural and unspoilt region of Haute-Savoie. The region is mainly characterized by agricultural zones and wooded areas. The site is located at the foot of the Vuache mountain, overlooking the plain below. The Dingy-en-Vuache municipality is crossed by the motorway but has no access, which is in Saint-Julien-en-Genevois (Illustration 334).

Illustration 334: Map showing location of photos taken around the PJ site.

Livestock zones
(number 1 on the map showing the location).

Hamlets overlooking the plain
(number 2 on the map showing the location).

motorway passage
(number 3 on the map showing the location).

Wooded zones
(number 4 on the map showing the location).

13.2.2. Urban planning, architecture and landscape

The village of Dingy-en-Vuache is located on sloped ground at the foot of the Vuache mountain, overlooking the plain below. The area is essentially forests and farmland.

Architecturally, the buildings, whether historic or contemporary, are mainly residential or agricultural.

From a landscape point of view, it is a high-quality zone with great exposure. There are remarkable views of the mountains and plain below.

It should be noted that the photographs presented here are intended to provide some context for the site’s surroundings, and in no way indicate the future architecture of the sites.

Traditional buildings.

Traditional buildings.

View of the plain below.

View over the plain and forests.

Illustration 335: View from the north of the initial site in PA31-1.0 showing the extension towards the main site to the south (number 5 on the map showing the location).

Illustration 336: View from the south of the initial site in PA31-1.0 to the north (number 6 on the map showing the location).

13.3. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

The sites are located along the A40 motorway, in sparsely populated agricultural areas.

Summary map of constraints

Illustration 337: Map of constraints at the PJ site.

The initial site from scenario PA31-1.0 has several constraints, which also apply to the preferred site from scenario PA31-4.0:

- the Acor zone is an agricultural zone located in an ecological corridor, indicated in the PLUi urban plan. Acor zoning is intended to guarantee connectivity between biodiversity reservoirs and allow wildlife to move freely. The use of this zone would need to be justified based on the agronomic value of the soil and the eventual adoption of compensation measures to ensure that wildlife can move freely;
- classified wooded area to the west. Use of the classified wooded area would require a revision of the PLUi urban plan and the adoption of compensation measures if it were destroyed;
- the northern part is affected by the presence of a protected agricultural zone, close to a protected natural area. The protected agricultural zone is imposed by prefectural decree, which could also be lifted by prefectural decree, and would require the adoption of compensation measures;
- it should be noted that, to the east of the proposed plots, several Nh zones are indicated in the PLUi: these are natural zones on the banks of the Rhône or wetlands in the inventory. In the event of a connection to the Valleiry motorway service area, these will be taken into account;
- the plot of land to be examined lies within an SRCE ecological corridor, which is not currently included in the PLUi zoning for this site.

13.4. ACCESS ANALYSIS

The plots of land proposed for the PJ site are located in the municipality of Dingy-en-Vuache, not far from the RD1206 road.

13.4.1. Location in relation to main road network and railways

Illustration 338: Map of main road network and railways.

Points of interest of main road network and railways (Illustration 338):

E13: interchange 13 on the A40 motorway

EA: Valleiry motorway service area

EP: Viry toll booth

G1: closed Collonges Sud train station

G2: Viry railway branch

G3: branch to be added to existing line

Connection to railways

There are three possible connections to the various railroads in the area. These options are as follows:

- the use of existing additional tracks across from the closed Collonges Sud train station (G1);
- industrial branch line of Viry (G2);
- the creation of a branch on the existing line between Vublens and Valleiry.

Discussions about these connections with the current operators of these railroad hubs should make it possible to obtain a more detailed picture of the possibilities for access and use, and to select the best access. This applies in particular to the identified closed site, or for the creation of the new branch line, which may require major works to bring into service.

The **Collonges Sud train station** (Illustration 339) is 7 km from the PJ site. This is a passenger station that has been closed for around ten years, with sidings for loading freight trains. It is located on the Valserhône-Geneva line, which is in service. These sidings are still used, albeit irregularly. Aerial views and Google Street Views show these sidings are busy at certain times, and empty at others. This station could also be used for the PL site. Access is direct from the D1206 road, with no particular difficulties.

Illustration 339: Aerial view of the closed Collonges Sud train station (G1). Coordinates 46.127765, 5.909805.

The **Viry branch (Illustration 340)** is located 9 km from the PJ site. These are a series of branch lines used by industrial companies or unused. It is located on the Valserhône-Annemasse line, which is in service. There is easy access from the D1206 road via the village of Viry, and it already appears to be suitable for heavy goods vehicles. It should be noted, however, that these heavy goods vehicles will have to drive 1.5 km through the village of Valleiry to reach the branch line. Particular attention must therefore be given to this crossing.

Illustration 340: Aerial view of the Viry branch line. Coordinates 46.123210, 6.028611.

A **new branch line (Illustration 341)** could be considered (G3) on the existing line between Vulbens and Valleiry.

This new branch line could be built 1.5 km from the PJ site, and would be the destination for excavated materials via a conveyor. It is located on the Valserhône-Annemasse line, west of Valleiry, which is in service. Even if a conveyor is installed in this location (Illustration 342), it will still be necessary to create access via road to the selected plot for deliveries of equipment and for employee traffic.

Illustration 341: Planned location for creation of a possible branch line. Coordinates 46.108173, 5.958125.

Illustration 342: Map of possible conveyor route connecting the PJ site and G3.

Connection to the road network

The main road network near the PJ site includes the A40 (Lyon-A41) motorway and the RD1206 road.

The A40 motorway can be reached via interchange 13 on the A40 (E13), via the RD1206 road. The primary constraints on this departmental road are presented in the following section.

Two other connections could eventually be possible, but would require special access authorisations for the FCC construction needs, as common law does not allow this type of access:

- Valleiry motorway service area (EA),
- Viry toll gate (EP), eastbound only.

Access from the PJ site to these two connecting points is described in more detail below.

13.4.2. Feasibility of connection to the Valleiry motorway area

The technical, legal and financial feasibility of direct access to motorways has been discussed with the concessioning authority, DGITM.

There seem to be three possible options for reaching the motorway area from the north:

- by truck from the west via the “Chemin de Maigy” road and a new section to be created (on which an engineering structure will be needed to cross the Nant from Vosogne);
- by truck from the east via the D7, D347, D47 and the road running alongside the motorway area to the north. This route passes through the hamlet of Bloux;
- by conveyor along the motorway and motorway area.

To reach the motorway area from the south, three options also seem possible:

- by truck from the west via the “Chemin de Maigy” road and the “Coûtant” rural road;
- by truck from the east via the D7, D347, D47 and the road running alongside the motorway area to the south (“Coûtant” rural road). This route passes through the hamlet of Bloux;
- by conveyor along the motorway, with a crossing of the motorway to be planned.

The different options for routes to the motorway area are shown on the following map, including the proposed storage and loading zones along the area.

Illustration 343: Map showing the location between the PJ site and the Valleiry motorway area, with the theoretical conveyor and heavy goods vehicle routes.

Valleiry Nord motorway area

This preferred solution would involve loading and unloading heavy goods vehicles on the plot of land identified as a storage/loading zone. HGVs on the motorway would then have to use a new gate created between the motorway area and the plot. This gate would only be used to exit the area and would be located on the light vehicle lane before reaching the light vehicle parking areas. A relatively long section of road would be needed at the exit of the motorway area, due to the difference in elevation between the area and the outside road running alongside it. This road would be located close to the old ramp. A ramp would be used to enter the plot. The HGVs would then cross through the existing gate and would exit via the light-vehicle road running alongside the restaurant. The curve to the south of the existing gate should be widened to allow the HGVs to turn properly.

In this option, the heavy goods vehicles would only use lanes currently used by light vehicles. They would, however, avoid the parking and picnic areas intended for light vehicles. Visibility and safety conditions are good.

Illustration 344: Preferred solution for Valleiry Nord: truck loading on a plot of land away from the motorway area.

Valleiry Sud motorway area

Illustration 345: Preferred solution for Valleiry Sud: truck loading on a plot of land away from the motorway area.

13.4.3. Departmental roads connecting to the main road network

Illustration 346: Map of routes to the main road network via the departmental roads.

Constraints of departmental road network (Illustration 346)

Constraint 1: 5% slope over 2 km, narrow bridge

Constraint 2: crossing through the village of Vulbens over a distance of 1.5 km (central traffic islands)

Constraint 3: crossing through the village of Valleiry over a distance of 1.5 km (central traffic islands)

Constraint 4: crossing through the hamlet of La Boutique (around ten houses near the departmental road)

Constraint 5: crossing through the hamlet of Essertet (around forty houses near the departmental road)

Constraint 6: crossing through Viry over a distance of 650 m (central traffic islands)

Constraint 7: crossing through Cervonnex over a distance of 1 km, 6% slope over 400 m

In all cases, the road leading to the main road network is the RD1206. Its overall characteristics are satisfactory. The following clarifications should be considered:

- steep slopes: near the Rhone, gradient of approximately 5% over 2 km. In Cervonnex, gradient of approximately 6% over 400 m;
- hamlets and villages: six identified crossings, with the occasional central traffic island;
- carriageway structures: appear to be suitable.

13.4.4. Connection to local road network

Illustration 347: Connections to the local network for the PJ site.

Constraints of local road network (Illustration 347):

Constraint 8: crossing through a narrow section of Vulbens, limited to vehicles weighing 3.5 tonnes

Constraint 9: La Vy du Crêt, 7% slope over 600 m

Constraint 10: existing structure probably to be demolished/rebuilt (inspection required)

Constraint 11: the “Chemin des Tattes” road, 7% slope over 500 m

Constraint 12: crossing through the village of Dingy-en-Vuache (ten houses close to the D7) with very narrow existing intersection, to be widened

Constraint 13: crossing through the hamlet of Bloux over a distance of 800 m, 5% slope over 700 m, central traffic island

Constraint 14: crossing through a portion of the village of Valleiry over a distance of 600 m, 6% gradient over 1 km, central traffic island

Constraint 15: bridge to be built over the Nant from Vosogne

Constraint 16: the “Coûtant” rural road, 13% slope over 400 m, underpass of unknown size

Table of costs and roadworks for each route:
Table 34: Detailed description of work by route

Route	Length	Cross-section	Slopes	Intersections	Engineering structures (ES)	Other	Cost
Dark blue: La Vy du Crêt, the Gillin rural road, the Rippaz municipal road and the "Chemin des Tattes" road	1 200 m of existing road to be widened	Existing: 3 m carriageway, to be widened to 5.50 m + 50 cm shoulders to enable cross-traffic	7% over 600 m	-	ES on the Rippaz municipal road to be assessed and destroyed/rebuilt if necessary	-3.5 t weight limit in La Vy du Crêt -Carriageway structures to be checked -200 m of narrow passages, difficult to widen, in Vulbens (4.50 m wide)	€1.030 M excluding any ESs
Yellow: "Chemin des Tattes" road	630 m of existing road to be widened	Existing: 3 m carriageway, to be widened to 5.50 m + 50 cm shoulders to enable cross-traffic	7% over 500 m	Narrow intersection with the D1206 road, probably needs to be modified	-	Carriageway structures to be checked	€700 000
Red: D7, D347 and D47 roads	3 450 m of existing road and 100 m to be created for site access	Existing: 5.50 m except the D347 road (4.5 m) and along motorway (3 m), to be widened to 5.50 m + 50 cm shoulders along the D347 road and at 4 m + 50 cm shoulders along the motorway	-5% over 700 m when crossing through Bloux -6% over 1 km in Valleiry	Narrow intersection with the D1206 road, probably needs to be modified	-	-Crossing through Valleiry over a distance of 600 m and Bloux for 800 m -Carriageway structures to be checked	€860 000 (only for work on the D347 road, along the motorway and for a connection 100 m long between the road and the plot of land + modified intersection)
Black: the "Coûtant" rural road	1 300 m (350 m of road near the site, 800 m of unpaved roads and 450 m of road along the motorway area)	Existing: approx. 3 m near the site and on the unpaved road. Approx. 5 m along the motorway area, to be widened to 5.50 m + 50 cm shoulders near the site and at 4 m + 50 cm shoulders on the road	13% over 400 m and other short sections of approx. 7%	-	-	Carriageway structures to be checked on existing asphalt surfaces	€840 000

Cyan: direct access to the motorway area	600 m of existing or new road	.Existing: approx. 3 m, to be widened or created with 4 m + 50 cm shoulders	8% over 100 m and ES on slope on the Nant of Vosogne	-	To be created to cross the Nant of Vosogne	Carriageway structures to be checked on existing asphalt surfaces	€530 000 excluding ES
--	-------------------------------	---	--	---	--	---	-----------------------

13.5. SUMMARY OF THE PJ SITE

The PJ site is located in the municipalities of Vulbens (northern part of the site) and Dingy-en-Vuache (southern part of the site), not far from small departmental roads, in a pristine, rural area. The A40 motorway runs alongside the potential sites, but there are no direct connections nearby. This location appears to be feasible, but special care would have to be taken to ensure its proper integration into the landscape.

From an environmental standpoint, the proposed plots have protected zones (protected agricultural zones, agricultural zones protected for their agronomic and ecological potential, classified wooded areas), which will have to be taken into account, with the adoption of the appropriate compensation measures in the corresponding procedures.

Access to the main road networks is quite far away and requires crossing many hamlets. Direct connections to the motorway via the Valleiry motorway area have been discussed with the concessioning authority, DGITM. Northbound and southbound connections are possible.

For the railways, various connections seem possible and will need to be studied in conjunction with SNCF Réseau.

14. THE PL SITE - CHALLEX (AIN, FRANCE)

Chapter 14 provides a detailed presentation of the location environment of the PL site in Challex. The description of the site and its environment is followed by an urban and landscape analysis, an environmental analysis (current constraints) and an analysis of access, particularly connections to the railway, motorway and local road networks.

The site boundary presented in this chapter is a conceptual draft and does not necessarily correspond to the exact boundary currently being considered. Section 15.3 presents the latest version of this boundary in detail.

14.1. DESCRIPTION

The site is located in the municipality of Challex in the Ain department, on the border with Switzerland, close to the RD884 road (Illustration 348).

Challex is a well-preserved, residential village in a high-quality natural and agricultural setting. Main access is via the RD89 departmental road (“Route de Greny”).

The proposed site is located in a vast agricultural area to the northeast of the village, offering a range of possible development scenarios.

Illustration 348: Map showing the location of the PL site.

The WGS84 coordinates of the theoretical point are:

- Latitude: 46.1926255° N,
- Longitude : 5.9810829° E.

The elevation is 508 m. Shaft depth is 250 m.

The PL site is a technical site. The shaft can be moved to a more suitable zone.

The map below shows a larger area of study than what is required for the surface site.

The indicated point is the theoretical location of the midpoint of the straight segment. The access shaft can be moved along the ring up to 1 000 m and laterally inside the ring over a distance of approximately 30 m. The feasibility of a shaft outside the ring has yet to be analysed. Technically and financially, the impact would be significant. A service cavern would be located inside the tunnel. The exact dimensions of the cavern depend on technical requirements and have yet to be defined.

The general context for a site placed at the nominal point (centre of the straight section) is as follows (Illustration 349):

- protected agricultural zone;
- presence to be confirmed of a temporary water table on both sides of the border at a depth of around 25 m;
- close to a rented villa;
- presence of two additional single-family homes 300 m away (one renovated, one built in 2021 on the opposite side of the small “Route de Dardagny” road, across from the protected vineyard);
- all the land is on private plots;
- the “Route de Dardagny” road cannot be used for access because it is small and crosses through Challex. In addition, the road is closed for cross-border travel.;
- the plot is completely flat, with a slight incline behind the villa closest to the Swiss border.

Illustration 349: Map showing the location of the foreseen plots of land for the PL site.

The characteristics of a site at the nominal point at the centre of the straight section of the ring are as follows:

- the site's perimeter is currently being optimised, and a surface area of up to 4 ha seems possible;
- the presence of a temporary groundwater table has yet to be confirmed or disconfirmed by subsoil investigations, and compatibility with this potential constraint needs to be confirmed when optimizing the location of the shaft and the overall site;
- a single shaft above a service cavern inside the ring;
- two family homes within the zone near the nominal point: acquire these properties or create a site behind the homes, at equal distance from the three existing buildings;
- the need to preserve protected vineyards on both sides of the border;
- presence of a forest (which includes wetlands) to the northwest, approximately 800 m from the site;
- presence of the village to the south, approximately 600 m from the site;
- very good integration in the existing landscape is necessary;
- no existing utility networks (drinking water, sewage system, electricity);
- no access road. Creation of access to connect to the D884 road via the D89 road;
- avoid visibility from houses and the village;
- preserve the landscape of the hiking trail through the vineyards;
- access possible to the railway at the closed Pont Carnot train station, approximately 10 km away. It should be noted that the Carnot bridge is located on the "TE72" road network, which is open to exceptional convoys with a total rolling weight of 72 tonnes or less (prefectoral decree no. DREAL-RCTV-TE01-01/2018).

The main **opportunities** offered by the site are as follows (Illustration 350):

- close to the CERN sites in Meyrin and Prévessin and their services;
- close to the 400 kV power line;
- close to various public facilities;
- possibility of creating a heating network for public facilities, businesses or housing, for example with the ZAC de Thoiry mixed development zone or the La Plaine zone (with the company Firmenich);
- possibility of developing activities that require a heat source, in conjunction with the supply of residual heat (e.g. aquaponics, wood drying, greenhouses);
- possible partnerships with nearby restaurants;
- possibility of reopening the Collonges-Divonne-les-Bains railway line for the transport of goods and travellers (discussions are underway to turn it into a greenway);
- close to the Val Thoiry shopping centre (4 km);
- possibility of creating a conveyor to transport excavated materials to nearby recycling sites, to the closed Collonges train station and to the La Plaine train station in Switzerland.

Illustration 350: General map of the main opportunities for the PL site.

Table 35 shows the possible layout scenarios with their main advantages and disadvantages.

Table 35: Proposed layout scenarios.

<p>Scenario 1</p> <p>Contiguous site as close as possible to the village, but at a sufficient distance to limit visibility from dwellings.</p> <p>Depending on the location, the nearest houses are around 100 m to the southeast.</p> <p>Advantages: short access route to the site, in direction of the D89 road. No direct visibility from entrance to the village. Negligible environmental constraints and no hydrogeological constraints. Difficulties accessing the collider tunnel from outside the ring. Access must not be at the midpoint or at the end of the straight section.</p> <p>Disadvantage: close to certain dwellings, depending on the layout configuration.</p>	
<p>Scenario 2</p> <p>A contiguous site close to protected vineyards, not requiring the acquisition of houses or land takes.</p> <p>There are three houses 175 m away to the east, 240 m away to the south and 300 m away to the southwest, with potential residual disturbances.</p> <p>Advantages: access to the nominal point, at the midpoint of the straight section of the ring and inside the ring, is closer than in scenario 1. Away from the village and no direct visibility of the site.</p> <p>Disadvantages: close to certain dwellings, access route is long and difficult to create. Constraints due to an ecological corridor and protected areas in the vicinity. Two remote dwellings nearby.</p>	

Scenario 3

A contiguous site away from the residential zone, with an extension for the shaft location.

There are three houses 200 m away to the east, 260 m away to the south and 300 m away to the southwest, with less potential residual disturbances than in scenario 2.

Advantages: access to the nominal point, at the midpoint of the straight section of the ring and inside the ring, is closer than in scenario 1. Away from the village and no direct visibility of the site.

Disadvantages: close to certain dwellings, access route is a bit long and difficult to create. Constraints due to an ecological corridor and protected areas in the vicinity. Two remote dwellings nearby.

Scenario 4

A contiguous site away from the residential zone, with the possibility of an extension for the shaft located inside the ring at the nominal point.

The distance to the houses to the southeast is around 300 m, but the site is adjacent to a villa located about 100 m away. Technical infrastructures can also be located 130 m north of these two houses.

Advantages: direct access to the nominal point, at the midpoint of the straight section of the ring and inside the ring. Entirely outside the village with no direct visibility of the site.

Disadvantages: access road to be created in the direction of the D89 road through farmlands. Potential technical constraints due to the presence of a temporary water table (to be confirmed or disconfirmed), but no blocking points. Constraints due to an ecological corridor must be respected. One remote dwelling nearby, which would need to be acquired.

Scenario 5

Advantages: direct access to “Rue de la Craz” road. Less impact on nature than the other scenarios, with direct access to the main utility networks (roads, sewage systems, drinking water, electricity). Possibility of moving some of the surface site's technical facilities further away from the village.

Disadvantages: the site is visible from the D89 road. Close to a few houses. If it is not possible to use a portion of land between the community hall and the sports field, a shaft outside the ring will have to be considered, which will require a technical feasibility analysis and entail additional costs for the research infrastructure. At a distance of 1,050 m from the nominal point.

Scenario 6

A contiguous site away from dwellings, in an Ap zone.

Advantages: the location is away from dwellings and behind a line of trees. The access route from the “Route de Greny” road (D89) would only be 370 m long.

Disadvantages: the location is outside the collider tunnel, meaning a solution needs to be developed to gain access to the machinery, entailing additional costs. The site is in the immediate vicinity of protected natural areas and zones of high ecological value, which means that the surface area cannot be increased. The available area of 1.7 ha is too small for a surface site. The distances of 720 m to the nominal point and of 300 m for a connecting tunnel to the main tunnel would result in significant additional costs.

Scenario 7

A contiguous 4-hectare site away from dwellings, in an Np zone.

Advantages: the location is away from dwellings and behind a line of trees. and has enough space to accommodate an above-ground technical site.

Disadvantages: the location is outside the collider tunnel, meaning a solution needs to be developed to gain access to the machinery, entailing additional costs. It is located in the immediate vicinity of wetlands, in a natural protection zone with high ecological value.

The access route from the “Route de Greny” road (D89) would be long (over 800 m) and through the forest and protected zones.

The distances of 580 m to the nominal point and of 380 m for a connecting tunnel to the main tunnel would result in excessive additional costs.

This option is therefore ruled out.

Scenario 8

A contiguous site as close as possible to the village, to the north of Scenario 1, on a field on almost level ground.

Depending on the location, the nearest houses are approximately 250 m to the south.

Advantage: surface area of approximately 4.4 ha to accommodate a surface site with good landscape integration. No hydrogeological constraints. Difficulties accessing the collider tunnel from outside the ring. with an underground connecting tunnel 150 m long entailing an acceptable extra cost. Access must not be at the midpoint or at the end of the straight section.

Disadvantages: the access route from the “Route de Greny” road (D89) would be long (between 650 and 850 m). Possible shared visibility with the dwellings on the Pré de Cure housing estate and with the “Route de Dardagny” road cannot be ruled out. Presence of a forest, which includes wetlands, in the immediate vicinity of the site.

Land

The site is made up entirely of private plots of land, except for a slight encroachment on departmental and municipal plots in scenarios 4 and 7, respectively (Illustration 351).

Illustration 351: Map of landowners at the PL site. Source: anonymous parcel register.

Farmers

Several farmers would appear to be affected, depending on the scenario (Illustration 352).

Illustration 352: Maps of agricultural activities around the PL site. Source: Graphical parcel register.

14.2. URBAN AND LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

14.2.1. State of the premises

The site is located in the municipality of Challex, near the Swiss border. The agglomeration, farmland and vineyards are on the French side, and protected wine-growing areas are on the Swiss side. The geographical area concerned is characterised by a rural plain at the foot of the Jura mountains. The D884 departmental road connecting Collonges to Saint-Genis-Pouilly passes outside the village but not far from the site (Illustration 353). Access is via the D89 road.

Illustration 353: Map showing location of photos taken around the PL site.

The land is flat, with wooded surroundings. A gentle slope leads from the village towards the D884 road and the forest to the north.

Illustration 354: View of fields to the southwest (number 1 on the map showing the location).

Agricultural plain at the foot of the Jura mountains.

The D884 departmental road.

Presence of a great deal of woodlands.

Residential urban agglomeration.

14.2.2. Urban planning, architecture and landscape

The village of Challex is a small, residential agglomeration with relatively dense urban development. The surrounding area is made up of farmlands and wooded areas. The "traditional" home is a single-family house with a garden surrounded by a hedge to preserve privacy, which creates a sense of isolation when strolling through the narrow village streets.

It should be noted that the photographs presented here are intended to provide some context for the site's surroundings, and in no way indicate the future architecture of the sites.

"Rue du Village" road in Challex.

Residences seen from afar. In the background, the Jura mountains.

14.3. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

Summary map of constraints

Illustration 355 : Map of constraints around the PL site.

Environmental constraints (Illustration 355)

The site has a wide perimeter, offering a range of possibilities, that includes the houses to the east that may need to be acquired.

Each plot of land is protected (Ap zoning: protected agricultural zone; Np zoning: protected natural area), with an orange sensitivity level.

- for the protected agricultural zones: where applicable, this protection imposed by prefectural decree could be lifted, also by prefectural decree, and would require the adoption of compensatory measures;
- for the protected natural area: fauna and flora inventories will be carried out in this zone. A wetland (Zh) to the west, corresponding to a Ramsar site in Switzerland, appears to indicate a potentially rich natural environment (Illustration 355). It is also considered to be a zone to be avoided in France. A buffer space to the south of the forest must be maintained.

A fauna-flora inventory is included in the feasibility study to obtain more detailed information.

It should be noted that a groundwater table close to the border is currently under investigation.

Other environmental factors are also worth mentioning:

- wetlands and forests to the north and west (Ramsar classification in Switzerland);
- high-quality natural environment nearby;
- rich flora and fauna to be inventoried (detailed environmental study to be carried out in the sector);
- protected vineyards nearby on both sides of the border, which must be preserved;
- very quiet residential area, with no major construction:
- marked hiking trails for nature observation, historical trail through vineyards and historical stones on the border between France and Switzerland;
- underpass beneath the D884 road on the D89 road to CERN and Challex, with a clearance of 4.4 m. No obstacles when coming from Collonges;
- for local access to the PL site, it is necessary to bypass farms and to respect all sensitive areas (forests, hedges, ecological corridors between the forest and the Rhone).

Illustration 356: Map of strategic water bodies around the PL site.

The site lies between the Rhone and a strategic body of water (Illustration 356). The zone, is close to the Swiss border in Switzerland and in the forest to the north, is characterised by the presence of temporary water tables and wetlands to the north.

There is an ecological corridor between the forest/Ramsar site and the Rhone (Illustration 358).

Ramsar Site CH-6, Le Rhône genevois - Vallons de l'Allondon et de la Laire

Illustration 357: Map of the Ramsar network in the Challex region.

Illustration 358: Sign for wildlife corridors on the Swiss side; this type of sign is mainly placed along watercourses (taken from an information sign on the Bornes trail, May 2022).

Optimizing the layout close to the Swiss border in the protected agricultural zone (Ap) or in the protected natural area (Np) will require a more detailed analysis of the factors that led to this zoning (Illustration 359).

Illustration 359: Map showing protected natural areas and protected agricultural zones adjacent to the PL site.

Illustration 360 shows the environmental constraints for the proposed scenarios.

Illustration 360: Maps showing the constraints for the PL site scenarios.

Existing or ongoing projects to be taken into account

Plot A197 is occupied by a villa (Illustration 361).

A house was recently renovated (plot A26), and a new one was built in November 2021 at the location indicated in orange on the “Route de Dardagny” road (plot A1750), just opposite the planned zone (Illustration 362).

Illustration 361: Map showing the location of the existing house and the construction project for a house around the nominal PL point, at the midpoint of the straight section of the ring. The construction project for the house has since been completed.

Two single-family homes are close to the Swiss border. The plots concerned are A498, A499, A500, A501, A502, A503, A504 and A505.

Plots A500, A501 and A504 make up one property; A502 and A503 make up a second property. A505 provides joint access (Illustration 362).

Illustration 362: Aerial view of the cadastral plots surrounding the dwellings and hedges at the nominal point PL.

Plots A498 and A499 make up a property and include a protected tree line, indicated in the PLU (local urban plan).

The PLU mentions "landscape elements (sites and sectors) to be preserved for ecological reasons" for the tenement with two houses (Illustration 363).

The identified constraint is orange, and if use of this land is foreseen, the hedgerows could be recreated.

Illustration 363: Status of tree lines surrounding the developed plots of land.

Possibilities for temporary storage and processing of excavated materials

In the initial approach, subject to more specific studies, the excavated materials could be temporarily stored on the agricultural plots if authorised by the owners and operators.

Aspects concerning the evacuation of materials are covered in the "Access analysis" section.

Opportunities

Determining the most suitable perimeter within the proposed location will make it possible to develop or renaturalise the land in a way that best meets needs and expectations.

Tourism could be a sector for the development and enhancement of the region through a variety of activities: hiking, sports, visits to vineyards, discovery of historical aspects of the border region and the nature areas.

Although it already has a good digital network, the village of Challex could benefit from more reliable and less costly telecommunication infrastructures by linking up with the CERN infrastructures.

Residual heat from the site could be supplied to the village for heating purposes. If necessary, fruit and vegetable growers would particularly benefit from this supply. Heat can also be conveyed to the Val Thoiry shopping centre to the northeast, or to La Plaine (Switzerland) to the south.

The reopening of the closed Collonges Sud train station (plot AB201) near the Rhone could create long-term opportunities for freight transport.

14.4. ACCESS ANALYSIS

The plots of land under consideration for the proposed PL site options are in the Challex municipality, near the RD884 road (Illustration 364).

14.4.1. Location in relation to main road network and railways

Connections to the main road network in the vicinity of the PL site can be made via the 2x2-lane RD884 road, then via the “Route de Meyrin” road to the A1 motorway (total length of 16 km).

The RD884 road, followed by the RD984 road heading southbound, provide access to the A40 motorway, but these are longer, two-way roads through several towns and villages.

Illustration 364: Map of access to main road network and railways.

Points of interest on the main road network and railways (Illustration 364):

- E5: interchange 5 (Meyrin) on the A1 motorway
- G1: Meyrin train stations
- G2: connection to a closed railway line in Péron
- G3: closed Collonges Sud train station
- G4: the La Plaine train station

Constraint 1: engineering structure with clearance of 4.40 m on the D984 road after the D884 road to G3

Constraint 2: engineering structure with clearance of 4.40 m on the D884 road

Constraint 3: customs station on “Route de Meyrin” road

Connection to railways:

Four connections are possible to railways in the sector. These options are:

- the Meyrin train stations (G1);
- the creation of a train station for loading materials on the closed line passing through Péron (G2);
- the use of existing additional tracks across from the closed Collonges Sud train station (G3);
- the La Plaine train station (G4).

For these connections, discussions with the current operators of these railroad hubs should make it possible to obtain a more detailed picture of the possibilities for access and use, and to select the best access. This applies in particular to the identified lines and sites that are closed, as their return to service may require significant work.

The Meyrin train stations (Illustration 365), located approximately 15 km from the PL site, are made up of two passenger stations (Zimeysa and Meyrin) and have multiple sidings used by neighbouring industrial companies. It seems possible to remove the excavated materials via one of these sidings, or to build a new one. Access to this railroad complex is easy for heavy goods vehicles, as the roads between the “Route de Meyrin” road and the railways are already suitable for heavy goods vehicles from the industrial zone. This train station could also be useful for the PA site.

Illustration 365: Map of the Meyrin train stations.

Connection to the partially closed Pied du Jura line

This line, on which a connection is conceivable, runs from Valserhône to Gex (Illustration 366). It has been closed for several decades and would probably need to be renovated (some sections have been developed as greenways), and its structural capacity would have to be checked (engineering structures in particular). Any connection will have to be in line with the¹³⁴ discussions currently underway between local French and Swiss authorities.

Illustration 366: Potential development of the Pied du Jura railway line.

¹³⁴ [https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ligne_de_Collonges_-_Fort-l'Écluse_-_Divonne-les-Bains_\(frontière\)](https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ligne_de_Collonges_-_Fort-l'Écluse_-_Divonne-les-Bains_(frontière)) et https://www.grand-geneve.org/wp-content/uploads/2a04_rapport_autosaisine_tranports_ferroviaires_juin_2021.pdf

Railway connection in Péron

A connection could be created between Péron and Saint-Jean-de-Gonville (Illustration 367) on an existing line along the D984 road. The train station to be created would be 4.5 km away (eastern option, shown in cyan) or 6 km away (western option, shown in orange).

Illustration 367: Map of possible connection to the closed line in Péron.

Constraints of the connection to the Péron line (Illustration 367):

Constraint 4: underpass beneath the D884 road, maximum clearance of 4.40 m

Constraint 5: on the RD984 road, crossing through the southern part of the village of Péron, with approximately 25 dwellings

Constraint 6: on the RD89 road, crossing through the hamlet of Greny with approximately ten dwellings, a reduced cross-section only 5 m wide between a sidewalk and a low wall (widening to at least 5.50 m to allow heavy goods vehicles to pass each other)

The orange route (D884-D884A-D984) has satisfactory characteristics. The following clarifications should be considered:

- crossing through the southeastern part of the village of Péron;
- structure of the carriageways: to be assessed but appear to be satisfactory.
- underpass beneath the D884 road (height clearance of 4.40 m).

The cyan route (D89-D984) has satisfactory characteristics. The following clarifications should be considered:

- cross-section: for crossing through Greny with 2 x 2.5 m between the sidewalk and the low wall, widening may be necessary to allow two heavy goods vehicles to pass each other;
- structure of the carriageways: to be assessed but appear to be satisfactory.
- underpass beneath the D884 road (height clearance of 4.40 m).

The (closed) Collonges Sud train station is located 13 km from the PL site (Illustration 368 and Illustration 370). This is a passenger station that has been closed for approximately ten years, with sidings for loading freight trains. It is located on the Valsershône-Geneva line, which is in service. These sidings are still in use, albeit irregularly (aerial views and Google Street Views show these sidings are busy at certain times, and empty at others). This train station could also be used by the PJ site.

Access to the train station (D906-D1206) has satisfactory characteristics. The last curve leading to the entrance gate from the selected route is on the inside of the curve and is very tight; it will probably need to be widened (constraint 7).

Illustration 368: Aerial view of the Collonges Sud train station. Coordinates 46.127483, 5.909203.

Illustration 369: Access to the Collonges Sud train station.

La Plaine train station: there is a siding to the north of the La Plaine station that appears to be unused (Illustration 370). It could be reached by means of a conveyor belt approximately 2.3 km long (feasibility to be verified given the topographical conditions, Illustration 371). The installation of this conveyor does not remove the need for one of the proposed road access options, particularly for equipment deliveries to the site.

Illustration 370: Aerial view of the La Plaine train station. Coordinates 46.17886, 5.999594.

Illustration 371 : Possible conveyor route to the La Plaine train station.

It should be noted that:

- depending on the location of the site, the conveyor route may cross protected agricultural areas;
- the La Plaine train station is located close to residential areas;
- the use of the Meyrin train station, the La Plaine train station, or another loading platform located in Switzerland for the removal of excavated materials to French territory is subject to the notification procedure for waste exportation.

The hypothetical installation of a conveyor to the “Les Baraques” locality (southeast of Challex, near the Rhone on the French side) also seems difficult, given the potential disturbances to nearby dwellings.

14.4.2. Departmental roads connecting to the main road network

The hypothetical connection to the main network presented here is for the location northeast of Challex. This is the most unfavourable case in terms of the length of the connection.

Illustration 372: Map of routes to the main road network via the departmental roads.

Constraint 4: engineering structure with clearance of 4.40 m on the D89 underpass beneath the D884 road

Routes taken (Illustration 372):

RD89 (magenta route): the length of the existing road up to the RD884 road is approximately 1 km and presents no particular difficulties, apart from the carriageway structures, which probably need reinforcing. This is the only possible route to the south of Challex, with a 12-tonne vehicle weight limit and a clearance of 4.40 m under the RD884.

14.4.3. Connection to local road network

In scenario 5 (site to the southwest), the connection to the local road network is direct (the “Rue de la Craz” road).

For the other hypothetical plots of land examined below, the proposed solutions are based on the decision to avoid crossing through the village of Challex.

The **yellow route**, which uses a portion of the “Route de Dardagny” road (Illustration 372), **should be ruled out** due to the small size of the road, its use for tourism and walking, and its proximity to residential areas. The following analysis is presented for informational purposes.

Route 1 blue (preferred): this route provides a direct connection to the RD89 road to the west of the PL site. The slope is gentle (maximum 4%) and the horizontal alignment is fairly straight. A 1.3 km stretch of road would then have to be created across the fields. The minimum cross-section would be 4 m, and instructions would be specified to facilitate manoeuvres when two HGVs pass each other. This route is shorter and straighter than the yellow variant, and not as close to dwellings. Two-thirds of it is located on the proposed plot of land for the site, making it the preferred alternative.

Route 2 yellow (not selected): this route connects to the RD89 road to the west of the PL site, making maximum use of existing paths and roads, including the “Route de Dardagny” road. The slope is gentle, apart from a portion approximately 80 m long with a 9% slope on the existing section of road to the northeast of the “Route de Dardagny” road. The road has many curves, but the turn radius can be adapted to accommodate heavy goods vehicles. Widening will be necessary. This would mean creating approximately 1 km of road through the fields and widening and reinforcing 700 m of existing roads and paths. The minimum cross-section would be 4 m on the new sections, and instructions would be specified to facilitate manoeuvres when two HGVs pass each other.

Previously, a **site to the southeast had been considered, but then ruled out** due major difficulties obtaining access.

The purpose of the following analysis is to keep track of these analyses and to present the identified difficulties.

Possible access from another site (to the south of the previous PL site)

Illustration 373: Constraint 8: two houses nearby.

Blue route (Illustration 373): this route provides a direct connection to the RD89 road to the northwest of Challex, bypassing the village to the north. It has a high impact on protected agricultural areas. The route starts at the highest point of the plot. The slope is on average 6% over 900 m and is gentle for the rest of the route. The horizontal alignment includes two curves with a wide radius that allow the passage of heavy goods vehicles. A stretch of road 1.9 km long would need to be built through fields and, in part, on a hillside with vineyards. The minimum cross-section would be 4 m (same cross-section as for the initial point L), with instructions specified to facilitate manoeuvres when two HGVs pass each other, and would require extra widths on the inside of the curves.

Yellow route (Illustration 373): this route differs from the previous one in its eastern portion. It has a lower impact on protected agricultural areas. It connects to the “Route de Dardagny” road via a slope and partly follows an existing path. The slope averages 11% over 320 m after exiting the proposed plot of land for the site. It becomes less steep when arriving at the “Route de Dardagny” road. The horizontal alignment features a single sharp curve, which must have a turn radius and width that allow for the passage of heavy goods vehicles. The cross-section is the same as for the blue route. The route includes 650 m of road to be widened and reinforced and 950 m of road to be built (a total of 1.6 km).

Red route: a route to the south connected to the other proposed plot was examined (Illustration 374), but the amount of space that would need to be used seems unrealistic.

Illustration 374: Map of red route.

Conveyor to the La Plaine train station: to remove materials, a siding north of the La Plaine train station (Illustration 375) appears to be unused. It could be reached by a conveyor belt about 1.25 km long (feasibility to be verified for these topographical conditions). The installation of this conveyor does not remove the need for one of the previously proposed road access options, particularly for equipment deliveries to the site.

Illustration 375: Possible conveyor route to the La Plaine train station.

More detailed local route

Illustration 376: Aerial view and local access route.

Illustration 377: Elevation profile of the local route.

Advantages:

- the connexion to the D89 road is satisfactory (visibility);
- longitudinal profile with no significant slope ($< 3.6\%$, except near the PL site);
- no zones with significant environmental impact;
- minimum horizontal radius of 54 m (suitable for 50 km/h);
- more direct access and a shorter total distance of 1 300 m to the shaft;
- far away from dwellings and less visible from a distance.

Disadvantages:

- fewer existing roads used;
- crosses through a farm.

Cost of local connections

For a more detailed local route from the PL site, the cost of access would be roughly €1.8 M excluding tax. This cost is calculated on the basis of a cost of €1 M/km for the new sections and €800 000/km for the reinforced section of the D89 road, assuming that the current structure under the D89 road between the interchange with the D884 road and the new section is insufficient. This cost does not include land acquisition.

14.5. SUMMARY OF THE PL SITE

The PL site is located in the municipality of Challex, not far from the RD 884 road. It is in the rural Ain region, on an agricultural and residential plain at the foot of the Jura mountains. Particular attention must be paid to the village of Challex.

From an environmental standpoint, a number of issues have been identified: protections due to the high-quality agricultural and natural value of the land (classified wooded areas, hedges and wetlands).

Access routes to major road networks will not cross through the village. The site proposed at the nominal point, northwest of the “Route de Dardagny” road, presents some challenges:

- presence of a temporary cross-border water table to be confirmed or disconfirmed;
- close to a remote dwelling;
- access routes to be built that cross through agricultural areas, zones with Ap and Np classification and an ecological corridor;
- hiking and leisure area.

Connecting routes to other possible sites to the southeast of the “Route de Dardagny” road also appears complex and unrealistic.

The location at the entrance to the municipality, near the sports field, provides the easiest access and appears to have the least impact. However, the municipality wishes to preserve the view from the D89 road; this option was therefore ruled out after two meetings with local stakeholders.

As a result, the FCC study, carried out in dialogue with the municipality, identified other possible locations described in this chapter. The analysis of their feasibility from a social and technical point of view, and their impact on costs, led to the conclusion that the location at the nominal point is to be preferred.

15. REFERENCE SCENARIO PA31-4.0

Chapter 15 provides an overview of the most successful and balanced scenario, PA31-4.0, its characteristics and overall performance, and then details the configuration of the various surface sites. It contains the latest data from ongoing studies.

15.1. INTRODUCTION

Of the many scenarios analysed, based mainly on bibliographical data and field visits, it was the PA31 scenario type that seemed the most interesting to retain for in-depth studies (all themes).

The route proposed in version 1.0 (PA31-1.0) stands out from the other routes studied. It proposes a balance between territorial location, scientific machine performance and technical feasibility. This working hypothesis, based on the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) process described in Chapter 1, has made it possible to gain in-depth knowledge of the regions, with a view to continuously improve the project.

The **PA31-4.0 reference scenario** presented in this chapter is the result of a number of optimisations carried out following discussions with representatives of the concerned regions. This improved scenario further reduces the impact of constraints and enhances opportunities for all stakeholders.

It should be stressed that the regions and legal frameworks in France, Switzerland and Europe are constantly evolving. Since 2014, a number of options and scenarios for locations are no longer feasible due to these changes. The feasibility of the FCC based on the PA31-4.0 reference scenario has yet to be confirmed. In addition, the rights to the necessary land must be definitively obtained without delay to allow the project approval process to continue.

15.2. CHARACTERISTICS AND PARAMETERS OF THE PA31-4.0 SCENARIO

15.2.1. Characteristics

Illustration 378: The functions of the various sites in the PA31-4.0 configuration.

The PA31-4.0 reference scenario (Illustration 378) is an optimisation of the PA31-1.0 working hypothesis. It takes into account the progress made on design studies for the FCC-ee and FCC-hh colliders, infrastructure and civil engineering studies, as well as meetings with local stakeholders (mayors and town councils of the municipalities concerned, departmental directorates of the territories and the Direction Régionale de l'Environnement, de l'Aménagement et du Logement in France and the services of the Canton of Geneva).

The two shafts at the PA site (Ferney-Voltaire, France) were moved further north from the “Route de Meyrin” road to maintain a safe distance, to provide space for traffic on the surface site around the experiment assembly hall and shafts, and to protect against direct visibility. Moving the location of points PD, PG and PJ further northward would be favourable, but is ruled out due to the presence of the road. Moving them further eastward is also ruled out due to the presence of the compensation zone. This move would also displace the PG point to Charvonnex, deeper into the forest and on a steep slope.

The shafts at the PD site (Nangy, France) were rotated away from the motorway to ensure compatibility with the road development project, and to ensure the technical feasibility of creating a service shaft on the land take for the site without installing an additional cavern between the service cavern and the experiment cavern. A move further southward is ruled out, as this would create incompatibility due to the presence of the motorway and the RD903 road on the PD site, and topographical difficulties (steep slope) on the PG site (Charvonnex and Groisy).

The shifting and rotating of the scenario took into account the objective of placing the PG site in both the forest and on the plateau, where the soil is of poor quality for agriculture. In addition, the shafts should be kept away from the steep slope to the south to ensure the technical feasibility of building the shafts and buildings. It was not possible to move the shafts further away from the forest, towards the plateau, without creating a problem for the PD site (Nangy), due to the presence of the motorway, and for the PJ site (Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens), due to the presence of a stream and topographical constraints.

The PJ site is therefore kept at a distance from the motorway to the south, and from the creek and topographical constraints to the west. The wildlife corridor can be maintained.

The location of the PB technical site (Presinge, Switzerland) was optimised by taking into account maps of biodiversity and ecological indicators, and the results of a study of possible access routes carried out by a specialist firm in the canton of Geneva. The site would be located mainly in Presinge, directly along the “Route de Jussy” road. A connection with the tunnel between the shaft and the service cavern, approximately 85 m long, is required.

The preferred location for the PF technical site is in Eteaux (France), directly adjacent to the RN203 road. It includes a connecting tunnel between the 400 m-deep shaft and the service cavern at the the collider tunnel.

The preferred location for the PH technical site is in Cercier and mainly in Marlioz (France), directly adjacent to the D203 departmental road (Route de Choisy, at the “Chez Papet” locality. Taking into account the analysis of fauna, flora and biodiversity, the state of the forest, topographical constraints and technical risks (gas pipeline), the site closely follows the “Route de Choisy” road to the north.

The preferred location for the PL technical site (Challex, France) is on the nominal point to the east of the town, on a field and a plot of land containing two single-family homes. Another possible location, 600 m west of the nominal point, is being studied. This option presents technical difficulties, would entail additional costs due to the need to build a shaft approximately 150 m outside the tunnel, and would potentially create shared visibility between the site and the municipality.

15.2.2. Parameters

The parameters of the PA31-4.0 reference scenario resulting from this optimization are as follows:

Coordinates WGS84 of theoretical beam interaction points for scientific sites:

Site	Location	Latitude	Longitude
PA	Ferney-Voltaire, FR	46.2480475° N	6.0986019° E
PD	Nangy, FR	46.1453657° N	6.3169260° E
PG	Charvonnex and Groisy, FR	45.9938019° N	6.1693009° E
PJ	Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens, FR	46.0962036° N	5.9513024° E

Coordinates WGS84 of theoretical midpoints of straight sections for technical sites:

Site	Location	Latitude	Longitude
PB	Choulex and Presinge, CH	46.2271027° N	6.2374818° E
PF	La Roche-sur-Foron, FR	46.0490317° N	6.2865850° E
PH	Cercier and Marlioz, FR	46.0146646° N	6.0309816° E
PL	Challex, FR	46.1926255° N	5.9810829° E

Collider parameters:

Parameter	Value
Elevation of the tunnel under the PA site shaft	202 m above sea level
Length of straight sections at PA, PD, PG and PJ sites	1 400 m
Length of straight sections at PB, PF, PH and PL sites	2 032 m
East-west rotation of the collider around the PA site	10.97 degrees
Length of one cell in the arcs (FCC-hh collider construction unit)	275.792 m
Number of cells in a curved section (arc) per octant	26
Total length of curves (arcs)	78 684.476 m
Total circumference of footprint	90 657.4 m for the FCC-hh footprint and 90 658.745 m for the FCC-ee footprint in the same tunnel

Illustration 379: Map of the PA31-4.0 footprint in the region, showing the municipalities crossed.

The functions of each site are as follows:

- PA:** scientific site with one experiment, injecting the beam line from another CERN accelerator into the pre-accelerator (booster) located in the same tunnel as the collider
- PB:** injection of booster beam line into the collider, extraction of beam line from collider
- PD:** optional scientific site, with one experiment
- PF:** collimation (betatron and momentum)
- PG:** scientific site, with one experiment
- PH:** radiofrequency particle acceleration system for the collider
- PJ:** optional scientific site, with one experiment
- PL:** radiofrequency particle acceleration system for “booster” pre-accelerator

15.2.3. Performance of scenario

Illustration 380 presents a multi-criteria analysis of the scenario in terms of territorial compatibility (T), implementation and risk management for the scenario (I), and scientific value (S).

PA31-4.0	PA	PB	-	PD	-	PF	PG	PH	-	PJ	-	PL	Tracé	Total
FCC-ee	EXP	Tec		Tec		Tec	EXP	RF		Tec		RF	90,6 km	B
FCC-hh	EXP	Cryo		EXP		Cryo	EXP	Cryo		EXP		Cryo		
Site														
Score	84	70	-	89	-	79	78	72	-	75	-	77	82	79

Illustration 380: Summary of the multi-criteria analysis of scenario PA31-4.0.

15.2.4. Establish of inventories of natural heritage

Since the beginning of 2023, experts in environmental studies have been carrying out inventories of natural heritage to better define the ecological challenges of each surface site.

Various study areas have been created:

- ZIP (project location zone): boundaries of surface sites (3-8 ha);
- ZEI (immediate study area): depending on the ecological functions of the biological group studied (5-100 ha);
- ZER (close study area): functional zones (25-250 ha);
- ZEE (remote study zone): bibliographical research, for example on biological corridors (5 km)

These study areas and their scale are methodological principles used by all consulting firms in the environmental assessment of projects. This methodology, widely adopted by environmental authorities, is not subject to regulatory approval.

15.3. THE PA SITE IN FERNEY-VOLTAIRE (FRANCE)

15.3.1. Description of the surface site

The main site is located south of the “Route de Meyrin” road, east of the Espace Candide shopping centre. The site would be connected to Point 8 of the LHC by the Chemin des Prés Jins, a public road. An extension to the south of LHC Point 8, already planned as part of the HL-LHC project, would make it possible to accommodate site infrastructure and reduce the land take for the main site.

The surface area of the site along the “Route de Meyrin” road is 5.2 ha, and the surface area of the LHC Point 8 site extension is 2.7 ha.

Illustration 381: Surface site in Ferney-Voltaire, proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

15.3.2. Constraints

The site is located in an Ap zone, close to a compensation zone classified as Np.

The water and gas networks pass close by Point 8 of the LHC. A gas pipeline runs along the boundary of the main surface site, before crossing the border between France and Switzerland.

There is a facility along the “Route de Meyrin” road that supplies waste heat from LHC Point 8 to dwellings and to the ZAC (mixed development zone).

Good urban and landscape integration is necessary because of the view facing the Alps.

Due to heavy traffic in the area, a concept must be developed together with the municipality's technical services for an access route.

15.3.3. Synergies and potential

Waste heat can be recovered and supplied to dwellings and business parks around the site, building on the current heat supplied by the LHC.

Residual water from the cooling system can be used for agricultural purposes, or for the development of natural wetlands (the Poirier de l'Épine zone) close to the site.

Synergy with LHC Point 8 would reduce the footprint of the PA site.

Synergy with the CERN site in Prévessin and the Bois-Tollot substation would provide the electricity supply (400 kV line).

A visitor centre could be created in synergy with LHC Point 8.

15.4. THE PB SITE IN PRESINGE (SWITZERLAND)

15.4.1. Description of the surface site

The site lies to the south of the Nant du Paradis stream, on a field classified as a crop rotation area, bordering the “Route de Jussy” road. The surface area of the site shown on the map is 4.5 ha.

Illustration 382: Surface site in Presinge proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

15.4.2. Constraints

The protective distances between the Nant du Paradis (amphibian breeding area) and the forest are respected. The environmental consultant did not detect any interference with protected environments, in particular with the amphibian breeding site, at the studied location.

The impact on the crop rotation area should be kept to a minimum.

To blend in well with the surrounding landscape, the site needs to be small, and possibly semi-underground.

A study of the cooling system is necessary to reduce noise and visual disturbances.

It is also necessary to develop a concept for reducing light pollution during the construction phase.

The road access was studied by a specialised engineering firm with in-depth knowledge of the sector. The chosen option has yet to be validated by the canton of Geneva. A detailed technical access plan should be drawn up at a later stage.

15.4.3. Synergies and potential

According to the study carried out by a specialised firm, direct access to the site from the “Route de Jussy” road is feasible and preferable. This scenario would avoid the need to create a new access road.

The green buffer zone around the site would reinforce and extend the natural environment in the vicinity of the Nant du Paradis watercourse.

The farmlands to the northwest could be used to recycle excavated materials.

The reinforcement of the local power grid, necessary for the construction of the FCC, is seen as an opportunity to improve the infrastructure for the inhabitants of the entire area.

Improved public transport, including cross-border transport as part of the FCC, also represents an opportunity for the area.

The acceptance of the harbour crossing by 62% of voters in June 2016 opens up the possibility of taking advantage of the infrastructure required for the FCC site as part of the construction of this traffic tunnel¹³⁵.

There is a possibility of supplying heat nearby, for example with HEPIA, and to a new correctional institution slated for construction by 2030 on the Champ-Dollon site.

¹³⁵ <https://www.ge.ch/document/traversee-du-lac-boucllement-autoroutier-rapport-final-25092017>

15.5. THE PD SITE IN NANGY (FRANCE)

15.5.1. Description of the surface site

The site is located in Nangy, between the A40 motorway and the RD903 road on a field with Zone A classification in the PLU (local urban plan). The surface area of the indicated site is approximately 4.9 ha.

Illustration 383: Surface site in Nangy proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

15.5.2. Constraints

The site is subject to space constraints to the west, east and south due to existing roads and plans to build a new connection between the roads. Access would be via a traffic circle, which would be built to the north, in the direction of Findrol. An access design study was carried out by a specialised firm. Road traffic is heavy.

15.5.3. Synergies and potential

The site is not easily accessible from roads, and is not visible from residential areas, which facilitates its integration into the landscape.

There are a number of possibilities for supplying waste heat from the cooling system, for example to a Findrol cheese factory, to an industrial and business park, and to the Alpes-Léman hospital complex.

There are also possibilities for supplying residual water from the cooling system, for example to a wetland on the other side of the motorway to the west, to the Arve and to a waste water treatment plant close to the Arve.

An access route to the motorway during the construction phase has been studied. It could facilitate the removal and supply of materials. Synergy with the RD903 road development project could help improve traffic flow.

It is likely that there are areas in the vicinity where excavated materials can be recycled, and these should be identified in cooperation with local authorities and government departments (DDT, DREAL).

15.6. THE PF SITE IN ETEAUX (FRANCE)

15.6.1. Description of the surface site

Illustration 384: Surface sites in Eteaux and La Roche-sur-Foron proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

A surface site at the nominal point is not feasible because:

- the site would be in the middle of a hamlet of single-family homes;
- the presence of the Lavillat road in the direction of La Roche-sur-Foron is incompatible with the construction and installation of the accelerator site and equipment;
- the nominal point is located on high ground (755 m), with an unfavourable topography;
- a slight movement of the ring inwards is ruled out due to the presence of steep slopes and the risk of landslides.

The option selected for a surface site is a location to the north of Eteaux, alongside the RD1203 road, with a surface area of 4 ha. An annex to the south option in La Roche-sur-Foron, north of the motorway and on the perimeter of an ISDI (inert waste storage facility), is conceivable if this becomes technically necessary for phase 2 of the FCC, after 2060. It will need to be verified that its construction is compatible with the materials deposited in the ISDI.

15.6.2. Constraints

Main site to the north:

The shaft of the site and the accelerator tunnel are 558.5 m apart, depending on the position of the shaft.

The wetlands to the east of the site must be maintained and could be integrated into the site.

A certain distance must be maintained between the site and the hamlet to the east.

As a result, there is little space left for the surface site, and the size of the site should be reduced.

Work should be undertaken with the local authority and government departments (DDT, DREAL) to define zones for recycling excavated materials in the vicinity of the site.

The area available for the surface site is very limited (4 ha). It may therefore be necessary to relocate certain elements, such as an electrical substation or cooling towers, to the south option for the site in La Roche-sur-Foron or to another nearby location.

Option of an annex to the south:

The site is located on the land take of an ISDI (inert waste storage facility), currently under construction, with ICPE status (facility classified for environmental protection). Following an analysis carried out by civil engineering contractors, CERN concluded that the ISDI was in principle compatible with the construction of a surface site. However, this option would entail significant additional costs and additional technical difficulties. For example, it would be necessary to employ pillars for construction on inert waste dumps.

It would be necessary to create an access road 2.4 km long that crosses the railway line, and to build an underpass under the motorway.

Lastly, this option is located in the immediate vicinity of the ZNIEFF, which is rich in biodiversity and includes a wildlife corridor that must be preserved.

The available surface area is virtually the same as for the north option (4.1 ha, versus 4.0 ha). However, this site could accommodate certain technical infrastructures that are easily compatible with inert waste deposits, such as an electrical substation or cooling towers. An analysis will be carried out during the detailed technical design phase.

15.6.3. Synergies and potential

For the north option, it is possible to supply waste heat from the cooling system to public facilities and businesses within a radius of less than 3 km.

Residual water from the cooling system can be used for wetlands or the Vuaz stream.

Renaturation around the wetlands would enhance the area, which is currently in a degraded state, and is open to discussion.

Lastly, direct access from the main road is possible and would avoid the creation of a new access road.

15.7. THE PG SITE IN CHARVONNEX AND GROISY (FRANCE)

15.7.1. Description of the surface site

The site lies to the north of the “Route d’Annecy” road on a plateau, partly in a forest and partly on grasslands. It is approximately 800 m south of the A410 motorway area in Groisy. It is far from any dwellings.

The surface area of the main site is 6.9 ha. Annexes of 1.9 ha and 1.7 ha for equipment storage, an electrical substation and cooling towers close to the motorway are also indicated.

Illustration 385: Surface site in Groisy and Charvonnex proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

15.7.2. Constraints

The forest is an EBC (classified wooded area), valued for its biodiversity. The use of the forest for the site will be reduced and limited to the part with the lowest quality in terms of its natural environment. Clearing can be compensated for, for example by reforesting the southern part of the plateau or existing brownfields in the forest.

The site is on the edge of a steep slope towards the “Route d’Annecy” road to the south, and must therefore remain on the top of the plateau.

It is a quiet, natural area. Measures will need to be taken to reduce noise and light pollution during the construction and operating phases.

15.7.3. Synergies and potential

The possibility of reforestation compensates for the clearing of approximately 1.5 ha of forest.

A forest road over flat land provides access, and makes it possible to create a route over approximately 800 m to the Groisy motorway area and a wide road alongside the motorway.

Access to the motorway during the construction phase for supplies and the removal of excavated materials has been studied and appears feasible. There are two temporary storage areas for inert waste and other materials in the immediate vicinity of the site and the forest road.

Annexes close to the motorway could accommodate those elements most likely to generate disturbances, such as cooling towers.

The supply of waste heat from the cooling system appears to be possible. There are several potential customers in the vicinity, including public facilities (elementary school, middle school, fire station), the shopping centre and the veterinary clinic. There is also the possibility of creating a network in Charvonnex and Groisy.

The fire station provides makes emergency services available to the site.

Waste water from the cooling system could be used to feed the Fattes stream, the Fillière river and wetlands in the forest.

There is enough space on the site to build a visitor centre that can be reached via the Groisy motorway area or the “Route d'Annecy” road. The site is located near Annecy, within easy reach for CNRS/LAPP staff.

Sites for recycling excavated materials for agriculture and forestry have yet to be defined in cooperation with local authorities and government departments (DDT, DREAL).

15.8. THE PH SITE IN CERCIER AND MARLIOZ (FRANCE)

15.8.1. Description of the surface site

The site is located right along the D203 road near the “Chez Papet” locality in Cercier. The site is located in the forest, straddling the municipalities of Cercier and Marlioz. It is far from any dwellings and is not visible. It is in a nature setting. The indicated area, located in an area with less biodiversity, is 8.2 ha.

Illustration 386: Surface site in Cercier and Marlioz proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

15.8.2. Constraints

The forested sector to the north of the indicated site is of great value (rich biodiversity, natural environment).

The site will respect the buffer zone for the gas pipeline to the north of the site.

Considering the quiet, natural setting, noise and light pollution must be given particular attention. A dwelling is located approximately 200 m away, but is not directly visible.

Given the small size of the road, it is necessary to identify nearby recycling sites for excavated materials, so that they can be used in agriculture or for reforestation.

RTE will have to take into account the need to supply electricity via buried cables when carrying out the study for the creation of a substation for access to the 400 kV line.

15.8.3. Synergies and potential

There is a great deal of interest in reusing waste water for agricultural activities around the site (apple and pear trees). A water basin exists nearby, to the northeast, and a study could be carried out to find a way of integrating it into the site or creating an additional basin.

It is also advisable to work with local authorities to take advantage of opportunities to supply heat to various customers, such as Val' fruits.

15.9. THE PJ SITE IN DINGY-EN-VUACHE AND VULBENS (FRANCE)

15.9.1. Description of the surface site

The site is located in a field to the north of the A40 motorway and to the west of the Valleiry motorway area, at the junction of the “Chemin des Tattes” and “Chemin de Maigy” roads. To the west is a stream. The site straddles the municipalities of Dingy-en-Vuache (south) and Vulbens (north). It is far from any dwellings.

The surface area of the indicated site is 6.1 ha.

Illustration 387: Surface site in Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

15.9.2. Constraints

A wildlife corridor needs to be respected, or even improved, as it currently functions poorly.

It will also be necessary to take into account plans to improve soft mobility between Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens.

15.9.3. Synergies and potential

The site is surrounded by numerous sloping farmlands. It will be necessary to work with local authorities and government departments (DDT, DREAL) to determine where agricultural activities can benefit from the recovery of excavated materials.

The scientific site can also benefit from nearby developments to the south, over the same time frame (e.g. new national police station).

It seems feasible to make waste heat available to public institutions and nearby business districts in Vulbens and Valleiry.

It would be a good idea to work with the department on educational aspects (new middle school, planned construction of a new high school, integration of the site in school activities, apprenticeships and internships).

The creation of a visitor centre would enable the development of high-quality, sustainable tourism. It requires cooperation with local authorities, the department and/or the region.

The connection to the Valleiry motorway area for removing materials and receiving supplies via the motorway has been analysed and appears feasible.

There is considerable interest in developing synergies for the use of waste water to feed streams and for crop irrigation.

15.10. THE PL SITE IN CHALLEX (FRANCE)

15.10.1. Description of the surface site

The challenges associated with the different options studied are described in Chapter 14. A dialogue held with the municipality in 2023 and 2024 enabled location options to be identified and evaluated. The preferred location is at the nominal point, near the border between France and Switzerland. The location still needs to be optimised in close cooperation with the municipality. This option, located away from the village, requires the creation of an access road. The area of the site near the border is 5.5 ha.

Illustration 388: Possible locations for a surface site in Challex, proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

15.10.2. Constraints

Option with location at nominal point

The proximity of the Franco-Swiss border, close to vineyards, presents a challenge, as there are no roads or other infrastructure. However, one remote dwelling in the vicinity would be affected by disturbances and would therefore have to be acquired.

Access through the village is ruled out. The roads are too narrow and the disturbances would be unacceptable. Building a new access route through the fields to the north of the village is complicated but feasible. The theoretical point is separated from the main roads (“Route de Greney” and “Rue de la Craz” roads) at the entrance to the municipality by natural areas. The forest to the north of Challex is a zone rich in biodiversity. On the Swiss side, the forest is a zone reserved for absolute protection (Ramsar site).

A temporary, shallow water table was added to the Swiss maps in 2023. Technically, the creation of a shaft is feasible, even after confirmation of the presence of a water table and its location. However, drilling is required to confirm or deny the presence of the water table, and to determine its seasonal nature if it does exist and the possibility of cross-border connections. The positioning of the shaft and of the entire site can be optimised according to the results of these underground investigations.

This option for the location is preferred by CERN following an analysis conducted with the local municipality.

Illustration 389: Surface site in Challex proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

Option for the location 800 m east of nominal point (not selected)

A location 800 m east of the nominal point would not allow access inside the ring. However, a technically feasible solution, albeit at a higher cost, has been developed. The shaft would be located between 50 m and 150 m outside the ring. The site would be approximately 150 m from dwellings, 5 to 10 m lower than the municipality, on a gentle slope of approximately 3%. It would be visible from certain dwellings. This scenario would not generate any significant environmental constraints. It would be necessary to build an access road to the D89 road (approx. 400 m) or to the “Rue de la Craz” road (approx. 300 m). This scenario was used as a basis for discussions with the municipality to find an alternative location to Option 1 (location at nominal point).

Illustration 390: Surface site in Challex proposed in scenario PA31-4.0.

Option with location near the sports field (not selected)

Moving the site 1 000 m to the end of the straight section north of the sports field was considered, but ruled out following discussions with local stakeholders. The distance between the shaft and the midpoint of the straight section would also be an engineering challenge. This is not a blocking point but could have budgetary consequences, and would require the development of other concepts for installation and operation. Positioning the access shaft inside the ring would require using a portion of the parking lot between the sports field and the multi-purpose community hall. The shaft access building and its ventilation system would be visible. Moving the shaft approximately 200 m outside the site would reduce direct disturbances and visibility, but this option is not acceptable to local residents. It would require a horizontal connection tunnel in the gallery above the accelerator tunnel. The municipality wishes to preserve the view from the D89 road and is worried about deterioration of the landscape. Which is why this option was ultimately ruled out.

Illustration 391: Surface site in Challex, considered but ruled out following discussions with the concerned municipality.

Option with location near the forest (not selected)

A location close to the forest, at a distance of 570 m from the nominal point, was analysed. This location would not be directly visible from the town. However, it would be located in a protected natural area in the immediate vicinity of a wetland, and would require the creation of an access road through highly sensitive natural zones and wooded areas. Lastly, the distance between the site and the collider tunnel would entail significant additional costs. Which is why this option was ultimately ruled out.

Illustration 392: Surface site in Challex, considered but ruled out due to environmental constraints and unjustified additional costs.

Option with a location north of the one shown on Illustration 391 (not selected)

A location north of the one shown on Illustration 391, between a line of trees and the forest, would provide a more hidden site closer to the D89 road. It would avoid interference with the protected natural area, but would risk impacting the forest and the natural setting between the forest and the tree line. The distance to the tunnel is quite long, meaning significant additional costs for the project. Lastly, the available area (1.7 ha) is too small for a surface site and for the construction work. Which is why this option was ultimately ruled out.

Illustration 393: Surface site in Challex, considered but ruled out following discussions with the concerned municipality.

Option for location with an access shaft outside the ring (not selected)

A site in a field to the northeast of the footprint, bordering a rural road, has a surface area of 4 ha, which is sufficient for a surface site and the construction work. Placing the access shaft outside the tunnel would entail acceptable additional costs for the project, with the creation of an underground connection approximately 150 m long with the main collider tunnel (Illustration 394).

Illustration 394: Access to the main tunnel from the exterior via an underground connection.

The verification regarding its visibility from isolated dwellings on the outskirts of the municipality has shown that this location should not be prioritized. The site would partially affect the protected natural area, but the impact would remain limited since it is currently a field, and the biological corridor passes further to the east of the site.

Illustration 395: Scenario for the Challex surface site with an access shaft outside the ring.

Illustration 396: Artistic view of the PL site in Challex.

15.10.3. Synergies and potential

The proximity of the CERN site (Prévessin in France and Meyrin in Switzerland) represents an exceptional opportunity to benefit from synergies for the installation, operation, maintenance and repair of equipment in the shortest possible time.

The fields to the north of the municipality appear to be suitable for recycling excavated materials for agricultural use. There is no direct visibility from the village.

The proximity of the former Collonges train station (12 km) represents an opportunity for removing materials and providing supplies.

A connection to the La Plaine train station in Switzerland, subject to an agreement between France and Switzerland, would provide an opportunity for material removal.

The improvement of the local power grid, necessary for the FCC, would benefit the municipality and its residents. It would enable increased use of renewable energies and more robust vehicle recharging stations.

Improving the public transport network, starting at the FCC construction phase, can also be of benefit to residents of the municipality, who currently mainly use private vehicles on the D884 road in France and to travel to Meyrin and La Plaine in Switzerland. Challex has traditionally been a home to employees of international organizations, many of whom work at CERN. Strengthening the infrastructure would therefore benefit both the community and the FCC project.

Waste heat could be used for heating individual and collective residences (e.g. the Les Cyclamens long-term care centre), as well as for the Val Thoiry shopping centre approximately 7 km away. Other nearby communities such as Greny, Saint-Jean-de-Gonville, Péron and La Plaine (Switzerland) could also benefit from this heat supply. The company Firmenich (perfumes and fragrances), based in La Plaine, could also benefit from this heat. Waste heat could also be used in innovative ways for fish farming, aquaponics,¹³⁶ market gardening and greenhouses.

¹³⁶ <https://www.lafermeaquaponique.com>

15.11. FEASIBILITY OF SURFACE SITES

The table below shows the status of the feasibility analysis for the surface site locations in scenario PA31-4.0. Their technical feasibility was assessed using maps and data available to those working on the FCC study and to contractors, as well as field work and environmental studies carried out by specialised companies and discussions with the relevant technical departments of the two host states, and with local elected official (mayors, town councillors, departmental councillors and regional councillors), who represent the citizens and act in their interests.

Table 36: Status of technical feasibility assessment for surface sites of PA31 scenario.

Site	Location	Technical feasibility	Feasibility conditions
PA	Ferney-Voltaire, Ain, France	Confirmed	<p>Limit impact on the landscape, enhance the natural area and the existing compensation zone. Maximise synergy with LHC point 8. Compensate for the loss of agricultural space.</p> <p>Develop a visitor centre, for example on the LHC Point 8 site. Develop synergies based on heat recovery with municipalities within a 10 km radius, including Swiss municipalities and the Geneva airport.</p>
PB	Presinge, Geneva, Switzerland	Confirmed	<p>Define the exact location of the site on the plot and initiate discussions with the municipality. Limit impact on the landscape. Take into account the sensitive location of the site in a natural setting.</p> <p>Validation of the road access concept established by the State of Geneva.</p> <p>Reach an agreement to recycle excavated materials, preferably locally.</p> <p>Compensate for the loss of agricultural space.</p> <p>Develop synergies based on heat recovery around the site with local authorities.</p>
PD	Nangy, Haute-Savoie, France	Confirmed	<p>There are no specific blocking points, but the major issues in this sector call for careful joint development of the site in coordination with local stakeholders.</p> <p>Maintain compatibility with the proposed connection between the RD903 road and the A40 motorway. Estimated start of construction: first quarter of 2025. Develop site access that limits impact on farmland.</p> <p>Develop a transportation concept for the construction phase to limit impacts on a sector that is already overburdened.</p> <p>Limit the loss of agricultural space by working on a smaller surface site. Compensate for the loss of agricultural space.</p> <p>Develop synergies with the communities around CHAL, the Scientrier STEP (waste water treatment plant) and the industrial zone to the north.</p>

PF	Eteaux, Haute-Savoie, France	Confirmed	<p>The north option along the RD1203 road was confirmed, provided that nearby wetlands are avoided. This is the preferred reference scenario.</p> <p>For the south option, a decision to go ahead with the project would be required before the start of phase 2 of the ISDI (inert waste storage facility) in La Roche-sur-Foron in 2027, which would allow earthworks to be carried out on the western part for a smaller site, rather than complete development for the ISDI. An agreement must be reached with the ISDI operator and the landowners. The access layout should be developed for this option. Any economic loss suffered by the ISDI operator must be taken into account when developing synergies between the site and the operator.</p> <p>Develop synergies with local authorities in terms of site development with emergency services.</p>
PG	Charvonnex and Groisy, Haute-Savoie, France	Confirmed	<p>The site straddles the forest and the plateau, which includes unused grasslands (currently used by the owner for two horses). Two annexes close to the motorway area will accommodate certain facilities (water cooling system, electrical substation) to avoid any disturbance to the wooded area. Foresee a visitor centre to develop high-quality, sustainable tourism. Develop synergies with the municipalities of Groisy and Charvonnex to develop the site with neighbourhood services for on-site researchers and emergency services.</p> <p>The loss of approximately 1.5 ha of woodland can be compensated by reforestation around the site. The layout of the existing access route to the north is suitable.</p>
PH	Cercier and Marlioz, Haute-Savoie, France	Confirmed	<p>Limit the site's footprint and remain within the wooded area to avoid any impact on the dwellings to the south of the site. Compensate for the loss of woodland. Respect the easement for the gas pipeline near the site and decide what distance to maintain between the pipeline and above-ground infrastructure.</p> <p>Reduce the impact on habitats. Continue considering a displaced site location in case the potential negative effects exceed the benefits of the reference location.</p>
PJ	Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens, Haute-Savoie, France	Confirmed	<p>Preserve ecological corridors. Compensate for the loss of agricultural space. Integrate the foreseen projects to develop soft mobility between Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens. Foresee a visitor centre to develop high-quality, sustainable tourism.</p> <p>Work with the municipalities to develop synergy for the site with regards to neighbourhood services for on-site researchers, emergency services and schools.</p>
PL	Challex, Ain, France	Confirmed	<p>The location at the nominal point has been agreed with the municipality.</p> <p>A joint optimization with the municipality of the location is in progress.</p>

16. ANNEXES

Chapter 16 presents appendices:

- source of illustrations;
- data used and area of relevance ;
- list of cadastral plots for each site;
- cantonal interdepartmental cell structure (Switzerland).

16.1. SOURCE OF ILLUSTRATIONS

Unless otherwise indicated in the legend, the illustrations presented in this report are taken from:

- CERN diagrams, illustrations and photographs;
- Cerema diagrams, illustrations and photographs;
- Setec and Ecotec diagrams, illustrations and photographs;
- screenshots from Géoportail, Google Maps, the Système d'information du territoire à Genève (SITG) and the CERN Geographic Information System (GIS).

16.2. DATA USED AND AREA OF RELEVANCE

French data

This report is based on available data, updated as indicated in the following tables.

For the remainder of the studies, particular attention must be paid to any changes in regulations and to any projects launched by local authorities.

Source of biodiversity data

The following biodiversity data was used to create the French maps showing constraints (Table 37):

Table 37: Source of biodiversity data used in this report.

Biodiversity issue	Document/file	Source	Date consulted
Corridors, permeable spaces, artificial spaces, wetlands, reservoirs, obstacles, etc.	SRADDET Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes	datara.gouv.fr	2020-2024
Natura 2000 zones, biotope protection orders, ZNIEFF, ZICO	Maps of sites	inpn.mnhn.fr	2020-2024
Compensatory measures, wetland inventories, spawning grounds	Maps of measures	datara.gouv.fr geocatalogue.fr	2020-2024

Source of urban planning data

Table 38 shows the source of the urban planning documents used to create the French maps showing the constraints.

Table 38: Source of urban planning data used in this report.

Urban planning issues	Document/file	Source	Date consulted
PLU (local urban plan) zoning, surface and linear requirements	Zoning maps	geoportail-urbanisme.gouv.fr/	2020-2024
Natural hazard prevention plan (PPRN) regulations	Maps of perimeters	datara.gouv.fr	2020-2023
Public utility easement (pipeline)	Maps of footprint	DDT de la Haute-Savoie	2020
Drinking water supply catchments	ARS mapping	Regional Health Agency (ARS)	2022-2024

Source of other data

A great deal of additional data is used for maps and illustrations (Table 39).

Table 39: Data sources used to produce this report.

Issue/use	Source	Date consulted
Environmental issues	GIS of CERN	2022-2024
Technical infrastructures	SITG (Switzerland) Open Data Réseaux Énergies (ODRÉ) data.gouv.fr (France)	2022-2024
Cadastral plots	Cerema land files Marceleon and CERN land files	2022-2023 2023
Farmers	Graphic parcel register	2020
Topographic and base maps	WGS IGN and OSM flows	2022-2023
Constructions	BD Topo 2021®	2022-2023
Illustration photos	Google Street View CERN Setec and Ecotec	2020-2023 2023-2024 2023
Aerial photographs	Google Maps and geoportail.gouv.fr	2022-2023

For road data, at this early stage, the plot connections are traced using the topography of the IGN digital terrain model (metric accuracy is questionable). Land surveys will be required at a later stage.

Swiss data

The Swiss data is taken from the *FCC Layout Review in Switzerland* report drawn up by Ecotec in 2017¹³⁷ and supplemented by elements from the Geographic Information System of the canton of Geneva (<https://ge.ch/sitg>) and information gathered during thematic sessions organised with cantonal departments as part of the interdepartmental unit set up by the canton to support the FCC study.

A more in-depth analysis of environmental issues, combined with field visits, was carried out by Setec and Ecotec for the FCC study beginning in December 2022¹³⁸.

Data for the PB site in Switzerland was collected and produced by CERN in coordination with the Swiss services. Data from cantonal information systems also includes part of the zones of the PA site in Ferney-Voltaire and the PL site in Challex.

A review/verification of all the elements relating to Switzerland produced in this way was carried out in 2022 by the consulting firm Latitude Durable.

Table 40: Swiss data source.

Issues	Source	Date consulted
Environmental issues	GIS of CERN	2022-2024
	Measurement campaign by Setec and Ecotec	2023-2024
All issues	SITG	July 2022-June 2024
Base map	OSM and SITG	2022-2024
Illustration photos	Google Street View	2022-2024
	CERN	
	Setec and Ecotec	

Field visits

The presentation of the sites is based on collected bibliographical data and field visits carried out between 2022 and 2024. These visits made it possible to make many valuable observations to better understand the feasibility of the project at an early stage, and to optimise the location and perimeter of the sites while taking into account several previously unknown environmental constraints (e.g. visibility, topography, noise pollution, wetlands, natural environments and traffic).

The initial observations to obtain general information in 2022 were then examined in greater detail between autumn 2022 and summer 2024 by specialised consulting firms commissioned by CERN. These improvements have been taken into account in the updated version of this report.

The report includes information about the possibility of storing materials at sites which do not appear to be available. However, it will be necessary to carry out additional, in-depth studies in cooperation with the relevant departments in the host countries to define these areas.

¹³⁷ M. Zahnd, *FCC layout review in Switzerland*, ECOTEC Environnement SA, V2.0, 13 December 2017, FCC-INF-RPT-0007 / EDM5 1838912, contract CA 6797383, limited access.

¹³⁸ See website fcc-faisabilite.eu for further information.

16.3. LIST OF CADASTRAL PLOTS FOR EACH SITE IN SCENARIO PA31-4.0

The indicated plots correspond to the list of proposed plots to be communicated to the French government for registration purposes as part of the "perimeter of consideration" procedure, and to the canton of Geneva and the Swiss Confederation as part of the feasibility analysis of the administrative procedures. The number of plots is greater than the number required for the demarcated surface sites.

The register of cadastral plots used for France and Switzerland dates from October 2022. Some plots may have changed since then.

Table 41: List of cadastral plots concerned for each site in working hypothesis PA31-4.0.

Site	Country	Department code	Municipality number	Name of municipality	Section number	Plot number	Surface (m2)
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	55	10556
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	56	17275
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	122	14150
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	143	24997
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	175	18148
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	177	8488
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	184	13225
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	214	17997
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	285	9301
PA	FR	01	160	Ferney-Voltaire	A	286	599
PB	CH		38	Presinge		2112	3693
PB	CH		38	Presinge		2113	57664
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	380	2969
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	383	2402
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	844	8270
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	846	438
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	850	1828
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	853	8875
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	855	1231
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1292	4116
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1298	720
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1301	2020
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1304	3071
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1305	8021
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1307	7200
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1312	2209
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1627	152
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1628	1842
PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1637	365

PD	FR	74	197	Nangy	B	1638	453
PF	FR	74	116	Eteaux	B	563	24268
PF	FR	74	116	Eteaux	B	564	8865
PF	FR	74	116	Eteaux	B	748	7270
PF	FR	74	116	Eteaux	B	2308	42020
PF	FR	74	224	La Roche-sur-Foron	ZA	381	3124
PF	FR	74	224	La Roche-sur-Foron	ZA	470	668
PF	FR	74	224	La Roche-sur-Foron	ZA	471	496
PF	FR	74	224	La Roche-sur-Foron	ZA	472	464
PF	FR	74	224	La Roche-sur-Foron	ZA	509	57954
PG	FR	74	62	Charvonnex	AC	136	1550
PG	FR	74	62	Charvonnex	AC	137	2748
PG	FR	74	62	Charvonnex	AC	138	34355
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	685	2355
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	686	2750
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	687	4854
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	688	4776
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	689	4312
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	733	1736
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	773	3194
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	785	2604
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	1696	14614
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	1699	31580
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	1757	528
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	1760	3091
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	2310	879
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	2311	770
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	2312	355
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	2823	4998
PG	FR	74	137	Groisy	D	2824	4998
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	370	6062
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	371	226
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	372	966
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	374	5151
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	375	2119
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	376	9889
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	377	3002
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	378	2848
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	379	1474
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	380	1657

PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	381	1118
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	382	2320
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	383	853
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	384	1280
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	385	1070
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	386	962
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	387	2101
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	388	2013
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	389	1024
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	390	1197
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	394	1105
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	395	872
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	396	1948
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	402	3600
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	403	10465
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	408	1209
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	409	1401
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	410	1582
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	411	883
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	412	1094
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	413	2730
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	414	1254
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	415	542
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	416	761
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	417	1315
PH	FR	74	168	Marlioz	B	418	9015
PH	FR	74	51	Cercier	C	834	6050
PH	FR	74	51	Cercier	C	835	2915
PH	FR	74	51	Cercier	C	836	9080
PH	FR	74	51	Cercier	C	837	1880
PH	FR	74	51	Cercier	C	838	6385
PH	FR	74	51	Cercier	C	1225	3410
PJ	FR	74	314	Vulbens	A	768	45164
PJ	FR	74	101	Dingy-En-Vuache	A	2873	3800
PJ	FR	74	101	Dingy-En-Vuache	A	2874	35137
PJ	FR	74	101	Dingy-En-Vuache	A	2877	7200
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	138	2543
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	139	1553
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	140	3437
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	141	2380

PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	142	3891
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	143	1481
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	144	7470
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	145	1571
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	146	1578
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	147	2855
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	148	1487
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	149	1443
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	150	1512
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	151	3718
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	155	1494
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	156	1622
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	157	1521
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	158	1070
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	159	1700
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	160	1860
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	161	2737
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	498	139
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	499	1293
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	500	3047
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	501	139
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	502	320
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	503	716
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	504	320
PL	FR	01	78	Challex	A	505	455

16.4. INTERDEPARTMENTAL CANTONAL UNIT FOR CERN PROJECTS

The objectives and the mandate of the interdepartmental unit of the canton of Geneva are as follows:

- 1) proactively coordinate a complex system with many stakeholders;
- 2) plan the project;
- 3) ensure the feasibility of a project with major territorial, energy and institutional impacts within a constrained normative system.

The cell's organizational chart as of 15 December 2021 is shown in Illustration 397.

Illustration 397: Interdepartmental cantonal unit for CERN projects.